

**ENTREPRENEURIAL LEADERSHIP IN
A DEVELOPING ECONOMY: A STUDY
IN NIGERIA**

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Dedication

First and foremost, I will like to express my gratitude to God for giving me the grace and strength to complete this thesis. Without God it would not have been possible.

This thesis is dedicated to my wife, Anuoluwapo Laura Harrison, whose love and patience has inspired me. Thank you for being there for me through thick and thin and believing in me. To my son and daughter, Christian Harrison, Jr and Lily Harrison, I hope one day you will both read this thesis and be inspired. You motivate me every day and this work is dedicated to you and your mum.

Student Declaration

I declare that this thesis has not been submitted for another comparable academic award.

Signed: _____

Date: _____

Abstract

The dynamic nature of the business environment and the challenges faced by entrepreneurs and owner managers has led practitioners and academics to embrace entrepreneurial leadership. The concept of entrepreneurial leadership has been formulated by merging the fields of entrepreneurship and leadership. Although much work has been done in the individual fields of entrepreneurship and leadership, the domain of entrepreneurial leadership lacks focus and empirical work. While researchers and practitioners have acknowledged the importance of entrepreneurial leadership in organisations, this field still remains in a state of infancy, and considerable scholarship is still required.

The aim of this research project was to examine entrepreneurial leadership in a developing economy, to understand the challenges entrepreneurs face, and to determine the entrepreneurial leadership skills which are important for success in a developing economy environment. Specifically, the focus of this research was on entrepreneurial leadership within the retail pharmacy sector in Nigeria. This study was guided by an interpretivist–constructionist perspective. By adopting a qualitative approach, the lived experiences of the retail pharmacy entrepreneurs could be understood. Semi-structured interviews were the mode of data collection, and data was triangulated via three sources: entrepreneurs, employees, and literature. This study identified key findings which provide more theoretical insights into entrepreneurial leadership.

From the study results, a vivid picture of entrepreneurial leadership was formed, which in turn provides the basis for an empirical skill-based model of this phenomenon in a developing economy. The findings of this study show the factors and conditions necessary for entrepreneurial leadership in a developing economy. In this study, the role of culture, attributes, experience, resources, family dynamics and followers for understanding entrepreneurial leadership in an organisation are considered. In addition, the challenges which entrepreneurs face in running their businesses in this context are examined.

The findings of this study have implications in theory and practice. Its results provide an empirical, skill-based framework on entrepreneurial leadership in a developing economy, a subject area for which there exists a lack of background literature. In practice, the findings of this study serve as a useful reference for practitioners and policy makers of the skills and other factors required for people to succeed as entrepreneurial leaders.

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List of abbreviations

ACPN- Association of Community Pharmacists of Nigeria

B.Pharm- Bachelor of Pharmacy

CIA- Central Intelligence Agency

EFCC- Economic and Financial Crimes Commission

EL- Entrepreneurial leadership

FDI- Foreign Direct Investment

GDP- Gross Domestic Product

GNI- Gross National Income

IT- Information Technology

MBA- Master of Business Administration

NAFDAC- National Agency for Food, Drug Administration and Control

NBS- National Bureau of Statistics

SLR- Systematic literature review

PSN- Pharmaceutical Society of Nigeria

PCN- Pharmacists Council of Nigeria

UNCTAD- United Nations Conference on Trade and Development

CHAPTER ONE – INTRODUCTION

1.1 Background to research

There is a considerable body of research in the fields of entrepreneurship and leadership spanning several decades. Despite such work across both domains, entrepreneurship and leadership still remain ambiguous concepts. There are considerable overlaps and parallels between entrepreneurship and leadership, both historically and conceptually (Cogliser and Brigham, 2004; Galloway et al., 2015), with some researchers defining entrepreneurship as leadership within a narrow context (Vecchio, 2003). This research has led to the emergence of a new paradigm known as “*Entrepreneurial leadership*” (Cogliser and Brigham, 2004; Fernald et al., 2005; Kuratko, 2007).

Nowadays, businesses exist in environments which are both complex and turbulent. Entrepreneurial leadership has been proposed as a concept which entrepreneurs should embrace in order to maintain their competitiveness in a dynamic business environment (Fernald et al., 2005), and researchers have shown that entrepreneurial leadership is positively related to business performance (Agus and Hassan, 2010; Hmieleski and Ensley, 2007; Van Zyl and Mathur-Helm, 2007). According to Van Zyl and Mathur-Helm (2007), entrepreneurial leaders with high levels of innovation, and both customer and competitor orientation, have a positive effect on business performance. Due to the recognition of the value of this new form of leadership in enhancing organisational performance, interest in entrepreneurial leadership has increased among scholars. Evidence of this can be seen in the large number of definitions that have emerged in regard to entrepreneurial leadership, which in turn has been defined as a type of leadership that creates visionary scenarios that are used to assemble and mobilize a “supporting cast” of participants, who in turn are captivated by the vision of discovery and exploitation of strategic value creation (Gupta et al., 2004, p. 242). Surie and Ashley (2008) define entrepreneurial leadership as leadership capable of sustaining innovation and adaptation in high velocity, uncertain environments. Entrepreneurial leadership is also known as “...the

dynamic process of presenting vision, making commitment among followers and accepting risks when facing opportunities that require efficient use of available resources, along with discovering and utilizing new resources with respect to the leader's vision" (Hejazi et al., 2012, p. 71). Greenberg et al. (2013, p. 57) argue that it is a leadership style that is used "...to solve complex business, social, and environmental problems". According to Renko et al. (2012b, p. 2), entrepreneurial leadership involves "...influencing and directing the performance of group members towards achieving those organisational goals that involves recognising and exploiting entrepreneurial opportunities".

This range of definitions shows that, although there is heightened interest among scholars, there is no universal consensus on the concept of entrepreneurial leadership. Progress in this new field has been hindered by a lack of conceptual development and the absence of adequate tools to assess an entrepreneurial leader's characteristics and behaviours (Renko et al., 2012b). This thesis develops a conceptual and empirical foundation for entrepreneurial leadership from an international perspective.

Notwithstanding the growing body of literature from both empirical and conceptual standpoints on entrepreneurial leadership (for example, Chen, 2007; Cogliser and Brigham, 2004; Fernald et al., 2005; Gupta et al., 2004; Nicholson, 1998; Renko et al., 2012b; Swiercz and Lydon, 2002; etc.), there has been little scholarship which has examined the subject from the perspective of a developing country (Chen, 2007; Hejazi et al., 2012). In particular, there have been no significant qualitative studies within the context of entrepreneurial leadership in Sub-Saharan Africa. Exploring entrepreneurial leadership from the perspective of a developing country will add a valuable contextual perspective.

As Dodd and Patra (2002, p. 131) remind researchers,

"It must never be assumed that what holds true for entrepreneurs in one part of the world can therefore, de facto, form a legitimate basis for studies elsewhere. Beyond national divergence, other cultural variables such as gender, class, race, industry norms, and religion can be expected, and have often been demonstrated to impact upon the degree and nature of entrepreneurship in a given group."

Several scholars agree that any comprehensive analysis of economic development should include some appraisal of the role of entrepreneurship (Harbison, 1956). The entrepreneurial activity of nascent entrepreneurs and owner managers of young businesses affects economic growth (Van Stel et al., 2005). This can come about by introducing important innovations (Acs and Audretsch, 2003), or by increasing productivity through competition (Nickel et al., 1997). Indeed, entrepreneurship is indispensable for economic development (Naude, 2010) and is the engine of economic growth (Holcombe, 1998). The greater the number of entrepreneurs in an economy, the faster it will grow (Dejardin, 2000).

There are more entrepreneurial opportunities in developing countries (Ho and Wong, 2007), and the demand for entrepreneurship in developing countries is indeed matched by the higher rate of opportunity-motivated entrepreneurs entering the market (Naude, 2009). Furthermore, entrepreneurs in countries with different levels of GDP face different challenges and, consequently, policies and conditions favourable to entrepreneurship in one country (or region) may not be effective or favourable in another (Acs, 2006).

Nigeria provides a dynamic context in which to conduct research into entrepreneurial leadership since it is a developing economy and findings from such research may be applicable in similar countries. Acs (2006) argues that a balance needs to be struck between general conditions and the entrepreneurial framework conditions; however, that balance depends on the level of economic development. Recently, the Nigerian economy has faced numerous challenges which have impacted on its overall economic activity, and there have been declines in its real growth rates and GDP (National Bureau of Statistics, 2015b).

The focus of this research study is Nigeria's retail pharmaceutical market. The challenges faced by retail pharmacy entrepreneurs resonate with entrepreneurs generally. Many of these challenges include changing stakeholder demands, leadership skills, and inadequate capital and infrastructural facilities. The once stable system of health care has become unpredictable. While techno-entrepreneurs are faced with the impact of technology, retail pharmacy entrepreneurs are faced with demographic changes that affect the health system, technology, the influence of the market, and the "...increasing drive to integrate organisation and finance into a

seamless pattern of services” (O’Neil, 2000, p. 892). The implication of such large-scale changes is that retail pharmacy entrepreneurs are required to exhibit leadership skills to meet these diverse challenges. Therefore, in this study, entrepreneurial leadership in the context of the retail pharmacy sector in Nigeria is modelled with the aim of drawing more general conclusions which can be applied in other regions.

1.2 Scope of study

Blunt and Jones (1997) argue that most modern concepts of leadership originated from the Western world, and that people in developing countries are more intent on replicating these conceptions than in resisting them. However, Western views may be ineffective if applied uncritically to developing countries (Blunt and Jones, 1997). As a result, it is paramount that primary research on leadership in a developing country context is required for learning lessons rather than applying them.

The study presented in this thesis was conducted in Nigeria. The significance of examining Nigeria lies in the fact that it is an example of an economy facing challenges which are prevalent in many developing countries, namely political instability, poor infrastructure, and corruption (Nkechi et al., 2012). The retail pharmacy sector was selected for this study because of its importance to the Nigerian economy as well as the dynamic setting it provides. As stated by Euromonitor International (2013, p. 1), “The Nigerian retail environment achieved considerable growth over the review period (2013). This can mainly be attributed to the growing Nigerian population, which is generating increasing demand for retailers in the country.” In particular, the retail pharmacy industry provides an appropriate context for this study. With the increase in the number of online stores, retail pharmacy has become more competitive (Jambulingam et al., 2005). Pharmacies had been a very profitable business until the mid-1980s when managed care became dominant. The once stable and predictable system of health care has become an environment that is anything but stable: “In the current competitive health care environment, entrepreneurial leaders are needed to enable their organisations to succeed” (Guo, 2009, p. 23). As the Nigerian health care system has become increasingly susceptible

to market forces, it has become a less predictable setting for health professionals and consumers alike, and turbulence is expected to continue in the foreseeable future. Pharmacy entrepreneurs are also faced with demographic changes that affect the health system, technology, influence of the market, and the increasing drive to integrate organisation and financing into a seamless pattern of services. According to Erah (2003, p. 196), “Pharmacists practising in Nigeria have many challenges to address that are born of the rapid change being experienced in health care delivery over the last twenty years.” As advised by Pierpaoli and Hethcox (1997), one of the overarching leadership challenges for pharmacy managers is to convince all members in a practice setting of the need for new pharmaceutical care models, in contrast with traditional products and the control model of pharmacy services. The role of pharmacists has switched from mixing medications to retailing high quality manufactured products. As a result of this change as well as increased competition, the need for effective leadership has become paramount. Without highly competent, assertive leadership, the role of the pharmacist may become subsumed by those of other healthcare professionals (O'Neil, 2000).

1.3 Research aim

The aim of this study was to examine the concept of entrepreneurial leadership within the context of a developing economy, in an effort to understand the challenges entrepreneurs face in such a setting, and to determine the entrepreneurial leadership skills which are essential for success in the environment of a developing economy. Specifically, the focus of this research was on entrepreneurial leadership within the retail pharmacy sector in Nigeria. An interpretivist-constructionist approach was used to construct a theory of entrepreneurial leadership from the subjective experience of retail pharmacy entrepreneurial leaders and their employees.

1.4 Research objectives

To satisfy the research aim, five research objectives were developed as follows:

Research objective 1: to provide valid empirical evidence that contributes to the understanding of entrepreneurial leadership, particularly in the context of a developing economy.

Research Objective 2: to understand the lived experience¹ of entrepreneurs in a developing economy, namely Nigeria.

Research Objective 3: to identify the skills of effective entrepreneurial leaders.

Research Objective 4: to consider the role of entrepreneurial leadership skills in addressing the challenges faced by entrepreneurs in a developing economy.

Research Objective 5: to utilise empirical evidence to contribute to theory on entrepreneurial leadership.

1.5 Research questions

This study was performed in an effort to answer the following research questions, which were formulated after the literature review:

- What is entrepreneurial leadership?
- What are the challenges that entrepreneurs in a developing economy face in running their businesses?
- What entrepreneurial leadership skills are valuable for running businesses successfully in a developing economy?

¹ “Lived experience is man’s experience of life, [and its] main characteristics include authenticity, instantaneity, fluidity, integrity, and non-mystique” (Chang and Liu, 2010, p. 114). It is important in “...understanding the sense that owner-managers make of their here-and-now” (Pittaway and Thorpe, 2012, p. 840).

- What are the employees' perceptions of the entrepreneurial leadership of the entrepreneurs?

1.6 Definition of terms

Since this study was focused on a particular sector, it is important that key terms used throughout this thesis are defined to ensure a proper understanding of the context. Therefore, the following key terms are defined:

- **Developing Economy:** an economy with a gross national income per capita of less than US\$12,746 (World Bank, 2015).
- **Retail Pharmacy:** an organisation that is principally involved in selling and dispensing medication and drugs, as well as cosmetics and other household items to consumers.
- **Retail Pharmacy Entrepreneurs:** they are the founders of the retail pharmacies and they are usually pharmacists.
- **Pharmacists:** they are professionally registered experts in drug therapy who are involved in selling and dispensing drugs.
- **Followers:** these are the employees of the retail pharmacy entrepreneurs, and are paid for their services.
- **Drugs:** these are substances that have a therapeutic effect on the body.

1.7 Research methodology

The study is based on an interpretivist-constructionist perspective and has employed an abductive approach. Since the study is exploratory, and since the aim is to understand how entrepreneurial leaders display their leadership skills in a challenging and dynamic environment, a qualitative method (which encourages participation, and allows for an in-depth understanding of the meanings these individuals make of their world) was adopted for the study (Galloway and Haniff, 2015; Lee, 1999; Yin, 2003).

In previous research studies, only the perspective of the leaders has been considered in the examination of entrepreneurial leadership (Gupta et al., 2004). This research study therefore breaks new ground by also examining the phenomenon from followers' points of view. An interview guide based on the literature review findings was developed, and the questions were used to explore the perception of the entrepreneurial leadership skills of the retail pharmacy owners from the dual perspective of the entrepreneurs themselves and their employees. The main study involved 17 retail pharmacies located in Lagos, Nigeria. At each pharmacy, in-depth interviews were conducted with the founder of the business and (separately) with two long-serving employees, and so 51 respondents in total were involved in the study. Interviews were recorded and transcribed, and the proceedings were analysed using the software package NVivo 10.

Further details of the research philosophy, data collection and findings are provided in chapters 6 and 7.

1.8 Originality and contribution to knowledge

In this section, the originality of the thesis and its contribution to the canon of knowledge in the subject domain are described.

1.8.1 Originality

Originality is a major criterion used to evaluate academic scholarship. According to Guetzkow et al. (2004, p. 190), originality in research may involve any, or all, of the following criteria:

- Using a new approach, theory, method, or data
- Studying a new topic
- Doing research in an understudied area

- Providing new findings.

Furthermore, Phillips and Pugh (1994) (cited in Eggleston (2001, p. 62)) identified 14 different ways in which research can be original (illustrated in Table 1):

Table 1 Originality of research

<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Setting down a major piece of new information in writing for the first time 2. Continuing a previously original piece of work 3. Carrying out original work designed by a senior colleague 4. Providing a single original technique, observation or result in an otherwise unoriginal but competent piece of research 5. Having many original ideas, methods and interpretations all performed by others under the direction of the writer 6. Showing originality in testing somebody else's idea by carrying out empirical work that has not been done before 7. Making a synthesis that has not been made before 8. Using already known material but with a new interpretation 9. Trying out something in one country that has previously only been done in other countries 10. Adopting a particularly well-known technique and applying it in a new area 11. Bringing new evidence to bear on an old issue 12. Being cross-disciplinary and using different methodologies 13. Looking at areas that people in the discipline have not considered before 14. Adding to knowledge in a way that has not previously been done
--

Therefore, this study can be said to be original on the basis of the fourth criterion set out by Guetzkow et al. (2004), and on the tenth, eleventh, thirteenth and fourteenth criteria by Phillips and Pugh (1994). These are summarised below:

1.8.1.1 New dimension to knowledge

In this study, a skill-based model for entrepreneurial leadership in a developing economy has been produced, thereby adding knowledge in a way that has not been previously done.

1.8.1.2 Application of a methodological technique in a new area

This study includes a systematic literature review, which is a detailed investigation of the new paradigm of entrepreneurial leadership. This has not been provided in any previous studies.

1.8.1.3 New evidence

Entrepreneurial leadership is a phenomenon, on which there exists sparse empirical research. This study provides new evidence on this phenomenon.

1.8.2 Contribution to knowledge

Contribution to knowledge is an important factor in any doctoral thesis, but its conceptualisation remains ambiguous. Phillips and Pugh (1994, p. 34) point out that a contribution to knowledge "...does not mean an enormous breakthrough which has the subject rocking on its foundation". However, the findings in a thesis should be proof that the researcher has a good grasp of how such activity is done in the relevant field (Cryer, 2006).

The study contributes to the canon of knowledge in the following ways:

1.8.2.1 Empirical contribution

- In this study, the entrepreneurial leadership skills which are essential in the retail pharmacy sector of a developing economy, and the training needs required for retail pharmacy entrepreneurs to run their organisations successfully, are identified.
- The study will serve as a valuable document for policy-making decisions by stakeholders such as the Pharmaceutical Society of Nigeria (PSN), the Pharmacists Council of Nigeria (PCN), the Association of Community Pharmacists of Nigeria (ACPN), and the Federal Republic of Nigeria.

1.8.2.2 Theoretical contribution

- Through this research, a skill-based model for entrepreneurial leadership in a developing economy was developed to address a significant knowledge gap in the literature.
- Although the focus of the study was on entrepreneurial leadership skills, additional attributes that influence entrepreneurial leadership were also identified, and these can be added to the lists provided in previous studies (for example, Nicholson, 1998; Swiercz and Lydon, 2002).

1.8.2.3 Methodological contribution

- This research included a systematic literature review, an approach which has not been applied in the domain of entrepreneurial leadership. The application of a systematic literature review will benefit researchers conducting future studies in this field.

1.9 Structure of the thesis

The thesis comprises nine chapters:

This introductory chapter (Chapter 1) covers the background and scope of the research study. The research aim, objectives and questions are set out in this chapter. Key terms used in this thesis, and the methodology employed in this study, have also been detailed, along with the study's originality and contribution to the canon of knowledge.

The literature review consists of four chapters (chapters 2, 3, 4 and 5). Chapter 2 contains an extensive review on leadership literature, including the concept and definition of leadership. Leadership research and theory are discussed in terms of their historical perspectives and emerging paradigms in the field. Chapter 3 concerns entrepreneurship, and includes definitions of entrepreneurship, and a discussion on the debates on entrepreneurship among scholars in this field. Various approaches to entrepreneurship are examined, and empirical findings for each perspective are provided. Entrepreneurship is examined as a process, as new venture creation, and as an art of opportunity recognition and exploitation. In Chapter 4, the role of entrepreneurship in a developing economy is discussed, and Nigeria is identified as an appropriate context for this particular research study. The geography, political and economic landscape of Nigeria is described. In this chapter, the retail pharmacy sector and the potential challenges facing them are also discussed. In the final part of the literature review (Chapter 5), a systematic literature review on entrepreneurial leadership is provided, whereby the main approaches to entrepreneurial leadership are identified, and evidence for each perspective is provided.

The research methodology employed is set out in Chapter 6, wherein the research approach and paradigm adopted are described in detail, and the research method employed in this study is justified. The data collection process and method of analysis are also described, and the ethical issues of the study are also considered.

In Chapter 7, the findings obtained from the semi-structured interviews with the retail pharmacy entrepreneurs and their employees are presented. The challenges faced by entrepreneurs in a developing economy are identified, and the entrepreneurial leadership skills necessary for success in this context are highlighted. The findings also confirm the importance of other variables in entrepreneurial leadership, namely attributes, culture, family, followers, resources, and experience.

In Chapter 8, the findings in relation to entrepreneurial leadership literature are detailed, and an empirical model of entrepreneurial leadership is presented and discussed. This skill-based model of entrepreneurial leadership covers the key skills required of entrepreneurs. In addition, the model suggests that although entrepreneurial leadership skills are important, there are other factors which are needed for combating challenges, and for recognising opportunities that will improve business performance. This chapter is concluded with a definition of entrepreneurial leadership, based on the findings in this study.

In Chapter 9, the contributions of the study and implications of the research are presented. The limitations of the study are discussed, and recommendations for future research are presented.

CHAPTER TWO – LITERATURE REVIEW

(PART 1): LEADERSHIP

2.1 Introduction

The number of published research studies in the field of leadership is vast and spans several decades. However, despite such a large body of scholarship, leadership still remains an elusive concept. Despite considerable investment in research by both governments and organisations, knowledge gaps about leadership still exist due to a lack of comprehensive information studies of the field (Leitch et al., 2009).

This chapter provides a comprehensive literature review on leadership. The aim is to provide a critical insight into leadership research. The first part of this chapter concerns the concept and definition of leadership. Thereafter, the evolution of leadership research and theory and their historical perspectives is discussed. In addition, emerging paradigms and theories of new approaches to leadership are identified and addressed. Finally, the chapter is concluded with a discussion on the current state of leadership research.

2.2 The definitions of leadership

To date there is no precise definition of the term Leadership. Stogdill (1974, p. 259) argued that “...there are almost as many different definitions of leadership as there are people who have attempted to define the concept”. This is evident, given the large volume of publications and studies relating to the domain of leadership. Upon entering the search string ‘lead*’ into Web of Knowledge, 5,485,535 publications were listed, and on SpringerLink, 2,676,974 publications in form of journals and books were identified as being relevant to the topic (12th November, 2013). Researchers have proposed varying concepts of leadership, and have investigated it by using different phenomena that suited them (Yukl, 2010). This is not surprising

because, although leadership is a universal phenomenon (Bass and Bass, 2009), it remains complex. Alvesson and Sveningsson (2003) argue that a universally acceptable definition for leadership is practically impossible, and will hinder new ideas and creative ways of thinking. Some of the different ways in which leadership has been defined over the past 70 years, with reference to conceptual underpinning, are listed in Table 2:

Table 2 Definitions of leadership

<i>Author</i>	<i>Definition</i>	<i>Concept</i>
Hemphill (1949)	The behaviour of an individual while he is involved in directing group activities.	Behaviour
Stogdill (1950)	“Leadership may be considered as the process (act) of influencing the activities of an organized group in its efforts toward goal setting and goal achievement.”	Process
Bennis (1959)	Leadership is “the process by which an agent induces a subordinate to behave in a desired manner”.	Process
Katz and Kahn (1978)	Leadership is “the influential increment over and above mechanical compliance with the routine directives of the organisation”.	Behavioural process
Smircich and Morgan (1982)	“Leadership is realised in the process whereby one or more individuals succeeds in attempting to frame and define the reality of other.” “It involves a complicity or process of negotiation through which certain individuals implicitly or explicitly surrender their power to define the nature of their experience to others.”	Process
Richards and Engle (1986)	“Leadership is about articulating visions, embodying values, and creating the environment within which things can be accomplished.”	Behaviour
Gardner (1990)	Leadership is “the process of persuasion or example by which an individual (or leadership team) induces a group to pursue objectives held	Process

	by the leader or shared by the leader and his or her follower.”	
Jacobs and Jaques (1990)	“Leadership is a process of giving purpose (meaningful direction) to collective effort, and causing willing effort to be expended to achieve purpose.”	Process
Kotter (1990)	Leadership “refers to a process that helps direct and mobilize people and/or their ideas...”	Process
Drath and Palus (1994)	“Leadership is the process of making sense of what people are doing together so that people will understand and be committed.”	Process
Clark and Clark (1996)	“Leadership is an activity or set of activities, observable to others, that occurs in a group, organization, or institution, and which involves a leader and followers who willingly subscribe to common purposes and work together to achieve them.”	Process
Barnard (1997)	Leadership “refers to the quality of the behaviour of individuals guiding other people or their activities in organized efforts”.	Behaviour
Stogdill (1997)	Leadership is “the process of influencing the activities of an organised group in its efforts towards goal-setting and goal achievement”.	Process
Robbins (1998)	Leadership is “the ability to influence a group toward the achievement of goals”.	Ability
Barker (2001)	Leadership is “a process of transformative change where the ethics of individuals are integrated into the mores of a community as a means of evolutionary social development”.	Process
Lussier and Achua (2001)	“Leadership is the influencing process of leaders and followers to achieve organizational objectives through change.”	Process
Northouse (2010)	“Leadership is a process whereby an individual influences a group of individuals to achieve a common goal.”	Process
Yukl (2010)	“Leadership is the process of influencing others to understand and agree about what needs to be done and how to do it, and the process of facilitating individual and collective efforts to accomplish shared objectives.”	Process

The definitions listed in the table above demonstrate how the perception of leadership has evolved from it being viewed as an ability or behaviour, to being viewed as a process of influence. The section below examines the different perspectives of leadership over the years.

2.3 Leadership research and theory: historical perspective, new paradigms, and critical review

2.3.1 Historical perspective

Leadership theories are plagued by the absence of a definitional consensus among scholars. Many theories have emerged about leadership over the years, and it might even be said that there are as many theories of leadership as there are leaders (Gill, 2011). According to House and Aditya (1997, p. 409-410),

“Almost all of the prevailing theories of leadership, and about 98% of the empirical evidence at hand, are rather distinctly American in character: individualistic rather than collectivistic, stressing follower responsibilities rather than rights, assuming hedonism rather than commitment to duty or altruistic motivation, assuming centrality of work and democratic value orientation, and emphasizing assumptions of rationality rather than asceticism, religion, or superstition.”

This suggests that leadership research over time has developed a bias towards the outlooks of the developed world; hence, more research is required, especially from a developing economy perspective, to better understand this phenomenon.

Many approaches on leadership have emerged over the years. The main theories which can be identified are the great man, trait, skill, behaviour, contingency, implicit leadership, leader-member exchange, servant, charismatic, transactional, transformational, distributed, authentic, and entrepreneurial leadership. Of these theories, entrepreneurial leadership is the least developed in terms of research and

theory (Dinh et al., 2014). The timeline during which these leadership theories² emerged is illustrated in Figure 1:

Figure 1 Timeline showing the approaches to leadership

In this section, a critical overview of these theories is therefore presented:

2.3.1.1 Great Man theory

The Great Man theory of leadership can be traced to the nineteenth century and before. One of the major proponents of this theory was Carlyle in 1866, whose “...fascination with great men of history effectively reduced the role of mere mortals to extras” (Grint, 2011, p. 8). Successful leaders who had shown greatness were examined; hence, the theories were called ‘Great Man theories’. The lives and achievements of political leaders such as Napoleon Bonaparte, Indira Ghandi, Martin Luther King and others have been studied to explain the difference between people

² A theory is a “...statement of concepts and their interrelationships that shows how and/or why a phenomenon occurs” (Corley and Gioia, 2011, p. 12)

who are leaders, and those who are non-leaders or followers. A fundamental notion of the Great Man theory is that people are born with traits that make them natural leaders, and only great individuals possess such traits. As stated by Bass and Bass (2009, p. 49), “Without Moses, according to these theorists, the Jews would have remained in Egypt; without Winston Churchill, the British would have given up in 1940; without Bill Gates, there would have been no firm like Microsoft.” However, this theory is based on fascination with great men of history and has been criticised for its failure to explore the role of leadership in ensuring business and organisational coherence (Grint, 2011).

2.3.1.2 Trait theory

The Great Man theory, which attributed innate qualities to special people, resulted in research into leadership that focused on the personality characteristics of the leader (Wright, 1996). Researchers and scholars sought to determine the specific traits that differentiated leaders from followers (Bass, 1990).

This theory led to an accumulation of a long list of traits. As stated by Wright (1996, p. 34), “The problem was not the fact that the research failed to find any relationship between personality and leadership, but that relationships found were inconsistent.” One of the most influential studies on traits was carried out by Stogdill (1948), which changed the course of this approach. In his study, he analysed 124 trait studies conducted between 1904 and 1947 and identified eight traits that differentiates a leader from a non-leader. These are:

- Intelligence
- Alertness to the needs of others
- Insight
- Initiative
- Responsibility
- Persistence in dealing with problems
- Self-confidence
- Sociability

Stogdill proposed that the making of a successful leader is not determined by some particular traits but, rather, the traits possessed must be relevant to the situation in which a leader finds him or herself. Therefore, a successful leader in a particular situation might be ineffective in another. The results of Stogdill's work led many scholars to re-examine their approach in the search for universal traits. House and Aditya (1997, p. 410) point out that, "It should be noted, however, that the most influential author to address this issue (Stogdill, 1948) did not call for an abandonment of the study of traits, but rather for an interactional approach in which traits would be considered as interacting with situational demands facing leaders." Mann (1959) went a stage further by examining more than 1400 findings regarding personality and leadership. He drew up a list of traits such as intelligence, masculinity, adjustment, extraversion, conservatism, and dominance, all of which had been considered as important; but then pointed out that there were inconsistencies in results of studies showing relationships between leadership and some of the traits such as dominance, extraversion and intelligence.

Many more scholars undertook further studies into traits, and endless lists of traits emerged. Traits such as dominance, high energy, achievement orientation, the need for power, a moderately low need for affiliation, internal locus of control, integrity, flexibility, self-confidence, stability, intelligence, sensitivity to others, and narcissism have been deemed as being important to leadership, according to researchers (Bass and Bass, 2009; Lord et al., 1986; Lussier and Achua, 2001; McClelland, 1965; 1975; 1985; Northouse, 2010; Yukl, 2010). Despite this long list of personality traits, the picture of personal qualities of leadership is still not complete (Gill, 2011). There is no evidence to prove that leaders who possess all the identified traits mentioned in prior studies will be effective. In addition, how realistic is it for a leader to possess all traits that have been associated with effective leadership? House and Aditya (1997, p. 410) suggest that, "One of the problems with early trait research was there was little empirically substantiated personality theory to guide the search for leadership." The broad range of traits has made them susceptible to various subjective interpretations, and the origin of these lists is not based on strong empirical research. Moreover, the trait approach does not effectively justify the role of leadership in entrepreneurial settings. However, in recent years the trait approach has re-emerged in the form of charismatic and transformational

leadership (that will be discussed later in this thesis). Despite the aforementioned criticisms, the trait theory still remains a popular theory of leadership due to its intuitive appeal and its use of benchmarks for identifying effective leaders (Northouse, 2010).

2.3.1.3 Skill theory

Although leadership studies began with the concept of the ‘Great Man’, in which a leader is seen as born and not made, Katz (1955) proposed a shift from a focus on personality traits, to an emphasis on skills and abilities of individuals that can be learned and developed (Northouse, 2010). Therefore, the major difference between the trait approach and the skill approach was that, unlike the traits (which were said to be innate and cannot be learned), skills or competencies could be developed. Katz (1955) put forward three skills which he argued were essential to being an effective administrator - technical, human, and conceptual skills. These leadership skills are diagrammatically presented in Figure 2:

Figure 2 Katz leadership skill set

Source: Katz (1955, 1974)

These skills have found merit among leadership scholars and are worthy of close scrutiny, and are discussed below:

Technical skills

Technical skill is the in-depth understanding of and the proficiency in a specific type of activity, particularly one involving methods, processes, procedures, or techniques (Katz, 1974). It includes competencies in a specialised area as well as analytical ability (Katz, 1955). This skill includes factual knowledge about the organisation, and its products and services. Such knowledge is usually obtained by a combination of training, formal education, and job experience (Haq, 2011; Yukl, 2010). To successfully guide subordinates and steer the organisation to success, an in-depth knowledge of the products and services offered is a prerequisite.

Technical skills have been shown to be an important factor in enhancing a leader's performance (Bass, 1990; Haq, 2011; Katz, 1955; Katz, 1974; Lord and Hall, 2005; Shiba, 1998). However, research has also shown that technical skills vary at different levels of management (McCall and Lombardo, 1983), becoming less relevant at higher levels of management (Bass, 1990; McCall and Lombardo, 1983; Northouse, 2010). However, recent research by Mumford et al. (2007) provides contrary evidence, with the inference that higher levels of an organisation require higher levels of all leadership skills. Although no consensus may have been reached on whether technical skills become more or less important as an individual moves up the organisational ladder, there is an agreement among scholars that technical skills are required in every leader. Indeed, it can be argued that technical skills are even more important for an entrepreneur. Research on entrepreneurs who established successful companies suggests that technical knowledge is the fertile ground in which seeds of inspiration yields innovative products (Westley and Mintzberg, 1989). In addition, it is not sufficient for entrepreneurs to have extensive technical knowledge of their own products and services; knowledge of their competitors in this respect is also vital (Yukl, 2010).

Researchers have classified these skills under sub-components such as business skills (Mumford et al., 2007; Siewiorek et al., 2012) and technological skills (Zaccaro and Klimoski, 2001), or under the broader umbrella term of task skills (Lord and Hall, 2005). Leaders of today's organisations are expected to possess business skills, which relate to managing material, human, and financial resources (Katz, 1974; Luthans et al., 1988; Mumford et al., 2007). The effective management of these resources form the bedrock of any successful business, and any individual

who possesses such skills stands a greater chance of succeeding in such a dynamic and turbulent environment.

Human skills

Human skills involve the knowledge and ability to work with people. These include knowledge about human behaviour and group processes; the ability to understand other people's feelings, attitudes, and motives; and, the ability to communicate unambiguously and persuasively (Yukl, 2010). In addition, human skills, as cited in Mumford et al. (2007, p. 157), includes "...skills required for coordination of actions of oneself and others (Gillen and Carroll, 1985; Mumford et al., 2000b), negotiation skills for reconciling differences among employee perspectives and establishing mutually satisfying relationships (Copeman, 1971; Mahoney et al., 1963; Mahoney et al., 1965; Mintzberg, 1973); and, persuasion skills to influence others to more effectively accomplish organizational objectives (Katz, 1974; Mintzberg, 1973; Yukl, 1989)". It is these skills that help a leader to work effectively with their subordinates to achieve the set objectives of the organisation. In short, human skills are people skills (Northouse, 2010) and without such skills, the capacity to get along with other people is almost impossible.

Human skills form the basis for leadership, since leadership is about influencing people. Hence, the focus of possessing such skills cannot be overemphasised. These skills are not limited to just influencing other people, but also include understanding their perspectives, and seeing matters from their points of view. Hence, leaders ought to be empathetic. The human skill perspective, first introduced by Katz (1955), is broad, and has since been broken down into several components. Even Katz (1974) introduced social skills in conjunction with human skills, while many other researchers have preferred the term "interpersonal skills" (Haq, 2011; Mumford et al., 2007; Wright and Taylor, 1994; Yukl, 2010). Under the broad reach of human skills, skills such as empathy (Yukl, 2010), self- or meta-monitoring; adjustment of one's behaviour to fit the situation (Lord and Hall, 2005), and influence and management tactics (Harris et al., 2007) have been placed. As with technical skills, researchers have shown that human skills are important in management as well as in leadership (Bass, 1990; Boyatzis, 1982; McCall and Lombardo, 1983; Wright and

Taylor, 1994). However, unlike technical skills, Katz (1955; 1974) suggests that human skills are equally important at any level of management.

Conceptual skills

As the name implies, conceptual skills involve dealing with concepts and ideas. People who possess such skills are comfortable with hypothetical notions and abstractions. According to Yukl (2010), conceptual skills include good judgement, foresight, intuition, creativity, and the ability to understand ambiguous and uncertain events. The leader who possesses conceptual skills sees the enterprise as a whole, and recognises how its various functions depend on one another and how changes in any part may affect the whole (Schedlitzki and Edwards, 2014).

Conceptual skills have been referred to as cognitive skills by a number of scholars such as Katz (1955; 1974) and Mumford et al. (2007). Some researchers use the term “cognitive abilities” (Mumford et al., 2000a; Mumford et al., 2000b; Mumford et al., 2000c; Mumford et al., 2000d; Zaccaro et al., 2000). Whatever label is used, skills in this area are key to leadership, and include proficiency in oral communication (Shipper and Dillard, 2000); written communication (Wright, 1996); active listening (Graham, 1983); active learning (Jacobs and Jacques, 1987); critical thinking (Gillen and Carroll, 1985); analysing the strengths and weaknesses of approaches taken; and, cognitive complexity (Yukl, 2010), which refers to the ability to identify complex relations and to provide creative solutions to problems.

Leaders need conceptual skills for effective organisation and planning. To succeed in any organisation, leaders need to understand how its components work, and how changes, especially in the external environment, will affect its competitive position. Strategic skills are conceptual skills that include dealing with ambiguity, and exerting an influence in the organisation (Mumford et al., 2007; Siewiorek et al., 2012). Those enable leaders to recognise relationships between problems and opportunities, and to implement appropriate strategies to deal with them (Mumford et al., 2007).

Katz proposed that the need for conceptual skills increases as an individual ascends to higher levels of management. Researchers have shown an increased requirement

for conceptual skills in higher levels of the organisational hierarchy (Mumford et al., 2007; Pavett and Lau, 1983). Indeed, Mumford et al. (2007) showed that strategic skills, which are highly conceptual skills, only fully emerge at the highest levels in an organisation.

Many scholars lament that the conceptualisation of leadership skills has received insufficient attention (for example, Mumford et al., 2007; Wright, 1996; Yammarino, 2000). Mumford et al. (2007) has appealed for a greater focus on leadership skills with the argument that leaders can become better leaders. By learning and developing even better leadership skills, an individual will be able to lead more effectively, as well as influence people to accomplish set goals and objectives (Siewiorek et al., 2012). According to Gordon and Yukl, (2004, p. 364), “More research is needed on traits and skills that seem especially relevant for leadership in a complex, turbulent environment (e.g. emotional intelligence, social intelligence, systems thinking, situational awareness, personal integrity).” In today’s volatile and turbulent business environment, the importance of possessing leadership skills cannot be overemphasised.

2.3.1.4 Behavioural theory

The inconsistencies in the evidence for the trait theory led researchers to pay attention to what leaders actually do, and not what they inherently possess. The focus of behavioural theory is on how leaders behave towards their subordinates in various contexts (Northouse, 2010; Wright, 1996).

There have been four pivotal studies on the behavioural theory on leadership. The first one was carried out in the early 1930s at Iowa State University by Kurt Lewin and his associates, who focused on the leadership style of managers (Lewin et al., 1939). In their study, they identified two leadership styles: the autocratic leadership style (which involves telling the employees what to do), and the democratic leadership style (which encourages participation in decision making). The second group of studies were carried out at Ohio State University, which were done concurrently with the third group of studies at the University of Michigan (Kahn,

1956). Based on the “fruitlessness” (Northouse, 2010, p. 70) of the results of trait studies, the Ohio State researchers decided to analyse how individuals acted when they led organisations. Using questionnaires, they identified behaviours that they grouped into two categories: initiating structure, and consideration (Stogdill, 1974). Initiating structure behaviour “...involves [a] leader’s concern for accomplishing the task. The leader defines and structures his or her own role and the role of subordinates towards attainment of task goals” (Yukl, 2010, p. 104); while consideration behaviours are “...essentially relationship behaviours and include camaraderie, respect, trust, and like between leaders and followers” (Northouse, 2010, p. 70). The Ohio State University researchers viewed these two behaviours as being independent and distinct; hence, a leader could be competent both in terms of consideration and initiating structure behaviours. Their views contrasted with the findings of the University of Michigan researchers, who identified two types of leadership behaviour: employee orientation, and production orientation (Northouse, 2010). The University of Michigan researchers proposed that both behaviours were of the same continuum and not opposite forms, making the measurement one-dimensional (Lussier and Achua 2001; Northouse, 2010); hence, leaders who are more oriented towards production will care less about the needs of their employees, and vice versa.

Studies carried out at the Ohio and Michigan universities laid the foundation for perhaps the most popular model of leadership behaviour, known as the Blake and Mouton managerial grid, and also referred to as the leadership grid (Daft, 1999; Northouse, 2010). Using the two-dimensional axes of concern for people and concern for tasks or results, leaders are grouped into five leadership styles: authority compliance (9, 1), country club management (1, 9), impoverished management (1, 1), middle of the road management (5, 5), and team management (9, 9). Blake and Mouton (1985) argued that the most effective leader is the team manager who shows high concern for both tasks and people. However, the empirical basis for the grid has been criticised by various researchers (Gill, 2011; Northouse, 2010; Yukl, 1999). As stated by Yukl (1999, p. 34), “Studies on the implications of the two behaviours for leadership have not yielded consistent results. Survey studies using behaviour description questionnaires failed to provide much support for the idea that effective leaders have high scores on both dimensions.” In some situations, it may be

necessary to adopt a more people-oriented perspective, while in other situations a task-oriented approach may be more effective.

Generally, studies into behavioural theory have failed to consider the situational contingencies associated with leadership. As with the trait research, the behavioural theory is limited on the basis of theory building and orientation (House and Aditya, 1997; Yukl, 1999). The task and relationship-based categories proposed in earlier studies do not include all types of leadership behaviour. Important behaviours that are relevant to understanding leadership (such as envisioning, leading by example, management of meaning and values) are absent (Gill, 2011; Yukl, 1999).

In conclusion, behavioural theory has marked a major shift of focus in leadership research. However, as with the trait approach, it is plagued by inconsistencies in research results, and researchers have not been able to prove exactly how leadership styles are associated with performance outcomes (Gill, 2011; Northouse, 2010; Yukl, 1999). The knowledge of the impact of situation and context in leadership, together with the inability of researchers to identify universal behaviours associated with effective leadership, led to the evolution of contingency theory.

2.3.1.5 Contingency theory

Due to weaknesses in past research findings concerning leader behaviours and effectiveness, scholars moved towards a contingency theory in an effort to redress the shortcomings of the behavioural theory (Cogliser and Brigham, 2004). The contingency theory proposes that there is no optimum style of leadership. Effective leaders will use different styles based on the contingencies of the situation; hence, a style of leadership which was ideal in the past might not be of great use in the present. This model to leadership has appealed to many researchers, the most prominent of whom is Fiedler, who proposed the contingency theory in the late 1960s (Gill, 2011). Fiedler's (1978) theory suggests that leadership effectiveness depends on how well the personality of the leader fits the situation or context. Fiedler proposed the least preferred co-worker (LPC) scale, with which the personality of the leader could be measured as being relationship-motivated or task-

motivated. Fiedler (1978) suggested that situational favourableness can be characterised by leader-member relations, task structure, and position power. A situation is highly favourable when there is a good relationship between the leader and the group, a clear cut structure, and when the leader has strong position power. Whereas, a situation is least favourable when there are poor leader-member relations, unstructured tasks, and weak leader position power (Fiedler, 1997; Gill, 2011; Northouse, 2010). Based on their findings, it is said that people who are task-motivated (i.e. low LPC score) will be suited for highly favourable and unfavourable conditions, while those that are relationship-motivated (i.e. high LPC score) will be more effective in moderately favourable situations (Fiedler, 1978; Fiedler, 1997). The contingency theory proposed by Fiedler does not require that leaders be effective in every situation; instead, only those who are ideal for that situation should be allowed to lead, and a leader with the wrong attributes could cause an operation to fail.

The contingency theory-based research carried out by Fiedler has also been criticised for inconsistent results (Gill, 2011; Northouse, 2010; Wright, 1996; Yukl, 2010). It is difficult to validate the findings of the Fiedler model (Yukl, 2010), as they are built on the measurement of leadership style using the LPC scale, which itself has not been validated. Although Fiedler's model has broadened scholars' knowledge and understanding of leadership by bringing situation into perspective, it fails to explain why people with certain leadership styles are more effective in particular contexts than others (Northouse, 2010). Fiedler's approach concerned task-oriented and relationship-oriented leaders, while later research has shown that most leaders have a balance of both behaviours. As stated by Yukl (2010, p. 168), "The model (and most of the research) neglects medium LPC leaders, who probably outnumber the high and low LPC leaders. Research suggests that medium LPC leaders are more effective than high or low LPC leaders in a majority of situations (five of the eight octants), presumably because they balance concern for the tasks and concern for relationships more successfully."

In conclusion, the contingency theory has highlighted that situation needs to be considered when assessing leadership behaviour. In a world plagued with change, the idea that leaders in organisations must be able to adapt their behaviour to meet different situations is important. Despite their contribution, early contingency

theories possessed many conceptual weaknesses that made these theories difficult to validate and use (Yukl, 2011). The ambiguity of findings in relation to the early contingency theories led to a wane in scholarly interest (House and Aditya, 1997; Yukl, 2011). Scholars tuned their attention to other approaches, the most prominent of which was the concept of implicit leadership.

2.3.1.6 Implicit leadership theories

Just as leaders make attributions about their follower's ability and competence, followers in turn make attributions about the expected behaviour and traits of their leaders (Yukl, 2010). The implicit leadership theories represent a shift to an attributional perspective on leadership. Leadership is viewed subjectively from the lens of the followers. It involves leadership as a permanent entrenched part of the socially constructed reality by individuals; it is therefore a romanticized conception of leadership by those who are led (Meindl et al., 1985). The conceptualisation of implicit leadership theory is based on the work of Calder (1977) (see Lord et al., 1982; Lord et al., 1984; Lord and Maher, 1993; Phillips and Lord 1981), who proposed an attribution theory of leadership, in which followers use information based on a leader's actions and performance to reach conclusions about the competence of their leader. The implicit leadership theories represent a shift in focus, from the traits and behaviour of leaders, towards addressing how individuals perceive their leaders and the cognitive processes of the evaluation of their leaders. Lord and Maher (1991, p. 11) refer to leadership "...as a process of being perceived by others as a leader". Hence, they put forward the notion that no matter what traits or behaviours are present in an individual, if the subordinates do not perceive a person to be a leader, then the individual is not a leader. Lord and Maher (1993) argue that the perception of leadership by the followers is dependent on the traits and behaviour identified by them as well as the outcomes produced by their leaders. For example, an individual who is courageous, intelligent, and assertive could be regarded as a good leader, based on the followers' innate perception of these traits as being important for leadership. In addition, positive performance outcomes by the leader will also foster followers' perception that leaders possess such traits.

However, implicit leadership theories also have limitations that need to be considered, one of which is the validity of the method. The credibility of implicit leadership theories are affected by biased ratings in leadership behaviour questionnaires (Yukl, 2010). Researchers such as Bryman (1987) have expressed concern about the validity and meaning of the questionnaire measures. As stated by Yukl (2010, p. 249), “When relevant and irrelevant aspects of behaviour are confounded in the same questionnaire, it is difficult to interpret the results from research that uses it.”

In conclusion, implicit leadership theories represent a major shift from actual leadership behaviour to perceived leadership behaviour. They acknowledge the importance of the social construction of leadership by the followers. However, irrational observers will hold biased perceptions of leadership performance.

2.3.1.7 Leader-member exchange theory

Most of the early theories on leadership focused on leader’s behaviours and traits, or on the follower and the context in which leadership is enacted. The leader-member exchange theory takes a psycho-dynamic approach by conceptualising leadership based on the relationship and interaction between leaders and followers. The approach was proposed by Graen and his colleagues (Dansereau et al., 1975; Graen and Cashman, 1975), and was originally referred to as the vertical dyad linkage theory (VDL). The basic premise of this theory is that leaders develop different types of relationships with individual group members which are known as dyads. Graen and Cashman (1975) proposed that subordinates are members of either an in-group or an out-group. The in-group members develop a close relationship with the leader based on trust, respect, negotiation, and mutual influence (Dansereau et al., 1975; Graen and Uhl-Bien, 1995; Liden and Maslyn, 1998). The out-group members do not possess a close relationship with the leader; rather, the relationship is transactional, bound to employment contracts, and characterised by low trust, respect, and obligation (Graen and Uhl-Bien, 1995). Therefore, subordinates make their way into in-groups by doing extra work for their managers, while the out-group

members do little more than that which is specified for their jobs (or to use a colloquial phrase, “the bare minimum”).

Research findings on leader-member exchange and its impact in an organisation has also been plagued by inconsistencies and contradictory results. As stated by House and Aditya (1997, p. 433), “However, closer scrutiny indicates that empirical findings relating LMX (leader-member exchange) to dependent variables are mixed and less supportive of the theory than Graen and Uhl-Bien imply.” Controversy still surrounds the authenticity and efficacy of the leader-member exchange theory (see Gill, 2011; House and Aditya, 1997; Northouse, 2010; Wright, 1996; and Yukl, 2010). A prominent issue in this respect is the validity of the leader-member exchange scale that is used to measure the relationship between leaders and followers. The issue of discrimination and equality has also been a bone of contention. Works by Sias and Jablin (1995) and Scandura (1999) show that differentiating subordinates into in-groups and out-groups could be detrimental to the effectiveness of the organisation and may lead to conflict.

2.3.1.8 Servant leadership theory

Servant leadership theory represents a radical shift from the perception of a leader as an all-knowing individual to that of a selfless servant. There is an increasing concern in management research that in order to succeed as an organisation, people need to be empowered and the long term welfare of the followers must come first (Smith et al., 2004; Yukl, 2010). This is the basis of servant leadership. Servant leadership itself is a paradoxical concept because people view servants and leaders as entirely different people and it can be difficult to conceptualise an individual as being both at the same time.

The root of this type of leadership is grounded in the works of Greenleaf (1977). According to Greenleaf (1998, p. 19),

“The servant-leader is servant first... It begins with the natural feeling that one wants to serve, to serve first. Then conscious choices bring one to aspire to lead. That person is sharply different from one who is leader first, perhaps

because of the need to assuage an unusual power or to acquire material possessions.”

According to Greenleaf, servant leaders put their service before self-interest, earn trust by being trustworthy, help others to discover themselves, and listen actively to the problems of the group rather than impose their will on others (Daft, 1999). The focus of this type of leadership is similar to stewardship and has been used synonymously with spiritual leadership (Sendjaya and Sarros, 2002). However, unlike stewardship (which involves empowerment of employees); servant leadership goes further and calls for the highest level of selflessness (Lussier and Achua, 2001). There has been increased interest in the acceptance of the servant leadership theory proposed by Greenleaf (e.g. Russell and Stone, 2002; Sendjaya and Sarros, 2002; Smith et al., 2004; Spears, 1998). Spears (1998) identified ten characteristics of a servant leader:

- Listening
- Empathy
- Healing
- Awareness
- Persuasion
- Conceptualisation
- Foresight
- Stewardship
- Commitment to the growth of people
- Community building

Russell and Stone (2002) go further and identify 20 attributes that are important in servant leadership. These are categorised into functional attributes (which are identifiable characteristics necessary to enact leadership responsibilities), and accompanying attributes (which supplement the functional attributes). A list of the functional and accompanying attributes is provided in Table 3 below:

Table 3 Functional and accompanying attributes

Functional Attributes	Accompanying attributes
Vision	Communication
Honesty	Credibility
Integrity	Competence
Trust	Stewardship
Service	Visibility
Modelling	Influence
Pioneering	Persuasion
Appreciation of others	Listening
Empowerment	Encouragement
	Teaching
	Delegation

Source: Russell and Stone (2002, p. 147).

Many researchers have argued that servant leadership is essential for organisational success. Smith et al. (2004) contrasted transformational and servant leadership, and proposed that servant leadership is more effective than transformational leadership in stable environments such as non-profit, voluntary, and religious organisations. They also argued that the efficacy of servant leadership is based on the life cycle stage of the organisation. At the maturity stage, when concern for employees and personal growth is paramount, servant leadership is the most effective form of leadership. A lack of servant leadership will create a dysfunctional, unproductive job environment (Bausch, 1998). Sendjaya and Sarros (2002) examined the philosophical foundation of servant leadership, and suggested that servant leaders take on both the role and nature of a servant. They rebutted the claim by other researchers that servant leadership is not ideal in organisations, by stating that it exists and will continue to do so.

Although this type of leadership has been recognised in literature, there is insufficient empirical evidence available which can justify its validity. Yukl (2010) argues that most evidence about the impact of servant leadership consists of anecdotal accounts and case studies of historical leaders. Most accounts are descriptive and have not been tested by qualitative or quantitative research

methodologies (Northouse, 2010). As a result, researchers have developed different constructs to define servant leadership (e.g. Barbuto and Wheeler, 2006; Laub et al., 1999; Liden et al., 2008; and Page and Wong, 2000). The numerous constructs developed are proof that researchers conceptualise and measure servant leadership differently, which only increases the need for a uniform approach to measuring the phenomenon.

The efficacy of servant leadership in all settings has aroused controversy among researchers. Gill (2011) argues that servant leadership theories ignore the many demands that an organisation presents, especially in business where stakeholders' welfare and satisfaction comes before the interests of the employees. Servant leadership also fails to explain clearly how such a leader will cope when drastic measures such as downsizing have to be carried out to improve organisational performance (Yukl, 2010). With organisations needing to cope with change and increasing turbulence, servant leadership may not be suitable in a dynamic context. Although, Russell and Stone (2002, p. 154) state that, "Servant leadership is a concept that potentially change organisations and societies because it stimulates both personal and organisational metamorphosis." Research has shown that servant leadership may only be suitable in stable environments such as religious institutions, and may not be effective in more dynamic contexts (e.g. Smith et al., 2004); hence, future research is required to clarify how servant leadership could influence followers, and the ideal situation that guarantees its efficacy.

2.3.1.9 Charismatic leadership theory

After many years of comparative neglect, there has been a resurgence of interest in both traits and behavioural aspects of leadership in the form of charismatic leadership. The word "charisma" is a Greek word that means a gift of God's grace or divine power (Conger, 2011, p. 87). The current theories of charismatic leadership were strongly influenced by Max Weber. According to Weber (1947), charisma occurs when a leader emerges with a radical vision that offers solution to a crisis or problem and, as a result, enables followers to believe in the vision (Yukl, 2010). Following the work of Weber, several theorists proposed versions of theories

concerning charismatic leadership in organisations (e.g. Conger and Kanungo, 1987; 1998; House, 1977). For Conger and Kanungo (1987; 1998), charisma is an attribute based on the follower's perception of their leader's behaviour. The leader's qualities of dynamism, strategic insight, vision, and the ability to motivate are important traits that appear as extraordinary to subordinates, who in turn show a natural inclination towards them (Wright, 1996). Charismatic leaders empower their subordinates by providing opportunities to accomplish difficult tasks. For Conger and Kanungo (1998), charismatic leaders are not autocratic, but inspire with emotional appeal. They identify opportunities that others have failed to recognise and exploit, and thus endear their followers to them. House (1977), a proponent of charismatic leadership in organisations, outlined the leadership behaviours, traits, and situational variables associated with charismatic leadership. He suggested that charismatic leaders are self-confident, and have a strong conviction in their own abilities and beliefs. These leaders also have the ability to dominate and influence others. House (1977) theorised that charismatic leaders communicate high expectations for their followers as well as confidence in their subordinates' abilities to meet them. In concert with Weber, House contends that charismatic leadership is seen in settings marked by distress where subordinates feel the need for someone to come to their aid. As with many leadership theories, House's (1977) theory had its shortcomings. Important components of charismatic leadership such as self-sacrifice and unconventional behaviour were omitted, with leadership being viewed more as a dyadic process than as a collective one (Conger, 2011). This led to a revision of House's theory by Shamir et al. (1993), who proposed that through charismatic leadership, followers' self-concepts could be transformed by the use of intrinsic rewards. Followers should view their work as an expression of themselves and identify collectively with the organisation. For Shamir et al. (1993), charismatic leadership relates to personal and social identification with the leader, and internalization of the leader's values.

Charismatic leadership theory makes an important contribution to the study of leadership by emphasising the importance of the influence of leaders on their followers. However, charismatic leadership theory has been heavily criticised (House and Aditya, 1997; Wright, 1996; Yukl, 2010). It is built on the emergence of leadership under crisis, but businesses are not always facing a crisis. The concept of charismatic leadership stemmed from the observation of symbolic figures and great

leaders such as Winston Churchill, Martin Luther King, and a host of other leaders; however, research on charismatic leadership has failed to distinguish between positive and negative charisma. Can Adolf Hitler be said to be a charismatic leader? As with early trait theories, charisma is an “all or nothing matter” (Wright, 1996, p. 212) - one either has it or does not.

2.3.1.10 Transactional leadership theory

Transactional leadership is deeply rooted in the notion of the path goal theory, which is based on contingent rewards. The transactional theory was introduced by Burns (1978) and has been influential ever since (Gavan O’ Shea et al., 2009).

A transactional leader motivates followers through exchanges that appeal to their self-interests. According to Bass (1985), transactional leadership involves contingent rewards, and management-by-exception. Contingent rewards involve the use of incentives to motivate subordinates. Followers are made aware of the standard of performance expected, and the rewards that they can obtain once they meet the necessary standards. Management-by-exception, a concept which was later modified in subsequent research by Bass and Avolio (1990), can either be active or passive. In the active form, the leader seeks out mistakes while watching the followers, and enforces rules or takes coercive action to deter followers from making subsequent mistakes (Northouse, 2010; Yukl, 2010). With the passive form, the leader only intervenes after errors have occurred (hence, taking a passive approach).

A major source of controversy surrounding transactional leadership theory is based on the use of contingent rewards to influence subordinates. As stated by Gill (2011, p. 83) “... while this can result in short term achievement, it runs the risk of stifling human development, with the consequent loss of competitive advantage”. It should be noted, however, that subsequent research by scholars has shown that contingent rewards are valuable in enhancing job attitude and organisational effectiveness (Bass, 1985; Gavan O’Shea et al., 2009). But although transactional leadership has been particularly effective in business settings (Judge and Piccolo, 2004), there still remains an argument about its usefulness in diverse entrepreneurial settings.

2.3.1.11 Transformational leadership theory

During the 1970s and 1980s, when the environment confronting many organisations became more turbulent, researchers became more interested in how leadership could effect change. This focus led to the development of what has become known as transformational leadership. For the past 30 years, transformational leadership has been the most debated and studied aspect in the domain of leadership (Daiz-Saenz, 2011). The phrase “transformational leadership” was first coined by Dowton in 1973 (Daiz-Saenz, 2011; Northouse, 2010), but as with transactional leadership, it was Burns (1978) who brought it to wide prominence in his book, *Leadership*. At the same time during when Burns proposed the theory of transformational leadership, House (1977) published his theory on charismatic leadership. These approaches to leadership are often considered to be synonymous (Northouse, 2010).

For Burns (1978) and Bass (1985), transformational leadership involves stimulating followers to go beyond their self-interests in order to achieve organisational goals or objectives. Using a multifactor leadership questionnaire (MLQ), Bass (1985) developed a model for transformational leadership consisting of behaviours, namely idealised influence, inspirational motivation, intellectual stimulation, and individualised consideration. In addition to the model of transformational leadership proposed by Bass (1985), and Bass and Avolio (1994) (with modifications by other researchers), several other scholars have tried to redefine transformational leadership by incorporating vision which has led to the concept of visionary leadership (e.g. Bennis and Nanus, 1985; Kouzes and Posner, 1987; 2002).

Empirical research has shown that transformational leadership behaviours have a favourable effect on followers’ performance and satisfaction (Dionne et al., 2004). Nevertheless, as with extant theories of leadership, conceptual weaknesses and limitations have been observed by researchers (e.g. Diaz-Saenz, 2011; Gill, 2011; Northouse, 2010; Wright, 1996; Yukl, 2010). Though the validity of the MLQ in assessing transformational leadership has been confirmed by many researchers (e.g. Judge and Piccolo, 2004; Lowe et al., 1996; Yammarino et al., 1993), Carless (1998) proposed that it assesses only a single construct and is not valuable in measuring distinct transformational leadership behaviours. This stance was supported by

Podsakoff et al. (1990), and as a result, these researchers developed their own scale for measuring transformational leadership.

Furthermore, transformational theory tends to give much credit to the leader, at the expense of other factors (Diaz-Saenz, 2011). Transformational leadership has been seen as a “better” approach than transactional leadership, resulting in the latter being viewed more negatively (Dionne et al., 2004). However, studies have shown that transactional leadership may be a more effective style in stable and predictable environments (Lowe et al., 1996). In business and entrepreneurial settings, the role of contingent rewards in motivating staff members may be appropriate.

In conclusion, transformational leadership provides leaders with a broader view of the behaviours necessary for effectiveness. However, a more rigorous research is required to determine how these behaviours may improve subordinates’ responses and organisational effectiveness.

2.3.1.12 Distributed leadership theory

Another way of conceptualising leadership that has emerged in recent years is that of distributed leadership. The term “distributed leadership” has been used interchangeably with terms such as shared leadership, team leadership, participative leadership, and democratic leadership by some researchers. It is a type of leadership that involves interaction between people and their situation (Spillane, 2005). Leadership is dispersed among all members, and is not merely a function of a single leader’s action (Gronn, 2002; Spillane, 2005). Distributed leadership does not involve a single individual, but is a collective effort of the group. The traditional approach to understanding leadership examined it as a vertical process, whereby the individual’s skills, traits or behaviour in different situations are important for effective leadership; hence, there has been much research on ways of improving the skills and behaviours, or on influencing the context. The proponents of distributed leadership argue that it is impossible for an individual to have all the skills and knowledge necessary for effective leadership (e.g. Gronn, 2002; Harris, 2004;

Spillane et al., 2001). Followers, and the ways in which the leaders interact with them in different situations, must also be considered.

The construct of distributed leadership varies among different researchers. Some researchers view distributed leadership as an emergent property of a group or network of individuals (Bennet et al., 2003; Gronn, 2002), while others view it as either a democratic or autocratic process (Spillane, 2005). The common theme among researchers is that distributed leadership does involve responsibilities being shared across a team, either formally or informally. Several authors have considered the impact of distributed leadership in organisational effectiveness (e.g. Ensley et al., 2006; Mehra et al., 2006; Pearce and Sims, 2002), and have found a positive influence. In the field of entrepreneurship, distributed leadership has also been shown to be effective (e.g. Cope et al., 2011; Jones and Crompton, 2009). Jones and Crompton (2009) provided empirical evidence to support a more distributed leadership approach by entrepreneurs. Cope et al. (2011) have gone further by exploring distributed leadership in a small business context, stressing the difficulty of its implementation.

In conclusion, researchers have shown that the orientation of small businesses makes the implementation of distributed leadership difficult. Therefore, it could be suggested that distributed leadership may not be feasible in every context, especially in small businesses where subordinates may resist empowerment.

2.3.1.13 Authentic leadership theory

Authentic leadership research, which became widely recognised in 2003, “...has since attracted considerable theoretical attention and continues to figure prominently in practitioners’ treatment of leadership” (Caza and Jackson, 2011, p. 352). The scandals in companies such as Enron and in the banking sector have fuelled an increased interest in a leadership approach, which embodies integrity and increases trust within organisations. The result is a proposed theory of authentic leadership. In the past decade, this has become a major focus in academic journals such as *Leadership Quarterly*, *The Journal of Management Studies*, and *The European*

Management Journal (Ladkin and Taylor, 2010). Authentic leadership research is primarily formative, and the concept is still being defined (Caza and Jackson, 2011; Northouse 2010). The development of the theory arose from the shortcomings of transformational leadership with respect to ethics. The ethical basis for transformational leadership has been questioned by many researchers, since it is recognised that a leader may manipulate followers in order to attain their goals. For example, Howell and Avolio (1992) provided empirical evidence which supported the contentious assumption that transformational leaders do not need to be ethical. Although Bass and Steidlmeier (2004) responded to this criticism by differentiating between authentic and pseudo-transformational leaders, authentic leadership theory stresses the role of ethics and integrity from the onset of leadership (Caza and Jackson, 2011). There is a growing interest in authentic leadership by practitioners and researchers alike (e.g. Avolio and Gardner, 2005; Eagly, 2005; Gardner and Schermerhorn Jr, 2004; Ilies et al., 2005; Ladkin and Taylor, 2010; May et al., 2003; Sparrowe, 2005; Walumbwa et al., 2008; Yammarino et al., 2008). While there is no single acceptable definition of authentic leadership (Northouse, 2010), certain elements are shared by researchers as essential attributes of authentic leaders, namely self-knowledge, clarity of their values, and enacting their roles based on their values and convictions (Shamir and Eilam, 2005).

Luthans' and Avolio's (2003, p. 243) defined authentic leadership as "...a process that draws from both positive psychological capacities and a highly developed organizational context which results in both greater self-awareness and self-regulated positive behaviours on the part of leaders and associates, fostering positive self-development". This is generally regarded as the starting point of the research into this domain. However, there have been arguments against the inclusion of a moral dimension in authentic leadership (Shamir and Eilam, 2005). The concept of authentic leaders being self-aware of their abilities (proposed by George, 2003) and still behaving in an inconsistent manner has been criticised by some researchers (e.g. Kernis, 2003). Eagly (2005) suggests that for authenticity to produce positive outcomes, it must be acknowledged by followers; hence, authentic leadership is two-dimensional and relational. Despite the growing interest in and theories proposed by scholars on authentic leadership, there exists little underpinning empirical evidence.

2.4 Conclusion

In the first section of this chapter, the concept of leadership and its different definitions were examined, and the different approaches and theories of leadership were evaluated. The Great Man theory focuses on heroic individuals, implying that only a selected few can achieve greatness. The trait theory conceptualises leadership on the universality of some given attributes. The skill theory focuses on the abilities of a leader. Behavioural theory views leaders based on their actions and behaviour, while the contingency theory concerns the context of leadership. The shortcomings and limitations of these different theories, which have led to newer approaches to leadership, were also examined. The contemporary approaches to leadership, including charismatic, transactional, transformational, distributed, authentic, leader-member exchange, servant, and implicit leadership theories, were discussed.

Based on the literature review findings, it could be argued that existing theories do not effectively explain leadership in entrepreneurial settings (see Table 4 below, in which the strengths and weaknesses of previous approaches are listed). Entrepreneurial settings are characterised by turbulence, dynamism, and change. In a fast-moving business environment, leadership that is capable of identifying and exploiting opportunities is paramount and, hence, entrepreneurial leadership is required.

In this age of globalisation and increased competition, there is a need for business owners to use the most effective leadership approach. In light of the challenges facing entrepreneurs, sound leadership practises are no longer optional, but are essential for organisational success.

This literature review has established that leadership is an under-developed phenomenon, for which no unified theory currently exists. Leadership studies have traditionally focused narrowly on a limited set of elements by highlighting the leader while overlooking relevant elements of leadership (such as the follower and the context) (Avolio, 2007; Zaccaro and Klimoski, 2001). There remains a need for more research which considers both leaders' and followers' perspectives. There has been scant research about traditional leadership in entrepreneurial firms in

developing economies. In the next chapter the concept and domain of entrepreneurship from applied and theoretical perspectives are explored.

Table 4 Strengths and weaknesses of some of the theories of leadership

Leadership Approaches	Strengths	Weaknesses
Great Man/Trait Theories	Intuitively appealing and highlights the importance of a leader	Traits are not effective in every situation. It does not explain the role of leadership in ensuring business and organisational coherence
Skill Theory	Focuses on leadership skills and competencies	Essentially trait driven and difficult to differentiate skills from traits.
Behavioural Theory	Identifies leadership behaviour as a core part of the leadership process	Just like trait approach, it fails to consider the situational contingencies associated with leadership
Contingency Theory	It emphasises the importance of situations in leadership behaviour	It does not explain why people with certain leadership styles are more effective in particular situations than others
Implicit Leadership Theories	Stresses the importance of the social construction of leadership by the followers.	Followers may view such ineffective leadership behaviours as effective. Perception may vary with cultural values and even gender.
Leader-Member Exchange Theory	It provides a broader picture of leadership as an interactive exchange process between leaders and followers	It neglects the impact of conflict in the effectiveness of an organisation when followers are grouped into in-groups and out-groups.
Servant Leadership Theory	Views leaders as self-less individuals emphasising the importance of service, which is intuitively appealing	Not suitable for dynamic environments. It does not explain how leaders cope with drastic measures such as organisational change.
Transactional Leadership Theory	It provides a vivid picture of leadership as an exchange process with the end result the achievement of organisational goals.	Focuses mainly on contingent rewards as the tool to influence subordinates. This may not be effective in diverse entrepreneurial settings.
Charismatic/Transformational Leadership Theories	Conceptualises leadership as valuable in organisations facing turbulence and turmoil.	A modification of the trait approach and fails to explain clearly how such characteristics can improve organisational effectiveness.
Distributed Leadership Theory	Emphasises the importance of group effort and participation in leadership	It may not be feasible in every context especially in small businesses where subordinates adulate their leaders and resist empowerment.
Authentic Leadership Theory	Stresses the importance of integrity and ethics in leadership	Fails to explain how authenticity will always produce positive outcomes especially in entrepreneurial settings.

CHAPTER THREE – LITERATURE REVIEW

(PART 2): ENTREPRENEURSHIP

3.1 Introduction

Since the aim of this thesis is to examine leadership within entrepreneurial settings, it is essential that a critical literature review within the domain of entrepreneurship is included. The concept of entrepreneurship is not new. As a concept it remains elusive, diverse, and multi-faceted. Although there is an extensive body of research within the field, there is little consensus on what underpins entrepreneurship, and whether it should remain a distinct domain of study (Davidsson et al., 2001; Galloway et al., 2015; Gartner, 2000; Shane and Venkataraman, 2000; Shane, 2012; Smith and Anderson, 2007; Vecchio, 2003). As stated by Galloway et al. (2015, p. 683), “These various definitions make the analysis of entrepreneurship challenging”.

This chapter provides an extensive and overarching review of entrepreneurship literature. The review includes numerous definitions of entrepreneurship, and the continuous development of the concept and key debates amongst scholars are addressed. This review is a critical evaluation of the various approaches and perspectives that have been used to characterise the entrepreneur ever since the early Industrial Revolution. Nine themes are explored: the great person, economic perspective, psychological perspective, sociological perspective, behavioural perspective, management, intrapreneurship, cognitive perspective, and leadership perspective. This is followed by an examination of entrepreneurship as a process, as a new venture creation, and as an art of opportunity recognition and exploitation. In the last section of this chapter, current approaches to entrepreneurship are evaluated.

3.2 The definitions of entrepreneurship

The selection of an appropriate definition of entrepreneurship is a challenging task. It is widely recognised that the field of entrepreneurship suffers from a lack of definitional consensus (Bygrave and Hofer, 1991; Galloway et al., 2015; Gartner, 2000; Low and Macmillan, 1988; Shane and Venkataraman, 2000; Shane, 2012; Smith and Anderson, 2007). An overview of how entrepreneurship has been defined over the years is provided in Table 5, in which various perspectives related to the concept are also identified.

Bygrave and Hofer (1991) argue that for a construct³ to be operationalized, it must have a definition. According to Smith and Anderson (2007, p. 169), “Entrepreneurship is a poorly defined concept and that people use the bits of entrepreneurship meaning which suits their purposes”. The lack of an agreed definition of entrepreneurship among scholars is not likely to be resolved; as Low and Macmillan (1988 p. 141) stated, “...the desire for common definitions and a clearly defined area of inquiry will remain unfulfilled in the foreseeable future”. 25 years later, their prophecy has come to pass. Researchers and scholars have attempted to define entrepreneurship on the basis of their research interests and from different perspectives, but there exists no single definition that integrates them all. This was shown by Gartner (1990) when he surveyed several academics, researchers, politicians, and business leaders in search for a universal definition of entrepreneurship. His findings showed 90 different attributes, most of which were not linked to one other. However, the search continues because there is agreement among researchers that a universal definition may unite the field (Cunningham and Lischeron, 1991; Meyer et al., 2002). As stated by Meyer et al. (2002, p. 23), “Without an overarching definition of entrepreneurship...each researcher’s interpretation of entrepreneurship guides the research question, sample, and level of analysis. This limits the generalisability of findings and leads to an inability to replicate studies.”

³ A construct is a definition specifically invented for an image or idea for a given research project (Blumberg et al., 2011, p. 490)

Table 5 Definitions of entrepreneurship

<i>Author</i>	<i>Definition</i>	<i>Concept</i>
Knight (1921)	An entrepreneur profits from bearing uncertainty and risk.	Risk
Schumpeter (1934)	Entrepreneurship is seen as the doing of new things, or the doing of things that are already being done in a new way. New combinations include (1) introduction of new goods, (2) a new method of production, (3) opening of a new market, (4) a new source of supply, (5) a new organisation.	Innovation
Cole (1959)	“The purposeful activity (including an integrated sequence of decisions) of an individual or group of individuals, undertaken to initiate, maintain, or aggrandize a profit-oriented business unit for the production or distribution of economic goods and services.”	Behavioural process
Kirzner (1973)	Entrepreneurship is the ability to perceive new opportunities. The recognition and seizing of the opportunity will tend to “correct” the market and bring it back into equilibrium.	Opportunity identification and exploitation
Casson (1982)	Entrepreneurship involves “taking judgemental decisions about the coordination of scarce resources”.	Behavioural process
Sharma and Chrisman (1999)	Entrepreneurship refers to acts of organisational creation, renewal, or innovation that occur within or outside an existing organisation.	New venture creation and innovation
Shane and Venkataraman (2000)	Entrepreneurship is “the scholarly examination of how, by whom, and with what effects opportunities to create future goods and services are discovered, evaluated, and exploited.”	Opportunity identification and exploitation
Bruyat and Julien (2001)	Entrepreneurship is the “process of creating new value” (an innovation and/ or a new organisation).	New venture creation and innovation
Eckhardt and Shane (2003)	Entrepreneurship can be defined “as the discovery, evaluation, and exploitation of future goods and services”.	Opportunity identification and exploitation
Kuratko and Hodgetts (2007)	“Entrepreneurship is a dynamic process of vision, change, and creation. It requires an application of energy and passion toward the creation and implementation of new ideas and creative solutions.”	New venture creation and innovation
Stokes et al. (2010)	“Entrepreneurship is the emergent process of recognising and communicating creativity such that the resulting economic value can be appropriated by those involved.”	Innovation

The definitions set out in Table 5 are only a small selection of many ascribed to entrepreneurship; the number of definitions is nearly as abundant as the scholars themselves. If entrepreneurship researchers have not been able to agree upon a definition, at least a distinct domain (Davidsson et al., 2001) should be established for the field upon which to build knowledge. But even this has been a source of debate among researchers (e.g. Gartner, 2000; Shane and Venkataraman, 2000; Shane, 2012; Vecchio, 2003). While no universal definition for entrepreneurship has been reached, this is not to say that scholars should be discouraged from embarking on researching entrepreneurship, or that research within the field is of limited value. Indeed, the lack of agreement highlights the complexity of entrepreneurship, and that the field is still undergoing considerable theoretical development. It is clearly shown in Table 5 that although no consensus has been reached on a universal definition for entrepreneurship, there are recurring themes in each definition, such as entrepreneurship being viewed as a process, as a new venture creation, as a form of innovation and risk taking, or as opportunity recognition and exploitation. These recurring insights are discussed later in this chapter.

3.3 Entrepreneurship research and theory

3.3.1 Historical perspective

Different approaches have been used to explore the behaviour and contribution of the entrepreneur from a variety of disciplines (Westhead et al., 2011). Some researchers grouped the approaches into different schools of thoughts (e.g. Cunningham and Lischeron, 1991; Kuratko and Hodgetts, 2007), for example, the great person approach, the classical school, and others. Other researchers categorised the approaches on the basis of contributions by early theorists such as Knight (1921), Schumpeter (1934), Kirzner (1973), Casson (1982), and many others. Another method is to use perspectives from disciplines such as economics and psychology to understand the phenomenon. Stevenson and Sahlman (1989) grouped their perspectives regarding the nature of entrepreneurship into functional, personality,

and behavioural perspectives. Cope (2005) went further by adding a dynamic learning perspective.

In the next sub-section, the construct adopted by Cunningham and Lischeron (1991) and Westhead et al. (2011) (which clearly shows how research activity on entrepreneurship has evolved, and which provides a better view of the entrepreneurial process) is utilised, and the schools of thoughts about entrepreneurship based on the nine themes are described:

3.3.2 State of entrepreneurship research and theory

3.3.2.1 The Great Person perspective

The great person perspective takes a person-centric approach, whereby some people are regarded as special and destined to be entrepreneurs, while others are not. It suggests that the entrepreneurs are super-heroic figures with unique qualities in comparison to other people (Wickham, 2006). Indeed, the individual is considered as an entrepreneurial hero (Nijkamp, 2003). The great person perspective, although easy to comprehend, has been criticised by many researchers (e.g. Cunningham and Lischeron, 1991; Wickham, 2006). The perspective suggests that only a few people can be entrepreneurs, and does not assess the impact of the environment in initiating entrepreneurship; you are either born an entrepreneur, or you are not. This approach provides a discouraging implication to those who want to engage in entrepreneurship. Furthermore, it is not predictive; according to Wickham (2006, p. 12), “It can only tell us who will become an entrepreneur after they have done so (and achieved success).” As a result of these drawbacks, research based on the great person approach was abandoned, and scholars began to search for new ways to conceptualise entrepreneurship and the entrepreneur.

3.3.2.2 The economic perspective

The economic perspective explains the entrepreneurial function and how the entrepreneur, as an agent of change, affects the economic system. Proponents of this perspective include Knight (1921), Mises (1949), Hayek (1945), Schumpeter (1961), Leibenstein (1968), Kirzner (1973; 1997), and many others. Within this approach there are different perspectives as regards market equilibrium and the key function of the entrepreneur. The importance of entrepreneurs in economic growth was heightened following a study by Birch (1987) which showed that small businesses were responsible for most job creation in the United States. This study revealed that the economic impact of entrepreneurship was not only attributed to business formation, but also to the growth of new businesses, highlighting that as the engine of growth (Meyer et al., 2002). However, the economic perspective provides little insight as regards the entrepreneur's behaviour (Westhead et al., 2011). By trying to explain the function of an entrepreneur in the economic system, it attaches great importance to the economy and neglects the entrepreneur as an individual.

3.3.2.3 The psychological perspective

From the psychological perspective, entrepreneurial behaviour is perceived to be based on traits. It is similar to the great person perspective; however, the focus is on certain personality characteristics that make the entrepreneur unique and which distinguishes him/her from non-entrepreneurs. Works by McClelland (1961) and Brockhaus (1982) were instrumental in shaping this perspective, but this approach views personality traits as innate, stable, and universal, and refuses to acknowledge what the entrepreneur really does.

3.3.2.4 The behavioural perspective

According to the behavioural perspective, what the entrepreneurs really do is more relevant than who they are. The focus of this approach is on understanding how the behaviours displayed by the entrepreneurs could increase the potential for success in any entrepreneurial venture (Gonzalez-Benito et al., 2009). However, this perspective does not illustrate how individuals can adapt their behaviours in a turbulent business environment.

3.3.2.5 The sociological perspective

The sociological perspective places entrepreneurship within a wider social and environmental context by acknowledging the impact of social relations and the environment on the behaviour of the entrepreneur. This approach proposes that "...social experiences in turn influence the person's perception of the entrepreneurial role and expression of values in that role" (McCarthy, 2000, p. 47). The relationship between entrepreneurial activity and social factors such as culture (Konig et al., 2010; Noseleit, 2010; Steensma et al., 2000; Wilken, 1979), ethnicity (Hagen, 1962; Levie, 2007), role models (Bosma et al., 2012; Schere et al., 1989; Shapero, 1971; 1975; Van Auken et al., 2006), gender (Ohe et al., 1992), childhood experiences (Kets de Vries, 1977), education and employment history (Cooper, 1973; Storey, 1982) has been reported in literature. However, although this view of entrepreneurship is compelling, it has been criticised by scholars (Chell, 1985). It considers entrepreneurial intentions to emanate only as a result of family turbulence; whereas studies have shown that not all successful entrepreneurs come from deprived families. There is no clear explanation on why this model can be used to predict entrepreneurial activity. There is much emphasis on the context (i.e. entrepreneurship is solely due to environmental factors such as childhood relations and financial difficulties) that entrepreneurship is perceived to emerge out of necessity rather than opportunity.

3.3.2.6 The management perspective

The entrepreneur as an individual who organises or manages a business, and who takes the sole responsibility of the risk so as to profit from the venture is the focus of the management perspective. Many researchers have identified skills and competencies which the entrepreneur must develop in order to effectively manage a business (Jusoh et al., 2011; Ray, 1993; Stokes et al., 2010). Jusoh et al. (2011) identified 17 entrepreneurial skills within this perspective such as identifying business opportunities, efficiency in the use of software applications, creativity, knowledge skills, time management, leadership skills, and operations management. Ray (1993) identified problem solving, listening, negotiating, persuasive communication, opportunity identification, and critical thinking skills as important in starting and growing a business. Therefore, the focus of the management perspective has been on the way in which such skills will improve firm performance. Studies have shown that entrepreneurial skills have a positive effect on venture growth and performance (Baum et al., 2001), and since organisational performance is a critical factor in any economy, the management perspective has attracted considerable interest. This approach is similar to the dynamic learning perspective put forward by Cope (2005), which goes beyond the start-up phase to consider ways in which entrepreneurs learn to adapt as their business expands. However, the inability to effectively distinguish between a manager and an entrepreneur (especially in terms of behaviour and skills) plagues the management perspective.

3.3.2.7 The intrapreneurship perspective

Entrepreneurship within existing organisations is the focus of the intrapreneurship perspective. This perspective supports the notion of many scholars that entrepreneurship is not limited to new firms, but can occur within an existing organisation (Amit et al., 1993; Casson, 1982; Shane and Venkataraman, 2000; Venkataraman, 1997). A great array of literature has developed within the framework of the mature corporation. Intrapreneurship has been classified in terms of innovation, pro-activeness, and risk-taking (Covin and Slevin, 1991). More recent

work by Antoncic and Hisrich (2003) has put forward new business and self-renewal as being important additional parameters for intrapreneurship. Studies providing empirical evidence about this approach have considered organisational factors which influence intrapreneurship (Christensen, 2005; Hisrich and Peters 1995; Hornsby et al., 2002; Pinchot, 1985) by relating it with firm performance (Lumpkin and Dess 1996; Zahra, 1993; 1996). Studies have identified the characteristics of intrapreneurs (Fayolle, 2004; Howell and Higgins, 1990) as well as the factors that promote nascent intrapreneurship (as opposed to entrepreneurship) (Parker, 2011). However, the intrapreneurship perspective fails to recognise the structural and cultural differences (i.e. the bureaucratic setting) between a corporation and a small business venture; hence its potential usefulness is limited.

3.3.2.8 The cognitive perspective

The focus on the individual as an entrepreneur emerges in the cognitive perspective. Studies investigating the cognitive processes of entrepreneurs have been carried out by various researchers. Allinson and Hayes (1996) developed a cognitive style index and used it to confirm the relevance of cognitive style in the context of entrepreneurship. For these researchers, all individuals fall into a single continuum of intuitive and analytic orientations, whereby some may be very inclined to use their imaginations (intuitive) while others are more procedural (analytic), with no individual perfectly oriented along both dimensions. There have also been studies on the impact of the cognitive process of entrepreneurs on decision making (Busenitz and Barney, 1997; Mitchell et al., 2002), on their ability to spot entrepreneurial opportunities (Keh et al., 2002; McCline et al., 2000), on their ability to start a business venture (Simon et al., 1999), and in relation to risk (Chatterjee et al., 2003). For the cognitive perspective, a proper understanding of entrepreneurship involves a sufficient grasp of human thinking.

3.3.2.9 The leadership perspective

The leadership perspective, which is the focus of this thesis, has generated interest over the years, and emanates from the notion that an entrepreneur must be a leader who is able to define a vision of what is possible, and attract individuals to follow that vision and so bring it to fruition (Kao, 1989; cited in Cunningham and Lischeron, 1991). Contemporary research focuses more on this perspective, especially in light of the turbulence and competitive environment faced by organisations. As stated by Fernald et al. (2005, p. 1): “A whole new remodelling of the ways in which business, communication and government are conducted has emerged; hence, it is important for anyone involved in entrepreneurial ventures to fully comprehend the importance of sound leadership practises.” This evolving leadership is known as entrepreneurial leadership.

Although the different perspectives described above are important in examining the evolution of entrepreneurship, this concept has been viewed through various other lenses. Entrepreneurship has been viewed as a process, as a new venture creation, and as opportunity recognition and exploitation. These themes are elaborated in more detail in the next section.

3.4 Entrepreneurship as a process

Research relating to entrepreneurship has moved beyond studying the entrepreneur as the sole agent to examining the entrepreneurial process. Many researchers have argued that a better understanding of entrepreneurship can only be obtained through a process approach (e.g. Haber and Reichel, 2007; Jack and Anderson, 2002; Kodithuwakku and Rosa, 2002). By considering entrepreneurship as a process, many other important factors can be taken into account. One such factor is the context which tends to vary, and which will impact on the individual. Through the process perspective, entrepreneurship is not a product of an isolated agent, but may be

influenced by or arise from a social structure (Jack and Anderson, 2002). However, viewing entrepreneurship from the perspective of process is complex since the process occurs over time and the factors tend to vary according to the socio-economic context. This can make it difficult for research to be carried out using cross-sectional methodologies (Kodithuwakku and Rosa, 2002).

The process approach is concerned with what entrepreneurs do and how they carry out their activities. Typically, the entrepreneurial process involves idea generation; procurement of financial, human and knowledge resources; justification of the viability of the idea; the roll-out phase; maturity; and finally, growth or decline (Brockner et al., 2004). However, Brockner et al. (2004) argue that the process is not sequential, and can occur randomly. A breadth of empirical evidence has been provided by researchers about the entrepreneurial process. Kodithuwakku and Rosa (2002) studied the dynamics of the entrepreneurial process in a rural context in Sri Lanka, and their findings highlighted the importance of process to the success of entrepreneurs. By studying Sri Lankan rural entrepreneurs (whose differences in terms of socio-economic values with UK entrepreneurs are substantial), Kodithuwakku and Rosa (2002) reinforced the notion of Jack and Anderson (2002) that the social context is paramount in entrepreneurship, and that entrepreneurial embeddedness in such a structure is critical in creating and realising opportunities. Haber and Reichel (2007), by using a resource based perspective, went a step further by suggesting that human capital within the entrepreneurial process is the strongest contributor to the success of a small or medium enterprise, rather than the type or location of the enterprise.

Numerous models to structure the entrepreneurial process have also been developed by researchers (e.g. Fry, 1993; Jack and Anderson, 2002; Morris et al., 1994). Notable among these is the model by Morris et al. (1994), which applies an integrative approach to the entrepreneurial process. The model is composed of entrepreneurial inputs and outcomes, and the entrepreneurial process involves the entrepreneur, the organisational context, resources, business concepts, and opportunities. A positive outcome will depend on how effectively the entrepreneur is able to identify opportunities, acquire the necessary resources, develop business concepts, and exploit these opportunities in the organisational context.

Unfortunately, the numerous models approaching entrepreneurship from a process perspective are highly fragmented. As stated by Moroz and Hindle (2012, p. 781), "...the 32 extant models of entrepreneurial process are highly fragmented in their claims and emphasis, and are difficult for establishing an infrastructure upon which to synthesise an understanding of the entrepreneurial process that is both generic and distinct". Hence, there remains the need to develop a universal model of the entrepreneurial process which will help build more knowledge in the field.

3.5 Entrepreneurship as a new venture creation

The creation of a new venture is widely held by many individuals to be the core of what constitutes entrepreneurship. This view implies a business start-up, and that an entrepreneur is the founder of the organisation who is undertaking the task of bringing together all the factors of production. This concept dates back to when Gartner (1988) defined entrepreneurship as the creation of a new organisation. This view of entrepreneurship suggests that those individuals who transform existing organisations by enhancing their sustainability (e.g. as Ray Kroc did with McDonalds) or by inheriting an enterprise are not entrepreneurs. The venture creation approach has been heavily criticised by many scholars (e.g. Fry, 1993; Kuratko and Hodgetts 2007; Shane and Venkataraman, 2000; Sharma and Chrisman, 1999; Wickham, 2006), with some arguing that entrepreneurship may also occur in an existing organisation (e.g. Rumelt, 1987; Shane and Venkataraman, 2000; Sharma and Chrisman, 1999). Indeed, Shane and Venkataraman (2000) argue that entrepreneurship does not essentially require, but may include, the creation of a new organisation. Another source of debate among scholars concerning this perspective is whether all new businesses are entrepreneurial. This is illustrated by Fry (1993, p. 29), who suggests that a hobby of making cakes which translates into a business is not entrepreneurial, but at best is called a "small business" or a "profitable hobby" since the amount of risk taking, planning, or personal capital required is minimal, compared with other entrepreneurial ventures. For Drucker (1985), a new business is only entrepreneurial if it involves systematic innovation. This involves "... the purposeful and organised search for changes, and [the] systematic analysis of the

opportunities such changes might offer for economic or social innovation” (Drucker, 1985, p. 192). Therefore, businesses that do not offer economic or social innovation are not entrepreneurial. According to the Global entrepreneurship monitoring report, people start their own businesses either as a result of the motivation to pursue an opportunity (i.e. opportunity entrepreneurs), or as a result of lack of viable options (i.e. necessity entrepreneurs), with the latter group being less likely to generate job growth, exports and new market niches than the former group (Reynolds et al., 2002). In short, starting a new business due to necessity may lead to underdevelopment rather than development of the economy (Acs, 2006).

Regardless of the academic debates amongst scholars about the conceptualisation of entrepreneurship (Gartner, 1988), the relationship between new venture creation and entrepreneurship cannot be ignored simply because of the ease in gathering empirical data compared to other methods of researching the phenomenon. Moreover, new venture creation is the way in which many non-scholars perceive entrepreneurship.

3.6 Entrepreneurship as opportunity recognition and exploitation

The concept of entrepreneurship as acts of opportunity recognition and exploitation can be traced back to the work of Kirzner (1973), who believed that the entrepreneur is an individual who can perceive new opportunities. Recognising opportunities and exploiting them is therefore the basis of entrepreneurship. This view contradicts with that of entrepreneurship being regarded as the creation of a new organisation or enterprise. A key contribution to this perception of entrepreneurship as being acts of opportunity recognition and exploitation was made by Shane and Venkataraman (2000, p. 172), who claimed that entrepreneurship is “...the scholarly examination of how, by whom, and with what, [can] opportunities to create future goods and services [be] discovered, evaluated, and exploited”. But this raises another question: which opportunities can be called entrepreneurial, or are all new opportunities entrepreneurial? As a result, researchers have sought to study the nature of entrepreneurial opportunities. Venkataraman and Harting (2005, p. 100) state that,

“Entrepreneurial opportunity is the chance for an individual (or a team) to offer new value to society, often by introducing new products or services.” Drucker (1985) goes further by categorising opportunities as follows: (i) the creation of new information, (ii) the exploitation of market inefficiencies, and (iii) the reaction to shifts in the relative costs and benefits of alternative uses of resources. Although debatable, it could be argued that entrepreneurship can only result through entrepreneurial opportunities, and this could lead to either economic gain if exploited successfully, or failure.

Opportunity recognition without exploitation can be argued to be fruitless. Minniti and Bygrave (1999) suggest that the decision to exploit an opportunity is subjective, and individuals will embark on entrepreneurial activities rather than income-producing activities if the return on an entrepreneurial activity is relatively more positive. Shane and Venkataraman (2000) went further to state that the willingness of people to exploit opportunities is based on the nature of the opportunity and their individual differences. People will only exploit opportunities if the opportunity cost involved is profitable to them. Research has been carried out to study why some entrepreneurs exploit opportunities more effectively than others. Begley and Boyd (1987) discovered that people with a greater tolerance for ambiguity exploit opportunities more frequently, while Chen et al. (1998) put forward that self-efficacy and internal locus of control were important attributes of individuals who exploit opportunities more effectively.

Although there is a growing research focus on opportunity identification and exploitation, it still remains to be clearly explained how entrepreneurs choose whether or not to exploit an identified opportunity. More research is required to examine how entrepreneurs recognise opportunities and why some entrepreneurs exploit them more effectively than others. The conceptualisation of entrepreneurship as opportunity recognition and exploitation, although useful, fails to fully explain the phenomenon. Entrepreneurship is a complex process, and a proper understanding should embrace all facets of the entrepreneurial process, which include opportunity identification, opportunity exploitation, new venture creation, innovation, and value appropriation. Conceptualising those independently and neglecting others will only exacerbate the academic debate in the field.

3.7 Conclusion

Entrepreneurship is a budding field that over the years has been subject to many controversies, especially those concerning its definition and the legitimacy of the field as a distinct domain. It can be seen that attempts to provide a universal definition for entrepreneurship have been problematic, and scholars in the field have not yet reached a consensus. This may be due in part to the range of disciplines embraced by entrepreneurship, which has made it impossible to agree on an exact domain or definition of entrepreneurship (Low and Macmillan, 1988). Perhaps the best that academics can do now is to acknowledge that the subject of entrepreneurship is shared by inter-related empirical phenomena such as development of new firms, and opportunity identification and recognition. But by taking such a path, entrepreneurship research will remain a “potpourri” field (Gartner, 2000; Low and MacMillan, 1988), and so the debates will continue.

In this chapter, nine schools of thought within the field of entrepreneurship have been described, namely the great person, economic, psychological, behavioural, sociological, management, intrapreneurship, cognition, and leadership perspectives. An entrepreneur is more than a manager, and entrepreneurial leadership requires more than just traits, style, attributes, and behaviour. It includes the skills of empowering people, developing human resource systems, preserving organisational intimacy, inculcating values, setting clear goals, and creating opportunities, especially in turbulent environments (Cunningham and Lischeron, 1991). Hence, the study will focus on entrepreneurial leadership in developing economies that have not been previously examined in detail by researchers.

In this study, an entrepreneur is defined as the owner of a business, a definition that is in line with past research studies in entrepreneurship (e.g. Dollinger, 1999; Gartner, 1988; Low and Macmillan, 1988). By adopting such definition, the study provides a clearer representation of entrepreneurial leadership through empirical evidence.

CHAPTER FOUR – LITERATURE REVIEW (PART 3): NIGERIA – AN OPERATING ENVIRONMENT FOR RETAIL PHARMACY ENTREPRENEURS

4.1 Introduction

In this chapter, the impact of entrepreneurship in a developing economy context is examined, and the selection of the Nigerian economy as an appropriate setting for the research in this thesis is justified.

The role of context in shaping entrepreneurial activity cannot be ignored. Entrepreneurial opportunities and activities tend to differ across societies and geographical contexts (Boettke and Coyne, 2009). The effects of entrepreneurship (in the form of creation of new ventures) are not identical in all regions and countries (Michael, 2008). As set out by Spilling and Berg (2000, p. 39), “Since entrepreneurship and management is a creation of, and a creator of, the society which exists at any point of time (Sundin, 1996) and also of the geographical context (Berg 1994; 1997), it is important to continually update such pictures and to ‘draw’ them for countries or regions for which they have not been prepared so far.” If the impact of entrepreneurship on regions and countries is subject to considerable variation, then it is paramount that research into specific sectors and contexts be conducted.

This chapter begins with a discussion on the role of entrepreneurship in a developing economy, and on why there has been a surge in interest in this area. Nigeria provides the context for this thesis, and so the political, geographical and economic landscape of the country is examined. The focus of this thesis is on the retail pharmacy sector in Nigeria, and therefore the structure of this industry is set out.

4.2 Entrepreneurship in a developing economy

Entrepreneurs have been a dominant image in both the developed and developing economies (Inyang and Enuoh, 2009; Smith, 2006). The resulting interest in entrepreneurship may be due, by some large measure, to the link between entrepreneurial activity and economic growth or performance. Studies have shown that increased entrepreneurial activity can lead to improved economic performance (Berkowitz and DeJong, 2005; Carree and Thurik, 2010; Robbins et al., 2000). According to Yusof et al. (2007, p. 3), “It has a more critical role for economies of developing countries since entrepreneurship is seen as an engine of economic progress, job creation and social adjustment.”

The impact of entrepreneurship on a developing economy cannot be fully appreciated if there is no description of what constitutes a developing economy. According to the World Bank Development Data Group (2015), a developing economy is one with a low or middle level of income. A low level of income refers to a gross national income per capita of US\$1,005, while a middle level is between US\$1,005 and US\$12,275. Therefore, in a developing economy the majority of the people have access to less money and poorer public infrastructure, in contrast with developed countries.

Entrepreneurial firms have been shown to provide a great number of benefits in developing economies. The creation of jobs is arguably the most important of such benefits (McMillan and Woodruff, 2002). Haltiwanger and Vodopivec (2000) showed in their study of Estonia that entrepreneurship is pivotal to job creation. As well as the creation of new jobs, entrepreneurs are instrumental in providing other important benefits to developing economies such as supplying consumer goods, limiting the market power of government-owned firms, and enhancing reform momentum (McMillan and Woodruff, 2002). Although it is widely agreed by many researchers that entrepreneurial activity is positively related to economic and financial development (e.g. Berkowitz and DeJong, 2005; Klapper et al., 2010; Robbins et al., 2000), some scholars have produced contrary findings. Acs (2006) argues that in developing economies, entrepreneurial activity is inversely related to economic development since most people are trying to move from being self-

employed to more stable, salaried employment; whereas in developed economies, entrepreneurial activity may be positively related to economic development as more people migrate from working in salaried jobs to becoming entrepreneurs. Van Stel et al. (2005) suggest that entrepreneurship has a negative impact on gross domestic product growth in developing countries. From his empirical findings, Michael (2008) suggests that entrepreneurship in certain regions may lead to an increase in unemployment rather than an increase in the availability of jobs for the populace.

Whether or not entrepreneurship is the missing link for economic growth, one thing is certain – any debate about entrepreneurship in developing countries will be better informed if it is underpinned by empirical evidence. The focus of this thesis is on a country that is attempting to make the transition from a developing to a developed economy. Developing nations are different from the more developed nations in terms of gross national product, level of poverty, education, income, and other growth parameters. In developed economies, the focus tends to be on enhancing entrepreneurial framework conditions through high-value, high-technology, innovation and technology commercialisation; whereas in developing economies, there tends to be a more balanced approach to both national framework conditions and entrepreneurial framework conditions by strengthening the conditions of the entrepreneurial environment through improving management skills and market flexibility (Acs, 2006).

Based on this, Nigeria as a developing economy provides an appropriate context for this study, and is explored further in the next section.

4.3 Nigeria

In order to understand the context within which this study was set, it is useful to provide an introduction to the geographical and political landscape of Nigeria:

4.3.1 Geography

Nigeria is located in the western region of Sub-Saharan Africa. It has an area of 923,768 square kilometres. Nigeria protrudes into the Gulf of Guinea and is bounded on the south by the Atlantic Ocean, on the north by the Republic of Niger, on the west by Benin, and in the east by Cameroon (CIA World Fact Book, 2015). A map showing the location of Nigeria and its states is presented in Figure 3:

Figure 3 Map of Nigeria

Source: CIA World Fact Book, 2015

There are over 250 ethnic groups in Nigeria, consisting mostly of Hausas, Igbos, and Yorubas (CIA World Fact Book, 2015). These ethnic groups communicate in different languages. However, despite the tribal diversity, the official language of communication is English. Nigeria is the most populous nation in West Africa with a

population of over 174 million people, and the demography of Nigeria is illustrated in Table 6:

Table 6 Demography of Nigeria

Social indicators		
Population growth rate (average annual %)	2010-2015	2.8
Urban population growth rate (average annual %)	2010-2015	3.8
Rural population growth rate (average annual %)	2010-2015	1.3
Urban population (%)	2013	50.9
Population aged 0-14 years (%)	2013	44.4
Population aged 60+ years (females and males, % of total)	2013	4.7/4.2
Sex ratio (males per 100 females)	2013	103.7
Life expectancy at birth (females and males, years)	2010-2015	52.6/52.0
Infant mortality rate (per 1000 live births)	2010-2015	76.3
Fertility rate, total (live births per woman)	2010-2015	6
Contraceptive prevalence (ages 15-49, %)	2006-2012	14.1
International migrant stock (000's and % of total population)	mid-2013	1233.6/0.7
Refugees and others of concern to UNHCR	mid-2013	3051
Education: Primary-secondary gross enrolment ratio (females/males per 100)	2006-2012	61.3/67.6
Education: Female third-level students (% of total)	2006-2012	40.7
Intentional homicides (females and males, per 100000)	2008-2010	6.1/18.2
Seats held by women in national parliaments (%)	2014	6.7

Source: UN Data (2015)

4.3.2 Political landscape

Nigeria became an independent nation on October 1, 1960, prior to which she was a British colony. Following independence, the political environment of Nigeria experienced many changes and has been marked with instability. The large number

of ethnic groups and their differences made the country ungovernable and this led to a civil war in 1966. From the end of the civil war in 1970 until 1999, the military ruled the country. With the introduction of democracy on May 29, 1999, the people hoped things would change for the better. The government started to implement reforms. By 2011, President Goodluck Jonathan established a professional economic team in order to ensure transparency and improve fiscal management (CIA World Fact Book, 2015). However, despite his initiative, the stigma associated with ethnicity has adversely affected development. The rise of militant groups such as Boko Haram is a consequence of such ethnic politics. As stated by Osaghae (2003, p. 71), "...ethnic politics has attained dangerous proportions in Nigeria because of the inability of the state to perform its role as an autonomous, accountable and legitimate agency of distributive justice". This is not unusual since developing and transition economies are often characterised by corruption and lack of expertise (Bardhan, 1997; Luthans et al., 2000). The solution to such corruption and injustice may be to increase the growth rate of the economy (Bardhan, 1997).

4.4 The Nigerian economy

Nigeria is regarded as the 'Giant of Africa' and boasts a vibrant economy. It is the largest economy in Africa (The Telegraph, 2014) and is currently the leading African oil producer.

Nigeria's economic growth has been stimulated largely by its oil production. Oil contributes 40% to Nigeria's GDP at current prices (World Bank, 2015) with an estimated oil production of 2.18 million barrels per day in the first quarter of 2015 (National Bureau of Statistics, 2015a). However, the historical dependence on the oil sector is gradually waning (National Bureau of Statistics, 2015a), especially given the recent fall in oil prices. The fall in the oil price has led the Nigerian government to respond by devaluing its currency (the naira), imposing taxes on luxury items, and revising the budget (Atlantic Council, 2014). These are important since an oil price shock may stunt the growth of GDP (Ayadi, 2005).

Despite the fall in oil prices, Nigeria possesses a large market, driven not only by a large population, but also on the growth of other sectors of the economy. There has been an increase in the minimum wage during the past three decades in Nigeria (Jonah and Yousuo, 2013).

An economic overview based on the World Bank's (2015) profile of Nigeria is shown in Table 7 below:

Table 7 Economic Overview of Nigeria

Data Profile	2011	2012	2013	2014
GNI, PPP (current international \$)	808,825,539,152	865,537,954,917	930,235,010,659	..
GDP (current US\$)	411,743,801,712	462,979,245,902	521,803,314,654	..
GNI, Atlas method (current US\$)	281,270,090,646	415,469,998,545	469,729,969,327	..
Personal remittances, received (current US\$)	20,618,849,629	20,633,319,234
Foreign direct investment, net inflows (BoP, current US\$)	8,841,952,775	7,101,031,884	5,609,000,000	..
External debt stocks, total (DOD, current US\$)	8,962,799,000	10,058,908,000	13,791,937,000	..
Net official development assistance and official aid received (current US\$)	1,768,550,000	1,915,820,000	2,529,480,000	..
Population, total	164,192,925	168,833,776	173,615,345	..
Surface area (sq. km)	923,770	923,770	923,770	923,770
Forest area (sq. km)	86,314	82,218
GNI per capita, PPP (current international \$)	4,930	5,130	5,360	..
GNI per capita, Atlas method (current US\$)	1,710	2,460	2,710	..
Net barter terms of trade index (2000 = 100)	221	226	222	..
Population density (people per sq. km of land area)	180	185	191	..
Mortality rate, under-5 (per 1,000 live births)	126	122	117	..
Adolescent fertility rate (births per 1,000 women ages 15-19)	120	120	118	..
Merchandise trade (% of GDP)	41	36	30	..
Overall level of statistical capacity (scale 0 - 100)	73	74	72	72
Life expectancy at birth, total (years)	52	52	52	..
Immunization, measles (% of children ages 12-23 months)	52	37	59	..
Industry, value added (% of GDP)	25	24	22	..
Exports of goods and services (% of GDP)	31	31	18	..
Agriculture, value added (% of GDP)	22	22	21	..
Imports of goods and services (% of GDP)	21	13	13	..
Mobile cellular subscriptions (per 100 people)	58	67	73	..
Time required to start a business (days)	28	28	31	31
Services, etc., value added (% of GDP)	53	54	57	..
Domestic credit provided by financial sector (% of GDP)	22	21	22	..
Gross capital formation (% of GDP)	16	15	15	..
GDP growth (annual %)	5	4	5	..
Internet users (per 100 people)	28	33	38	..
Fertility rate, total (births per woman)	6	6	6	..
Urban population growth (annual %)	5	5	5	..
Inflation, GDP deflator (annual %)	10	9	6	..
Tax revenue (% of GDP)	2	2

Source: World Bank (2015)

The Nigerian economy is expanding and is attracting business investment. The World Bank (2013) places Nigeria as one of the fastest growing economies in the world, with an annual growth rate of over 7%. Its average GDP growth over the last decade was 8%, which implies that the size of the Nigerian economy is 1.7 times greater than it was 10 years ago (World Bank, 2013). The National Bureau of Statistics (2015b) showed that total trade was N5.51 trillion in 2014, 8.16% greater than it was in 2013. This was due to increase in the value of exports and a decrease in the value of imports.

However, despite the attractiveness of the Nigerian economy, there are still some problems, the most significant of which is unemployment. The unemployment rate of the working age population in Nigeria has increased from 12% in 2006 to 25% in 2014 (National Bureau of Statistics, 2014). Job creation has not been able to keep pace with the ever growing working age population, as illustrated in Table 8:

Table 8 National unemployment rate (%) (2000-2014)

Year	% unemployment
2000	13.1
2001	13.6
2002	12.6
2003	14.8
2004	13.4
2005	11.9
2006	12.3
2007	12.7
2008	14.9
2009	19.7
2010	21.4
2011	23.9
2012	27.4
2013	24.7
2014	25.1

Source: National Bureau of Statistics (2014)

In this climate, entrepreneurs with their innovations could potentially have a lasting positive impact in the Nigerian economy and help redress the unemployment levels.

Another major issue in the Nigerian economy is poverty. The number of Nigerians living in poverty is high despite the GDP growth of the economy. Sadly, Nigeria is ranked 152 out of 187 countries in the 2014 United Nations' human development

index (UNDP, 2014). Despite great strides in economic growth (in terms of GDP) by both oil and non-oil sectors, and despite Nigeria’s strong balance of trade, there has not been any significant positive impact on the welfare of the population. Table 9 shows the level of poverty among the Nigerian population:

Table 9 Level of poverty among the Nigerian Population

	2013-2014	2009-2010
<i>Per Capita</i>		
Poverty rate	64.2	62.6
Urban poverty	52.2	51.2
Rural poverty	73.4	69.0
<i>Adult equivalence</i>		
Poverty rate	48.3	46.1
Urban poverty	36.8	34.3
Rural poverty	57.4	52.9

Source: National Bureau of Statistics cited from World Bank (2013)

4.5 Nigeria’s retail pharmacy sector

Preliminary analysis suggests that its relatively lower requirements in terms of investment, human resources, knowledge, and capital are reasons why entrepreneurs in developing countries focus on the retail sector (Klapper et al., 2010). In developing countries, the retail trade is more favourable in terms of cost and time barriers (Adegbite et al., 2007). In Nigeria, the retail sector continues to grow. As stated by Euromonitor International (2013, p. 1), “The Nigerian retail environment achieved considerable growth over the review period. This can mainly be attributed to the growing Nigerian population, which is generating increasing demand for retailers in the country.”

The retail pharmacy industry provides a relevant context in which to conduct empirical research. The origins of retail pharmacy in Nigeria can be traced back to Richard Zacchaeus Bailey, who opened the first chemist shop on Balogun street in Lagos in 1887 (Pharmaceutical Society of Nigeria, 2015). Back then, the individuals who handled drugs were known as dispensers (Erah, 2003). But with developments in education, legislation and practice, the retail pharmacy sector quickly began to evolve. In 2013, the number of registered pharmacists had increased to 16,052 (Pharmacists Council of Nigeria, 2013).

The Pharmaceutical Society of Nigeria is the professional association charged with ensuring that all its members provide good quality pharmaceutical services (Pharmaceutical Society of Nigeria, 2015). Members of the society work in the retail, hospital, administrative, and manufacturing sectors. This thesis focuses on retail pharmacists who provide an invaluable source of healthcare for millions of people in low-income countries (Lowe and Montagu, 2009). Ease of access, availability of medication, anonymity, speed and quality of a service, and availability of credit are some of the reasons why pharmacies are the first point of call for many clients (Goel et al., 1996; Lowe and Montagu, 2009).

4.5.1 Potential obstacles to retail pharmacy entrepreneurs in Nigeria

Entrepreneurship and leadership are important for the economic development of Nigeria. Therefore, it is pertinent to identify the obstacles that the retail pharmacy entrepreneurs in this country encounter. As such, in this section, contextual challenges, inadequate capital and infrastructural facilities, and political instability and corruption (which form the bulk of the entrepreneurial problems faced in developing economies) are considered.

4.5.1.1 Contextual challenges

Previous studies in the pharmacy industry have shown that the drug distribution system in developing countries such as Nigeria is chaotic (Erhun et al., 2001) and the regulations, licensing and registration of pharmacies are grossly inadequate (Lowe and Montagu, 2009).

Such problems in form of a chaotic drug distribution network and ineffective regulations has led to an increase in the number of fake and substandard drugs which ultimately undermines the healthcare delivery effort of the government (Erhun et al., 2001) and affects the welfare of the society.

4.5.1.2 Inadequate capital

Previous studies have shown that inadequate capital is a major inhibitor of the growth of small businesses (Gray et al., 1997; Kiggundu, 1988; Mambula, 2002; Okpara and Wynn, 2007; Okpara, 2011; Trulsson, 1997; van Dijk, 1995). Nigeria is no exception, with research showing that the most significant obstacle affecting entrepreneurship in the country is inadequate capital (Nkechi et al. 2012; Okpara, 2011). Okpara (2011), by carrying out quantitative studies on entrepreneurs in Nigeria, discovered that the major problem they faced when managing their businesses was insufficient capital to support their business venture.

Many Nigerian entrepreneurs have little access to capital, and they obtain funds from family members. In the retail pharmacy sector, significant capital is required. Inventory is costly, and pharmaceuticals and other related products are usually expensive. In order to break into this market, a significant financial investment is required. Many retail pharmacy entrepreneurs often depend on personal savings, or loans from family members and friends (Nkechi et al., 2012). With the current state of recession in the global economy, banks are reluctant to issue loans without significant collateral. Furthermore, when such loans are given, the interest rates are sometimes as high as 21 percent (Nkechi et al., 2012), which discourages the entrepreneurs.

The Nigerian government has established policies to aid small businesses. A federal office of small business advocacy was established to encourage small business development and provide financial assistance. But these loans are seldom made available to the entrepreneurs. Instead, they are diverted by corrupt government officials (Okpara, 2011). Therefore, the inability to raise capital remains an on-going problem in the Nigerian economy.

4.5.1.3 Inadequate infrastructural facilities

Infrastructural facilities such as electricity, transport, security and access to technology are fundamental to a country's development and are positively linked to small business and economic growth (Okpara, 2011). However, in many developing countries such as Nigeria, these infrastructural facilities are either lacking, or are in an inadequate state of provision and repair. Studies have shown that poor infrastructural facilities negatively affect small business development and the economy (Mambula, 2002; Tushabomwe-kazooba, 2006).

A lack of good infrastructural facilities has an adverse effect on entrepreneurship in Nigeria, especially the retail pharmacy sector. The electrical power supply in Nigeria is episodic, and most retail pharmacies use generators, which can be considerably expensive. According to Nkechi et al., (2012, p. 96), "the cost of an alternative source of power most often erodes whatever profit or capital an entrepreneur has put aside for his enterprise." An uninterrupted power supply throughout Nigeria might not be achievable before 2020 (NPC, 2010).

In addition to the intermittent power supply, the poor transportation network is also problematic. In the retail pharmacy sector, good road access is important for transporting pharmaceutical and related products timeously. However, the poor state of the roads adversely affects the distribution network and, consequently, the supply of the products. Another issue in Nigeria is security. The police force in the country is inefficient, and retail pharmacy entrepreneurs have to employ private security officers to prevent theft and armed robbery. Furthermore, state of the art technologies especially in form of ICT are not readily available (Nkechi et al., 2012).

Research has shown that the inability to use or acquire technology inhibits small business development in Africa (Okpara and Wynn, 2007; Okpara, 2011). With the growing impact of globalisation, new technologies and the appropriate skills to take advantage for business benefit has become essential (Galloway, 2007). In referring to infrastructure in general, Nkechi et al. (2012, p. 97) wrote that, “All these put together have made entrepreneurial activities cost-intensive, unprofitable, and uninteresting, thereby dissuading the youth from assuming entrepreneurial leadership positions.”

4.5.1.4 Political instability and corruption

The political environment in Nigeria is marked by instability. Changes in government, especially in the form of military coups and transitions in civilian administrations, usually lead to changes in policies. Moreover, militant groups such as Boko Haram pose huge security challenges. Furthermore, some government policies change to favour friends and associates (Nkechi et al., 2012). Such an environment is not conducive for entrepreneurship and may also affect the effectiveness of the legal system (Okpara, 2011). Kiggundu (2002) identified corruption as a major challenge facing African entrepreneurs, and this remains a major issue in Nigeria. Transparency International (2014) has identified Nigeria as one of the most corrupt nations of the world. Studies have shown that corruption has a negative impact on business performance (Okpara, 2011). In the context of the pharmacy industry, corruption has been shown to be one of the contributing factors to the availability of counterfeit drugs (Erhun et al., 2001). It can negatively affect the confidence of entrepreneurs (Pop, 2002) and dissuade people from venturing into entrepreneurship (Nkechi et al., 2012).

4.6 Conclusion

This chapter has examined entrepreneurship in the Nigerian context. The Nigerian economy is buoyant, but a combination of political instability, poor infrastructure and corruption are the key challenges facing the country. Nevertheless, these challenges make the setting more dynamic, especially for the retail pharmacy sector. The retail pharmacy sector in Nigeria is competitive and dynamic, and in order to survive in such environment, effective leaders who understand such complexities are required. Therefore, it is necessary to conduct research into this sector to gain a better understanding of the challenges which these entrepreneurial leaders face.

CHAPTER FIVE – SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW: ENTREPRENEURIAL LEADERSHIP

5.1 Introduction

This chapter provides a systematic literature review of entrepreneurial leadership. A systematic literature review (SLR) is an acknowledged method for producing reliable knowledge by using an evidence-based approach. The quantitative results from the systematic literature review are presented, and the various approaches and perspectives that have been used to examine entrepreneurial leadership are evaluated. Finally, knowledge gaps in the literature are identified.

5.2 Results of the systematic literature review

The results obtained from the systematic literature review within the area of entrepreneurial leadership are detailed in this section. (The step-by-step procedure for the systematic literature review is discussed in more detail in the methodology chapter.)

5.2.1 Descriptive analysis

Although the purpose of the systematic review is to provide a critical examination of literature on entrepreneurial leadership, it also provides quantitative results from five perspectives: geographical distribution, types of studies, number of publications, literature sources, and spread of citations. Furthermore, the papers that address entrepreneurial leadership from the perspective of a developing economy were highlighted. An overview of the search results is provided in appendix 3. In addition, quantitative information about the articles reviewed is provided in appendices 4 and

5. In total, 79 articles were selected from the process, of which 77 were retained for analysis after validation (see section 6.6.2.2.). 45 of the 77 articles were obtained from 8 databases using a keyword search (see Table 16), and 32 were obtained via Google scholar as well as from citations and references obtained from the previous (keyword) search.

5.2.1.1 Contributions based on geographical distribution

A high number of studies (37) in this field originate from the United States (USA). Twenty other countries are also represented, with UK coming second to the USA in terms of contribution (see Figure 4). 22 studies on entrepreneurial leadership in developing countries were found. Apart from Malaysia (with 10 studies), all the developing countries listed in the review had either 1 or 2 studies. The most common perspective of entrepreneurial leadership is therefore strongly oriented from the perspective of developed economies.

Figure 4 Geographical distribution of studies

5.2.1.2 Type of study

Findings from the review show that out of the 77 studies, 69% are empirical in nature, 25% are conceptual, and 6% were literature reviews (see Figure 5). In addition, 66% of the empirical studies were qualitative in nature, 32% used quantitative methods, and 2% used a mixed method approach (see Figure 6).

The research instruments utilised for data collection included interviews (37%), questionnaires (33%), case studies (28%), and data mining (2%) (see Figure 7).

Figure 5 Type of studies

Figure 6 Empirical studies

Figure 7 Method of data collection

5.2.1.3 Number of publications

As shown in Figure 8, the cited research into entrepreneurial leadership essentially dates from 1995 and has continued to increase during successive periods:

Figure 8 Number of papers by 5-year intervals

5.2.1.4 Literature sources

The 77 articles identified by the SLR appeared in a wide variety of journals and sources. Indeed, only five journals carried 2 sourced articles:

- International Journal of Entrepreneurial Behaviour and Research
- The Leadership Quarterly
- Leadership
- International Review of Entrepreneurship
- Frontiers of Entrepreneurship Research

5.2.1.5 Citation

Figure 9 shows the top 5 articles with the highest citations. The most cited article is Gupta et al. (2004) with 188 citations. This is to be expected as it was the first empirical study that sought to develop a construct for entrepreneurial leadership. Figure 10 shows the spread of citations over 5-year intervals. The highest concentration of citations was found to date from 2005 to 2009.

Figure 9 Top 5 articles based on citations

Figure 10 Spread of citations

5.2.1.6 Papers focussing on a developing economy

Only 10 papers have addressed the impact of entrepreneurial leadership in a developing economy, as detailed in Table 10:

Table 10 Papers on entrepreneurial leadership in developing countries

<i>Researchers</i>	<i>Developing country studied</i>
Devarajan et al. (2003)	India
Chen (2007)	Taiwan
Mapunda (2007)	Tanzania
Van Zyl and Mathur-Helm (2007)	South Africa
Agus and Hassan (2010)	Malaysia
Ruvio et al. (2010)	Israel
Khayesi and Antonakis (2012)	Kenya
Agbim et al. (2013)	Nigeria
Pihie and Bagheri (2013)	Malaysia
Rahab (2013)	Indonesia

Several authors suggest that entrepreneurial leadership is critical for improving firm and business performance in developing nations (Khayesi and Antonakis, 2012; Rahab, 2013; Van Zyl, and Mathur-Helm, 2007). Agus and Hassan (2010) go a step further by proposing that it is also essential in enhancing the sales performance and success of such businesses. The impact of entrepreneurial leadership in enhancing innovative capabilities has also been identified as a key issue (Chen, 2007; Devarajan et al., 2003).

Based on the results of the review, the sections to follow provide a conceptualisation of entrepreneurial leadership.

5.3 The definition of entrepreneurial leadership

Entrepreneurial leadership is a new paradigm that has emerged from the domains of leadership and entrepreneurship. Leadership and entrepreneurship are concepts that have been difficult to define (Bygrave and Hofer, 1991; Stogdill, 1974). Entrepreneurial leadership, which developed from a convergence of both fields (Fernald et al., 2005), lacks definitional consensus.

There are many definitions of entrepreneurial leadership. It has been defined as a type of leadership that creates visionary scenarios, which in turn are used to assemble and mobilize a “supporting cast” of participants who become committed to the discovery and exploitation of strategic value creation (Gupta et al., 2004, p. 242). Some scholars (Hejazi et al., 2012; Renko et al., 2012b) have stressed the importance of recognising and exploiting opportunities, while others (Greenberg et al., 2013; Surie and Ashley, 2008) emphasise the role of entrepreneurial leadership in solving complex problems in uncertain environments. But even with a number of definitions and heightened interest in entrepreneurial leadership, progress has been hindered by the lack of conceptual development and the absence of adequate tools to assess a leader’s entrepreneurial characteristics and behaviours (Renko et al., 2012b).

5.4 Conceptions of entrepreneurial leadership

Through the SLR, eight main approaches for researching the concept of entrepreneurial leadership were uncovered, each of which examine the phenomenon from a different perspective. These are as follows:

- Entrepreneurial leadership as a convergence of entrepreneurship and leadership
- The psychological and behavioural profile of entrepreneurial leaders
- The context of entrepreneurial leadership
- Theoretical approaches to entrepreneurial leadership
- Entrepreneurial leadership compared with other forms of leadership

- Entrepreneurial leadership and values
- Entrepreneurial leadership education
- Entrepreneurial leadership and venture performance

A table listing the authors who have contributed to each conceptual approach is provided in appendix 6. The eight conceptual approaches are described in the following sub-sections:

5.4.1 A convergence of entrepreneurship and leadership

Entrepreneurial leadership has been considered as a convergence of entrepreneurship and leadership (Fernald et al. 2005). Cogliser and Brigham (2004), in a comparative review of the fields of leadership and entrepreneurship, acknowledge that both fields overlap in the areas of vision, influence, innovation, and creativity, and planning. However, in their publication they neither define the concept of entrepreneurial leadership (Roomi and Harrison, 2011), nor demonstrate how it can be effectively measured (Gupta et al., 2004; Renko et al., 2012b). Essentially, they only provide thoughts on how the field of entrepreneurship can avoid the “pit falls” (Cogliser and Brigham, 2004, p. 771) that exist in the field of leadership. In a review of 136 papers in the fields of entrepreneurship and leadership, Fernald et al. (2005) identified eight characteristics common to both successful entrepreneurs and leaders: the ability to motivate, achievement orientation, creativity, flexibility, patience, persistence, risk taking, and vision. However, their approach to entrepreneurial leadership is descriptive, and lacking in analysis and explanation (Roomi and Harrison, 2011). They do not suggest how to utilise these common characteristics, and why entrepreneurial leaders possess them. Moreover, entrepreneurial leadership in developing economies is not considered.

5.4.2 Psychological and behavioural profile of entrepreneurial leaders

Most research done in the field of entrepreneurial leadership to date has sought to identify characteristics deemed to be essential in entrepreneurial leaders (e.g. Darling and Beebe, 2007; Gupta et al., 2004; Karanian, 2007; Nicholson, 1998; Nieuwenhuizen, 2009; Renko et al., 2012b). According to Karanian (2007), every entrepreneurial leader should possess five core attributes: connection, vivid imagination, family and cultural background, an expectation for confrontation, and a unique gift of character. Communication skills such as paradoxical thinking, controlled reflecting, intentional focusing, instinctive responding, inclusive behaving, purposeful trusting, and relational being are put forward by Darling and Beebe, (2007) as being essential for entrepreneurial leaders. Nieuwenhuizen (2009) identifies ingenuity, leadership and calculated risk taking as important attributes of an entrepreneur, while Gupta et al. (2004) identified 19 attributes. These approaches mirror the trait perspective in mainstream leadership research, and have been heavily criticised for failing to take into account the impact of context.

Rather than examining the attributes of the entrepreneurial leader, some scholars have sought to identify what entrepreneurial leaders actually do (Flamholtz, 2011; Strubler and Redekop 2010), and the strategies they adopt (Darling et al., 2007a and 2007b). Entrepreneurial leadership strategies such as meaning through communication, trust through positioning, and confidence through respect have been highlighted (Darling et al., 2007a and 2007b). According to Flamholtz (2011), entrepreneurial leadership functions includes creating the vision, managing the organisational culture, coordinating operations, overseeing systems development, and leading innovation and change. However, these studies also fail to examine the role of context in entrepreneurial leadership.

5.4.3 Context of entrepreneurial leadership

Scholars have examined entrepreneurial leadership in a number of settings. It has been examined from the context of family business (Kansikas et al., 2012; Renko et al., 2012b), SMEs (Khayesi and Antonakis, 2012; Leitch et al., 2009), research groups in universities (Hansson and Monsted, 2008), the public sector (Currie et al., 2008), non-profit organisations (Santora et al., 1999), directors of libraries (Carpenter, 2012), indigenous businesses (Mapunda, 2007), gender (Patterson et al., 2012a - 2012c), human, social and institutional capital (Leitch et al., 2012), and the aircraft industry (D'Intino et al., 2008).

Other studies have tried to address entrepreneurial leadership from a national (country-based) perspective (Bremer, 2009; Choi, 2009; Wang et al., 2012) and in terms of its impact in politics (Van Assche, 2005). Bremer (2009) compared entrepreneurial leadership in Sweden and China, taking into consideration their political and economic histories, leadership styles, and regulations. Wang et al. (2012) examined entrepreneurial leadership from the context of two Chinese firms.

Few scholars have emphasised the context in which this type of leadership is required (Chen, 2007; Swiercz and Lydon, 2002). Although Chen (2007) appreciates the impact of context, a strategic construct of firms (which are risk taking, proactiveness, and innovation) was used to explain entrepreneurial leadership. However, there remains an on-going battle among researchers as to whether those dimensions can be used for individual analysis (Renko et al., 2012b). Additionally, Swiercz and Lydon (2002) investigated high-tech firms to determine whether organisations undergo transition, and to identify the leadership competencies required by successful career entrepreneurial leaders. However, they fail to clearly illustrate how these competencies can be developed, or how training programs can be established to meet the changes that both the organisation and the entrepreneur face.

These scholars have failed to address entrepreneurial leadership from the dual perspective of leader and follower. Hejazi et al. (2012) have developed and validated a scale for measuring entrepreneurial leadership. However, Hejazi et al. (2012)

provide a self-assessment tool, and they only explore entrepreneurial leadership from one perspective, and ignore the impact of the follower.

5.4.4 Theoretical approach to entrepreneurial leadership

Most studies on entrepreneurial leadership have taken a theoretical approach rather than an empirical approach (e.g. Abbas and Tatfi, 2010; Ahmed and Ramzan, 2013; Covin and Slevin, 2004; Greenberg et al., 2013; Hentschke, 2010; Kempster and Cope, 2010; Kuratko and Hornsby, 1999; Kuratko, 2007; Patterson et al., 2012c; Rahab, 2013; Reimers-Hild and King, 2009; Van Zyl and Mathur-Helm 2007; Vecchio, 2003). For example, Kempster and Cope (2010) examined entrepreneurial leadership as a social process; Kuratko and Hornsby (1999) developed a framework for entrepreneurial leadership in corporations; and, Kuratko (2007) examined the concept of entrepreneurial leadership by tracing how the theory of entrepreneurship has emerged. Although such studies are significant contributions, they are conceptual and lack an empirical underpinning.

5.4.5 Entrepreneurial leadership compared with other forms of leadership.

Researchers have also compared entrepreneurial leadership with other forms of leadership (Darling et al., 2007a; Jones and Crompton, 2009). Entrepreneurial leadership has been investigated on the basis of enterprise logic and authentic leadership (Jones and Crompton, 2009), and charismatic and transformational leadership (Darling et al., 2007a). Although these researchers have found some similarities between entrepreneurial leadership, and authentic, charismatic and transformational approaches, they have not produced convincing conceptual frameworks.

5.4.6 Entrepreneurial leadership and values

The importance of values in entrepreneurial leadership has been investigated by Darling et al. (2007a; 2007b) and Surie and Ashley (2008). Key leadership values such as joy, charity, hope, and peace have been suggested as important in entrepreneurial leadership. Surie and Ashley (2008) went further to develop a framework to show how ethics can be embedded in entrepreneurial leadership by viewing it through the lens of pragmatism. Their findings suggest that following ethical standards may be costly to a new business in the short term.

5.4.7 Entrepreneurial leadership education

The value of entrepreneurial leadership education has been investigated by various researchers (e.g. Bagheri and Pihie, 2010; Bagheri and Pihie 2011; Okudan and Rzasa, 2004 and 2006; Roomi and Harrison, 2011). Entrepreneurial leadership courses have been shown to improve entrepreneurial behaviour among students (Okudan and Rzasa, 2004; 2006). Research has also been carried out to identify the challenges and competencies of leading university entrepreneurship programmes (Bagheri and Pihie, 2011) as well as entrepreneurial leadership learning (Bagheri and Pihie, 2010; Roomi and Harrison, 2011). However, such work neglects the role of context in shaping entrepreneurial leadership. The impact of culture and demographics in entrepreneurial leadership education has not been considered.

5.4.8 Entrepreneurial leadership and venture performance

The upsurge of interest in entrepreneurial leadership can be attributed at least in part to the assertion by some scholars that it is important for improved performance and organisational success. Sundararajan et al. (2012) suggested that a spiritual entrepreneurial leadership model helps to address the problem of the high rate of start-up failures, although their meditative stance has yet to be tested empirically.

Studies have also shown that entrepreneurial leadership has a positive and direct effect on sales performance and customer satisfaction (Agus and Hassan, 2010), employee satisfaction, motivation, commitment, and effectiveness (Papalexandris and Galanaki, 2009). However, these studies (e.g. Hmieleski and Ensley, 2007) do not recognise the importance of other dimensions such as opportunity recognition, exploitation, or strategising, which may be important to entrepreneurial leadership (Carpenter, 2012; Gupta et al., 2004).

An in-depth summary of the reviewed articles is presented in Table 11 below:

Table 11 Summary of reviewed articles

<i>Name of author</i>	<i>Focus</i>
Abbas, S. and Tatfi, M. (2010)	This article is entirely theoretical, but it proposes that an effective entrepreneurial leader should build trust among employees, communicate effectively with them, seek self-improvement, possess technical skills, accept responsibility for actions, make decisions, and be a role model.
Agbim, K. C., Oriarewo, G. O. and Owutuamor, Z. B. (2013)	Agbim et al. examined the effect of the dimensions of entrepreneurial leadership on sustained entrepreneurial success in the Anambra state of Nigeria. However, they seek to only confirm the previous work by Hejazi et al. (2012). The authors use the scale proposed by Hejazi et al., which is a self-assessment tool and which neglects the impact of the follower in entrepreneurial leadership.
Agus, A. and Hassan, Z. (2010)	This article shows that entrepreneurial leadership has a positive impact on sales performance and customer satisfaction in a developing economy such as Malaysia. However, the study does not take a dual perspective; rather, the data was collected only from entrepreneurs via a self-reporting instrument, thereby raising questions about the validity of their assertions.
Ahmed, A. and Ramzan, M. A (2013)	This article adds nothing more to the study conducted by Bagheri and Pihie (2011).
Bagheri, A., and Pihie, Z. A. L. (2009)	This article is focused on facilitating entrepreneurial leadership development through university entrepreneurship programs. However, the article examines entrepreneurial leadership based only on

	students' creativity, risk taking and innovativeness.
Bagheri, A., Akmaliah, Z. and Pihie, L. (2010)	This article focuses on the role of family in improving entrepreneurial leadership competencies among university students.
Bagheri, A. and Pihie, Z. A. L. (2010)	This article focuses on entrepreneurial leadership learning from the perspective of university students.
Bagheri, A., Akmaliah, Z. and Pihie, L. (2011)	This article provides an integrated model for learning and developing entrepreneurial leadership. However, the model is built on Gupta et al.'s (2004) five competencies of scenario enactment (pro-activeness, risk taking, and innovativeness) and cast enactment (building commitment and specifying limits), which have been criticised by researchers. In addition, it does not provide empirical evidence to support its reliability and applicability.
Bagheri, A., and Pihie, Z. A. (2011)	This article mainly shows that entrepreneurial leadership, self-awareness, identity realisation, and self-efficacy can be improved through university entrepreneurship programmes rather than by focusing on entrepreneurial leadership attributes or their development.
Bagheri, A., and Pihie, Z. A. L. (2012)	This article shows that students' involvement in leadership tasks and roles is critical in their entrepreneurial leadership education.
Bagheri, A., Lope Pihie, Z. A. and Krauss, S. E. (2013)	This article examines entrepreneurial leadership competencies among Malaysian student entrepreneurial leaders. However, it should be noted that not all competencies or attributes are addressed. For example, risk taking is not considered.
Bagheri, A. and Lope Pihie, Z. A. (2013)	This article does not focus on entrepreneurial leadership programmes; rather, the emphasis is on the role of entrepreneurship programmes in developing a student's entrepreneurial leadership competencies.
Bremer, I. (2009)	This article fails to look at entrepreneurial leadership at an individual level. However, the article shows that entrepreneurial leadership style and capabilities tend to differ between countries as a result of their values and cultural differences, namely Sweden and China.
Carpenter, M. T. H. (2012)	This article is focused on the attributes of entrepreneurial leaders, and identifies them as cheerleaders and conveyors of vision, opportunity seekers, and master strategists.

Chen, Ming-Hei (2007)	Chen (2007) used the strategic construct of firms (which are risk taking, pro-activeness and innovation) to explain entrepreneurial leadership. But there remains an on-going battle among researchers as to whether those dimensions can be used for individual analysis (Renko et al., 2012b).
Choi, E. K. (2009)	The article is entirely conceptual and it suggests that clear vision (as displayed by Yamanobe and Watanobe in the Japanese cotton industry) is an essential entrepreneurial leadership attribute which can lead to ground-breaking global competitiveness.
Cogliser, C. C. and Brigham, K. H. (2004)	This article, which is a comparative review of the fields of leadership and entrepreneurship, acknowledges that both fields overlap in the areas of vision, influence, innovation and creativity, and planning. However, the work by Cogliser and Brigham does not define the concept of entrepreneurial leadership (Roomi and Harrison, 2011), nor demonstrates how it can effectively be measured (Gupta et al., 2004; Renko et al., 2012b). The authors only provide thoughts on how the field of entrepreneurship can avoid the “pit falls” in the field of leadership (Cogliser and Brigham, 2004, p.771). Cogliser and Brigham are only concerned about how entrepreneurship researchers can learn from the experiences and mistakes made by scholars in the field of leadership.
Currie, G., Humphreys, M., Ucbasaran, D. and Mcmanus, S. (2008)	This article focuses on the public sector, and exhibits a good understanding of (i) the impact of multiple stakeholders and on how to manage them, (ii) knowledge of the political landscape, and (iii) the ability to identify and exploit opportunities as important aspects of entrepreneurial leadership.
Covin, J. G. and Slevin, D. P. (2004)	This article is entirely conceptual, and its authors identify the major elements of entrepreneurial leadership as being social influence and opportunity.
Darling et al. (2007a)	This article focuses on entrepreneurial leadership strategies, such as attention through vision, meaning through communication, trust through positioning, and confidence through respect. Key leadership values such as joy, charity, hope, and peace are also identified.
Darling, J. R. and Beebe, S. A. (2007)	The article is entirely conceptual and identifies communication skills as important for entrepreneurial leadership.

Darling, J. R., Keeffe, M. J. and Ross, J. K. (2007b)	This article contributes nothing more to the work of Darling et al. (2007a).
Devarajan, T., Ramachandran, K. and Ramnarayan, S. (2003)	This article tests the theory that entrepreneurial leadership of top management teams enhance innovation, and thereby increase firm success. However, the relevant attributes necessary for an individual effective entrepreneurial leader are not discussed.
D'intino, R. S. Boyles, T., Neck, C. P. and Hall, J. R. (2008)	This article examines the important characteristics for developing a visionary entrepreneurial leadership. These characteristics are radical innovation, technological vision, courageous decision making, and rational risk-taking. However, it should be noted that the study is entirely based on a single case of Boeing, and makes no comparison with other companies in the aircraft industry.
Fernald, L. W Jr., Solomon, G. T. and Tarabishy, A. (2005)	This article is a review of 136 papers in both fields, in which 8 characteristics common among both successful entrepreneurs and leaders were identified. These characteristics include: the ability to motivate, achievement orientation, creativity, flexibility, patience, persistence, risk-taking, and vision. However, their approach to entrepreneurial leadership is descriptive, and lacks analysis and explanation (Roomi and Harrison, 2011). They do not suggest how to build on the common characteristics, or why entrepreneurs possess them. The peculiarity of a developing economy and entrepreneurial leadership is not considered either.
Flamholtz, E. G. (2011)	This article identifies five strategic leadership functions that are important in an entrepreneurial context, namely creating the vision, managing the organisational culture, coordinating operations, overseeing systems development, and leading innovation and change.
Greenberg, D., McKone-Sweet, K. and Wilson, H. J. (2013)	This article is essentially a thought piece, but it does suggest that entrepreneurial leadership is important for creating new opportunities.
Guo, K. L. (2009)	The article identifies three overlapping areas of core competencies required by health care entrepreneurial leaders, namely (i) system and environment competencies (which include knowledge of the system and stakeholders, as well as the ability to take risks and apply innovative strategies); (ii) organisational competence (consisting of financial quality and risk management skills); and, (iii) interpersonal

	<p>competencies (which is the development of one's own and others' professional skills through effective communication and motivation).</p> <p>However, the author only reviews past literature to generate a competency model for entrepreneurial health care leadership.</p>
Gupta, V., MacMillan, I. C. and Surie, G. (2004)	This article identifies 19 attributes which are classified into five roles: framing the challenge, absorbing uncertainty, path clearing, building commitment, and specifying limits. However, the researchers use GLOBE data not meant for entrepreneurial leadership to explain the phenomenon, and this has been widely criticised for failing to recognise the importance of ethics (Rahab, 2013).
Hansson, F. and Mønsted, M. (2008)	The article identifies five qualities for research entrepreneurial leadership: charisma, the ability to ensure networking in teaching and research, the capability of using external contacts to disseminate research, the capacity to negotiate and develop openings creatively, and the ability to create an environment of self-confidence. However, it should be noted that empirical results were obtained from only two cases in the same Danish university.
Hejazi, A. M., Maleki, M. M. and Naeji, M. J. (2012)	Hejazi et al. develop and validate a scale for measuring entrepreneurial leadership. Four different factors (strategy, communication, motivation and personal factors) are considered necessary for entrepreneurial leadership, based on questionnaire results. However, Hejazi et al. provide a self-assessment tool, and only consider entrepreneurial leadership from one perspective, while ignoring the impact of the follower.
Hentschke, G. C. (2010)	The article identifies entrepreneurial leadership attributes and skills that are important in the educational domain. However, the paper is entirely conceptual and is not backed by empirical findings.
Hmieleski, K. M. and Ensley, M. D. (2007)	These scholars argue that in dynamic environments, heterogeneous top management teams perform better when led by directive leaders, and that those with homogenous setups did better with an empowering leader. However, in stable environments, the reverse was observed, with directive leaders being better suited for homogenous top management teams, and empowering leaders being better suited for heterogeneous ones. However, the study looks at entrepreneurial leadership from an empowerment and directive construct in relation

	to the followers. The research does not recognise the importance of other dimensions such as opportunity recognition and exploitation which studies have shown to be vital in entrepreneurial leadership (Gupta et al., 2004; Carpenter, 2012).
Jones, O. and Crompton, H. (2009)	This article is mainly focused on building a model for entrepreneurial leadership which is based on authentic leadership and enterprise logic. It is not really aimed at identifying the essential attributes in entrepreneurial leadership, although there is a mention of the influence of key individuals, communication, delegation, organisational structures, people management, vision, and enactment.
Kansikas, J., Laakkonen, A., Sarpo, V. and Kontinen, T. (2012)	This article shows the impact of familiness and entrepreneurial leadership in family businesses in different countries.
Karanian, B. (2007)	This article suggests that every entrepreneurial leader should possess five core attributes: connection, vivid imagination, family and cultural background, an expectation for confrontation, and a unique gift of character. However, it should be noted that the study uses a thematic apperception test (TAT), whose validity remains a great source of debate among researchers.
Kempster, S. and Cope, J. (2010)	The article was aimed at analysing entrepreneurial leadership as a social process. Its focus is on how entrepreneurs learn to lead. The study falls short of explaining the impact of entrepreneurial leadership particularly in a developing economy.
Khayesi, J. N. and Antonakis, J. (2012)	This article shows that a relationship exists between the leadership attributes of entrepreneurs and firm performance in a developing economy, namely Kenya. However, it should be noted that the study uses a scale developed by Gupta et al. (2004) consisting of 19 attributes. There is a great debate among scholars about the exclusion of the ethical dimension from the construct developed by Gupta et al, which therefore limits the validity of the findings in this article.
Kuratko, D. F. and Hornsby, J. S. (1999)	The article is entirely theoretical, and identifies specific elements for entrepreneurial leadership: developing the vision, developing innovation, developing venture teams, and providing an entrepreneurial climate in the corporation.
Kuratko, D. F. (2007)	This article is entirely conceptual and similar to that by Chen (2007), who considered the strategic constructs of

	a firm when describing the characteristics of an entrepreneurial leader.
Lang, J. A. (2013)	This is a general review article that provides theoretical concepts of entrepreneurial leadership. However, it raises suggestions on how to develop leaders who will shape social and economic opportunities.
Leitch, C. M., Mcmullan, C. and Harrison, R. T. (2009)	This article is not focused on the impact of entrepreneurial leadership or on its attributes; rather, it investigates leadership development in SMEs. In addition, the participants in their study were similar in their profile in terms of gender and the capitalization of their businesses, therefore the education and learning that comes from diversity in experience and perspective was not explored in their study.
Leitch, C. M., Mcmullan, C. and Harrison, R. T. (2012)	The article examines entrepreneurial leadership from the context of human, social, and institutional capital, and makes no contribution to the field of entrepreneurial leadership skills. However, the development of human capital is identified as being important in entrepreneurial leadership.
Lippitt, G. L. (1987)	In this conceptual piece of work, the author lists six characteristics of an entrepreneurial leader: risk taking, divergent thinking, sharp focus, personal responsibility, economic orientation, and learning from experience. Lippitt goes further to suggest guidelines for developing entrepreneurial leadership: developing one's self understanding; diagnostic skills; learning how to get advice and setting life goals; dealing with adversity; and, coping with change. However, just like most other articles listed in this table, their study is conceptual and does not provide any empirical justification for the acclaimed characteristics and guidelines.
Mapunda, G. (2007)	This article examines the role of entrepreneurial leadership in the development of indigenous business enterprises in Tanzania and South Australia. However, the follower's perspective of entrepreneurial leadership was neglected.
Nicholson, N. (1998)	This article provides a personality profile for entrepreneurial leaders. Being tough minded, unattached by social distractions, being assertive, and not getting diverted by curiosity make up such a profile. However, the study views entrepreneurial leadership from a unilateral perspective, and does not consider the effect of followers. In addition, such a trait approach used in the

	study has been criticised by various researchers as a narrow view (Vecchio 2003).
Nieuwenhuizen, C. (2009)	This article focuses on entrepreneurial leadership attributes. It identifies ingenuity, leadership and calculated risk taking as being important attributes of an entrepreneur. However, the study uses data from previous studies not originally meant for this purpose. As a result, the validity of these findings remains unclear. An approach that uses primary data obtained from entrepreneurs may be more suitable for identifying such characteristics.
Okudan, G. E. and Rzasa, S. E. (2004)	(This article covers the same aspects as the 2006 article below)
Okudan, G. E. and Rzasa, S. E. (2006)	This article examines the effect of entrepreneurial leadership courses in developing entrepreneurial leadership behaviour among students. However, it should be noted that no pre-testing of the study was done. In addition, no control sample was used. So although their approach is informative, it is not possible to assess the extent of the impact of the new course in improving entrepreneurial leadership behaviour.
Oliver, T. R. and Paul-Shaheen, P. (1997)	The article is mainly aimed at identifying different strategies that leaders in six states in the US used to carry out their entrepreneurial tasks. The study fails to identify essential entrepreneurial leadership skills.
Papalexandris, N. and Galanaki, E. (2009)	This article shows a positive impact of entrepreneurial leadership on employees' satisfaction, motivation, commitment, and effectiveness. However, the study uses questionnaires developed from the GLOBE study which were not meant originally for this research, and which could affect the validity of their findings.
Pashiardis, P. and Savvides, V. (2011)	This article shows the impact of entrepreneurial leadership in Cyprus, a society which is still undergoing transition. It suggests that entrepreneurial leadership is relevant only in the external context (such as developing networks with parents and the community, and acquiring resources). They argue that instructional leadership involves the internal dynamics of vision building and communication. However, research has shown that entrepreneurial leaders are indeed vision builders and effective communicators (Darling and Beebe, 2007).
Patterson, N., Sharon, M. and Turner, J. (2012a)	These articles mainly focus on entrepreneurial leadership from a gender perspective.

Patterson, N., Sharon, M. and Turner, J. (2012b)	
Patterson, N., Sharon, M. and Turner, J. (2012c)	
Pihie, Z. A. L. and Bagheri, A. (2013)	<p>This article shows that the entrepreneurial leadership behaviour of principals have a significant positive impact on teachers' perception of the school's organisational innovativeness.</p> <p>However, the study only examines a principal's entrepreneurial leadership behaviour from the singular perspective of the teacher. It may be more accurate to view entrepreneurial leadership from a dual perspective of both the teacher and the principal. The quantitative instrument used had a discriminant issue in terms of measuring the components of entrepreneurial leadership; hence this could affect the validity of their findings.</p>
Rahab, R. (2013)	The study is similar to the work carried out by Van Zyl and Mathur-Helm (2007), but was conducted in Indonesia.
Reimers-Hild, C. and King, J. W. (2009)	<p>This article suggests that entrepreneurial leaders required in the distance education sector must communicate a relevant vision; inspire and motivate others; leverage human and social capital; and, develop a global mind-set in the institution that embraces value, change, and continuous innovation.</p> <p>However, their study is theoretical and no empirical evidence is provided to back up their assertions.</p>
Renko, M., Tarabishy, A. and Carsrud, A. R. (2009)	(This article has nothing more to add to what was stated by Renko et al. (2012b).)
Renko, M., Tarabishy, A., Carsrud, A. L. and Brannback, M. (2012a)	This article is focused on the impact of entrepreneurial leadership from the perspective of family-owned businesses. Although the authors identify communicating desired vision, entrepreneurial culture and role modelling as being important aspects of entrepreneurship, they do not consider whether these are attributes and if so, how they can be developed.
Renko, M., Tarabishy, A., Carsrud, A. L. and Brannback, M. (2012b)	The authors developed a scale for measuring entrepreneurial leadership based on the follower's perspective, but did not consider how leaders perceive leadership abilities.

Roomi, M. A. and Harrison, C., (2011)	This article mainly reviews past literature on entrepreneurial leadership, especially on entrepreneurship teaching and development. The authors prescribe suggestions on entrepreneurial leadership development, but provide no statistical validation of their assertions.
Ruvio, A., Rosenblatt, Z. and Hertz-Lazarowitz, R. (2010)	This article shows that vision is an important entrepreneurial leadership attribute in both profit-making and non-profit organisations. However, it should be noted that they used a self-assessment tool to gather data from the entrepreneurs; a multi-perspective stance may have been more suitable.
Santora, J. C., Seaton, W. and Sarros, J. C. (1999)	This article focuses on the impact of entrepreneurial leadership and change in a Hispanic community-based non-profit organisation. The authors put forward that entrepreneurial leadership is vital to the success of non-profit based organisations. However, only a single case is used.
Siddiqui, S. (2007)	This article focuses on seven suggested groups of entrepreneurial leadership traits: subordinate factor, intelligence, physical factor, action, nerve, task, and innovation. However, the author fails to recognise that traits could be innate and might not be easy to learn.
Strubler, D. C. and Redekop, B. W. (2010)	This article examines entrepreneurial leadership from a human resources stance, and the authors assert that innovation, hard work, a sense of fun, and team spirit will make employees more motivated and productive. However, Carlson is the only entrepreneur considered in their study; more successful entrepreneurs from different sectors may have added more value to their research on entrepreneurial leadership.
Sundararajan, M., Sundararajan, B. and Henderson, S. (2012)	This article focuses on the impact of entrepreneurial leadership (but not always in developing economies), and the authors propose a spiritual entrepreneurial leadership model to solve the problem of the high rate of start-up failures. However, their meditative foundation stance has yet to be tested empirically.
Surie, G. and Ashley, A. (2008)	This article contributes to entrepreneurial leadership attributes by suggesting that ethics should be embedded among them. However, the authors agree that following ethical standards could be costly in the short term, hence fuelling the debate on whether ethics are really essential.
Swiercz, P. M. and Lydon, S. R. (2002)	These scholars investigated high-tech firms to determine whether organisations undergo transition, and they studied leadership competencies required by successful

	career entrepreneurial leaders. However, they fail to clearly illustrate how these competencies can be developed.
Tarabishy, A., Fernald Jr, L. W. and Solomon, G. T. (2002)	This study is entirely conceptual and does not provide any empirical justification, but seeks to encourage more research into entrepreneurial leadership. However, they suggest that an entrepreneurial leader must possess transformational leadership dimensions, including clarity, communication, consistency, compassion, the ability to create opportunities, self-confidence, the desire for power, and vision.
Tarabishy, A., Solomon, G., Fernald Jr, L. W. and Sashkin, M. (2005)	The authors examine the impact of entrepreneurial leadership on the development of a strategic posture for an organisation to compete in today's dynamic market. However, they only consider transformational and transactional dimensions, whereas characteristics such as opportunity recognition and exploitation (which have been identified by other researchers as paramount) are neglected.
Tice, B. P. (2005)	This article is essentially a thought piece but it does suggest that to advance the pharmacy profession, entrepreneurial leadership principles must be integrated into pharmacy school curricula and practice, and that incubators should be established.
Van Assche, T. (2005)	This study only offers a hypothesis that entrepreneurial leadership is a necessary factor in the international area that requires further testing in other international organisations. However, the author proposes that entrepreneurial leadership requires skilful setting of agendas, popularisation of issues, adeptness in devising innovative policies, and making deals that enhances support (as seen in the leadership approach of Jacques Delors).
Van Zyl, H. and Mathur-Helm, B. (2007)	This article puts forward the case for the inclusion of ethics in the entrepreneurial leadership construct developed by Gupta et al. (2004). A model showing the impact of entrepreneurial leadership in business performance is presented, but no empirical evidence is provided.
Vecchio, R. P. (2003)	This article mainly focuses on the treatment of entrepreneurship as a separate study rather than on its impact in a developing economy.

Wang, C. L., Tee, D. D. and Ahmed, P. K. (2012)	This article identifies multi-level factors such as philosophical traditions, cultural values, and organisational, personal and transitional factors, all of which are valuable for determining the impact of entrepreneurial leadership (using two Chinese firms in this case study). The authors claim that entrepreneurial leadership style could be transactional, transformational, benevolent, or situational.
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Following an intensive review of the literature, knowledge gaps were identified, which in turn are examined in the following section.

5.5 Gaps from the systematic literature review and the narrative review

The systematic literature review (SLR) has shown entrepreneurial leadership to be a comparatively new research area in which empirical work lags behind in theoretical and conceptual development. Notwithstanding this, there is a consensus that entrepreneurial leadership is an important factor in the development of an enterprise. Within the existing body of research, the impact of entrepreneurial leadership in a developing economy has received limited attention, and this represents a substantial gap in existing knowledge. This gap has two dimensions: evidence, and theory.

5.5.1.1 Evidence-based gaps

- Research on entrepreneurial leadership has generally shown that it has a positive impact on the economy. However, limited research has been conducted about the impact of entrepreneurial leadership in a developing economy.

- Despite the importance of leader/ follower research having been established in the business leadership literature, studies which adopt this perspective to investigate entrepreneurial leadership rarely exist.
- There are no significant studies in which entrepreneurial leadership within Nigeria has been rigorously investigated. During the course of the literature review, no studies on the challenges confronting retail pharmacy entrepreneurs in the Nigerian economy were found. Most relevant studies only highlight the challenges that Nigerian entrepreneurs face (Nkechi et al., 2012; Okpara, 2011), or on the nature of the retail pharmacy sector in a developing economy (Goel et al., 1996), or on legislation and regulations affecting this sector in low-income countries (Lowe and Montagu, 2009). There has been no empirical investigation of the challenges that retail pharmacy entrepreneurs are exposed to in Nigeria.

5.5.1.2 Theoretical gaps

- No significant study highlights the important entrepreneurial leadership skills required to succeed in a developing economy. In particular, there is no definite skill-based model for entrepreneurial leadership.
- Studies on entrepreneurial leadership have revealed divergent views in terms of the necessary attributes. For example, Hentschke (2010, p. 122) identifies perseverance as a “critical survival skill” for any entrepreneurial leader, while Carpenter (2012) identifies perseverance as one of the lowest rated attributes. Moreover, no consensus has been reached by researchers on the level of risk propensity (Vecchio, 2003). For example, Chen (2007) suggests that entrepreneurial leaders need to take higher risks to stimulate their teams to be more creative, but Lippit (1987) suggests that entrepreneurial leaders should only take moderate risks.

Overall, it can be concluded that previous research has neglected the role of entrepreneurial leadership in developing countries. Therefore, the focus of this doctoral study is both original and necessary. Moreover, by adopting a skill-based perspective, this study follows a path trodden by researchers in the field of business leadership who have made significant contributions to this area of study. More specifically, this study was guided by Katz's skills model of business leadership.

5.6 Conclusion

In this chapter, the findings from the systematic review of literature on entrepreneurial leadership were presented. These results were set out according to five perspectives: geographical distribution, types of studies, number of publications, literature sources, and the spread of citations over the years. Furthermore, the various approaches adopted by scholars when researching entrepreneurial leadership were evaluated, and gaps in literature were identified.

The findings of the systematic literature review highlight the diverse nature of entrepreneurial leadership. In a fast-moving business environment, leaders must be able to identify and exploit opportunities. Therefore, there remains a great need for research into the ways in which entrepreneurial leadership can be effective in dynamic contexts.

CHAPTER SIX – METHODOLOGY

6.1 Introduction

In previous chapters the understanding of entrepreneurial leadership has been deepened by critically reviewing literature from the fields of entrepreneurship, leadership and entrepreneurial leadership. Following the literature review, it was concluded that there remains an inadequate theoretical and conceptual understanding of entrepreneurial leadership. In light of this, the aim of this study was to address these limitations and, in so doing, gain an understanding of the challenges that entrepreneurial leaders face, and the skills which are essential for running their businesses. Furthermore, this study addresses specific research questions stated below:

Research questions

- What is entrepreneurial leadership?
- What are the challenges that entrepreneurs in a developing economy face in running their businesses?
- What entrepreneurial leadership skills are valuable for running businesses successfully in a developing economy?
- What are the employees' perceptions of the entrepreneurial leadership of the entrepreneurs?

In this chapter, the research design is described, and the related methodological considerations of this study are outlined. This chapter begins with an introduction to the methodological approach that was adopted, followed by an overview of different paradigms used in management research, together with a justification of why an interpretivist paradigm was chosen for the study (see sections 6.2 and 6.3). This is followed by a discussion of the philosophical stance for the research in section 6.4. In Section 6.5, the adopted qualitative research method is discussed, and similar studies of entrepreneurial leadership that have been applied in such an approach are evaluated. A research design compatible with the objectives of this study is derived

in section 6.6, and the sample and sector selected for the research are outlined. The process of data collection in the form of in-depth interviews with the entrepreneurs and their employees are explained in section 6.7. The data analysis and interpretation process, which was based on thematic analysis, is described in section 6.8. The issues of credibility, dependability, confirmability, and transferability of the qualitative findings are discussed in section 6.9. Section 6.10 addresses the ethical issues considered. Finally, the chapter is concluded with a summary in section 6.11.

A diagrammatic representation of the various layers of research addressed in this chapter is set out below in Figure 11:

Figure 11 Layers of Research

6.2 Research approach

There are two main approaches to research: the deductive (hypo-deductive) approach, and the inductive approach. The key reasoning behind the two approaches is highlighted in Table 12:

Table 12 Reasoning behind deductive and inductive Approaches

	DEDUCTION	INDUCTION
<i>Logic</i>	In a deductive inference, when the premises are true, the conclusion must also be true.	In an inductive inference, known premises are used to generate untested conclusions.
<i>Generalisability</i>	Generalising from the general to the specific.	Generalising from the specific to the general.
<i>Use of data</i>	Data collection is used to evaluate propositions or hypotheses in relation to an existing theory.	Data collection is used to explore a phenomenon, identify themes and patterns, and create a conceptual framework.
<i>Theory</i>	Theory falsification or verification.	Theory generation and building.

Source: Saunders et al. (2012)

According to Saunders et al. (2012, p. 145), deductive reasoning “...involves the development of theory that is then subjected to a rigorous testing through a series of propositions”. As a result, it is popularly used in science and mostly involves the use of experiments. Deductive reasoning uses statements obtained from *a priori* logic to explain specific instances (Harrison, 2002), and conclusions reached must follow from the earlier premise given (Blumberg et al., 2011). In contrast, the inductive approach involves “...moving from the plane of observation of the empirical world to the construction of explanations and theories about what has been observed” (Gill and Johnson, 1997, p. 33). Unlike the deductive approach, theory is an outcome of the empirical research, and no conceptual or theoretical basis is developed prior to it.

The knowledge obtained during the course of the research provides the basis for theory development (Flick, 2011) and can be fed back into the “...stock of theory and research associated with a certain domain of enquiry” (Bryman and Bell, 2011, p. 11).

However, a more recent approach has emerged which combines both deductive and inductive reasoning, which is called the abductive approach (Agar, 2010; Klag and Langley, 2013; Reichertz, 2007). An abductive approach is a research approach used in discovery related processes. This approach brings together different ideas about a phenomenon (Reichertz, 2007). Some scholars have viewed the dichotomy between deductive and inductive approaches as “problematic”, suggesting it to be a form of “naïve empiricism” that ignores pre-existing theoretical ideas (Klag and Langley, 2013, p. 151). These scholars have increasingly argued that it is misleading to infer that any research is entirely deductive or inductive, and that the issues are not as clear-cut as usually presented (Bryman and Bell, 2011; Saunders et al., 2012).

Reichertz (2007, p. 220) defines abduction as “...a cerebral process, an intellectual act, a mental leap that brings together things which one had never associated with one another: a cognitive logic of discovery”. It is a process of reasoning through which ongoing observations lead to some kind of surprise (Klag and Langley, 2013). It consists of assembling or discovering collected data for which there is no appropriate explanation in the canon of knowledge that already exists (Klag and Langley, 2013). Unlike deductive reasoning (which moves from theory to data) and inductive reasoning (which moves from data to theory), an abductive approach moves back and forth. Hence, it combines both deduction and induction (Suddaby, 2006). The abductive approach is inherently interactive and recursive (Agar, 2010), and is embedded in observation and ambient ideas (Klag and Langley, 2013). It seeks out unexpected data and creates new concepts to explain it (Agar, 2010).

The intent of this study was to search for unexpected data, and create new concepts about entrepreneurial leadership, with particular reference to a developing economy. An abductive approach, which is a discovery-oriented process that combines both inductive and deductive reasoning, was therefore adopted for this study.

6.3 Research paradigms

The aim of this chapter is to discuss the research design in terms of the methodology applied. However, such a discussion will not be complete if the paradigm on which the research is based is not elaborated. A paradigm is "...a system of ideas, or world view, used by a community of researchers to generate knowledge" (Fossey et al., 2002, p. 718). According to Gioia and Pitre (1990, p. 585), it "...is a general perspective or way of thinking that reflects fundamental beliefs and assumptions about the nature of organisations". Bryman (1988) (cited in Bryman and Bell, 2011, p. 24) describes a paradigm as a "...cluster of beliefs and dictates which for scientists in a particular discipline influence what should be studied, how research should be done, [and] how results should be interpreted". In general, a paradigm captures the philosophy behind the researcher's approach, and assumptions about the world in which she/he lives.

Scholars have presented several paradigms in relation to understanding the epistemology and ontology of business research (see Burrell and Morgan, 1979; Creswell, 2009; Lincoln and Guba, 2003). However, it can be argued that the most significant influence in business research has been through Burrell and Morgan's framework of four paradigms, which are the functionalist (i.e. positivist), interpretative, radical humanist, and the radical structuralist paradigms. The functionalist paradigm is characterised by an objectivist view of the world based on a problem solving orientation that brings about a rational explanation for any phenomenon. The interpretative paradigm is more subjective, questioning the existence of organisations beyond the impact of social actors. The radical humanist paradigm views the organisation as a social arrangement requiring radical change, and the radical structuralist paradigm is typified by conflict, viewing the organisation on the basis of power relationships (Bryman and Bell, 2011; Gioia and Pitre, 1990; Saunders et al., 2012). The functionalist and interpretative paradigms are more popular among scholars, and will be discussed in this chapter.

The functionalist paradigm, also known as positivism, is sustained by an "...ontological view that humans can be studied in the same way as other objects in the physical world" (King and Horrocks, 2012, p. 12). It provides an objective

stance, and views research as being value-neutral and unbiased by the researcher's perspective or by the research process (King and Horrocks, 2012; Saunders et al., 2012). It is the paradigm adopted in science in which knowledge about reality is obtained mainly by observing objective facts. The world is viewed from an external perspective, and explanations to understand any phenomenon are provided through objective means. As stated by Chia (2002, p. 7), "For positivists, therefore, good research consists of the undistorted recording of observations obtained through efficiency-driven methods of investigation and use of precise terminologies and classifications in the documentary process." Therefore, positivists neglect the impact of subjectivity, believing that a dispassionate and objective means is the only way to obtain reliable and valid data.

By contrast, interpretivism views people as social constructors of their own organisational realities (Gioia and Pitre, 1990). Unlike positivism, interpretivists argue that the apparatus of science cannot be used to understand the social world. They believe that the social world can only be understood subjectively through the lens of people, and that the impact of the researcher during the course of the research cannot be neglected (Blumberg et al., 2011). For them, a social phenomenon can only be understood by looking at the whole picture; research is never value-free, but is socially constructed even by the researcher.

The different viewpoints of both paradigms are represented in Table 13:

Table 13 Different viewpoints of Positivism and Interpretivism

Basic principles	Positivism (Functionalist)	Interpretivism
<i>View of the world</i>	The world is external and objective.	The world is socially constructed and subjective.
<i>Involvement of Researcher</i>	Researcher is independent.	Researcher is part of what is observed and sometimes even actively collaborates.
<i>Researcher's influence</i>	Research is value-free.	Research is driven by human interest.
Assumptions		
<i>What is observed?</i>	Objective, often quantitative, facts.	Subjective interpretations of meanings.
<i>How is knowledge developed?</i>	Reducing phenomena to simple elements representing general laws.	Taking a broad and total view of phenomena to detect explanations beyond the current knowledge.

Source: Blumberg et al. (2011, p. 19)

This study was exploratory, and involved building a theory about entrepreneurial leadership based on the subjective experience of entrepreneurial leaders. Therefore, the interpretivist paradigm was more suitable and was adopted. This paradigm helps in understanding how entrepreneurs make sense and interpret their social world. The world of business is dynamic and in a state of constant flux; hence, theories can easily become obsolete. According to Blumberg et al. (2011), in a changing world, generalisations, even within short periods, are questionable. Since the purpose of this research study was to gain insights into entrepreneurial leadership, an interpretivist stance, which builds theory from the subjective view of people and the interpretation of their meanings, was considered the most appropriate. The interpretivist aspect of inquiry results from an acceptance that deep meaning and understanding of an area of study can only be uncovered through researcher-subject interaction (Gergen, 1985). This approach poses considerable challenges to researchers if they are to convince their audience of the thoroughness and validity of the research process.

Specifically, in an entrepreneurial context, Leitch et al. (2010, p. 73) remind interpretivist researchers that it is “...their responsibility to provide the reader with sufficient information on the design and conduct of their research so that he or she may assess the integrity and rigour of the research process”. Therefore, comprehensive information was provided for this study, and the interpretivist paradigm is well suited to answer the research questions.

6.4 Philosophy of research

Curran and Blackburn (2001) argue that knowledge of philosophical issues is necessary for the accomplishment of successful entrepreneurship research. Failure to think about such issues may impact adversely on the quality of management research (Easterby-Smith et al., 2008). Therefore, before embarking on a research methodology, it is important to understand both the epistemology and ontology behind the research philosophy. Shane and Venkataraman (2000) argue that the ontological and epistemological assumptions of entrepreneurship research must be addressed in order to give legitimacy to the field. Similar to the research paradigms addressed earlier, the philosophies behind research have been represented in various forms by scholars (see Blumberg et al., 2011; Easterby-Smith et al., 2008; King and Horrocks, 2012; Saunders et al., 2012). However, the most popular philosophies are positivism, realism, and social constructionism. Positivism, as discussed earlier, is grounded in the natural sciences. The realists accept the existence of a reality that is independent of human beliefs and behaviour, but they also acknowledge that in order to understand peoples’ beliefs and behaviour, a subjective stance is required (Blumberg et al., 2011). By contrast, social constructionists argue that reality is shared dynamically and is individually constructed (Eriksson and Kovalainen, 2011).

In this study, the challenges that entrepreneurial leaders face, and the skills they require to overcome them were investigated. Constructionism is grounded in human experiences within their social-cultural milieu, thus enabling a full account to be taken of the context in which learning takes place (Guba and Lincoln, 1998). Thus, a social constructionist philosophy was applied in this research study, since it provides

a basis for understanding the lived experiences of entrepreneurial leaders. This philosophy enables the researcher to understand better how entrepreneurial leaders view their world. It allows the researcher to adjust to new issues as more ideas emerge, and thereby contribute to the development of theory in entrepreneurial leadership (Easterby-Smith et al., 2008). What people say when they talk about entrepreneurship may contradict with what they end up doing (Anderson and Starnawska, 2008). Hence the positivist philosophy, which views the world based on objective reality governed by natural laws, may not be suited for the study. Although positivist philosophy is predominant in entrepreneurship and leadership studies, many scholars have argued against such an approach. Anderson and Starnawska (2008, p. 13) argue that, "Positivism necessarily creates a one-dimensional view which is atomistic and consequently loses much of the richness and idiosyncrasy that characterises the more comprehensive picture of what we mean by entrepreneurship." It has been suggested that the positivist philosophy used by scholars has led to fragmentary research looking narrowly at aspects of entrepreneurship, when in fact the field itself is a rich and elusive concept (Anderson and Starnawska, 2008; Bygrave, 2007). Entrepreneurial leadership is even more elusive since it involves both leadership and entrepreneurship. Therefore, an approach which taps into and describes the meanings that underpin entrepreneurial leadership will be instrumental in understanding the concept. By utilising the social constructionist perspective, a researcher can consider the social and environmental context within which entrepreneurial activities are constructed (Anderson and Smith, 2007; Fletcher, 2006).

However, although social constructionism has been widely recognised to be an appropriate philosophy in understanding people, the credibility of findings using this approach remains a bone of contention (Easterby-Smith et al., 2008). This study recognises the limitations associated with the subjective opinions of the individuals; the results obtained from the study are not intended to provide an objective evidence of reality but, rather, provide a socially created picture of it (Hammersley, 2002). The research is concerned about how the entrepreneurial leaders construct their world, based on their social relationship with their employees. The social constructionist perspective allows for such multiple perspectives.

6.5 Research methodologies

A research methodology is the framework which a researcher uses for a study, and it usually involves the process of data collection, analysis, and interpretation (Creswell, 2009). There are two types of research methodologies based on the epistemological and ontological assumptions of the researcher: the qualitative method, and the quantitative method. The quantitative method is deductive and tends to examine relationships between variables using statistical techniques; while the qualitative approach is usually inductive, and is helpful in understanding the meaning of the world from the lens of the participants (Saunders et al., 2012). The research methodology used by a researcher to investigate a phenomenon is usually driven by the individual's philosophy. The previous section highlighted the philosophy adopted for this study, which is the interpretivist-constructionist perspective. This perspective is usually supportive of the qualitative approach, whereas positivist philosophy is more aligned with the quantitative method since the latter is more focused on testing theory rather than developing it (Creswell, 2009; Easterby-Smith et al., 2008; Saunders et al., 2012).

Since this study is exploratory, and the aim is to understand how entrepreneurial leaders display their leadership skills in a challenging and dynamic environment, a qualitative method (which encourages participation and allows for an in-depth understanding of the meanings these individuals make of their world) was judged to be more suitable for this study. In the next section, the reasons behind the choice of the qualitative strategy are discussed briefly, and the studies that have adopted such a methodology are highlighted.

6.5.1 Qualitative research methodology: a justification

A study can employ either a quantitative, or a qualitative method, or sometimes a combination of both. However, to justify the adoption of a qualitative approach, the types of methodology and their differences need to be considered. The difference

between the quantitative and the qualitative method, based on their ontological, epistemological and axiological assumptions, are presented in Table 14:

Table 14 Fundamental differences between quantitative and qualitative research methodologies

	<i>Quantitative</i>	<i>Qualitative</i>
<i>Principal orientation to the role of theory in relation to research</i>	Deductive; testing of theory	Inductive; generation of theory
<i>Epistemological orientation</i>	Natural science model, namely positivism	Interpretivism
<i>Ontological orientation</i>	Objectivism	Constructionism

Source: Bryman and Bell (2011, p. 27).

Entrepreneurial leadership as a phenomenon cannot be explained in isolation. It is complex in nature, and the use of quantitative designs, which are based on cause-effect relationships, are too simple and cannot be used to properly investigate the complexity of entrepreneurial leadership. As argued by Pittaway (2005, p. 216) on the subject of entrepreneurship, “Mechanistic assumptions sit uncomfortably with the subject because they tend to rule out behavioural complexity and ascribe law like qualities to social interactions.”

6.5.2 Similar studies using qualitative methods

A number of previous studies on entrepreneurial leadership have adopted qualitative techniques (e.g. Bagheri and Pihie, 2011; Currie et al., 2008; D'Intino et al., 2008; Hansson and Mønsted, 2008; Kansikas et al., 2012; Kempster and Cope, 2010; Leitch et al., 2009; Surie and Ashley, 2008; Swiercz and Lydon, 2002). The qualitative approaches adopted by these researchers are set out in Table 15:

Table 15 Methodologies employed in entrepreneurial leadership studies

Authors	Year	Topic	Method
Bagheri and Pihie	2011	Student Entrepreneurial Leaders: Challenges and Competencies of Leading University Entrepreneurship Programs.	Semi-structured interviews
Currie et al.	2008	Entrepreneurial Leadership in the English Public Sector: Paradox or Possibility?	Semi-structured interviews
D'Intino et al.	2008	Visionary entrepreneurial leadership in the aircraft industry: The Boeing Company legacy.	Case Study
Hansson and Mønsted	2008	Research leadership as entrepreneurial organizing for research.	Case Study
Kansikas et al.	2012	Entrepreneurial leadership and familiness as resources for strategic entrepreneurship.	Case Study
Kempster and Cope	2010	Learning to lead in the entrepreneurial context.	Qualitative phenomenological interviews with entrepreneurs
Leitch, McMullan and Harrison	2009	Leadership development in SMEs: an action learning approach.	Semi-structured interviews
Surie and Ashley	2008	Integrating Pragmatism and Ethics in Entrepreneurial Leadership for Sustainable Value Creation.	Case Study
Swiercz and Lydon	2002	Entrepreneurial leadership in high-tech firms: a field study.	Semi-structured interviews

6.6 Research design

6.6.1 Definition

According to Saunders et al. (2012, p. 152), a research design refers to “...the general plan of how you will go about answering your research question(s)...It will contain clear objectives derived from your research question(s), specify the sources from which you intend to collect data, how you propose to collect and analyse these, discuss ethical issues and the constraints you will inevitably encounter.” A research design framework should guide the selection of sources to be used, as well as provide a definite outline of the procedures involved in research activity (Blumberg

et al., 2011). Based on this, a detailed description of the qualitative research design adopted is provided below.

6.6.2 The research design adopted for the study

The research design consisted of four phases:

Figure 12 The research design for the study

6.6.2.1 Phase 1: scoping study

To achieve the aims of the study, a scoping study was conducted. This was undertaken to map out and understand the literature on entrepreneurial leadership. Two main questions were addressed in the scoping study:

- What is entrepreneurial leadership?
- Is this new paradigm “entrepreneurial leadership” a valid concept, especially in dynamic settings?

Following the scoping study, definition of entrepreneurial leadership in line with that of Gupta et al. (2004) was adopted. This views entrepreneurial leadership as a type

of leadership that “...creates visionary scenarios that are used to assemble and mobilize a supporting cast of participants who become committed by the vision to the discovery and exploitation of strategic value creation” (Gupta et al. 2004, p. 242).

6.6.2.2 Phase 2: literature review

The second phase of the research design was the literature review, in which both a narrative and systematic approach were applied.

Narrative literature review

A narrative literature review has been described as the examination of literature on a particular subject to enrich human discourse by “...generating understanding rather than by accumulating knowledge” (Bryman and Bell, 2011, p. 101). This type of review offers a wide scope.

The approach taken in this study was abductive; hence, it was important that an initial impression of the topic area was gained. The research involves two fields: entrepreneurship, and leadership. Therefore, a narrative literature review was undertaken to gain a deeper understanding of entrepreneurship and leadership, and the context where the study was to be carried out, namely, a developing economy, Nigeria. A list of keywords and databases used for the narrative literature review is provided in Table 16:

Table 16 List of keywords and databases

Keywords	Databases
Entrep*	Google Scholar
Entrepreneur*	Taylor and Francis
Entrepreneurship	Emerald
Lead*	Ingentaconnect
Leader*	Springerlink
Leadership	Web of knowledge
Retail pharmacy	Science Direct
Pharmacy in Nigeria	Sage
	Wiley Online

Systematic literature review

The narrative literature review approach has been criticised for lacking criticality (Tranfield et al., 2003), and a systematic approach to reviewing literature has been proposed (Denyer and Tranfield, 2009). A systematic literature review (SLR) has been defined as “...a replicable, scientific and transparent process; in other words, a detailed technology that aims to minimise bias through exhaustive literature searches of published and unpublished studies, and by providing an audit trail of the reviewer’s decisions, procedures, and conclusions” (Tranfield et al., 2003, p. 209).

An SLR adopts a replicable, transparent, and scientific process (Tranfield et al., 2003) and in this way differs from a traditional narrative review. According to Denyer and Tranfield (2009), systematic reviews in management studies are expected to be transparent, inclusive, explanatory, and heuristic in nature. In this study, the SLR methodology developed by Tranfield et al. (2003), which is a three stage process, was adopted:

- Stage 1: Planning the review
- Stage 2: Conducting the review
- Stage 3: Reporting and dissemination (refer back to section 5.2)

The purpose of the SLR is to identify and appraise all scholarly works on entrepreneurial leadership that have been published in academic journals or conference proceedings that are important to the study.

Stage 1: Planning the review

Prior to undertaking the literature review process, a panel of experts in the field of entrepreneurship and leadership were consulted. The panel assisted in the process, especially since entrepreneurial leadership is cross-disciplinary and many perspectives about this phenomenon exist. A scoping study was also conducted to map out and understand the literature on entrepreneurial leadership. This was instrumental to developing a review protocol, which consisted of the review questions needing to be addressed, the population focus of the study, and the inclusion and exclusion criteria for literature to be examined.

The following questions guided the review:

- What is the impact of entrepreneurial leadership in a developing economy?
- What are the characteristics of an entrepreneurial leader?
- How do these leaders develop these characteristics?

Finally, evaluation criteria were developed to eliminate low quality papers and ensure that only high quality sources would be selected for the review. The exclusion and inclusion criteria for the papers to be reviewed are stated below:

Inclusion Criteria

- Papers should be in English
- The focus of the paper must be on entrepreneurial leadership as a type of leadership
- The paper directly addresses one or more of the review questions
- Papers must have been published between 1970 and 2013

Exclusion Criteria

- Papers not in peer reviewed publications (i.e. conference or journals)
- Papers focused on other styles of leadership

Stage 2: Conducting the review

In this study, the review methodology began with the identification of keywords obtained from the review panel and the scoping study. The keywords and search strings are outlined in Table 17:

Table 17 Systematic literature review - search strings and keywords

SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW SEARCH STRINGS AND KEYWORDS	
Search String Number	Keywords
Search string 01	Entrep*
Search string 1a	Lead*
Search string 1b	Developing
Search string 1c	Entrepreneurial leadership
Search string 02	Lead*
Search string 2a	Entrep*
Search string 2b	Developing
Search string 2c	Entrepreneurial leadership
Search string 03	Entrepreneurial leadership
Search string 3a	Pharm*
Search string 04	Entrepreneurial leadership
Search string 4a	Developing
Search string 4b	Challenges OR Abilities OR Capabilities OR Skills OR Attributes OR Competencies
Search string 05	Entrepreneurial leadership (for Google scholar)
Lead* means leader, leadership etc. Entrep* means entrepreneur, entrepreneurial, entrepreneurship etc. Pharm* means Pharmaceutical, Pharmacy etc	

The search strings were used within eight databases, which were identified as the most suitable for management research (see Table 18):

Table 18 Databases used in the systematic literature review

DATA BASES SEARCHED FOR THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW		
Emerald	Wiley Online	Sage Journals
Science Direct	Taylor & Francis	Web of Knowledge
Springerlink	Ingentaconnect	

The literature was selected on the basis of the search strings. The title and abstract screening were based on the inclusion and exclusion criteria. Citations and references of articles were examined to determine whether they were to be included or excluded.

After the initial search through the databases, Google Scholar was then used to obtain literature not available on the databases. Duplicate articles obtained from the databases were filtered, and a total of 72 articles were selected from the process. Citations and references of these articles were examined according to the inclusion and exclusion criteria, and 7 articles were chosen (see appendices 4 and 5). Finally, 79 articles were selected for the review, and the search process was concluded on 12th November 2013.

Study quality assessment

Each article accepted from the SLR process was assessed for its quality, based on the following questions:

- Does the study report unambiguous findings based on evidence and argument?
- Is the paper appropriately referenced?

All the papers included in the review passed the above quality assessment criteria.

Data extraction, synthesis and validation

The EndnoteTM software package was used to generate reference details of each article. Data was synthesised to identify themes that emanated from the findings in each accepted paper. A final validation exercise was carried out on the 79 accepted papers. When the 79 papers were read again, 2 were disallowed on the basis that those papers could not effectively answer any of the review questions. The final tally was 77 papers.

Sample for study

When choosing research participants, it is necessary that an appropriate sampling technique that effectively answers the research questions is adopted (Saunders et al., 2012). For this study, a purposive sampling strategy was considered the most appropriate one. According to Shaw (1999, p. 63), the power of purposive sampling “...lies in the selection of cases rich in information about the substantive research problem”. The researcher selects the most productive sample to fulfil the objectives of the study and to answer the research questions (Marshall, 1996). As such, purposive sampling was adopted to select retail pharmacy entrepreneurs and their employees who could contribute to the study, as well as to obtain an insight on entrepreneurial leadership based on their experiences.

As stated earlier, the retail pharmacy sector was chosen as a proxy for this study since the challenges faced by retail pharmacy entrepreneurs resonate with entrepreneurs generally. The sample in this study consisted of 17 retail pharmacy entrepreneurs, with 2 employees from each pharmacy. However, the number in the sample was not predetermined in advance. As Shaw (1999, p. 63) advised, “As the research progresses and inductive analysis of data identifies common themes and patterns with the potential for understanding the research problem, the number of participating cases is determined by the extent to which the collection of data from an additional case will contribute to that understanding.” Thematic analysis was used for analysing data, and the interviews ceased when the collected data was considered

saturated (i.e. no new information about entrepreneurial leadership could be obtained). As Baker and Edwards (2012) remind researchers, the answer to the question of how many qualitative interviews are required is this - *it depends*. The focus of this study was not to generate a large corpus of data for generalisation, but to obtain a rich description of entrepreneurial leadership; this can only be achieved from a productive and controlled sample size.

Since a purposive sample was to be utilised, it was necessary to determine criteria for inclusion in the sample. In establishing the criteria for sampling, it is important that an appropriate definition of an entrepreneur is reached. In this study, a retail pharmacy entrepreneur is defined as the owner of the business, a definition that is in line with past research studies in entrepreneurship (e.g. Dollinger, 1999; Gartner, 1988; Low and Macmillan, 1988; Rumelt, 1987). Therefore, the criteria for selection were as follows:

- The entrepreneur should own her/his retail pharmacy, which must have been operating as a business for at least five years. Longevity of the business indicates that the owner has been successful through the conception, start-up, and management phases.
- The business has to have achieved significant growth in terms of retail expansion, namely having, at the time of the research, more than one outlet. As a result, life-style businesses (which are essentially a hobby of the owner) were excluded.
- The business must have at least five employees, of whom two would be willing to be interviewed as part of the research process.

In order to identify participants who met the above criteria, a directory was obtained from the Pharmacists Council of Nigeria (PCN), which is the regulatory body of pharmacists in the country. The directory listed 500 registered retail pharmacy outlets in Lagos, Nigeria, including their owners, addresses, contact telephone numbers, and year of establishment. 44 pharmacists met the criteria set out above. When a retail pharmacy entrepreneur who met such criteria was identified from the directory, the respondent was asked to participate in the study, and was followed up with e-mail messages and phone calls. However, despite these efforts, only a few

recipients were willing to participate in the study. As a result, a snowball sampling strategy was used in conjunction with the sampling frame from PCN. Snowball sampling is effective in identifying further members of a population via the initial participants involved in the research study (Saunders et al., 2012). In this research study, snowball sampling was utilised to obtain more retail pharmacy entrepreneurs who fitted the profile. The retail pharmacy entrepreneurs who had initially responded and were willing to participate in the study referred other individuals whom they knew would be interested and fitted the desired profile. Consequently, the final sample for the study was generated.

6.7 Data collection process

In this section, the method of data collection utilised in the study is discussed. There are a number of different methods of data collection in qualitative research such as observation (direct or participant), interviews, and focus groups. In-depth interviewing was employed in this study as the primary means of obtaining data. As elaborated in the section below, the use of interviews was chosen over other methods as the appropriate means of collecting data for this study.

6.7.1 In-depth interviews

Qualitative interviewing was employed as the primary means of collecting data. It is the most widely used method in qualitative research (Blumberg et al., 2011; Bryman and Bell, 2011), especially in form of one-to-one interviews (Barbour, 2008). According to Saunders et al. (2012, p. 372), a research interview "...is a purposeful conversation between two or more people, requiring the interviewer to establish rapport, to ask concise and unambiguous questions, to which the interviewee is willing to respond and to listen attentively".

According to Eriksson and Kovalainen (2011, p. 81), in-depth interviews are suited to business research when "...the aim is to study people's experience as seen from

their points of view or the social construction of knowledge concerning the chosen topic”. This method is the most conducive in understanding “...uncountable, process data peculiar to individuals” (Galloway and Kelly, 2009, p. 8). When complex issues are to be covered, an interview is the best or only means of collecting data (Saunders et al., 2012). Since entrepreneurial leadership is a complex phenomenon, interviews were chosen to provide detailed insights of the impact of this phenomenon in business.

Entrepreneurs are often keen to share their experiences and enjoy telling their stories (Gray, 2009; McKenzie, 2007; Smith and Anderson, 2004; Smith, 2006); hence, the use of interviews, which provides this opportunity, can be an effective approach to capture rich data. By telling their stories, interviewees provide rich data which reveal their visions and actions, as well as the context and structure of their lives (Charmaz, 2005). Using qualitative interviews helps the researcher to see the world as the entrepreneur does, thus providing an insight into the world of the entrepreneurial leader.

Within the one-to-one interview approach there is a continuum of interviews formats, from the structured to the semi-structured to the unstructured. The structured interview favours the positivist philosophy and a quantitative methodology, whereby data is collected systematically and put into numerical form (Johnstone, 2007). However, given that the focus of this study was to obtain rich descriptions and meaning rather than numerical data, a semi-structured or unstructured interview was judged to be more suitable.

At the opposite end of the continuum is the unstructured interview, which is non-standardised and informal. In this form of interview, there is no predetermined list of questions, and the interviewee is allowed to talk freely about events and behaviour in the topic area (Saunders et al., 2012). The open-ended or unstructured interview, although flexible and of great importance in exploratory studies, does not provide a concise view of the topic area. According to Easterby-Smith et al. (2008, p. 143-144), an unstructured approach is more likely “...to produce no clear picture in the mind of the interviewee of what questions or issues the interviewer is interested in, and in the mind of the interviewer of what question the interviewee is answering”. This also exacerbates the danger of the “interviewer effect” (Gray, 2009, p. 217),

where the interviewer may influence the course of the interview. Such interviews are also difficult to analyse since different questions may be asked of different interviewees, with the result that there is no emergent pattern (Gray, 2009).

An appropriate approach when conducting in-depth interviews is to develop a structure with which to plot out themes that emerge during the study (Easterby-Smith et al., 2008). As a result, most qualitative researchers favour the use of semi-structured interviews, which allows for the ordering of questions to be employed flexibly to take account of the topics that interest the interviewee (Barbour, 2008). The use of semi-structured interviews often leads to discussion in areas that had not been previously considered, but which may be of significance to the understanding of the subject area, and also valuable in addressing the research questions and objectives (Saunders et al., 2012). This is achieved by the researcher probing for more detailed responses by asking the respondent to provide clearer answers to the issues discussed (Gray, 2009). As stated by Blumberg et al. (2011, p. 258), semi-structured interviews have two main objectives: “On one hand, the researcher wants to know the informant’s perspective on the issue; on the other, they also want to know whether the informant can confirm insights and information the researcher already holds.” As a result, a semi-structured interviewing format was chosen for this study as it better enabled the capturing of the perspectives of entrepreneurs and their employees on the issue of entrepreneurial leadership.

The choice of semi-structured interviews was also influenced by the number of studies on entrepreneurial leadership that also used this approach. It should be noted that a number of researchers have utilised semi-structured interviews in their investigation of entrepreneurial leadership (including Bagheri and Pihie, 2011; Carpenter, 2012; Currie et al., 2008; Jones and Crompton, 2009; Kempster and Cope, 2010; Leitch et al., 2009; and, Swiercz and Lydon, 2002). However, such studies have focused only on the entrepreneurs, and these scholars did not interview followers. This is a methodological weakness, as other research has shown that entrepreneurs tend to have an over-exaggerated conception of their abilities (Busenitz and Barney, 1997; Cooper et al., 1988). In order to address this limitation, the research in this thesis also included interviews with employees within each pharmacy. This leader/follower approach is well established in the leadership domain (e.g. Groves, 2005; Meindl, 1995), but this is missing in the field of

entrepreneurial leadership. A major advantage of adopting a leader/follower approach is that it facilitates data triangulation⁴. Using more than one data source (i.e. the leader, follower, and existing research) within a single study to examine a particular phenomenon enhances the validity of the findings. By adopting such an approach to research entrepreneurial leadership, this study provides a distinctive perspective.

It should be noted, however, that semi-structured interviews are not without their limitations. One major limitation to their use is the issue of reliability as similar information is expected to be revealed by alternative researchers (Saunders et al., 2012). Another limitation is the issue of bias of the interviewee or interviewer. The interviewer can demonstrate bias in the way he or she interprets responses, and the interviewee may also introduce bias by withholding relevant information on the topic of interest (Saunders et al., 2012). However, many researchers have argued that findings derived from semi-structured interviews are not meant to be repeatable, since they reflect the reality at that point in time they were collected; hence, the situation could be subject to change (Bryman and Bell, 2011). Entrepreneurial leadership is complex and dynamic; hence, the value of using semi-structured interviews as a primary means of data collection is derived from its flexibility, and not its repeatability. As Saunders et al. (2012, p. 382) states: “Replicability will only undermine the strength of the research.” Although interviewer and interviewee bias is a recognised limitation, it can be mitigated by an interviewer’s situational competence (Flick, 2011). This was addressed by developing appropriate interview themes and an interview guide.

6.7.1.1 Interview guide

An interview protocol setting out the main themes and questions to be covered during the interview was developed. As stated by Blumberg et al. (2011, p. 266), an

⁴ Triangulation involves the use of multiple investigators, multiple data sources, or methods to confirm emerging findings (Merriam, 1995).

interview guide should serve as a "...memory list to the interviewer to ensure that the same issues are addressed in every interview".

The dependability and credibility of the study was strengthened by the use of an interview guide (Bryman and Bell, 2011; Saunders et al., 2012). The interview guide was based on the comprehensive literature review on entrepreneurial leadership, and on the research objectives of this study. Flexibility was paramount, hence why the interview guide was not so restrictive as to miss capturing perspectives that may be unanticipated but which could be valuable to the study (King and Horrocks, 2012). Care was taken to ensure that the order of the questions during the interview was logical, and that the language used was unambiguous and understandable. As the interviews progressed, the guide was amended in order to introduce insights obtained during the initial interviews, thereby helping to improve subsequent ones. In order to ensure that bias was not introduced during the interviews, no leading questions were asked. However, since the nature of the topic (especially on the part of the employees) was sensitive, the respondents were assured of their confidentiality, and also reminded that they were not obliged to answer all questions.

The interviews with the entrepreneurs were conducted on their business premises, but those with their employees were held away from the site to ensure confidentiality. The settings were quiet and private so that the respondents did not feel concerned about being overhead (Bryman and Bell, 2011). The interviews were recorded, and the transcripts were given back to each entrepreneur and employee 48 hours after each interview so as to confirm the accuracy of its content. The full interview guide which was developed is attached in appendix 1.

6.7.2 The pilot study

Saunders et al. (2012) assert that pilot testing and pre-testing interview questions should be conducted prior to the main study in order to minimise the likelihood of respondents encountering problems, and to ensure the validity and reliability of data. Bryman and Bell (2011) argue that a pilot study should be carried out on individuals who are not members of the sample, but who would be eligible in the study. As such,

four pilot interviews were carried out with two retail pharmacy entrepreneurs and one employee from each pharmacy in Nigeria. In line with the advice of Bryman and Bell (2011), the respondents approached for the pilot study were not approached for the main study.

Prior to conducting the pilot interviews, as per the suggestion of Blumberg et al. (2011), research colleagues were brought into the process to informally test the interview questions so as to refine the instrument. Feedback obtained from the director of studies and from other colleagues was used in refining the questions and finalising a draft interview guide.

Entrepreneurs for the pilot interviews were formally invited by letter, in which the purpose of the research was clarified. The letter stated clearly that the interviews were to last approximately 45 minutes, and that respondents had the right to withdraw from the pilot study if they so desired. The pilot interviews were carried out in their business premises and, in line with ethical guidelines, the participants were assured of their confidentiality and anonymity. The interviews were recorded and transcribed verbatim within 48 hours. The transcripts were given to the respondents to determine the accuracy of the data as well as the interpretation of its meaning by the researcher. At the end of the interview, the respondents were asked to give feedback on how the interview was conducted, and to suggest ways that the process could be improved.

During the pilot study, it was observed that the entrepreneurs and their employees were willing to talk about their experiences, and the flexibility of the semi-structured interview approach provided individuals with the freedom to express themselves. This would not have been possible with a more structured approach, which therefore justifies the choice of the semi-structured interview approach as the means of data collection in this study. Overall, the pilot study provided an opportunity to refine interviewing skills and ensure credibility in the main study.

6.7.3 Main study

6.7.3.1 Profiles of the respondents

The respondents for this study included 17 entrepreneurs and 34 employees (i.e. 2 employees per entrepreneur) across 17 enterprises. The demographic details of the respondents are set out in tables 19 and 20. Face-to-face interviews were conducted with the respondents, which lasted between 45 and 120 minutes.

For the 17 entrepreneurs interviewed, 9 were male and 8 were female, with the youngest aged 37, and the oldest aged 61. All the entrepreneurs were pharmacists and possessed at least a Bachelor degree in pharmacy. In addition, 6 had masters' degrees. Most of the entrepreneurs had a diverse range of work experience prior to establishing their pharmaceutical businesses. In one instance, a respondent gained 19 years of experience within a prior venture before entering the pharmaceutical industry. However, 4 entrepreneurs had had no prior experience in any sector before establishing their company.

For this study, company success was judged based on the number of branches, age of the company, and the number of employees. These criteria are consistent with previous works in broad stream entrepreneurship literature (e.g. Cooper, 1982; Cressy, 2006; Schutjens and Wever, 2000). 6 of the entrepreneurs had 2 branches; another 6 entrepreneurs had 3 branches; 3 of them had 4 branches; while 1 entrepreneur had 16; and another owned 22 branches. The companies established by the entrepreneurs had been in existence for between 5 and 29 years. All the entrepreneurs were in charge of at least 5 employees, with some having over 100 employees. Table 19 provides details of the entrepreneurs involved in the study. This is arranged based on the order in which the interviews were conducted, with entrepreneur A being the first interviewee, and entrepreneur Q the last.

Table 19 Demographic profile of the entrepreneurs

Entrepreneurs	Gender	Maximum Qualification	Prior experience in the retail pharmacy sector	Number of branches	Age	Company's duration of existence (Years)
A	Male	MBA	5 years	4	61	29
B	Male	MBA	10 years	2	53	24
C	Female	B. Pharm	No prior experience	4	50	20
D	Male	B. Pharm	8 years	2	40	5
E	Female	B. Pharm	6 years	3	42	10
F	Male	B. Pharm	4 years	4	43	14
G	Female	MBA	No prior experience	2	37	8
H	Female	MBA	2 years	22	44	13
I	Female	B. Pharm	3 years	2	43	12
J	Female	B. Pharm	2 years	16	45	12
K	Female	B. Pharm	2 years	3	42	10
L	Male	M. Pharm	7 years	3	45	7
M	Female	B. Pharm	19 years	2	49	5
N	Male	B. Pharm	No prior experience	2	46	13
O	Male	MBA	No prior experience	3	41	6
P	Male	B. Pharm	2 years	3	52	18
Q	Male	B. Pharm	4 years	3	44	8

Of the 34 employees interviewed, 12 were male and 22 were female. The length of service ranged from 18 years to less than a year. The researcher was allowed to choose any 2 employees from the list of employees provided by the employer, and so random sampling was adopted. Table 20 provides the details of the employees involved in the study. The pseudonyms used were similar to the entrepreneurs, with respondents A1 and A2 as employees of entrepreneur A.

Table 20 Profile of the employees

Employees	Gender	Length of Service
A1	Male	18 years
A2	Male	3 years
B1	Female	1 year
B2	Male	2 years
C1	Female	1 year
C2	Male	7 months
D1	Female	8 months
D2	Female	4 months
E1	Female	7 months
E2	Female	1 year
F1	Female	7 years
F2	Male	7 years
G1	Female	4 years
G2	Male	8 years
H1	Female	2 years
H2	Female	8 years
I1	Male	2 years
I2	Female	4 years
J1	Male	4 months
J2	Female	11 years
K1	Female	4.5 years
K2	Female	4 years
L1	Female	3 years
L2	Male	4.5 years
M1	Female	1 year
M2	Female	4.5 years
N1	Male	4 years
N2	Female	1 year
O1	Female	1 year
O2	Male	5 years
P1	Female	3 years
P2	Female	3 years
Q1	Female	1 year
Q2	Male	1.5 years

6.7.3.2 The interview process

The main study focused on a sample comprising 17 retail pharmacy entrepreneurs and 34 employees (i.e. 2 from each pharmacy). These respondents were invited to participate by receiving a letter that clarified the purpose of the study (see Appendix 2). In the letter, it was explained that the interviews were to last for an hour and 30 minutes, and that the respondents had the right to withdraw from the study if they so desired. This amendment was made following the pilot interviews, when it was recognised that 45 minutes was insufficient.

The final sample size was chosen on the basis of theoretical saturation (refer back to sub-section 6.6.2). By the time the twelfth entrepreneur and their employees had been interviewed, it was judged that theoretical saturation had been reached. However, since most of the interviews had already been scheduled, the researcher conducted 15 more interviews (i.e. 5 entrepreneurs and 10 employees).

It was anticipated that during the course of the interviews, respondents would have difficulty distinguishing between skills and other more personal attributes. This indeed proved to be the case, with many respondents moving between skills and other areas at frequent intervals. In order to address this key problem, considerable thought was given as to how in the analysis of the interview data, skills could be distinguished from other personal attributes and characteristics. This was achieved by the application of rigorous definitions of both skills and attributes drawn from the wider literature. Skills were defined as being expertise, competencies, and practised abilities that can be learned or developed by the leaders (Northouse, 2010; Schedlitzki and Edwards, 2014). Attributes were defined as characteristics and distinctive features belonging to the leaders, which are observed through their behaviour in the workplace (Russell and Stone, 2002).

To encourage them to speak openly, the interviewees were assured that, in any publication of research outcomes, their identities would neither be revealed nor be capable of being deduced. With the permission of each respondent, interviews were recorded, and these lasted from 45 minutes to 2 hours, and were conducted at a place of the interviewee's choosing (often an office on the premises). Specifically, the employees in the study were interviewed in private locations away from the site to

ensure confidentiality. The research was conducted over a six month period in 2014, during which time there was little change to the industry context, a point confirmed by interviewees.

6.8 Data interpretation and analysis

The interpretation of data is the core of empirical procedure in qualitative research (Flick, 2011). As stated by Creswell (2009, p. 184), "...data analysis involves collecting open-ended data, based on asking general questions and developing an analysis from the information supplied by participants".

There are many different methods used by qualitative researchers in analysing data (see Bryman and Bell, 2011; Gray, 2009; Saunders et al., 2012). However, since this study is exploratory and its focus is to generate a rich and detailed account of the emerging paradigm entrepreneurial leadership, a method of analysis that helps develop themes from a set of data was required. Based on these pre-suppositions and the use of qualitative interviews as the means of data collection, thematic analysis was therefore chosen.

Thematic analysis as the method of choice is described in the next sub-section. This step-by-step process was adopted for analysing data obtained from the participants.

6.8.1 Thematic analysis

Thematic analysis is a widely used qualitative analytical method (Braun and Clark, 2006; King and Horrocks, 2012; Welch and Piekkari, 2006). As the name implies, thematic analysis refers to the analysis of data through emerging themes. Braun and Clark (2006, p. 79) define it as a method "...for identifying, analysing and reporting patterns (themes) within data". This method of analysis is not new to business and management research; however, it is not utilised as often as other methods (e.g. discourse analysis, grounded theory). As Braun and Clarke (2006, p. 80) state, "It

[thematic analysis] is often not explicitly claimed as the method of analysis, when, in actuality, we argue that a lot of analysis is essentially thematic.” It is not uncommon for researchers to state that themes emerge from collected data during their analyses. However, if there exists insufficient information on how researchers go about analysing their data and on the assumptions they make in their studies, this may impede future research (Attride-Stirling, 2001). As a result, clarity in the use of thematic analysis is vital.

King and Horrocks (2012) provide a three-stage process for analysing data using thematic analysis. The three stages are descriptive coding, interpretative coding, and defining overarching themes. In this sub-section, details on how this framework was utilised in analysing and interpreting data obtained from the respondents is provided.

6.8.1.1 Descriptive coding

The first step in King’s and Horrocks’ (2012) framework is descriptive coding. Descriptive coding as defined by Braun and Clarke (2006, p. 88) is the “...production of initial codes from the data”. Essentially, it involves organising data into meaningful groups (Tuckett, 2005).

All the interviews were recorded using an audio recorder. These were then transcribed verbatim by the researcher for data analysis. Before analysis, the transcripts were given to the respondents for them to proofread in order to ensure accuracy of the data. The QSR-NVivoTM (version 10) software package was used as the tool for coding data. Prior to the study, the researcher attended training workshops on the use of this software package in order to increase personal proficiency. The NVivo 10 software was not only useful in facilitating the coding process, but was also instrumental in data management and in the final writing up of this thesis.

The researcher familiarised himself with each transcript by re-reading it without making any attempt to code it. This was important in order to develop a thorough understanding of what each participant said about entrepreneurial leadership as a whole. After reading through a transcript, brief and important comments were

highlighted using NVivo. Based on these comments, descriptive codes were generated. This was done for successive transcripts from the interviews. Descriptive codes were re-examined, and the overlapping codes were merged or redefined. This process took several days, and when no more changes could be made to the codes (or, as stated by King and Horrocks (2012, p. 154), "...the descriptive codes are good enough"), the next stage of analysis commenced.

An example of a section of the highlighted interview transcript from Respondent A and the descriptive codes attached are provided in the Table 21 below:

Table 21 Example of the descriptive coding stage

<i>Interview extract from Respondent A (highlighted)</i>	<i>Descriptive codes</i>
1 We are on the move. We are growing much more and have a blue print...	Positive mind-set, plan for the business
2 We are 100 now; we should be 500 in 5 years' time.	Foresight
3 I want to have made up to a thousand mark...	Vision for the business
4 I want to employ up to 1000 people in 10 years.	Vision for the business, plan for the business

6.8.1.2 Interpretative coding

The second step in the analysis is interpretative coding. Interpretative coding refers to the process of defining "...codes that go beyond describing relevant features of participants' accounts and focus more on your interpretation of their meaning" (King and Horrocks, 2012, p. 154). It involves generating codes based on the interpretation of the account by the researcher. In this phase of the study, interpretative codes for the accounts on the transcripts were generated. As with the descriptive coding stage, the interpretative codes were redefined in order to capture the meanings offered by the text.

This is exemplified in the Table 22, which shows how the interpretative codes were assigned from the section of Respondent A’s interview transcript:

Table 22 Example of the interpretative coding stage

<i>Interview extract from Respondent A (highlighted)</i>	<i>Descriptive codes</i>	<i>Interpretative codes</i>
1 We are on the move. We are growing much more and have a blue print.	Positive mind-set, plan for the business	STRATEGIC PLANNING
2 we are 100 now; we should be 500 in 5 years’ time.	Foresight	ENVISIONING
3 I want to have made up to a thousand mark...	Vision for the business	ENVISIONING
4 I want to employ up to 1000 people in 10 years.	Vision for the business, plan for the business	ENVISIONING STRATEGIC PLANNING

6.8.1.3 Defining overarching themes

This is the final step of the analysis, in which the descriptive and interpretative codes are analysed and combined to form an overarching theme. It involves identifying a “...number of overarching themes that characterise key concepts in your analysis” (King and Horrocks, 2012, p. 156). This is the stage during which theoretical ideas concerning the study may be drawn. Several overarching themes were developed, but on closer examination some were discarded. For example, themes such as “issues” were discarded for “challenges” because most of the respondents in the study attributed the same meaning to both themes. Some of the themes were similar and hence were merged, while others were broken down into separate themes.

It was ensured that the themes obtained from the respondents fitted together and represented the key issues about entrepreneurial leadership emanating from the data. Each theme had sub-themes which were based on the descriptive and interpretative codes. These were then used to establish a thematic framework of entrepreneurial leadership.

The emergence of the overlapping theme from the highlighted section of Respondent A's interview transcript is exemplified in Figure 13, in which all the three coding levels are shown:

Figure 13 Diagram showing the coding levels for the highlighted section of the interview transcript of Respondent A

As shown above, the overarching theme is conceptual skills. There are other interpretative codes assigned in the study but which are not identified in this example. (Please refer to Appendix 8 for the full list of identified codes used in the study.)

6.9 Evaluation of the research

Research methods should not only be viewed in terms of the aims and contexts of the research; priority should also be given to the quality of the study (Bush, 2002). Research, whether qualitative or quantitative, requires rigour to ensure that findings are trusted and believed (Merriam, 1995). By so doing, the confidence of the academic community can be satisfied regarding the credibility of the findings.

Lincoln and Guba (1985) proposed criteria for evaluating qualitative research. These include credibility, dependability, confirmability, and transferability. This framework was adopted to assist in ensuring methodological rigour. In the subsection below, the manner in which the concepts of credibility, dependability, confirmability, and transferability were established in the study are described.

6.9.1 Credibility

Credibility involves demonstrating that a true picture of the phenomenon under investigation is represented (Shenton, 2004). According to Krefting (1991, p. 215), "...it asks whether the researcher has established confidence in the truth of the findings for the subjects or informants and the contexts in which the study was undertaken". Lincoln and Guba (1985) refer to it as the "truth value", and it is perhaps the most important criterion for assessing a qualitative study (Krefting, 1991).

Shenton (2004) proposes that the credibility of research is enhanced when well-established methods are adopted. In this study, a semi-structured interview approach was used as the method of data collection. The use of semi-structured interviews has previously been used by researchers in investigating entrepreneurial leadership (e.g. Bagheri and Pihie, 2011; Currie et al., 2008; Leitch et al., 2009); hence, the research method and analysis has been used in previous research, thereby strengthening the credibility of research findings.

A key strategy of gaining credibility in research is via triangulation (Creswell, 2009). Triangulation involves the use of multiple investigators, multiple data sources or multiple methods to confirm emerging findings (Merriam, 1995). As Shenton (2004, p. 66) states, in triangulation, "...individual viewpoints and experiences can be verified against others and ultimately a rich picture of the attitudes, needs or behaviour of those under scrutiny may be constructed based on the contribution of a range of people". Triangulation was therefore incorporated in the research design. Rather than gathering information only from entrepreneurs (as previous researchers have done), the perspective of their employees (concerning the entrepreneurial leadership skills of their employers) was also captured. By approaching this version of reality from different viewpoints (Eriksson and Kovalainen, 2011), a better understanding of entrepreneurial leadership was obtained.

Lincoln and Guba (1985) recognise member checking as an important provision in bolstering credibility. It involves continually testing the researcher's data, interpretations and conclusions with the participants (Krefting, 1991). Bryman and Bell (2011) refer to it as "respondent validation". The interviews were therefore audio-recorded and transcribed verbatim. The transcripts were given to the participants to ensure the accuracy of the data. It is important that the voice of the respondents is not lost when the purpose of the research is to see a phenomenon from the eyes of the participants (Bryman and Bell, 2011). As Sandelowski (cited in Krefting, 1991, p. 216) stated, "A qualitative study is credible when it presents such accurate descriptions or interpretations of human experience that people who also share that experience would immediately recognise the descriptions."

Participants in the study were not coerced to engage in the research. Only willing respondents were chosen to be involved in the study. This was necessary in order to engender openness on the part of the entrepreneurs and their employees, and to enhance the credibility of the information provided. The independent stance of the researcher was also emphasised during interviews (Shenton, 2004). This was important, particularly to employees who might have felt inhibited from speaking frankly about their employers. The participants were also informed that they could withdraw from the research if ever they felt uncomfortable, thereby satisfying the ethical guidelines of the study.

Peer debriefing is a recognised strategy of establishing credibility in qualitative research (Creswell, 2009; Lincoln and Guba, 1985; Merriam, 1995; Shenton, 2004). It involves obtaining an external perspective to enhance the accuracy of the account (Creswell, 2009). In this study, debriefing sessions were organised regularly with the director of studies. This was particularly valuable given the choice of a semi-structured interview approach as the sole means of data collection for this study. Conferences such as the British Academy of Management served as venues at which general feedback from senior researchers and colleagues during the course of the research was obtained. Fresh perspectives obtained from such individuals were valuable in shaping the research design and objectives.

A study's credibility may also be affected by bias from the respondents, especially when they elicit response that they think sound favourable to the researcher, or intentionally withhold sensitive information (Krefting, 1991). In this study, the issue of bias was addressed by the use of prolonged engagement with each interviewee (Flick, 2011). Probing methods and iterative questioning during the interview (Shenton, 2004) were used to elicit detailed data, and questions were re-phrased to elicit frank responses from participants. The researcher also briefly mentioned his previous experience in interviewing, and provided evidence of his pharmacy qualifications.

However, the fact that the researcher is a pharmacist could in itself have introduced bias which could affect the truth value in the research findings; hence, in order to minimise this, reflexivity was considered (Alvesson et al., 2008). Reflexivity refers to the assessment of the influence of the researcher's background, experience, perception, and intentions upon a study (Krefting, 1991). It refers to the acknowledgement by researchers that it is impossible for their actions not to affect the outcome of the research (Horsburgh, 2003). That means neutrality is impossible. In this study, the researcher recognised his role, not just an observer, but also as a participant, and hence it was imperative (for ensuring credibility in the research) for the researcher to consider how his previous background, especially as a pharmacist, would affect data collection and analysis. Lincoln and Guba (1985) suggest that a field journal be kept by a researcher during the course of a study, so he/she can interpret and describe their behaviour within the research context. For this study, the researcher kept such a journal, and recorded daily schedules and the rationale behind

the methods used. An extract from the field journal is provided in Appendix 10. Personal thoughts and ideas were also written in the journal, the purpose of which was to assist in detecting any bias that may have affected the data collection and analysis.

6.9.2 Dependability

Dependability refers to the assurance that the research process is logical, traceable, and documented (Wigren, 2007). Lincoln and Guba (1985) refer to it as an auditing approach in which the research process is detailed.

In this study, dependability was enhanced by producing a complete record of all phases of the research process. Raw data included the interview transcripts, field work notes, and the personal journal. Personal notes, as well as process notes concerning the methodological stance used in the research, were also kept (Flick, 2011).

A code/re-code method was carried out on data during the analytical phase of the study (Krefting, 1991). The coding and re-coding was carried out every two weeks during the descriptive coding phase to ensure that the results obtained were consistent. In this regard, member checking was valuable in bolstering dependability. The interview transcripts were given to the respondents to ensure that the recorded information was accurate.

Peers were used as auditors to ensure that all procedures stated for the research were followed. They checked and confirmed that the process had been logically followed. Despite the large volume of data, colleagues were patient in assessing the research procedure. The aim was not to ensure replicability (since variability is expected in qualitative research) (Krefting, 1991), but to provide a rich description of entrepreneurial leadership. The emphasis of this research was on the uniqueness of the human situation (Fossey et al., 2002), so variation in terms of respondents' experiences was expected.

6.9.3 Confirmability

According to Bryman and Bell (2011, p. 398), “Confirmability is concerned with ensuring that, while recognising that complete objectivity is impossible in business research, the researcher can be shown to have acted in good faith; in other words, it should be apparent that he or she has not overtly allowed personal values or theoretical inclinations manifestly to sway the conduct of the research and findings deriving from it.” Steps were therefore taken to ensure that the findings of the research were grounded in the experiences and ideas of the participants, rather than in those of the researcher (Shenton, 2004).

The use of an audit trail has been proposed by researchers as a key strategy in ensuring confirmability (Lincoln and Guba, 1985; Seale, 1999; Shenton, 2004). The descriptions of the method used for obtaining data and of the step-by-step decisions made during the research are instrumental in ensuring confirmability. In this study, there is transparency in the data that was collected, and in the criteria that were used in selecting the participants for the study. Results obtained from the interviews, and the recommendations drawn from both data and literature have been clearly stated (Shenton, 2004). External auditors in the form of PhD supervisors made a valuable contribution to the confirmability of results obtained in this study. They have scrutinised the research process from the beginning, and critically reviewed records retained for the study (such as process and personal notes).

Miles and Huberman (1994) state that a basic issue for confirmability is the extent to which researchers acknowledge their own bias. In this study, the method of choice was acknowledged, the rationale behind the use of a qualitative approach (in the form of semi-structured interviews rather than other approaches) was developed, and the limitations of the chosen design were stated. This is essential in order to give a clear description to readers of this thesis, and to enhance the confirmability of the research. Reflexivity is another key strategy of bolstering confirmability (Krefting, 1991). The researcher hereby acknowledges his role in influencing data during the research, and, as mentioned above, therefore kept a field journal.

6.9.4 Transferability

Transferability emphasises the extent to which the studied situation matches other situations in which one is interested (Schofield, 2002). Lincoln and Guba (1985) refer to this as “fittingness”.

The focus of this research was to obtain a rich account of entrepreneurial leadership in a particular setting, which might not necessarily apply to other populations. Hence, generalisability was not paramount. Notwithstanding this, the notion of transferability (as proposed by Lincoln and Guba, 1985) has been acknowledged. Here, the onus rests on the individual who wants to transfer the findings to another study. The only responsibility of the researcher of this study is to provide sufficient descriptive data that would be of value when making judgements about such transferability (Bryman and Bell, 2011).

In this study, it was ensured that all background information about the respondents, the research context, and the specific setting was obtained. Moreover, to enable future investigators to adequately assess the transferability of findings from this thesis, the following information (as suggested by Shenton, 2004) is provided:

- The number of participants involved in the fieldwork.
- The data collection method used (which for this study was a semi-structured interview approach).
- The time allotted for the interviews with the entrepreneurs and their employees.
- The time period during which the data was collected.

Such information will be valuable for understanding entrepreneurial leadership within other developing economies besides Nigeria.

6.10 Ethical considerations

The ethical practice of business research involving human participants is a complex and demanding responsibility for any researcher (King and Horrocks, 2012). This research has satisfied the requirements of the University of the West of Scotland's ethics committee guidelines (2009), and was thereby guided by four major principles stipulated by the committee: non-maleficence and beneficence; autonomy; justice; and, confidentiality and anonymity.

6.10.1 Non-maleficence and beneficence

According to the University ethics committee (2009), non-maleficence means to do no harm, while beneficence implies doing good. Therefore, during the course of the research study, the risks of causing harm, whether emotional or physical, to the participants was continually assessed. It was ensured that sensitive questions which could adversely affect the emotional well-being of the interviewees, as well as the cohesion of the group, were excluded. The participants were also informed that it was not compulsory to provide answers to all questions. The employees were not prompted to give their opinions about the negative qualities of their employers; hence, their participation in this study did not expose them to an unacceptable risk or incurring the disapproval of their employers.

Beneficence was promoted during the course of research. The entrepreneurs were pleased that they were being interviewed, with the majority saying that they benefitted from the process of identifying their leadership skills and making them think about the challenges they faced in the day-to-day running of their business. The employees were glad that they were instrumental in identifying their employers' entrepreneurial leadership skills. In general, the participants were willing to devote more time than initially requested, and promised their commitment to future research.

6.10.2 Autonomy

Autonomy demands that individuals participate voluntarily, after having been told both what the research entails and its consequences (King and Horrocks, 2012). Autonomy can only therefore be established when there is an informed and voluntary consent by the participants.

In the words of Blumberg et al. (2011, p. 116), informed consent entails “...fully disclosing the procedures of the proposed survey or the research design before requesting permission to proceed with the study”. Saunders et al. (2012, p. 231) elaborates further that the “...principle of informed consent involves researchers providing sufficient information and assurances about taking part to allow individuals to understand the implications of participation and to reach a fully informed, considered and freely given decision about whether or not to do so, without the exercise of any pressure or coercion”.

In this study, informed consent from the participating entrepreneurs and employees was obtained both verbally and in writing. Signed informed consent was obtained from all respondents involved, and a copy of the consent form is attached in Appendix 9. The researcher sent a formal invitation letter via email to participants, and visited each of them at their own convenience prior to the scheduled interview to discuss the research process and clarify its scope. The respondents were also reminded that they had the right to decline to answer any question with which they were not comfortable, and that they could withdraw their participation from the study at any time.

6.10.3 Justice

The concept of justice in a research project involves treating the participants fairly and equally (Flick, 2011). It requires that all respondents have access to the same information by the researcher, and that there is a fair distribution of both the benefits and burden of the study (King and Horrocks, 2012).

In this study, it was ensured that all respondents were treated equally and that no particular entrepreneur was assumed to be more successful or possessed greater entrepreneurial leadership skills (based on the size of their business or the revenue it generated). All participants were asked similar questions during the interview and were also briefed on the impact of their interview on the study. The researcher also ensured that there was no bias in handling interviews with the employees, compared to those of their employers. Both the entrepreneurs and their employees were treated equally, with the same level of consideration and commitment given to each group.

6.10.4 Confidentiality and anonymity

According to Saunders et al. (2010, p. 231), “Research is designed to answer ‘who’, ‘what’, ‘when’, ‘where’, ‘how’ and ‘why’ questions, not to focus on those who provide the data to answer these.” Eriksson and Kovalainen (2011) argue that the anonymity of the participants in any study should be the priority of any research, and that their personal information should remain confidential.

In keeping with the guidelines proposed by the university’s ethics committee (2009), the confidentiality and anonymity of the participants were upheld. Participants were informed verbally and in writing how their confidentiality and anonymity would be ensured. Before conducting the interviews, respondents’ permission to record the interviews was sought, and respondents were assured that the proceedings would remain confidential. Rather than using names, codes have been used to identify the respondents in line with this assurance. Furthermore, any event that might lead to an easy identification of an individual or the organisation is not included in this thesis.

6.11 Conclusion

The purpose of this study was to investigate the leadership skills of entrepreneurs in a developing country and the challenges they face, based on dual perspectives of the entrepreneurs and their employees. In this chapter, the research approach and paradigms adopted in this study have been described. The philosophical stance of the study has been elaborated upon, and the rationale underpinning the choice of the qualitative approach has also been provided.

In this chapter, the adopted research design has been examined, and both the choice of sample as well as the method of data collection has been identified. The method of data analysis, thematic analysis has also been discussed. A thorough explanation of the three-stage process of thematic analysis used in this study was provided. The research method has also been evaluated to demonstrate the trustworthiness of its findings. Finally, the ethical implications of this study have been considered

A detailed account of the findings obtained from this research study is provided in the next chapter.

CHAPTER SEVEN – FINDINGS

7.1 Introduction

In the previous chapters, an extensive review of relevant literature was provided, and the research methods adopted in this study were outlined. In this chapter, the findings from the face-to-face interviews with the 51 respondents are presented. All respondents are given a pseudonym, and the names of their organisations are not revealed. This approach was followed to ensure that the ethical guidelines of the research are satisfied.

This chapter is sub-divided into five sections:

- Section 7.1 Introduction to the findings
- Section 7.2 Entrepreneurial leadership skills that enable entrepreneurs to be successful in business
- Section 7.3 Challenges faced by entrepreneurial leaders in the context of a developing economy
- Section 7.4 Additional themes emerging from the interviews
- Section 7.5 Conclusion

These sections address the specific research questions and objectives outlined back in Chapter 1 which, for the sake of emphasis, are reiterated below:

Research questions

- What is entrepreneurial leadership?
- What are the challenges that entrepreneurs in a developing economy face in running their businesses?
- What entrepreneurial leadership skills are valuable for running businesses successfully in a developing economy?
- What are the employees' perceptions of the entrepreneurial leadership of the entrepreneurs?

Research objectives

Research objective 1: to provide valid empirical evidence that contributes to the understanding of entrepreneurial leadership, particularly in the context of a developing economy.

Research Objective 2: to understand the lived experience of entrepreneurs in a developing economy, namely Nigeria.

Research Objective 3: to identify the skills of effective entrepreneurial leaders.

Research Objective 4: to consider the role of entrepreneurial leadership skills in addressing the challenges faced by entrepreneurs in a developing economy.

Research Objective 5: to utilise empirical evidence and contribute to theory on entrepreneurial leadership.

7.2 Entrepreneurial leadership skills enabling entrepreneurs to be successful in business

In this section, the entrepreneurial leadership skills identified from the analysis of the interview transcripts are described. The entrepreneurial leadership skills perceived by the entrepreneurs and their employees to be essential to the success of the business are considered. The results are presented in Table 23 by way of a frequency analysis, in which the number of respondents (both the entrepreneurs and employees) who mentioned each particular skill is indicated. Thus, the findings provide a clear representation of responses from 17 entrepreneurs and 34 employees.

Table 23 Frequency table of identified entrepreneurial leadership skills

Entrepreneurial leadership skills	Entrepreneurs	Employees
Technical/Business skills		
Technical expertise		
Pharmacy skills	17	34
Business function skills	17	34
Accounting and financial management	17	8
Administration	13	24
Marketing	17	20
Conceptual skills	17	34
Analytical skills	13	11
Idea generation skills	13	34
Problem solving skills	12	16
Envisioning skills	17	34
Strategic planning skills	17	34
Decision making skills	17	11
Interpersonal skills	17	34
Empathy	12	14
Communication/listening skills	10	16
Motivating skills	17	34
Team building skills	17	34
People management and development skills	14	34
Self-management skills	17	34
Entrepreneurial skills	17	34
Opportunity identification skills	17	13
Opportunity exploitation skills	10	14
Risk management skills	17	34

To develop a complete understanding of the features of entrepreneurial leadership, insights were sought not only from entrepreneurs but also from their respective employees. These employees have worked with the entrepreneurs over a period of time and so were in a good position to relate their perceptions of the skills that have made these businesses successful. This encapsulates the leader/follower approach which is a key part of this research study.

It had been anticipated that respondents would have difficulty distinguishing between skills and other personal attributes. This proved to be the case. The definition of skills and attributes (set out back in sub-section 6.7.3.2) proved to be useful in isolating skills from other aspects of personality and behaviour. It is therefore useful to repeat these definitions at this juncture. Attributes were defined as characteristics and distinctive features belonging to the leaders, which are observed through their behaviour in the workplace (Russell and Stone, 2002), while skills refer to the expertise, competencies and practised abilities that can be learned or developed by the leaders (Northouse, 2010; Schedlitzki and Edwards, 2014).

The respondents (entrepreneurs and employees) interviewed did not view entrepreneurship and leadership differently; instead, they emphasised the value of managing and leading in an entrepreneurial context. According to the respondents, it is important that all entrepreneurs have the ability to lead, and so there is the need for entrepreneurial leadership. Their business context is plagued with uncertainty and competition, and entrepreneurial leadership skills have been paramount to their success. Four broad entrepreneurial leadership skill categories were identified by the respondents:

- Technical/Business skills
- Conceptual skills
- Interpersonal skills
- Entrepreneurial skills

Three of these skills (technical, interpersonal and conceptual skills) are compatible with the skill-based framework advanced by Katz (1955; 1974), which in turn was further developed by Yukl (2010). The skill-based model first proposed by Katz (1955) has become a universally accepted framework within the leadership domain

(Bass, 1990; Hunt, 1991; Schedlitzki and Edwards, 2014; Yukl, 2010). However, it was found in this study that the Katz framework does not encompass all the skills that are expected of an entrepreneurial leader. In this study, distinct leadership skills for entrepreneurs not previously identified in literature were identified. These skills were grouped under the general heading of entrepreneurial skills, and include opportunity identification, opportunity exploitation, and risk management skills.

In the following section, the entrepreneurial leadership skills identified by the respondents (entrepreneurs and employees) are presented, with reference to the conceptual framework of Katz. The findings confirm the usefulness of the model but also show that skills in addition to those identified by Katz are required in order to gain a full understanding of effective entrepreneurial leadership.

7.2.1 Technical/Business skills

The respondents in the study agreed that the technical/business skills they possessed have been instrumental in running their business. While discussing these skills, they identified technical expertise in the form of pharmacy practice (See Figure 14). In addition, they also identified specific functional skills namely; accounting and financial management, and administration and marketing skills. These skills are discussed below from both the entrepreneur and the employee perspectives.

Figure 14 Composition of technical/business skills

7.2.1.1 Technical expertise skills

The respondents in the study concurred that technical expertise was essential for running their businesses successfully. According to the evidence gathered in the interviews, technical expertise differs from business function skills, as the former consisted mainly of professional expertise in relation to pharmacy. Pharmacy skills, which are a key feature of the technical expertise skills, are presented below.

Pharmacy skills

Entrepreneurs

All the respondents (17) recognised pharmacy expertise as an important technical skill. They were only able to start their businesses by being pharmacists themselves. As highlighted by respondent Q,

“Yes it is quite useful because pharmacy practice is a profession, and you practice better when you are a professional, when you have been trained in the art and science of pharmaceutical practice. So it is quite useful because if I was not a pharmacist, I don’t think I would be getting many clients as I do now. We get our clients, we don’t advertise. But people come to us based on the experience that they have had that these people are well trained, that these people are good in what they are doing. So it is basically one of the keys to our success; we are quite skilled and we are quite trained in what we are doing. The pharmacy professional training has gone a long way in helping me in this practice.” (Q)

However, respondent G argued that pharmacy skills are ‘just 10% of what you need’. In her opinion, entrepreneurs need to be ‘street savvy’ and many pharmacies fail because their entrepreneurs only possess the technical expertise and lack the necessary business acumen. Most of the respondents supported the stance of respondent G, in that while technical skills are important, business skills were just as

valuable for the success of the entrepreneur/business. This is summarised in the remark by respondent O:

“There are 2 components – the pharmacy component and the administrative component. Being pharmacists, most of us don’t know how to run business. [For] some people the administrative factor is innate and they can expand with their theory and practice, becoming better administrators. Most of us are not.”
(O)

Employees

Just like their bosses, the employees recognised pharmacy expertise as an important technical skill that their employers possessed. Respondent Q2 stressed that the business is a highly technical one, and the entrepreneur must possess pharmacy knowledge so that he or she can provide the right advice to customers. Furthermore, respondent Q2 pointed out that it is not possible to manage a retail pharmacy legally if one is not an accredited pharmacist.

For respondent M1, it is practically impossible to set up a pharmacy if one is not a pharmacist because it involves issuing prescriptions. On the other hand, though technical skills are important, respondent Q2 argued that they are just the starting point, and other skills such as business knowledge are important and form a determining factor for success:

“In managing a pharmacy you need good business knowledge. You need very, very sound business knowledge and that is the reason why I think most community pharmacies don’t succeed. Apart from your pharmacy knowledge, you need good human resource management and good management of finance. You can’t do without it... So it is not enough to have B. Pharm. B. Pharm is just the starting stage and that is why most pharmacies don’t do well. The pharmacy I was coming from is a smaller pharmacy and for years it has not grown because of [the need for] other qualifications. The woman is very sound technically but there are other qualifications that [she is] lacking. So that is why most pharmacists don’t do well.”* (Q2) * B Pharm is a bachelor degree in Pharmacy.

Business function skills

Entrepreneurs

The respondents in this study shared the view that business skills are important for successfully running their enterprises. These entrepreneurs were pharmacists by trade and felt that a key difference between those who were successful and those who were not was due to whether or not they possess strong business skills. These views reflect an economic awareness for the need of business acumen and a good understanding of the business environment. This is illustrated in the comments made by respondent K:

“You need the business skill. That’s why there is a big gap between the pharmacists that are doing well in Nigeria and those that are struggling. You need to use the business knowledge.” (K)

Five of these respondents had developed their business skill through MBA programmes (see Appendix 7.1a). For respondents A and O, the MBA has helped them acquire functional skills such as finance, marketing, operations, and HR. These skills have helped them gain a better overview of the business world and a deeper understanding of the business environment. For respondent B, the MBA course had been very important in terms of staff management. The people management skills he had learned from networking with people from diverse backgrounds had been instrumental in managing his employees. Although the cost of the MBA course had been substantial, the respondents with MBAs felt that gaining the qualification was a cost-effective way of acquiring expertise.

12 respondents were also undertaking training to improve their business skills. Along with MBAs, training programmes were also reported to be expensive and demanding, but beneficial nevertheless.

Employees

The employees’ perceptions of their employers’ business function skills was positive. They felt that the business function skills these entrepreneurs possessed had

been a key factor to their success, which has distinguished them from their rivals. This is reflected in the comments made by respondent B2:

“He is not just a pharmacist. He is a pharmacist and also a business man. I have really taken a survey round the [other] pharmacy outlets we have in this axis. I could see that they were lacking in that area. He has what his contemporaries don’t have.” (B2)

Respondent J2 went further to state that without business skills, it is impossible to run a pharmacy despite being a pharmacist. The employees confirmed that their employers had developed these business skills through MBAs or other business training courses, which have provided their employers with an all-round knowledge of the business. Respondent H2 stressed that it is important to understand the function of every department in the business, and this can only be learned through business courses.

However, just like the entrepreneurs, seven employees confirmed that these business skills were not solely linked to MBA courses. They just knew that their bosses possessed business skills. Respondent K2 suggested that her boss has a high business IQ compared with other Nigerians, probably due to experience and knowledge gained when travelling outside the country. Respondent K2 establishes a link between business function skills and conceptual skills. Respondent H1 emphasised that her boss developed her skills through reading books in her own time, and not only through external training.

Analysis of the interviews of the respondents (entrepreneurs and employees) enabled three key functional skills to be identified:

- Accounting and financial management
- Administration
- Marketing

Each is discussed below in this order.

Accounting and financial management

Entrepreneurs

All respondents (17) agreed that accounting and finance were key business function skills. These entrepreneurs ran efficient accounts departments, and they possessed a very good understanding of accounting and inventory management. For these respondents, such an understanding had been a key to their success. This is typified in respondent I's comment:

“Most people think that computerising and keeping accounts is just a waste of time - no! I know that it helps you to track where you have gone wrong. It helps you to know whether to push harder or just go backwards. Accounting and inventory has been the key to my success and other abilities.” (I)

The respondents also shared the view that the ability to manage finance effectively and prudently had been pivotal to their success. They suggested that the business is quite capital-intensive and they have been successful because they have exercised good financial discipline. This is seen in respondent L's remarks below:

“People thought that I borrowed money to finance it. I told them I did it myself. At the time [when] we were about to start, I had just N250,000 which is less than \$2000...however, I started with the money, buying bit by bit. I also had cooperation from colleagues and companies.” (L)

Employees

The entrepreneurs' knowledge of accounting and inventory management, which was a recurring theme in the interviews with the employers, was confirmed by their employees in the main study. Respondent L1 stated that her boss knew whatever she (as an accountant) did not know about accounting. Respondent O2 highlighted that his boss runs the accounting aspects and still performs his main role as a pharmacist. In addition, the ability of the entrepreneurs to manage finance effectively was confirmed by the respondents. Respondent G1 stressed that her boss is very good at

managing money, while respondent Q1 opined that finance management affects the way that people work in the pharmacy (therefore linking it to motivation).

Administration

Entrepreneurs

Another theme that emerged under business function skills was administration. The respondents perceived themselves to be effective administrators of their business. They had put in place structures and systems to ensure the smooth running of the business (see Appendix 7.1b). This is seen in a comment made by respondent E, which is typical of many:

“Apart from being a pharmacist, you should probably know a little about business administration which will help you a lot. This is because when you know a little about business administration, you will know the key and necessary things to do to move it forward...You know, when you don’t know all these things and you...leave it in someone else’s hands, the person could mess it up.” (E)

Employees

Administrative skills were also identified by employees. Respondent A1 stated clearly that his boss was a good administrator, while G1 went further in her opinion of administrative skills:

“Let me use the words “administrative skill” because it is difficult to manage money, material, and human resources.” (G1)

The respondents agreed that their bosses put a structure and system in place to ensure the smooth running of the business. Respondent C1 explained that each branch has a superintendent, and her boss tries as often as possible to visit each branch every week. Respondent Q2 confirmed this view by saying that his boss oversees his various outlets through his managers.

Marketing

Entrepreneurs

Marketing was highlighted as an essential business function skill by all the respondents. When discussing marketing, the role of customer service was emphasised by all respondents. There was a shared view that good customer service should be the ethos and culture of a pharmacy, and that the culture should be shared by all employees. 14 respondents saw customer service as a means of developing a sustainable competitive advantage. This was highlighted by respondent J:

“I think when it comes to customer service; nobody beats us to it in the pharmacy industry. Nobody! I can say that confidently anywhere because we don’t think that those things [customer service] are important but those are things that are really our concern to fill in the gap.” (J)

In addition, according to these respondents, there is a link between customer service and human relations (see Appendix 7.1c).

Employees

Marketing skills were identified and confirmed as one of the core business function skills that are possessed by their employers. The employees agreed with the entrepreneurs that marketing especially in form of providing effective customer service is an important part of the business function skill set. They remarked that their bosses usually go the extra mile to satisfy their customers. This is reflected in the comments made by respondent H2:

“You can’t be a leader without serving. You need to be able to serve. She attends to customers excellently. She makes sure that customers are given the best service.” (H2)

The use of customer service as a tool to achieve a sustainable competitive advantage (which was identified by the entrepreneurs) was also highlighted by the employees. Respondent F2 stressed that her boss tried as much as possible to convince the

customers to buy her products, and when certain products were not available, her boss would ask customers for their contact information so that she could contact them when the product stock was replenished.

The respondents confirmed the link between customer service skill and human relations. The respondents believed that their employers had interpersonal skills which have been instrumental in providing good customer service, and that their employers have a good rapport with their customers. Both these qualities have helped to improve customer retention. Respondents A2 and L1 went a step further to stress that the ability of their bosses to render good customer service is a matter of good listening skills. This is reflected in the comment by respondent A2:

“He has cultivated this not just a good listener but [by] being a good customer service person. He is someone who is inclined to listening to what customers want.” (A2)

As identified by the entrepreneurs, the employees also believed that marketing skills in the form of customer service should be shown by all staff members. Their bosses have fostered good customer service skills among their employees by training and observation. Respondent C1 explained how during their meetings they are taught about building good customer relationships and interaction. Respondent M2 noted that her boss was so good at dealing with customers, and she enjoyed watching and learning how it is done.

7.2.2 Conceptual skills

One of the key elements of the skills framework advanced by Katz was that of conceptual skills. Conceptual skills refer to the ability to find meanings to ambiguous and complex situations. In relation to this definition, six skills were identified during the interviews, as illustrated in Figure 15. Each of these is set out below from both the entrepreneur perspective and the employee perspective.

Figure 15 Composition of conceptual skills

7.2.2.1 Analytical skills

Entrepreneurs

13 respondents shared the view that gathering information systematically was important for establishing facts and for decision making, which are key features of conceptual skills. They took pride in being able to examine information objectively rather than subjectively, and to think critically of all possible outcomes in making good decisions. This is reflected in the comment by respondent B:

“I compare the reports together just to [gain] an understanding of where I make money and where [I do] not. I observe the branch that does excellently well [and] evaluate the figures to determine the potential.” (B)

Employees

11 respondents believed that the analytical and calculative approach taken by their employers was an important conceptual skill. They felt that their bosses thought differently and this has had an effect on their decision making. Respondent O2 narrated that his boss is very calculative and that he was expected to defend his suggestions in order to convince him. Respondent H2 supported this by reiterating that before she spoke with her boss, she always prepared because everything she said would lead to another question.

7.2.2.2 Idea generation skills

Entrepreneurs

13 respondents identified the ability to generate new ideas as a skill that is paramount to their success. These respondents stressed that there was a link between innovativeness and their own success. They believed that their ability to generate new ideas was essential as it provided them with a greater customer base. This is reflected by respondent K in her comment:

“[If] you...just open a business - be it retail pharmacy or any other retail - and ... [put] whatever you are selling...out there and don't do any other thing, it's going to die a natural death, so you have to keep reinventing the business. The business has to keep reinventing itself.” (K)

11 respondents readily admitted that the ideas generated were not always their own; some very good ideas came from their employees. Indeed, respondents B and M stated that they engaged with younger employees in order to generate fresh ideas. As well as employees, new ideas were also obtained from conferences or shows they attended.

Three respondents (K, L, and M) believed that in addition to generating new ideas, it was important to challenge the accepted way of doing things. Indeed, for respondent M, her love of challenges and questioning assumptions had been a major reason for starting the business in the first place. This is reflected in her comments below:

“I think that is the major issue with our country - the stock. We have the same old people with the same old ideas and they keep telling that this is the way they have been doing it. But if it is not working can't you use another way? That's why I set up mine; I could not work for anybody again.” (M)

Employees

All the respondents (34) confirmed that their bosses indeed generated new ideas. In their view, this is an important conceptual skill in the growth of the business. The respondents stressed that their bosses bring in new ideas, and that this is pivotal to improving their businesses year on year (see Appendix 7.3a). The employees confirmed the link between innovativeness and the success of the business. They believed that their bosses were very innovative. Respondent E2 stated that her boss' willingness to introduce new things to her customers has paid off, and that not many people can do this. Respondent Q2 believed that his boss has a "*mind of innovation*" and as result has been successful.

The innovations by these entrepreneurs added value to the business and made it easier to run. Respondent O2 stressed that the introduction of new software for inventory management by the employer has improved the business:

"Before now there was no software that they are using today to account for stocks and prices. Before, the business was strictly business, but now the management has changed, making the work a bit less stressful...we have software that we use to record and actually know what is coming out and going in." (O2)

On the other hand, not everyone believed that the innovations by the entrepreneurial leaders were useful to the business. For respondent N2, the introduction of software has done more harm than good and some employees have not been able to adapt to using it.

As mentioned in the interviews with the entrepreneurs, the employees confirmed that they were involved in idea generation. Their bosses encouraged them to generate ideas and, most importantly, they listened. The employees established a relationship between listening skills and idea generation. Respondent B2 stated that his boss listens to every staff member's idea and buys into it. Respondent L1 narrated that her boss welcomes such ideas and even negotiates a timeframe set aside for implementing them.

12 respondents stressed the impact of challenging the accepted way of doing things. Respondent H1 stressed that her boss believed in challenging the status quo. Her

boss believed in questioning assumptions and encouraged staff to do likewise. This is reflected in her comment:

“She always says, ‘Challenge the status quo - don’t just come here and say, ‘This is the way they are doing it so I am going to follow them.’ If you think that there is a better way it can be done, please by all means let us know...[Don’t] just sit down and say, ‘This is how they clean their shelf even though it is not entirely clean but this is how they do it, so let me...do it the way they are doing it.’” (H1)

7.2.2.3 Problem solving skills

Entrepreneurs

12 entrepreneurs recognised the ability to solve problems as an important skill for running their business. They claimed they have the creative ability to provide solutions to new, unusual, and ill-defined organisational problems. Respondent A stressed that his success was mainly due to his ability to look for problems and solve them:

“Try to solve problems? We have a strong inclination to solve problems and to do what others cannot do, and that is where we build our own blue ocean strategy. We always try to find something new in our environment and that will always work everywhere. You get to the desert and you try to find ways of how to help people in the desert, [then] you will be successful.” (A)

According to the respondents (H, M and E), there is always a solution to every problem, and they were upbeat about it. This attitude is reflected in respondent H’s comment:

“Whatever [problem] you see there is a solution to it. So I don’t feel that... [the problem should] be there at all - there is a solution.” (H)

Employees

The respondents agreed that their bosses have the ability to solve problems and that this was a key skill responsible for their success. Their employers were apt at providing solutions to novel and ill-defined organisational problems. These problems ranged from employee conflicts to customer needs. Their bosses have the ability to resolve issues. Respondent E2 narrates her experience of how her boss was able to resolve conflict:

“For the [whole] amount of time I have worked here I will say she is a brilliant boss because I have noticed several incidents happening here and I have seen the way she handles everything...For example there was a misunderstanding between her and one of her workers last week. Usually what you expect from a Nigerian boss is to just come out and shout at the person and have a go at them. But she called the person in and said, ‘This is what happened, this is what I saw. I cannot see the evidence of so-so goods being sold and the money being taken. So if you have your evidence [then] present it to me, but if not, I will not be at a loss. This will be deducted from your salary.’ And she treated the matter in a very direct way. She put everything on the table. She did not hold back her feelings and at the same time she was not rude about it. She tried as much as possible to keep the matter quiet so that other people in the store will not get involved or something. I was quite impressed by that.” (E2)

Apart from employee incidents, their bosses were able to offer solutions to the problems and needs of their customers. Respondent A2 stressed that his boss provides the kinds of products that help customers with recurrent health issues. For him, the most important skill of his boss is being a “*solver of problems*”. According to the respondents, their bosses did not believe that there are problems without solutions. They were optimistic that every problem could be solved. Respondent H1 emphasised that her boss has a mantra that to every problem there is a solution, and never wants to hear the word “impossible” and that, interestingly; this strategy has not failed her yet.

7.2.2.4 Envisioning skills

Entrepreneurs

The findings from the data show that the respondents possessed what can be called ‘envisioning skills’, in that they had a clear and explicit objective of what they wanted their business to become. This ranged from expansion to greater brand awareness. It was found that these respondents were not just day-dreamers, but had specific plans for achieving their visions. Respondent P showed a clear link between strategic planning skills and envisioning. For him, to achieve a vision, an ambitious implementation plan is required. This is illustrated in his comment:

“...we still need to weed out some people because we are looking at ten (more pharmacies) in five years [which] is not too far away. So we have to weed out some people and keep the strategy. Our plan to build a manufacturing plant is still in the pipeline.” (P)

The respondents supported the stance of respondent P, in that envisioning requires strategic planning. This is summarised in the remark by respondent K:

“My brand is going to be stronger. We are going to some strategic places. We are going to Port Harcourt. We are in Delta state. We are going to some strategic places. Abuja - we are working on that. It is going to be a brand to be reckoned with.” (K)

Employees

As with the entrepreneurs, all the employees (34) recognised envisioning as a core conceptual skill that their bosses possessed, and that their bosses have a vision and foresight for their business. Respondent B2 emphasised this:

“This is a man that sits and compares his business with the big banks not minding [that] those banks have been in existence over centuries. He always [thinks] ahead.” (B2)

On the other hand, the respondents agreed that there are specific plans in place to achieve the visions of their bosses; hence a link is established between strategic planning skills and envisioning. According to respondent H1, to become the pharmacy of choice in the country, they have to be accessible. They must be positioned where people can easily reach them. For her, this drives and pushes their growth.

7.2.2.5 Strategic planning skills

Entrepreneurs

As well as having a long-term vision for their businesses, the respondents were able to demonstrate strategic planning skills aimed at achieving the vision. These strategies ranged from unique customer experience, to value for money products and even niche products to cater for different types of customers. However, the strategies adopted by the respondents varied, especially when dealing with competition. Respondent B monitored competitors and, where appropriate, imitated them:

“I go to their shops, talk to their manager. I look at business as a football game. We are both on the playing field and to make sure [my business] gets customers...have to copy them, try it and if [it is] not successful, dump the strategy. It all boils down to having what the consumer needs and the best prices.” (B)

Respondents O, M and P believed that an entrepreneur should have a strategy which is different from that of others. Respondent M stressed that running a pharmacy is not simply a price war but that *“it involves outsmarting your competitor”*.

These entrepreneurs said they were able to draft out plans and anticipate changes in their business. This is reflected in the comment by respondent A:

“You should be able to anticipate and plan. You should be able to know where the government is moving [and know] government policy. You have to align with the environmental factors and take advantage of your strengths and know...your weaknesses.” (A)

Respondents J and K emphasised that planning requires extensive forecasting. These respondents believed that envisioning where their businesses would be in the future is related to strategic planning. Respondent K also stressed that while planning, time management is very important. For her, *“You have to schedule time for everything otherwise you will never really achieve anything.”*

13 respondents discussed their strategic planning skills from the lens of competition (see Appendix 7.1d). They are usually a step ahead of their competitors and provide a unique experience for their customers. They have been able to develop a sustainable competitive advantage by strategic planning. However, respondent J emphasised that even though entrepreneurs need to know about their competitors, they should not change their plans simply because of them. For her, changing plans and aligning with those of competitors changes the focus of the business. These respondents shared the view of respondent J and believed that in strategic planning, an entrepreneur needs to be focused.

For respondents E and M, focus is very important in planning a business. This is reflected in respondent E’s remarks:

“You have to be focused. You have to make up your mind that this is actually what you want to do. So many people have come to me and I have advised them on starting [a] retail pharmacy. Two or three of them have gone back home. Some feel it is not profitable. Some will feel you put in so much time, and in everything you do you must put in time because if you don’t nurture any business it is not going to grow. So [in response to] that I will tell them that focus is important.” (E)

Furthermore, while strategically planning their businesses, seven respondents shared the view that goal setting was important. These respondents set goals, targets and objectives they wanted to achieve. According to respondent B, targets are necessary in guiding the employees:

“Be supportive, and insist on a target because it’s important in any new business. Even though they don’t accomplish, they may get close to it. This reduces the ‘I don’t care’ attitude.” (B)

According to respondent M, before anyone can even set up any business in the first place, one must have a goal. Some of the goals set not only cover the immediate activities of the company, but also concern the starting up of the business. Respondents J and K had set out goals for running their businesses many years ago. Respondent J specifically stated that she and her husband are pharmacists as well as former classmates and so from the beginning they had aimed at going into retail. They had planned to run standard pharmacy retail chains even before they graduated.

Respondent E identified the link between strategic planning and risk management skills, and claimed that one can only manage risks well if one plans around them to prevent the business from collapsing.

Employees

All the respondents (34) shared the view that their bosses possessed strategic planning skills which have been useful in running the business and which are a core conceptual skill. They agreed that their bosses had a strategy for their business. Respondent A2 explained one such strategy:

“We are a niche company. Most pharmaceutical companies carry OTC (over the counter) [products] and other products like some prescription medication, but we tend to carry medications for the tougher and more challenging conditions that people face.” (A2)

18 respondents were of the view that when dealing with competition, the strategy adopted by their bosses involved reducing prices. They ensured that there was little difference between their prices and those of their rivals. Respondent C2 stressed that they used a standard mark-up and did not necessarily provide the lowest price in the market. However, 16 respondents argued that the strategies employed by their bosses were unique and not just based on pricing. Respondent K1 stressed that her boss was always trying to get the best, to get what others cannot get, in that she tried to do something different in comparison with other pharmacies. According to respondent Q2, his boss has been able to establish a competitive edge through selling niche ethical products.

These respondents agreed that their bosses were able to draft plans and that they knew the plans for the business. This was recounted by respondent K1:

“Of course I know the plans. Like I said we started from one room and now we are in a duplex section and now we have three branches. We started from one branch and now we have three branches and we are hoping to open more branches and expand to other things - not only retailing but, in the future, other things.” (K1)

The interviewed employees believed that their bosses were focused and that focus is very important in planning a business – and so their sentiments were aligned with those of their bosses. Respondent Q1 stressed that focus is key and is linked to hard work and determination. She was of the opinion that her boss knew what he wanted to achieve and was focused on that.

Furthermore, 22 respondents confirmed that their bosses set goals. Their bosses had goals, targets, and objectives they wanted to achieve. Respondent L2 emphasised that her boss clearly mapped goals and devised a plan on how to achieve them. She established a link between envisioning and strategic planning. In addition, the respondents agreed that their bosses almost never gave up in their pursuit of the goals set out. A link is established between persistence and strategic planning skills. According to respondent L2,

“...we might face challenges sometimes, but he is the kind of person that never gives up, and [he] faces a particular goal that he needs to achieve.” (L2)

7.2.2.6 Decision making skills

Entrepreneurs

All the respondents (17) shared the view that the ability to make the best decisions is one of the conceptual skills that they possessed. Respondent C believed decision making was integral to the strategy she adopted for handling her business. She had learned in her early days not to build the business around herself, and this belief was core to her strategy. When these entrepreneurs made decisions relating to the

strategy of their companies, most of them involved their employees. Respondent L called this “*participatory management*”. They held meetings where they discussed the intended plans of the company. These respondents established a link between the decision making and interpersonal skills of an entrepreneur (see Appendix 7.1e).

However, five respondents suggested that members of staff were not always consulted whenever they were modifying the strategy or plans of the company. Respondent I suggested that some decisions are individual, but those relating to policies must be set by the management team.

Although decision making skills are regarded as essential, respondents M and P suggested that they are slow in making decisions. Respondent P acknowledged that his slow response is a weakness, but that he “*likes to get more information*” before making a decision; he also remarked, “*I don’t like the stampede.*” Respondent M did not perceive slow decision making as a weakness, claiming that it is important sometimes to take one’s time and not make hasty decisions:

“One thing I know is sometimes, you can’t just make snap decisions. There are some things that you can’t compromise on. There are some things [whereby] you just have to give it time...if you have a person that comes in late all the time, you give the person long rope, talk to the person and see whether he will change. But if I have someone who does not show and does not call, I draw the line.” (M)

Employees

11 respondents confirmed that their bosses had the ability to make decisions, and agreed that this is an important conceptual skill for running a business. Respondent A1 stressed that his boss’ decision making, leadership, and many other qualities can be traced to his Christian background. Respondent A1 tried to establish a link between decision making skills and values.

As for decisions that concern the strategy of a company, the employees believed that they were involved in such decisions to a particular level. Respondent H1 explained

that strategic meetings were held, wherein the strategy of the company was discussed with the employees:

“The management meetings are usually strategic meetings. Where are we as an organisation? Where do we want to go and how does each department fit in? What are some of the things that affect more than one department?...[The management] make sure that you discuss them so that we can move forward.”
(H1)

However, four respondents mentioned that members of staff were not always consulted whenever the strategy or plans of the company were being modified. Respondent M2 noted that the major decisions were usually made by her boss.

7.2.3 Interpersonal skills

One of the three key elements of the skill framework advanced by Katz was that of interpersonal skills. Interpersonal skills refer to the ability to understand the feelings, attitudes, and motives of others. It involves knowledge about human behaviour and group processes. In this study, all six skills (as set out in Figure 16 below) were identified. Each of these is set out below from both the perspective of the entrepreneur and the employee.

Figure 16 Composition of interpersonal skills

7.2.3.1 Empathy

Entrepreneurs

12 respondents shared the view that the ability to understand other people's motives, values, and emotions was an essential interpersonal skill for their business. This illustrates the importance of empathy. For respondent E, this skill is very important when dealing with customers and helping them feel relaxed. Respondent M said that it is impossible to succeed in the business if one cannot connect emotionally with people. For her, one cannot be in retail and be emotionally distant. According to Respondent M, it is vital to "come out of your shell". As well as empathising with customers, the entrepreneurs felt that empathy towards their own staff is also essential. They said they made efforts to understand their employees' feelings, and assist them in any way they could, financially or in other ways. Respondent P claimed that he tried as often as possible to treat his employees with compassion and empathy. Respondents E and O suggest that although empathy is important, no two members of staff are the same, and thus they would deal with them using different approaches. This is reflected in the comment by respondent E:

"But now I have come to the realisation that everybody can't be the same. So I try to study each and every one of them and take them as they come." (E)

11 entrepreneurs associated empathy with human sensitivity. Their ability to understand people's emotions made them compassionate towards them. However, they also remarked that such compassion could be detrimental to the business, especially since it affected profits. These entrepreneurs were aware of the link between self-awareness and human sensitivity. For respondent D, this compassion could be a weakness:

"I look at the person and I know the person needs to take the drug. So I tell the person, 'Okay, take [it], but do me a favour and bring it [back].' Some will, and some will not bring [back the medicine]. So my emotions are my problem." (D)

Just like respondent D, respondent L cared for his customers a lot, but he also believed that such compassion would reap rewards in the form of customer referrals.

Employees

14 respondents confirmed that their bosses understood people's motives, values, and emotions. Indeed, most of them identified empathy as an essential interpersonal skill. This was examined mainly from the perspective of the staff. Respondent C1 opined that her boss tried as often as possible to ensure that her employees are cheerful and that if one particular individual cannot cope with the shift, he or she is given the day off. Respondents F1, J2, and M1 stressed that their bosses understood them so well and were able to bring out the best in them. For respondent J2, her boss went to great efforts to identify her employees' capabilities. This is also shared by respondent M1 who believes that her boss knew every employee's strengths and weakness, and tried as much as possible to align herself towards them.

The respondents associated empathy with their bosses' human sensitivity. They agreed that their bosses were compassionate to their employees and customers. Respondent H2 stressed that her boss cared not only about her business but also about her employees; staff members' weddings, baby naming ceremonies, and other special events were never ignored.

7.2.3.2 Communication/Listening skills

Entrepreneurs

The ability to communicate well both verbally and in writing was highlighted by the respondents as an important interpersonal skill they possessed. According to respondent A, communication skills are important:

“You should be able to express yourself and should be intelligent enough to assess situations...you write reports and make good decisions.” (A)

However, communication is not only limited to verbal and written aspects; the respondents also highlighted the ability to listen. Respondents B and L stressed that they listened to their employees before making decisions. These entrepreneurs are good listeners. Respondent P stated that he listened to everybody because useful information can come from any source. However, after listening, respondent O

shares that his final decision was aligned more with “*his experience over the years*”. Whereas, respondent K went a step further by listening to the opinions of her competitors’ customers.

Employees

The ability to communicate well was confirmed and identified by 16 respondents as a key interpersonal skill that their bosses possessed. This is reflected in the comments by respondent H2:

“She communicates effectively. You can’t tell me that you don’t understand what she is saying. She has good communication skills.” (H2)

The respondents identified a link between communication skills and people management and development. They believed that good communication skills of their bosses have been vital in developing long lasting relationships with their customers and suppliers. Respondent L1 suggests that when her boss starts talking, the interlocutor would not want to go anywhere else. Other respondents such as M1 supported this view by recounting their experiences.

The employees highlighted the ability to listen as being a core part of the communication process, just as did the entrepreneurs. The respondents stressed that their bosses usually listened not only to customers and suppliers but also to them as well, and that this was vital in the business (see Appendix 7.3b).

7.2.3.3 Motivating skills

Entrepreneurs

The ability to motivate oneself and others was identified by the entrepreneurs as an essential interpersonal skill for their businesses. All the respondents (17) agreed that they were proficient in motivating their employees. They did so mostly through bonuses, pay rises, stakes in the business, and recognition. This is summarised in the remark made by respondent F:

“Basically, when you open up any branch, you try and get somebody that will be heading the branch. Let the person have a stake or more...have a share in the business...ensuring that my managers have good compensation, have good remuneration for their services...I make them feel okay and comfortable with what they get and from there [I] motivate them.” (F)

According to respondent Q, the mere fact that he pays his employees' salaries on time was instrumental in motivating them to do their best. However, respondent K explained that not only does she motivate her employees with extrinsic mechanisms, but she also uses a mini-motivational mechanism. A link is established between good communication skills and motivation.

In addition, all the respondents (17) are self-motivated. Respondent F remarked,

“I am a pharmacist. Right from when I was in school, I have been dreaming of establishing a company that will be like all these multinational companies like Pfizer, Novartis, and Sanofi. So that is what motivated me on starting.” (F)

14 respondents discussed motivation from the lens of their customers. They identified the ability to inspire confidence in their customers and their employees as being an important interpersonal skill in their possession. Respondent F explained that one can only inspire confidence in one's customers if one has the technical know-how. For example, he stated “...that you have to inspire the confidence in your customers or clients. For a client to have confidence in you, at least you must be a pharmacist”. Respondent I explained that not only is knowledge important, but the way in which it is communicated to the customer also determines whether the customer will buy a product. Self-confidence is required to inspire confidence in others.

Employees

The respondents agreed that their bosses were self-motivated, and believed this was essential to their success. Respondent B2 stressed that his boss believed in himself and was relentless in achieving his dream.

All the respondents (34) agreed that their bosses were quite skilled in motivating their staff. The respondents agreed that their bosses inspire their confidence. Respondent A2 stated that his boss is a very inspirational leader:

“Motivating people; he is a good motivator... It is important for you to have highly motivated people out there in your field force... And people that you can motivate to go out there to work as hard as they possibly can and not just for their earnings or remuneration but because they believe in you... We see that regularly in our meetings, our weekly meetings; after discussing everything, he spends time motivating people to go out and actually achieve the goals we have set for ourselves.” (A2)

The respondents shared the view that they were motivated mostly through bonuses, salary increases, and recognition. Respondents C1 and C2 stressed that these motivating tools have encouraged them to put their best efforts into the business. Respondent C1 stated that she felt she did not deserve the pay rise, and was working harder to prove to herself that she did. Respondent C2 mentioned that the mere fact that his boss appreciated his efforts through recognition compelled him into “giving 100%” to the job.

7.2.3.4 Team building skills

Entrepreneurs

The respondents were united in their view that the ability to build teams and promote team work was a key to their success. They believed that success was not based solely on themselves but on their ability to build and coordinate teams (see Appendix 7.1f). This is illustrated in the following remark:

“To run a successful establishment you need a team because you are not the most talented or knowledgeable person in the team. It is just your ability to coordinate the team and bring out the best from every member of the team. If you don't do that then you are limited. You don't have a business. You just have a job.” (P)

While discussing team work, 13 respondents stressed the importance of recruiting staff that were team-oriented. In particular, delegating tasks to their employees was seen to be an important part of team work.

Employees

All the respondents (34) confirmed that their employers had the ability to build teams and promote team work. This is reflected in the following remark by respondent E2:

“One thing about her is that she is a team worker and she doesn’t just lead and say, ‘This is what I want and this is what you must do.’ ...She takes into account what everyone has to say, especially her main pharmacists...She just carries the whole team along. That’s one thing I noticed is very clear about her.” (E2)

The respondents agreed that the reasons for their bosses’ success were also due to their commitment towards their employees. They believed that their bosses’ ability to hire team-oriented employees has helped in their success. Respondent C2 stated that her boss hired a good team of people and has been able to motivate them. Respondent L2 mentioned that because her boss’ employees are highly committed, she does not need to be on the ground all the time. Things will still work effectively in her absence. However, respondent K1 stressed that her boss’s ability to pick the right set of people and make them work together as a team is the reason for her success.

Furthermore, 18 respondents in the study shared the view that their bosses delegated responsibilities and tasks to them. This they believed is an important part of team work. Respondent Q2 took the following stance:

“Sometimes he gives me tasks. For example, as a pharmacist I know how to use the inventory on the computer. I know how to sell on the computer. I know how to use the POS (point of sale). Normally in the [other] pharmacies...I never had an idea of what they were doing there... I never had an idea, but

because I have worked with him, I am able to understand all these areas.”
(Q2)

However, not all tasks were delegated to staff. Some core responsibilities were still handled by their bosses. Respondent A2 stressed that a number of things were still under the total control of his boss, though his boss divested some of his responsibilities as the business grew larger.

7.2.3.5 People management and development skills

Entrepreneurs

14 respondents shared the view that people management skills (in terms of understanding, developing people, and matching skills to tasks) had been vital to the success of their businesses. Many stressed that people skills are very important, especially in retail business. In particular, the respondents believed that leading by example was essential. This was reflected in the following remark made by respondent O:

“[As] for the staff, they had to look up to me...to be a leader; ...You have to lead by example. Once you are on the level of the people, there will be no issues - they will want to contribute to the success.” (O)

The respondents also identified staff training to be an important aspect of managing their employees. They developed their employees through a combination of training courses and tasks. This is summarised in the remark by respondent P, who believed that he should have invested even more in training his employees:

“I would have done more...people training; training of people and [creating] the [right corporate] culture will run because the main derivatives are the people you have. How focused are they? Because if all of us are moving in the same direction, the results will be faster, from the despatch man getting the drugs to the customer, to the person who is at the cash point, to the person who is purchasing, to the person who is on the floor, and to the pharmacists - if

they are all working together as a team that means they are focused on the same goal.” (P)

Employees

All the respondents (34) confirmed that their bosses were quite skilled in managing people - their bosses have ‘people skills’. Respondents C2 and O2 explained that their bosses get their workers to do the right things because they cannot do everything all by themselves. Furthermore, a key theme that arose while discussing people management and development was role modelling (see Appendix 7.3c). The respondents identified their bosses as being positive role models. They had learned a lot by observing and working with their bosses. This was reflected in the remark by respondent C1:

“Apart from her being my boss, she is a mother figure. Working with her, I have learnt a lot of things from her. I have learnt how to be independent, how to work effectively. I have learnt how to work smarter. Working under her has been wonderful...” (C1)

The respondents believed that the skills their employers possessed have “rubbed off” on them. Respondent H2 suggested that her boss is such a hard worker that she has no choice than to be hard working as well. Respondent A1 supported this view by suggesting that his boss saw himself as a servant; and so those working with him also perceived themselves as servants, and so they all served with much dedication and passion. Respondent A1 opined that all his colleagues wanted to be like his boss.

All the respondents (34) confirmed that their bosses were constantly involved in training staff. This was an important aspect in the way their bosses managed people. Respondent H1 mentioned that her boss firmly believed in sending staff members to local and international training courses. Respondent H2 (an employee in the same establishment) confirmed this, reiterating that they are constantly trained to world-class standards to ensure that they stand out in the industry. Respondent J2 reported that her boss has made her organisation a training field, and that she and her colleagues have developed talents they never knew they possessed.

7.2.3.6 Self-management skills

Entrepreneurs

Each respondent believed that the ability to manage themselves was an essential interpersonal skill for running their businesses successfully, and that self-management was vital for planning and organising, handling difficult situations, and critically reflecting on their own strengths and weaknesses.

These respondents said they had the ability to prioritise, work effectively, and manage their time well. Respondent O stated, “*I am an organised person and don’t like things [being] scattered.*” Respondent K shared her experience of how well organised she is, and emphasised that she could not achieve anything if she was not organised and did not schedule her time. Time was always short; hence, she always kept a to-do list. Respondent Q stated that for a business to succeed, one must invest ample time in it:

“I will still like to put most of my time into the pharmacy, which my other colleagues don’t do. They open a pharmacy and leave the pharmacy and start pursuing other things - either supply, or other things. Even if they feel they have customers, they don’t have time. They don’t know that it is that time they [must] use to understand the dynamics of the business; to know what is not in the pharmacy, to know the kind of things that customers are looking for. If you don’t put in full time you won’t be able to know all these things.” (Q)

In managing themselves, they were able to handle pressure. The respondents stated clearly that their ability to handle pressure was paramount to their success. They were able to keep calm and were not overwhelmed by any situation. Respondent E, for instance believes that such situations are expected; hence, she is calm about it. For respondent N, these challenges have to come so you must be ready to face them squarely.

In particular, the respondents stressed the importance of self-development. They showed a conscious effort to develop themselves either via formal training or by self-directed study (reading) (see Appendix 7.1g). The respondents were of the opinion that self-development, although important, does not come easily.

Respondent J stressed that the entrepreneur has a busy schedule, and that self-development comes at a price. For her, it involved reading during the early hours of the morning when other people are sleeping. Her experience is quoted below:

“I put value on how I develop on a daily basis, but an average person probably does not. A lot of entrepreneurs and executives...don't read in the afternoons; they read in the middle of the night - 2 o'clock and 3 o'clock - that is when you see them read. That is when they grow because you don't have time in the afternoon to read but you will see somebody say 'by the time I get home by 6 o'clock I am tired'. How do you want...to be successful? ...but if you want to grow, you pay the price.” (J)

Employees

The respondents were united in their view that their bosses were able to manage themselves effectively. To them, this was paramount to their boss' success. The respondents claimed that their bosses were organised, competent in handling difficult situations, and understood their own strengths and weaknesses.

The respondents confirmed that their bosses had the ability to prioritise and manage their businesses effectively. Respondent A1 elaborated on how he himself had become organised as a result of following the example of his boss. These respondents stressed that their bosses were involved in multiple tasks and were able to balance all of them effectively. Respondent H2 elaborated that her boss, despite being the CEO, is also a mother, sister and aunt, and has been able to handle all those roles perfectly. Respondent J2 claimed that her boss knows how to balance her life - her home, business, and religion – all of which have made her successful.

19 respondents stated clearly that their bosses handled pressure effectively and that this was paramount to their success. Their bosses were calm and not flustered by challenging situations. This is reflected in the following remark by respondent A2:

“He is not someone that is easily flustered. He is usually calm under pressure no matter what the situation is.” (A2)

These respondents shared the view that their bosses had undertaken their own professional development either via formal training or by reading. This is illustrated by respondent H1:

“Mrs H is very passionate about reading and improving [her] knowledge. So she has gone the extra mile of acquiring this needed knowledge. She just completed the US Fortune mentorship programme in America and she has buddied with Johnson and Johnson where her mentor was.” (H1)

12 employees confirmed that their bosses were aware of their own abilities, weaknesses, and strengths. Respondent H1 admitted that her boss was aware that she was impatient and has tried to modify her own behaviour:

“So I think she has her moments when she is not as patient as she would have liked to be. I know she keeps saying that - that is one area she knows that she needs to work on. Mrs H identifies her weak points and her limitations as it were and does everything she can to improve them.” (H1)

7.2.4 Entrepreneurial skills

Analysis of the transcripts revealed three key skills, which are grouped under the banner of entrepreneurial skills (Figure 17). These are:

- Opportunity identification skills
- Opportunity exploitation skills
- Risk management skills

Figure 17 Composition of entrepreneurial skills

Each is now set out in turn.

7.2.4.1 Opportunity identification skills

Entrepreneurs

All respondents (17) believed that the ability to identify opportunities was an important entrepreneurial skill. Respondent B recalled his experience of relocating for family reasons and later identifying an opportunity to start his business in his home country. Respondent A identified an opportunity to exploit, in that there was a scarcity of products to which only he had access; exploiting such opportunities has become a core part of his strategy. Respondent K emphasised the importance of business location, and that her ability to identify locations that provide a high foot-fall has been instrumental to her success.

For these respondents, their ability to identify opportunities has put them in the position that they were during the time of interview. This is reflected by respondent P's comment:

"...the ability to recognise opportunities and trends in the industry...if you are able to recognise the opportunity and the trend and you can have the discipline to draw a strategy to harness it, then that will help your position." (P)

Employees

13 respondents shared the view that their bosses had the ability to identify opportunities and believed this is an important entrepreneurial skill that was attributable to their success. Respondent H1 attributes the expansion of her workplace to the ability of her boss to recognise a gap in the market. Respondent A2's recollection was typical - his boss had been able to spot the opportunities in the industry because he was constantly educating himself:

“Being able to know where the industry is tending towards and what doctors will need even before they need them. You will need to be someone who is constantly updating your knowledge. You can't just be in the same place and be seeing the future. Obviously you need to understand what the trends are, the direction the industry is going [in], and what people will...need even before they realise that they need it. So that will be a very important one or attribute to him.” (A2)

7.2.4.2 Opportunity exploitation skills

Entrepreneurs

In addition to opportunity identification, opportunity exploitation was identified as another key skill. Some opportunities arise by sheer providence, so the ability to exploit them is another key reason for an entrepreneur's success. This is illustrated in the comment by Respondent B:

“Though I came back home due to family issues, I saw an opportunity available, and decided to open a shop since it's what I have always wanted to do.” (B)

Respondents, such as Q and M, expanded the number of their outlets in order to fill a gap they had identified. Respondent M opened a branch in an emerging market, believing that *“it is a good place to be”*. For respondent Q, the number of outlets was increased to meet the demands of customers *“coming from far and wide”*.

Respondents A and I recounted their experiences about how they were able to exploit the opportunity of selling products at great profit whose shelf life was close to expiry. According to respondent I, “*you have to open your eyes*” to these opportunities. Respondent C stressed the importance of opportunity identification and exploitation. She stressed that her success cannot be attributed solely to hard work; rather, it had been the result of exploiting opportunities:

“...You could be working hard [and gaining] nothing...reaching out to seize the opportunities around you is the most important thing. So I don’t see myself as...I work hard in it but I didn’t work hard to earn the locations. Once I found myself, I took up the challenge... [it’s] not the other way round.” (C)

Employees

Just like the entrepreneurs, the employees agreed that their bosses have the ability to exploit recognised opportunities. Sometimes these opportunities were not new in the market, but their bosses were always quick to exploit them. Respondent A2 stressed that,

“There are none of these products [in this pharmacy] that are new. They have been in the market, whether it is oncology or fertility products, for years. But we are usually one of the first companies to register [on the] market and work hard at pushing these drugs. So much so that it shows the potential in some of these markets, [in] that other people in some cases have come and focused in one particular thing and will probably have a larger market share than us.” (A2)

According to respondent Q2, opportunity exploitation can be linked with envisioning skills. Her boss identified opportunities and tuned into them because he had a vision of what he wanted for the business.

7.2.4.3 Risk management skills

Entrepreneurs

A key skill identified by all respondents (17) was the management of risk, both in establishing their businesses, and in subsequent management and development. The respondents believed that they had the ability to manage the risks they encountered in their businesses. It is worth noting that risk is managed by being analytical and calculative. From analyses of the transcripts, a link between risk management and analytical skills was found. By managing risks effectively, they were able to save their resources and their time. This is reflected in the following comment below:

“I don’t want a situation [where] I will just lose woefully. I still have to consider and balance up before I take the risk.” (F)

In managing risks, respondents first identified the potential loss that could occur - the ‘downside’ risk. Thereafter, they considered the probability of such a loss and how it could be minimised. As mentioned by Respondent O,

“I’m a realist. I don’t like fantasises. If I want to dive into something, I make sure I get it right. I have had an opportunity of drug importation; many of my friends are doing it, they go to India, import drugs, register with NAFDAC and sell – some of them are drug dealers. It’s not something I want to do now.” (O)

However, though respondents were sensitive to risks, they were not risk averse. Rather, they always thought of ways to mitigate risks, and they estimated its impact on the financial position of their companies. This is reflected in the comment by respondent E:

“You must be able to find out what the end result might be, inasmuch [as] it might not be to your expectation, but you plan around it, and [if there] is some part you might lose, you may try and amend [that] part that may lead to loss... so that at least it won’t be total fallout.” (E)

Employees

All the respondents (34) shared a similar view that their bosses were able to take and manage risks effectively. Respondent D2 stated that there are risks involved, but it all depends on how the boss is able to manage them. This was further reflected in the comment by respondent A2:

“Part of the risk, especially with pharmaceutical products, is that it backfires spectacularly. We have taken so many hits that sometimes bigger companies would not have been able to recover so quickly or so well... Being able to handle all of that when things are not going well; maintaining composure, still being the team leader, still pushing people to achieve what they set out to achieve even when things are not going very well...those are the attributes I think sets him apart.” (A2)

The respondents agreed that their bosses managed risks by being analytical and calculative; they took calculated risks. Respondent H1 stated that her boss took bold, audacious, even scary risks, but it was always calculated. Respondent O1 observed that before his boss took a risk, he always considered the dangers and if the likely implications were great, he would not take the risk. His boss always tried to ensure that the risk is minimal.

The next section contains an examination of the data which serves to address the second research question concerning the challenges that entrepreneurial leaders in a developing economy face in running their business.

7.3 Challenges faced by entrepreneurial leaders in the context of a developing economy

This study was performed not only to identify the entrepreneurial leadership skills, but also to identify the challenges that entrepreneurial leaders in a developing

economy face in running their businesses. This is consistent with the following research objectives mentioned back in Chapter 1:

- Research Objective 2: to understand the lived experience of entrepreneurs in a developing economy, namely Nigeria.
- Research Objective 4: to consider the role of entrepreneurial leadership skills in addressing the challenges faced by entrepreneurs in a developing economy.

It is also consistent with research question 2:

- What are the challenges that entrepreneurs in a developing economy face in running their businesses?

In seeking to answer the research question and fulfil the objectives, both entrepreneurs and their employees were asked about the challenges they faced in running a business in their environment.

Four key challenges emerged from the analysis of the data, namely challenges within the industry, government and corruption, infrastructural deficit, and technology deficit. The following section sets out these challenges with reference to the interview transcripts.

7.3.1 Challenges within the industry

All respondents (17 entrepreneurs and 34 employees) highlighted specific contextual challenges as being one of the major issues affecting their business in a developing economy. These challenges include problems with drug distribution, and fake and substandard drugs.

7.3.1.1 Drug distribution

15 entrepreneurs and 28 employees cited problems with drug distribution and availability. According to them, the drug distribution logistics in the country is chaotic, and most people turn to the open market rather than the retail pharmacies. The respondents believed that hospitals have made matters worse by dispensing drugs and assuming the role of pharmacies. According to respondent Q,

“The general challenge - you talk of [the] open drug market or chaotic drug distribution system in Nigeria. Most of the time people go to the open market to buy drugs. When we first started you don’t have many wholesale outlets run by pharmacists in the streets, so you just had to go to Idumota to buy.” (Q)

7.3.1.2 Fake and substandard drugs

17 entrepreneurs and 30 employees were unified in the view that fake and substandard drugs pose a major challenge for the Nigerian retail pharmacy industry. Respondent A1 suggested that the problem is so complex that he cannot proffer a nomenclature:

“I think there is no one problem; there is no one name to give it; but you can lump a bunch of things together which will be fake and adulterated products [from] the parallel importers. I will just say [that] the unethical business people...have found their way into the pharmaceutical industry.” (A1)

Respondent M stressed that she had heard that there are drug stores where the expiry dates of pharmaceuticals have been changed. Respondent I1 mentioned that fake and substandard drugs are so widespread that customers have become distrustful; even Respondent I1 felt confused at times.

The respondents agreed that although fake and substandard drugs pose a challenge to the industry, they themselves would not meddle into such practice because of their integrity. This is summarised by respondent D’s comment below:

“I will not for any reason sell a drug that is expired or fake. That has been my guiding principle.” (D)

7.3.2 Government and corruption

All the respondents (51) identified the government as an important factor behind the challenges they face in running/working for their businesses. They identified corruption as a major challenge faced in the context of the developing economy of Nigeria. This is emphasised by Respondent J1:

“Corruption is also a factor because you need to bribe your way in, in some certain areas to bring in stuffs [products]”. (J1)

They perceived the country itself as being corrupt and encouraging dishonest behaviour (see Appendix 7.2a). The entrepreneurs in this study believed that inconsistent government policies and shifts have negatively affected them. Respondents A and D stressed that policies change easily. One complaint among them was that, after investing financially in improving their infrastructure in one direction, the government would suddenly change its policies. These policy inconsistencies have negatively affected their businesses and are a major issue.

In addition, respondent M stressed that the legal system is ineffective. For her, the problem was not merely government policies, but a failure of the whole legal system. The courts are ineffective; hence, sometimes she ended up paying extortionate fees charged by the government agencies. In her opinion, the governing bodies are impotent in upholding the law and protecting the interests of ordinary citizens.

Six respondents focused on the heavy taxes collected by the Nigerian government. Respondents A1 and O highlighted that the government’s heavy taxes on their businesses affected their capital base. As well as discussing the government from a broad perspective, 15 respondents mentioned that the regulatory bodies established by the government were also ineffective. They believed that if these regulatory bodies were more functional, there would be fewer problems concerning the quality of medication and sales. Respondent A, stressed that the regulatory authorities were

unable to enforce laws, and respondent Q2 believed that the agencies' inability to act has led to an increase in the number of charlatans in the sector.

7.3.3 Infrastructural deficits

Poor infrastructure was identified by the respondents as one of the problems they faced in running their businesses. The respondents highlighted bad roads as one of the infrastructural problems (see Appendix 7.2b). Bad roads had affected their customer loyalty by making their outlets inaccessible as a result of traffic.

Inconsistent power supply was identified by both entrepreneurs and their employees as another major infrastructural challenge. Respondent A1 referred to this as a continual problem which is not peculiar to the retail pharmacy sector, but which affects all businesses in Nigeria. For respondent P, power cuts are an Achilles hill in every industry, and respondent B1 believed that the government is to blame. All the respondents (51) felt that the businesses would be more profitable if there were no power generation issues. According to Respondent I,

“The power...I spend so much money in running the generators. If you see, at the end of the day, what really takes most of the expenses is it. When I usually do my analysis at the end of the month, there is a group I belong to and we submit our monthly expenses. I find out that the cost of running the generator and all that is high.” (I)

Respondent A1 believed that the cost of products would be cheaper for his clients if massive capital was not ploughed back into power generation. He explained that a large portion of the business' monthly profits went towards fuelling diesel generators.

However, these entrepreneurs have realised that in order to succeed, it is inevitable that they have to spend a sizable portion of their income on infrastructure. The nature of the business permits no room for lapse in terms of stock maintenance and customer satisfaction.

7.3.4 Technology deficit

The respondents identified the use and availability of technology as another challenge they faced in running pharmacy businesses in their country. The latest technologies were not readily available in the country, and importing such technology had high cost implications. The respondents were not used to technology but with the changes occurring in the industry worldwide, they knew it was essential. This is summarised in the comment by respondent O2, who explained how she struggled with technology:

“The challenges are also for now moving from one phase to another. It is just like moving from manual to digital. Before, we weren’t always using technology like that. Like before you came in we had a problem with the POS. Someone claimed they paid and they debited the person without indicating to us. So it is all those technical issues.” (O2)

The next section is an examination of the data which emerged during the course of this study on entrepreneurial leadership.

7.4 Other emerging themes

The purpose of this study was to identify the skills of and the challenges confronting entrepreneurial leaders in the context of a developing economy. However, during the course of the study, some important themes emerged. The respondents highlighted the following variables as important determining factors behind their success. These themes include attributes, culture, family, resources, management experience, and followers, all of which are discussed in this section.

7.4.1 Attributes

While a range of attributes were discussed by the respondents such as creativity, determination, attention to detail and so on, however in the context of Nigeria one key personal attribute stood out which was spirituality. This personal attribute is discussed below.

7.4.1.1 Spirituality

Spirituality was a recurring theme in the study; these respondents (entrepreneurs) were religious and believed in God. They attributed their decision making and success to God. This is reflected in the comment by respondent A2 about his boss:

“I will define him first and foremost as a child of God. You can look at everything [in] regards to him through that lens and you won’t be too far off. His decision making, leadership, and many of the qualities that define him can be traced to his Christian background.” (A2)

12 entrepreneurs claimed that their success was not a result solely of their efforts, but also of a “God factor”. Respondent K stressed that one can only succeed in the retail pharmacy business with God’s help, and she believed most of her ‘big breaks’ had not merely been the fruits of her own efforts.

7.4.2 Culture

National culture was another emerging theme in the study. The respondents were generally concerned about and were sensitive towards the needs of others. Usually their concern for family and friends was greater than that for themselves. In addition, when the respondents were asked about the challenges they faced, some of their stories reflected the impact of the Nigerian culture, which has made them tough and forceful. Respondent M bemoaned the administrative corruption in the country:

“The thing is that the pace in Nigeria is different. Like when you want to register, and all the human factors. We have a lot of Nigerian factors. There are some things I had to hand over to my husband to handle - getting the license, the inspection, and all. You need some documentation. They tell you that the receipt is not available, the receipt is finished. They have to [go] to Abuja to get it. They request from Abuja and [find out that] the director’s mother or wife died. So with all these things, you are waiting and you have your space. You have money that is going, things that are fixed, and there is nothing you can do about it. You can’t open except [when] they give you the go-ahead and all this is tied to a receipt that has not been issued. So those were the initial challenges for me. I was like, ‘What is this? So what, if something happens to somebody does it mean everything stops? That is not how it should be.’ I allowed my husband who is a real Nigerian to handle it.”
(M)

7.4.3 Family

Family dynamics was mentioned by respondents when discussing entrepreneurial leadership. 13 entrepreneurs developed the skills to start their business as a result of their family background. Respondent C explained that her mother was an entrepreneur and was instrumental in helping her discover her own entrepreneurial skills. For respondent D, the most important education that has influenced his entrepreneurial leadership is from his father:

“The best informal education I ever had is that I grew up with my father who was a trader. I will use the word ‘trader’ because he is into trading. He is a stenographer but he happened to open a bookshop and a stationery outfit that to an extent cultivated my habit for reading. I learnt day-to-day business activities from him. It’s an informal education but for the years I spent with him during my primary and secondary school, it was more like after school you go there to work. [During my] primary, secondary and even university [education]...when we were on holiday we go there to work.” (D)

As well as on their decisions to start and run a business, their family background also impacted on their decision making. The respondents mentioned that their families were understanding and contributed towards their businesses. Respondent K explained that she felt blessed to have a good husband who complemented her and who ran most of the activities. Her husband brought in his expertise by making branding a priority for the business. For her, an understanding and knowledgeable partner was vital to her success.

Due to the impact of family in their affairs, the respondents agreed that family was always a priority. They did not run the business at the expense of their families. Respondent J stressed that her family was more important than her business, and that she would rather sacrifice her income than default in her family values and tasks (e.g. collecting her children from school).

7.4.4 Resources

Resources were identified by the respondents as another important factor when discussing the challenges they faced in running their businesses. The respondents identified financial resources as a major constraint and a major determining factor of success. Without finance, no matter what one's entrepreneurial leadership skills, running the business would simply be impossible. This view was articulated in a comment by respondent A1:

“Then finance - to finance, even to start in a good ground, you must have a back bone and that is finance...you know the banks are there to use your shovel to take part of you. The tax, the government here tax you heavily and this affects your capital base, and if you are not buoyant enough you cannot go forward and you can't even have good staff anyway.” (A1)

The need for the right human resources was also identified as a critical factor. Respondent H1 emphasised on the need to hire appropriately skilled people when running a retail pharmacy business. For her, this was not an easy task.

7.4.5 Management Experience

The respondents recognised the management experience of the entrepreneurs as another important factor that influences entrepreneurial leadership. They identified experience as being important to the success of their businesses. 13 entrepreneurs had gained a vast experience in the field and as a result, they had formed strong and lasting relationships. Respondent A2 articulated this in his comment about his boss:

“He has over 30 years’ experience in the pharmaceutical industry and he has been working with pharmacists, doctors, and all our medical professionals for many years, and I think the strength of his own reputation and his friendship with many of them has helped to open doors for the company in some of the pharmacies, hospitals, and other places that we supply, and we give him credit for that as well.” (A2)

For respondent K, the importance of experience cannot be underestimated, and was key to her success. Her experience in the corporate world and retail pharmacy industry had prepared her for the business. She shared the opinion that without such prior experience, the pharmacy entrepreneur will struggle in the market. However, not all the interviewed entrepreneurs possessed a vast experience and those who did not agreed that a wealth of experience is indeed essential. Respondent G believed that if she had more experience (especially in form of apprenticeships), she would not have made the mistakes of over-stocking, which resulted in a high number of expired products.

7.4.6 Followers

The dedication and empowerment of their followers was recognised by the respondents (entrepreneurs) as an important factor that influenced their entrepreneurial leadership. When the respondents were asked about their leadership, their stories reflected the importance of their followers. According to respondent J,

“You can’t do it only by yourself. You need people around you. That’s one of the things that actually contribute to success - the people around you. I think if you have a fantastic person around you that’s it. I think we have some good people around us that makes it also easier because it’s not that one person runs the show, no! It is a team.” (J)

For them, their followers’ susceptibility to their entrepreneurial leadership is important. Respondent Q emphasised that only people who buy into the culture of the organisation are required. For him, structures, systems, and processes have to be in place for those people that believe in the culture of the organisation. He believed that, without an organisational culture and the right set of people, one cannot build a successful business.

These respondents agreed that employee empowerment was an important factor that influenced their entrepreneurial leadership. Respondent C believed that empowering people brings out the best in them and so she allowed them to work freely. However, although they empowered their followers, they did not relinquish total control to them. This view was reflected by both the entrepreneurs and employees. Respondent C stressed that checks and controls were always in place, while respondent M2 stated that employees rarely made the major decisions.

7.5 Conclusion

In this chapter, the findings from the face-to-face interviews with the 17 entrepreneurs and 34 employees in the retail pharmacy sector of a developing economy (in Nigeria) were presented. The data presented has provided answers to the research questions. In this chapter, the issues examined were as follows:

- The entrepreneurial leadership skills required for success in a developing economy.
- The challenges that the entrepreneurial leaders face when running their businesses in a developing economy context.

- The perception of the entrepreneurial leadership skills of the entrepreneurs by their employees.

The collected data has shown the entrepreneurial leadership skills, which the respondents believed enabled them to run their businesses effectively. Identified entrepreneurial leadership skills include technical/business skills, conceptual skills, interpersonal skills, and entrepreneurial skills. The perception of the entrepreneurial leadership skills of the entrepreneurs by their employees was examined and confirmed in the interviews.

During the interviews, the challenges that the entrepreneurial leaders faced in running their retail pharmacy businesses in a developing economy were also explored. They included challenges within the industry, government and corruption, infrastructural deficit, and technology deficit.

Finally, other themes emerged during the interviews that were not specifically relevant to the research questions. The importance of attributes, culture, family, resources, management experience, and followers was also discussed by the respondents.

CHAPTER EIGHT - DISCUSSION

8.1 Introduction

In this chapter, the findings of this study are analysed and synthesised in a sequence of inter-linked discussions. By drawing insights from literature, the findings are reviewed and discussed, and an empirical model of entrepreneurial leadership within the context of a developing economy is proposed. This empirical model is forged on a more advanced understanding of entrepreneurial leadership, whereby the skills necessary for success in this context are identified.

The chapter begins with a description of the empirical model of entrepreneurial leadership, which is structured in accordance with the results obtained from the interviews. The model is then critically described with reference to the theoretical insights provided in the literature review chapters. Finally, this chapter is concluded with an explanation of entrepreneurial leadership, and a new definition for entrepreneurial leadership, in answer to the first research question, based on the data obtained during the study.

8.2 An empirical model of entrepreneurial leadership

As reflected by the evidence in the systematic literature review (Chapter 5), entrepreneurial leadership is a diverse concept that influences several aspects of the performance of an organisation. However, this concept has received little focused attention and empirical development. Using the findings of this study, these gaps can be addressed through the creation of an empirical model on entrepreneurial leadership. The resulting model specifies the skills that influence entrepreneurial leadership within the context of a developing economy. It provides a representation of the interaction of the entrepreneurs and the environment in which they operate. A

model is a way of representing a phenomenon and is widely used in management research (Krishnaswamy et al., 2009). It is a representation of the real world and a useful tool for thinking (Pidd, 1999). Models can provide key insights through "...demonstrating the understanding of relationships within a phenomenon or several aspects of the phenomenon and most importantly for predicting the future performance of the phenomenon" (Krishnaswamy et al., 2009, p. 193). The domain of entrepreneurial leadership currently lacks a model that explores the phenomenon from a skill-based perspective. An empirically-based model will provide insights into the relationship between skills and other variables required for entrepreneurial leadership.

However, a model should not be expected to do anything for which it was not intended (Morris, 1967); hence, the purpose of the model is to specify the entrepreneurial leadership skills required in order to succeed in the context of a developing economy. According to Pidd (1999), a model is a useful tool, especially when researchers try to understand a complex system. Entrepreneurial leadership is complex; therefore, a model is required so that analysts have a better understanding of this phenomenon in the real world.

The model is the first of its kind within the domain of entrepreneurial leadership, and is built upon the previously published work of Katz (1974) on business leadership (refer back to Figure 2 in the literature review and Figure 18 for the Katz framework). The developed model identifies the causal conditions⁵ for entrepreneurial leadership and the wider implications of the phenomenon. Furthermore, it shows the influencing conditions of this phenomenon. Conditions such as resources, followers, culture, family dynamics, attributes, and experience were identified as important factors that influence entrepreneurial leadership.

The model identifies the key entrepreneurial leadership skills from the perspectives of both entrepreneurial leaders and their followers: technical/business skills, conceptual skills, interpersonal skills, and entrepreneurial skills. These skills were identified as being important for successful business creation, commercialisation, and management by entrepreneurial leaders. In a dynamic, complex, and uncertain

⁵ Causal conditions refer to the factors that lead to the occurrence of the phenomenon, the subject under study, or the central idea (Brown et al., 2002, p. 5)

competitive environment, an entrepreneurial leader who is distinct from other types of leaders is required. Such leadership is essential when there is high competition for limited resources, and organisations have to be resource-dependent in order to avoid maturity and decline (Santora et al., 1999). In a developing economy, this is even more important because there is high competition for scarce resources; hence, organisations must be more entrepreneurial; their performance, and their capacity for adaptation and long-term survival must be enhanced (Gupta et al., 2004). Organisational structures and strategies that are effective in stable markets constrain wealth creation in more dynamic settings (Tarabishy et al., 2002). Thus, a new type of leader who can operate in such conditions is required.

Figure 18 Katz's conception of leadership

Source: Katz (1955; 1974)

8.3 Presentation of the entrepreneurial leadership model

As noted earlier, the entrepreneurial leadership model derived from the research findings reported in this thesis builds on the works of Katz (Katz, 1955; 1974), which have been subsequently refined through a series of studies by mainstream leadership scholars (including Lord and Hall, 2005; Mumford et al., 2000a to 2000c; Mumford et al., 2007). The model is an empirical construct based on the findings

from this study, and it serves as a foundation for understanding and developing entrepreneurial leadership. It specifies the different variables for entrepreneurial leadership, and how they influence each other directly or indirectly. The model is presented diagrammatically in Figure 19.

In modelling entrepreneurial leadership, the approach of Strauss and Corbin (1998) and Russell and Stone (2002) was adopted. Although this approach is originally based on grounded theory, it has been used extensively in studies based on thematic analysis (Edwards and Lopez, 2006; Germann and Wilson, 2004). In line with the thinking of Strauss and Corbin (1998) and of Russell and Stone (2002) on modelling, causal conditions constitute the starting node of this model. These are the conditions that affect the manifestation of entrepreneurial leadership skills, and they comprise opportunities and challenges faced by these individuals. The second node represents the contextual conditions, which in this study is a developing economy. The last node represents the intervening conditions. Intervening variables such as attributes, family dynamics, culture, followers, resources, and experience may influence entrepreneurial leadership skills. They have a moderating effect on entrepreneurial leadership and hence have an effect on the outcome. The loop emanating from the nodes of the causal conditions and intervening conditions within the developing economy context shows that both variables are influenced by the nature of the context. Similarly, the developing economy context will also affect entrepreneurial leadership skills.

Entrepreneurial leadership skills are descriptors of the dependent variable, which in turn is entrepreneurial leadership. They determine the form and effectiveness of entrepreneurial leadership. The model sets out four entrepreneurial leadership skills, as derived from the analysis of the interview data. The data analysis enables each of these categories to be broken down into its component parts (see Figure 20). The research reported in this thesis included identification of a fourth skill area, namely entrepreneurial skills. This skill area comprises three skills: technical, human, and conceptual skills (see Figure 18). These four skills serve as the manifestation of the entrepreneurial leadership style by the entrepreneurs, and so entrepreneurial leadership is dependent on these skills. Consequently, entrepreneurial leadership itself ultimately becomes an independent variable that affects the consequent dependent variable, which in turn is successful business creation, commercialisation,

and management. It has been shown from the findings in this study that the manifestation of entrepreneurial leadership leads to positive outcomes and success in terms of creating, commercialising, and effectively managing the business. Finally, the output of a successful business enterprise results (see Figure 19).

Figure 19 Entrepreneurial leadership model

Figure 20 Detailed representation of the entrepreneurial leadership model

8.3.1 Developing economy context

According to Strauss and Corbin (1998, p. 132), contextual conditions are the “...specific set of conditions (patterns of conditions) that intersect dimensionally at this time and place to create a set of circumstances or problems to which persons respond through actions/interactions”. The context of this study is a developing economy, namely Nigeria, with the retail pharmacy sector being used as a proxy. The skill-based empirical model for entrepreneurial leadership is unique to this context, but it draws more general conclusions with wider applications. The nature of the context determines the causal and intervening conditions that influence the entrepreneurial leadership skill set.

8.3.2 Causal conditions

In this sub-section, the conditions that influence entrepreneurial leadership (but which are dependent on the nature of the environment) are discussed. The conditions identified from the respondents’ answers include challenges and opportunities:

8.3.2.1 Challenges

The focus of this study was on entrepreneurial leadership within the context of a developing economy. This extended beyond required skills, and encompassed the challenges that entrepreneurial leaders face when running their businesses in a developing economy. The challenges that the interviewed respondents in this study faced are important factors that influence entrepreneurial leadership. This is also reflected by evidence from the literature review. Renko et al. (2012b) studied entrepreneurial leadership in family businesses, and concluded that challenges such as succession, conflicts, and employee empowerment influence entrepreneurial leadership. According to Renko et al. (2012a), economic, societal, managerial

challenges, and recent changes to the business environment are also major influences. Following the evidence of the respondents (as shown back in section 7.3), the ability to combat these challenges is a key requirement of entrepreneurial leaders. These challenges include challenges within the industry, government and corruption, infrastructural deficit, and technology deficit.

Challenges within the industry concern specific issues that are unique to the business sector. In this case, they include drug distribution (logistic problems), and fake and substandard drugs. Government and corruption issues include inconsistencies in government policy, dishonesty, and ineffective legal and regulatory systems. Infrastructural deficits reported in this study included bad roads and an unreliable power supply. In addition, technology deficits in Nigerian pharmacies are a growing problem due to globalisation. Each of these areas is now discussed in turn:

Challenges within the industry

The respondents recognised challenges that are specific to the retail pharmacy industry as being one of the major issues they faced in running a business in a developing economy. The retail industry in Nigeria has grown rapidly, especially when the country's historical dependence on the oil sector is diminishing. The retail industry grew by 10.76% in the fourth quarter of 2012, and has been more attractive compared with previous years. Likewise, the retail pharmacy industry (which is the focus of this research) has continued to expand. This is seen with the number of registered pharmacists in the country totalling 16,052 (Pharmacists Council of Nigeria, 2013). The retail pharmacy industry has become an invaluable source of health care. However, retail pharmacy entrepreneurs are now faced with more challenges due to the rapid change and growth in this sector (Erah, 2003).

Respondents reiterated that the drug distribution system in the country is chaotic, with most people sourcing drugs from the open market. This confirms the findings in wider literature about the chaotic distribution network in Nigeria. According to Erhun et al. (2001, p. 24), "The drug distribution network in Nigeria is in a state of chaos, because it consists of open markets, patent medicine stores, community

pharmacies, private and public hospitals, wholesalers/importers, and pharmaceutical manufacturers.”

Finally, problems with the distribution network have been exacerbated by problems of fake and substandard drugs, which have resulted in customers not experiencing the desired outcome. This finding from the interviews supports the view of Erhun et al. (2001), who identified the problem of counterfeit drugs in Nigeria as being real and capable of undermining the health care delivery efforts of the government.

Government policy inconsistencies and corruption

The respondents identified government policy inconsistencies and corruption as major problems that they face when running a business in a developing economy context. The respondents perceived the government as corrupt or inefficient. This is not surprising, judging by past research (Kiggundu, 2002; Nkechi et al., 2012; Okpara, 2011; Pop, 2002), in which corruption was found to pose a major challenge to aspiring entrepreneurs in Africa. Moreover, Transparency International (2014) has identified Nigeria as one of the most corrupt nations in the world.

The respondents shared the view that inconsistent government policies and shifts have been detrimental to their business. This supports the research by Nkechi et al. (2012, p. 98), “...that some government policies it seems are made to favour friends and associates”. The respondents believed that the corrupt nature of the government has fostered an inefficient legal system. This supports the findings of Okpara (2011, p. 160), who reported that corruption affects “...the legal framework and national integrity” of a developing country such as Nigeria.

15 respondents attributed corruption not only to the government but also to the regulatory authorities. They claimed that the regulatory bodies are corrupt, ineffective, and cannot enforce the law, and that their inadequacies have led to an increase in the number of charlatans in the pharmacy sector. This is in line with the claim by Kiggundu (2002) that African businesses are faced with bribery, dishonesty, and other illegal business activities. Literature specific to retail pharmacy also confirms this view that regulations, licensing, and registration of pharmacies are

grossly inadequate in low-income countries (Lowe and Montagu, 2009). As highlighted by Erhun et al. (2001), corruption is one of the contributing factors to the availability of counterfeit drugs, and the level of corruption among officials of these regulatory bodies is also a determining factor.

Infrastructural deficit

All respondents (17 entrepreneurs and 34 employees) shared the view that poor infrastructure was one of the problems they faced when running their businesses. Infrastructural deficits included poor roads and episodic power supply, both of which were believed to be detrimental to their businesses.

The findings support evidence provided in literature about the negative link between poor infrastructure, and small business success and growth (Mambula, 2002; Okpara, 2011; Tushabomwe-Kazooba, 2006). The findings also support the stance of Nkechi et al. (2012) who identified the power sector as the greatest challenge of any aspiring entrepreneur in Nigeria. For her, “The cost of an alternative source of power most often erodes whatever profit or capital an entrepreneur has put aside for his enterprise” (p. 96). The entrepreneurs in the study, in their efforts to succeed, spend a sizable portion of their income on infrastructure, and this adds significantly to their overhead costs (a problem identified by Nkechi et al. (2012)).

Technology deficit

The respondents acknowledged the use and availability of technology as one of the challenges they faced when running a business in a developing economy. The best technologies were not readily available and individuals were not adept in their use. However, with the growing impact of technological innovations and globalisation, new technology and adeptness in its use has become important. In this “...ever-changing world of technology, the need for appropriate skills and competencies to take advantage of ICTs for business benefit is constant” (Galloway, 2007, p. 643).

The views of the respondents support the findings of Nkechi et al. (2012), who observed that ICT is not widely available in all regions in Nigeria. As outlined by Okpara (2011), the inability to use or acquire technology is one of the factors that impact small business development in Africa. Indeed, technology is an exogenous constraint to small businesses in Sub-Saharan Africa (Okpara and Wynn, 2007).

8.3.2.2 Opportunities

The analysis of the interview data revealed that opportunities are a key variable in entrepreneurial leadership. ‘Opportunity’ was a recurring theme among the respondents and is a major contributing factor for entrepreneurial leadership. Entrepreneurial leadership, as defined by the respondents, involved mainly seeking, creating, recognising, and exploiting opportunities. It is not surprising that the ability to recognise and exploit opportunities was one of the key entrepreneurial leadership skills identified by the respondents. The focus on entrepreneurial opportunities is not new, and the findings confirm those in literature, especially among scholars in the field (e.g. Gupta et al., 2004; Kuratko, 2007). This is seen in the definitions of entrepreneurial leadership. For example, Renko et al. (2012b, p. 2) define entrepreneurial leadership as “...influencing and directing the performance of group members toward the achievement of organizational goals that involve recognizing and exploiting entrepreneurial opportunities”. This view was expressed by the respondents, who believed that opportunity identification and exploitation is important especially for influencing the group and ensuring success. According to Carpenter (2012, p. 22), it is “...the ability to envisage, find, seize, and exploit opportunities”. It involves responding to opportunities (Darling et al., 2007a) which could be new (Greenberg et al., 2013) or existing (Renko et al., 2012b). The respondents were apt in identifying and exploiting opportunities in their business environment. In fact, without opportunities, there can be no entrepreneurial leadership (as suggested by some of the respondents); this is in line with the definition of Hejazi et al. (2012, p. 71):

“Entrepreneurial leadership is known as the dynamic process of presenting vision, making commitment among followers, and risk acceptance when facing opportunities that cause efficient use of available resources, along with discovering and utilizing new resources with respect to the leader’s vision.”

8.3.3 Intervening conditions

Intervening conditions refer to a broad host of factors that can bear down upon the phenomena under consideration (Hage, 2007). These are conditions that “...mitigate or otherwise impact causal conditions on phenomena” (Strauss and Corbin, 1998, p. 131). Conditions that shape and facilitate entrepreneurial leadership were identified during the interviews. These include attributes, culture, family, resources, experience, and followers, and they are discussed below:

8.3.3.1 Attributes

This study concerns the identification of entrepreneurial leadership skills. However, the findings from the interviews showed that most of the entrepreneurial leaders also linked their success to personal characteristics or attributes. For this study, attributes are defined in line with the definition by Russell and Stone (2002, p. 146), as “...operative qualities, characteristics and distinctive features belonging to leaders and observed through specific leader behaviours in the workplace”. The key attribute identified during the interviews was spirituality.

Spirituality

Spirituality was a recurring theme in the interviews. The entrepreneurial leaders partly attributed their success and decision making to a supernatural being. They were religious and believed that there was a “God factor”. For these respondents,

some of the opportunities they had exploited were not through their abilities or efforts but as a result of their strong religious beliefs. There is little evidence from literature about the effect of spirituality in entrepreneurial leadership. However, findings from this study confirm the view of Sundararajan et al. (2012), who examined the role of meditative foundation on entrepreneurial leadership and new venture success. According to Sundararajan et al., the spiritual dimension might help solve the problem of high rate of start-up failures. However, there is no evidence from the interviews to confirm this. Many of the interviewed entrepreneurs believed that they had to be religious in order to succeed in business. Evidently, religious life and background had a part to play in their success; hence, could be examined in more detail in future studies.

8.3.3.2 Culture

Although it is not the main focus of this study, the role of culture was cited by respondents when asked about the challenges they face as entrepreneurial leaders in Nigeria. Culture is “...the learned belief, values, rules, norms, symbols, and traditions that are common to a group of people” (Northouse, 2010, p. 336). Culture is hard to change, and it influences all aspects of an organisation (Schein, 2010). There is little doubt that culture can play an important role in entrepreneurial leadership. The findings from the respondents confirm the view of Wang et al. (2012) who examined entrepreneurial leadership in the context of two Chinese firms, and identified multi-level factors such as philosophical traditions and cultural values as being influential in defining this phenomenon.

There has been little examination of the influence of national culture in entrepreneurial leadership. Gupta et al. (2004) used Hofstede’s cultural dimensions in establishing the prediction validity of their empirical model, but failed to examine clearly the role of culture in entrepreneurial leadership. Cultural understanding is essential to entrepreneurs if they are to lead. Future research should examine the impact of culture on entrepreneurial leadership in more detail.

8.3.3.3 Family

The respondents identified family dynamics when discussing entrepreneurial leadership. These entrepreneurs believed that their entrepreneurial leadership skills could be attributed in part to their family backgrounds. This finding supports the work of Kansikas et al. (2012) and Karanian (2007) on entrepreneurial leadership. These scholars support the positive relationship of ‘familiness’ and entrepreneurial leadership. They also suggest that family and cultural background is a driving force for the entrepreneurial leader.

8.3.3.4 Resources

The availability of resources in an organisation was identified from the analysis of the data as an intervening condition for the success of entrepreneurial leadership. The respondents discussed resources in terms of financial and human resources. Without adequate finance and suitably talented personnel, irrespective of entrepreneurial leadership skills, it may not be possible to run a retail pharmacy business. This supports the view of Renko et al. (2012b, p. 14), who linked resources to successful entrepreneurial leadership, and stated that “...in absence of such investments, entrepreneurial leadership will struggle to achieve its goals of opportunity recognition and exploitation”. The findings of this study also support the view of Kuratko and Hornsby (1999), in that resource availability for innovative activities is one of the organisational dimensions that make entrepreneurial leadership effective.

However, there is some contrary evidence from literature about the role of resources. Tice (2005, p. 551) state that entrepreneurial leadership involves “...bringing together a unique package of resources to exploit an opportunity without regard to resources controlled”. In most cited studies, the perceived role of an entrepreneurial leader is to efficiently acquire and mobilise the limited resources (Chen, 2007; Gupta et al., 2004; Hejazi et al., 2012; Pashiardis and Savvides , 2011; Santora et al., 1999), which is based on entrepreneurial leadership qualities (Hanson and Monsted, 2008).

Findings from the interviews support the notion that availability of resources is an influencing factor for successful entrepreneurial leadership.

8.3.3.5 Management Experience

The respondents, both entrepreneurs and employees, recognised that management experience of the entrepreneurs was key to the success of a business. This corresponds with the findings from literature (Lussier, 1996; Mahadea, 1996; Murphy, 1996) that lack of management experience often makes it difficult for SMEs to succeed. The findings of the interviews also support the work of Tushabomwe-Kazooba (2006) and Okpara (2011), in that lack of management experience, and inadequate training and skills are major causes of small business failure.

8.3.3.6 Followers

All the respondents (17 entrepreneurs and 34 employees) recognised the importance of having good and dedicated followers. The role of followers is increasingly recognised in leadership theories (Shin and Zhou, 2003). The findings concur with existing literature on the impact of followers in entrepreneurial leadership. For example, Renko et al. (2012b) found that the successful outcome of entrepreneurial leadership was not only based on the attributes and actions of the leader, but also depend on the followers' entrepreneurial self-efficacy, their empowerment, and their level of passion. In addition, all the interviewed employees in this study felt comfortable with being empowered by their bosses. In fact, they craved for more empowerment and freedom to discharge their duties. This is contrary to the work of Renko et al. (2012b), who stated that "...empowerment comes with responsibility and for some the responsibility may be an unwelcome burden".

8.3.4 Entrepreneurial leadership skills

Entrepreneurial leadership skills are descriptors of the dependent variable (which is entrepreneurial leadership). This node determines the form and effectiveness of entrepreneurial leadership. The interviews with the entrepreneurial leaders and their employees produced a comprehensive list of entrepreneurial leadership skills that they perceived as being important to their success. The entrepreneurial leadership skills identified by the respondents included technical/business skills, conceptual skills, interpersonal skills, and entrepreneurial skills. For this study, the word ‘skills’ refers to expertise, practised ability and facility in an action (Schedlitzki and Edwards, 2014). These are competencies that can be developed and learned (Northouse, 2010). In this sub-section, these entrepreneurial leadership skills are discussed with reference to the literature in the domains of leadership and entrepreneurial leadership.

8.3.4.1 Technical/Business skills

All the respondents (i.e. entrepreneurs and employees) considered technical/business skills to be important. These respondents discussed the skills in relation to technical expertise and business function. These skills are discussed in more detail below:

Technical expertise skills

All the respondents (17 entrepreneurs and 34 employees) agreed that technical expertise is an important skill required for running a retail pharmacy business successfully. This technical expertise is usually acquired by a combination of formal education, training, and job experience (Haq, 2011; Yukl, 2010). Technical skills have been identified as an important factor in enhancing a leader’s performance (Bass, 1990; Haq, 2011; Katz, 1955; Katz, 1974; Lord and Hall, 2005; Shiba, 1998). The findings of the interviews also support the stance of Guo (2009), in that

entrepreneurial leaders have knowledge of the system and the environment in which they function.

The respondents stressed that although technical expertise is important, business skills were also vital. Respondents viewed technical skills and business skills as different parts of a continuum. This is contrary to Katz's framework, in which both are perceived as technical skills. Therefore, the research findings support the wider leadership literature, in which technical skills are dichotomised into business skills (Mumford et al., 2007; Siewiorek et al., 2012) and technological skills (Zaccaro and Klimoski, 2001).

Business function skills

All the respondents (17 entrepreneurs and 34 employees) considered functional skills to be important. The respondents agreed that although they were pharmacists by trade, their success was largely attributed to their business skills. This supports the view of literature on leadership as well as on entrepreneurial leadership. However, Katz's (1974) framework does not dichotomise technical skills into business skills, but takes a broader perspective by considering business skills as technical skills. By contrast, the respondents in this study identified technical skills (i.e. pharmacy skills) and business skills as separate, not similar, entities. As a result, the findings of this study confirm the studies of Mumford et al. (2007) and Siewiorek et al. (2012) in the leadership literature, in that business skills are critical leadership skills for any organisation. The findings also provide support to literature in the domain of entrepreneurial leadership (Ballein, 1998; Guo, 2009; Hentschke, 2010; Swiercz and Lydon, 2002).

The respondents (17 entrepreneurs and 34 employees) believed that business skills were developed by acquiring an MBA, or through other training and development programmes. This supports the findings on leadership development (Day, 2001; Mumford et al., 2000a; Paul and Whittam, 2015), in that well-timed training interventions can promote the development of leadership skills in general.

In particular, the respondents believed that one key business skill is accounting and financial management. This resonates with the findings from Zaccaro and Klimoski (2001) in the leadership literature. It also supports the stance of Copeman (1971) and Katz (1974), who claimed that management of financial resources is essential. For Hentschke (2010), financial management is arguably the most important skill of an entrepreneurial leader, as it involves developing and selling a business plan, raising financial capital, and spending it wisely. The financial management skill is a core competence of entrepreneurial leadership in an organisation (Guo, 2009; Swiercz and Lydon, 2002). One of the critical responsibilities of the entrepreneurial leader is to acquire capital for the company. As reported earlier, one of the resource constraints the respondents were facing is lack of access to finance, which forced them to be the chief fund-raisers of their own companies (Hentschke, 2010; Swiercz and Lydon, 2002).

The respondents also identified administration as another important business skill. The respondents (entrepreneurs and employees) believed that good administration was a core part of the business. This resonates with the work of Swiercz and Lydon (2002, p. 384) who identifies this skill as “operational competencies”, with the claim that an entrepreneurial leader needs to “conduct a symphony”.

The role of marketing as a business skill, especially in the form of customer service, was mentioned by many respondents. The interviewed entrepreneurial leaders were able to develop “...customised solutions based on their customer growing needs over time” (Swiercz and Lydon, 2002, p. 385). This is not surprising, since the study was conducted in a service-based sector (i.e. retail pharmacy). The respondents stressed that customer service skills helped them gain a competitive advantage, and should not apply only to entrepreneurial leaders. The respondents “...understood the importance of satisfying their customers and exceeding their expectations in order to maintain repeat customers” (Swiercz and Lydon, 2002, p. 385). Therefore, there is an amalgamation of business and interpersonal skills. This is confirmed in studies on leadership by Luthans et al. (1988) and Mahoney et al. (1965), who suggest that business skills should include specific skills for managing human resources. In contrast with the findings from the interviews, the relationship between business skills and interpersonal skills is not clearly reported in entrepreneurial leadership literature.

Evidently, the above findings reveal that business function skill is an important entrepreneurial leadership skill. It involves the ability to acquire and manage finance, understand accounting procedures and inventory control, and to perform book-keeping, administration, and marketing (in the form of customer service). Such business skills can be developed formally by training, or informally by independent learning. Most of the business skills could be linked with other entrepreneurial leadership skills such as interpersonal skills and conceptual skills; hence why a combination of all these skills is important in entrepreneurial leadership.

8.3.4.2 Conceptual skills

All the respondents (17 entrepreneurs and 34 employees) identified conceptual skills as an important skill. The entrepreneurs claimed that they were able to understand situations of varying degrees of complexity. This is similar to the conceptual skill element in Katz's framework on leadership. The respondents kept updating their knowledge, and were able to adapt successfully to changing situations (Yukl, 2010). Six forms of conceptual skills were identified from the analysis of the interview data, and they are discussed below:

Analytical skills

The findings of this study support the view in leadership literature that conceptual skills are related to cognitive capacities such as collecting, processing, and disseminating information (Mumford et al., 2007). Other aspects of conceptual thinking include analytical ability and logical thinking (Yukl, 2010). The respondents were analytical in their decision making and risk taking, and this is consistent with findings reported in entrepreneurial leadership literature (Carpenter 2012; Nieuwenhuizen, 2009). The respondents were able to think objectively, especially with regards to competition. The findings appear to support the view of Gillen and Carroll (1985) and Mumford et al. (2007) in leadership literature, who acknowledged the use of logic to analyse the strengths and weaknesses of different approaches to work.

Idea generation skills

The respondents (entrepreneurs and their employees) believed that the ability to generate new ideas and question assumptions was a vital skill. The entrepreneurs in the study were innovative and skilled in generating new ideas. This is consistent with the findings in literature on entrepreneurial leadership. Innovativeness has been defined as the ability of entrepreneurial leaders to be creative, and to develop new and useful ideas in terms of entrepreneurial opportunity recognition, resource utilisation, and problem solving (Agbim et al., 2013; Bagheri and Pihie, 2011; Ballein, 1998; Carpenter, 2012; Chen, 2007; Gupta et al., 2004).

However, innovativeness is also viewed from the construct of the firm (Chen, 2007) and as a dimension of entrepreneurial orientation (Kuratko, 2007). There is insufficient evidence to support previous research by Chen (2007), who views innovativeness as being a construct of the firm. The entrepreneurs agreed that the ideas they generated were shared with their employees. They encouraged their employees to generate and exploit new ideas. This is consistent with the findings of Carpenter (2012) and Strubler and Redekop (2010), in that entrepreneurial leaders create an environment that fosters innovation among their workers. It also supports the findings of Renko et al. (2012a, p. 181) in their examination of family businesses, in that under entrepreneurial leadership, each member strives to come up with entrepreneurial solutions to business problems, thus "...increasing the number of novel ideas considered by the organization". Some respondents agreed that challenging the status quo was essential to their success. Their ideas were sometimes radical and deviated far from the established norm in the industry. This is consistent with findings of D'Intino et al. (2008), who reported that entrepreneurial leaders in Boeing were radically innovative. The entrepreneurial leaders interviewed in this study love new challenges (Bagheri et al., 2013), question assumptions (Carpenter, 2012), and do not support the status quo (Renko et al., 2012b). The entrepreneurial leaders make their followers think about old problems in new ways, and re-examine assumptions about their jobs (Renko et al., 2012b).

Problem solving skills

The respondents shared the view that the ability to solve problems is a key skill and has been pivotal to their success. The entrepreneurial leaders were able to solve problems relating to employee conflicts, competition, and satisfaction of customer needs. The respondents solved problems by adopting analytical and logical approaches, despite their limited resources. They persisted until they found a solution to the problem. This problem solving orientated mind-set concurs with prior research in mainstream leadership literature, with many scholars agreeing that problem solving skills is an important skill in leadership (Connelly et al., 2000; Mumford et al., 2000a to 2000d; Mumford et al., 2007; Yammarino, 2000; Zaccaro et al., 2000), and has an important influence on a leader's performance (Mumford et al., 2000b). It is widely mentioned in entrepreneurial leadership literature that entrepreneurial leaders are able to solve complex business, social, and economic problems (Greenberg et al., 2013). The individuals in this study solved future problems and crises (Hejazi et al., 2012), and were constantly looking for new problems to solve (Darling et al., 2007a). This finding supports the stance of Surie and Ashley (2008), who claimed that entrepreneurial leadership is pragmatic and is focused on problem solving and value creation. From the interviews in this study, it was found that the entrepreneurial leaders are experts who have learned which problems affect their firms, and know how to solve them (Surie and Ashley, 2008).

Envisioning skills

Analysis of the data from the interviews has shown that envisioning is a core conceptual skill that entrepreneurial leaders should possess. This supports the findings in literature that entrepreneurial leaders have visionary capabilities. Vision involves "...creating a picture of what the future state will be like" (Flamholtz, 2011, p. 7). In other words, entrepreneurial leaders need to be able to create a vivid picture of the future for the organisation to create added value. When the vision is known and shared, it generates enthusiasm and motivation, and builds the confidence of people in the organisation (Karanian, 2007; Roomi and Harrison, 2011). As stated by Darling et al. (2007a, p. 10), "Vision grabs attention." Therefore, entrepreneurial leaders should be able to communicate the vision to their employees in an exciting

and inspirational fashion to ensure implementation (Abbas and Tatfi, 2010; Cogliser and Brigham, 2004).

Envisioning the future is fundamental to entrepreneurial leadership (Flamholtz, 2011). Similar to the findings of Paul and Whittam (2015) on leadership development, evidence from this study suggests that envisioning works best when an entrepreneurial leader views it as a two-stage process. The first stage of envisioning is a reflective activity, whereby an entrepreneurial leader envisages a business idea. To advance an idea, an entrepreneurial leader must cultivate not only a personal vision of how the idea may be achieved, but also a deep conviction that it will be successful.

The second stage of the envisioning process requires the individual to sell this vision to a range of diverse stakeholders (Paul and Whittam, 2015). These can include family, investors, and staff members, which altogether comprise the financial muscle and the talent necessary for a start-up to succeed. The requirement places a great demand upon an individual to articulate the future so that these various groups are satisfied.

This two-stage envisioning process can readily be applied by entrepreneurial leaders in other industries. Therefore, the entrepreneurial leaders in this study have established a link between strategic planning and envisioning. The findings of this study provide additional evidence to the assertion (found in literature) that the skill of putting envisioning into practice will be easier when an entrepreneurial leader follows a two-stage process.

Strategic planning skills

Analysis of the data from the interviews has shown that strategic planning skills form another important conceptual skill for any entrepreneurial leader, which is paramount to their success in running the business. This is not clearly stated in the Katz framework. However, the emphasis on strategy by the respondents in this study lends credence to the value placed on strategic planning skills. Their views support the findings in mainstream leadership literature, in which strategic skills have been

identified as a core skill for leadership (Mumford et al., 2007; Siewiorek et al., 2012).

The entrepreneurial leaders in this study developed strategies for their organisations, although the exact details varied among the individuals. They had strategies to overcome competition and to increase their profitability. This confirms the findings of Carpenter (2012, p. 16), who stated that entrepreneurial leaders are "...strategically oriented and can formulate strategy based on available resources". They think strategically (Ballein, 1998), take a holistic view (Hejazi et al., 2012), and "...develop risk taking and innovative strategies to meet the challenges of the environment, system, community and stakeholders" (Guo, 2009, p. 25).

The entrepreneurial leaders in this study said they were able to draft out plans and anticipate changes, abilities that were also confirmed by their employees. While planning, they made forecasts and managed their time effectively. The respondents were able to establish a link between strategic planning skills, self-management skills, and envisioning in form of forecasting. The perceptions of the respondents appear to confirm the opinions cited from leadership literature that leaders are involved in strategic planning (Marshall-Mies et al., 2000; Yukl, 2010), and that planning in complex and dynamic environments improves performance (Mumford et al., 2002).

Decision making skills

Finally, the analysis of data from the interviews has shown that the conceptual skills of the respondents (entrepreneurs) influenced their ability to make the best decisions; hence, decision making was a conceptual skill that the entrepreneurial leaders possessed. These entrepreneurial leaders made their decisions based on their strategies. They mostly involved others in their strategic decisions, but sometimes times they did not. Nevertheless, they all agreed that decision making skills are vital. This confirms the findings from the literature review that entrepreneurial leaders are decisive (Ballein, 1998; Carpenter, 2012; Gupta et al., 2004; Hentschke, 2010). These individuals make "...decisions quickly alone or with modest amounts of advice" (Hentschke, 2010, p. 122). They are constantly involved in courageous

decision making (Abbas and Tatfi, 2010; D'intino et al., 2008). However, not all the interviewed entrepreneurs were quick in their decision making. Some considered this as a weakness, while other respondents stressed that they did not always need to make decisions quickly: “...*there are some things* [for which] *you just give time*” (M). That view contrasts with the findings of Gupta et al. (2004, p. 250) that entrepreneurial leaders “make decisions firmly and quickly”. Hentschke (2010) also takes a similar stance. Interestingly, it is expected that in the retail pharmacy sector, which is a dynamic and turbulent environment, entrepreneurial leaders should make decisions quickly, but in this study it was found that this might not always be the case. The disparity between these findings with those from the literature review provides additional evidence to support the stance that entrepreneurial leaders must not always take quick decisions; rather, it is the quality of the decisions that matter. In addition, the interviewed entrepreneurial leaders established a link between decision making and their religious beliefs. This is not emphasised anywhere in the literature on entrepreneurial leadership. These findings may be due to the religious culture in Nigeria; hence, this study provides novel information.

Evidently, the findings from the interviews show that conceptual skills form an important entrepreneurial leadership skill. This confirms the work of Katz (1974). However, the elements that constitute conceptual skills appear to be more elaborate in the interview proceedings, compared to the findings of Katz. The respondents were able to show that the ability to analyse complex situations, generate new ideas, envision the future, plan strategically, solve problems, and make the right decisions are key conceptual skills of an entrepreneurial leader.

8.3.4.3 Interpersonal skills

Analysis of the data has shown that interpersonal skills are a core skill among the interviewed entrepreneurial leaders, which has enabled them to be successful in their businesses. It was found that interpersonal skills comprise six sub-skills: empathy,

communication and listening skills, motivating skills, team building skills, people management and development, and self-management. These are discussed below:

Empathy

It was shown in the data analysis that empathy is a core interpersonal skill that the entrepreneurial leaders possessed. This was evidenced by the ability of the entrepreneurial leaders to understand the feelings, motives, and emotions of others. They were empathetic towards their customers and employees, and this for most of them was the core reason for their success. These respondents associated empathy with human sensitivity, and were compassionate towards their customers and employees. These views confirm the claim found in mainstream leadership literature that leaders should have the ability to understand another person's motives, values, and emotions (Yukl, 2010). They should be sensitive to the emotions of others (Lord and Hall, 2005), since this is a strong predictor of leadership (Kellet et al., 2002). This is also in line with the findings from entrepreneurial leadership literature. Scholars have stated that entrepreneurial leaders should be able to recognise others' emotions (Hejazi et al., 2012), be thoughtful about their associates (Siddiqui, 2007), and caring towards their followers (Tarabishy et al., 2002). However, the respondents in this study shared the view that sometimes showing empathy in the form of compassion could be detrimental to the business' profitability. Though compassion is necessary, there is a need to strike a balance, and they were aware of this. Apparently, there is little evidence for this in entrepreneurial leadership literature. Rather, previous studies place an emphasis on the importance of empathy on the outcomes of entrepreneurial leadership, rather than on its disadvantages, especially in a turbulent business environment where profit margins are tight. This study therefore provides additional findings to the canon of knowledge in this regard.

Communication/listening skills

Communication and listening skills are identified as necessary for building interpersonal relationships. These help to inspire an understanding of the actions of employees, customers, and vendors (Hentschke, 2010). It is the "...process of

making sense to the world and sharing that sense with others by co-creating meaning through the use of verbal and non-verbal symbols” (Darling and Beebe, 2007, p. 152). The respondents agreed that entrepreneurial leaders must have the ability to listen to all stakeholders in the business. By listening to their staff members and customers, they were able to make better decisions. This is consistent with the findings of Graham (1983) and Mumford et al. (2007) that leaders must listen actively. It also resonates with the findings from literature, in that entrepreneurial leaders are active listeners (Hejazi et al., 2012). It confirms the findings by Hentschke (2010, p. 120), who wrote that for entrepreneurial leaders, “...it is more likely to mean the difference between success and failure”. Entrepreneurial leaders with “...good communication skills are better able to help others to make innovative decisions” (Guo, 2009, p. 27).

Motivating skills

It was shown in the data analysis that the ability to motivate and inspire confidence in employees and customers was a vital interpersonal skill for running a retail pharmacy business. The interviewed entrepreneurial leaders believed that knowledge of the domain in the form of technical know-how and good communication skills was important for inspiring confidence. The respondents established a relationship between motivation, and technical and communication skills. These perceptions concur with prior research in mainstream leadership literature that interpersonal skills are essential for influencing people (Yukl, 2010), especially in charismatic and transformational leadership (Bass and Avolio, 1990). The respondents’ perceptions support the findings in literature that entrepreneurial leaders are good motivators (Fernald et al., 2005; Kansikas et al., 2012; Reimers-Hild and King, 2009), and that the ability to motivate and communicate is vital (Hentschke, 2010). Entrepreneurial leaders motivate their followers to take on entrepreneurial roles (Renko et al., 2012a), which engenders their commitment (Gupta et al., 2004). In addition, the respondents’ views support the findings by Agbim et al. (2013), in that motivational dimensions of entrepreneurial leadership have positive effects on sustained entrepreneurial success. Their views resonate with those found in entrepreneurial leadership literature that entrepreneurial leaders are able to communicate in an

inspirational fashion to their followers (Cogliser and Brigham, 2004). Entrepreneurial leaders inspire the confidence, emotions, beliefs, values, and behaviours of others (Gupta et al., 2004; Hejazi et al., 2012; Reimers-Hild and King, 2009). These individuals inspire and influence a group of individuals towards the fulfilment of their goals (Darling et al., 2007a). While the respondents' views do not contradict with those found in the literature review, the respondents' emphasis on technical knowledge as a means of motivation is noteworthy, since the research was carried out in the retail pharmacy context where technical skills are highly important. These technical skills inspire confidence in the customer and, therefore, this study provides more information on the role that technical skills play in inspiring more confidence among the relevant stakeholders of a business.

In addition, the respondents (entrepreneurs and employees) agreed that entrepreneurial leaders must have the ability to motivate themselves, thereby establishing a link with self-management skills. The interviewed entrepreneurs were also proficient in motivating their employees, not only by using good communication skills, but also through extrinsic factors such as pay rises and bonuses.

Team building skills

It has been shown from the data analysis that the ability to build teams and promote team work was a vital interpersonal skill for entrepreneurial leadership. The interviewed entrepreneurs were team players and believed that staff commitment is a key to their success. This supports the view found in entrepreneurial leadership literature that entrepreneurial leaders promote team work (Bagheri and Pihie, 2011) and foster team spirit (Strubler and Redekop, 2010). They are able to move from "me to we" (Swiercz and Lydon, 2002, p. 387) and induce group members to work together (Gupta et al., 2004). Indeed, entrepreneurial leaders are team players (Ballein, 1998), and develop effective venture teams (Carpenter, 2012; Kuratko and Hornsby, 1999). The respondents agreed that within team building, delegating tasks to employees is important, not only for training them, but also for encouraging team work. They listened to other people's views before making decisions.

People management and development skills

It has been shown from the data analysis that skills in managing and developing people form an important interpersonal skill in entrepreneurial leadership. The respondents believed that people management skills in terms of understanding and training people were important for running their businesses. They considered this skill to be important, and they put their staff members through training sessions and other activities regardless of the cost. They identified the training needs of their staff by understanding them, thereby establishing a link between empathy and people development. This reflects the view of Renko et al. (2012b), who claim that empowering employees and providing an appropriate level of autonomy shifts their attention to new entrepreneurial opportunities. These entrepreneurial leaders need to understand the needs of their followers (Hejazi et al., 2012) if they are to build high performance teams in the organisation (Guo, 2009). The respondents believed that since entrepreneurial leaders manage people, they ought to be role models. They shared the view that it was important for them to lead by example. The employees had learned a lot by looking up to them as entrepreneurial leaders. These perceptions concur with previous research findings that entrepreneurial leaders serve as an “...example of opportunity focused behaviour for the followers, creating a culture for innovation” (Renko et al., 2012a, p. 180). They serve as role models to their employees (Abbas and Tatfi, 2010).

Self-management skills

It has been shown from the data analysis that the ability of entrepreneurial leaders to manage themselves is an essential interpersonal skill. This was evidenced in the respondents' planning and organising, in their handling of difficult situations, and in their critical reflection on their strengths and weaknesses. The respondents (entrepreneurs) considered the ability to handle pressure and exhibit self-control in difficult situations as being pivotal to their success. They were not flustered and they expected such challenges. They were able to control their emotions, and for some of them this may vary with the nature of the business. These perceptions are consistent with those found in the literature review in the domain of leadership. They also confirm the findings in the literature on self-regulation in leaders “...as an ability to

channel emotions behaviour that is appropriate for the situation” (Yukl, 2010, p. 66). The respondents said they were able to adjust their behaviour according to the situation, which Lord and Hall (2005) refer to as meta-monitoring; and they handled stress effectively (Cherniss, 1999) which made them more successful. This also supports findings from the literature review in the domain of entrepreneurial leadership. Entrepreneurial leaders must have the ability to deal with unforeseen circumstances and control their feelings (Hejazi et al., 2012). Hejazi et al. (2012) identifies emotional stability as an important personal factor in entrepreneurial leaders. It supports the findings of Karanian (2007) that entrepreneurial leaders expect and cope with internal and external confrontation.

The respondents (entrepreneurs and employees) agreed that self-development is important for running/working in their businesses. These entrepreneurial leaders showed a conscious effort to improve their conduct through formal training, or informally by their own reading. They perceived that, in order to rise to the competition and maintain profitability, they had to improve themselves. The respondents were compelled to do this, despite the cost and limited time. Their perceptions appear to confirm the findings from the literature in entrepreneurial leadership, in that scholars have claimed that entrepreneurial leaders are improvement-oriented (Abbas and Tatfi, 2010; Gupta et al., 2004). The respondents’ sentiments support the findings of Leitch et al. (2012), who observed that improvement of human capital through leadership development programmes is important in entrepreneurial leadership. Furthermore, the respondents’ views are consistent with the findings in mainstream leadership literature. According to Day (2001, p.605), “Effective leadership occurs through the development of individual leaders.” Leaders may acquire requisite leadership skills through leadership training courses (Mumford et al., 2000a) and HR processes (Day et al., 2014). The findings from the interviews also support the stance of Cherniss (1999), who claimed that emotional competence could be improved through training, thereby improving business performance. Apparently, there is no disparity in this regard between the findings of the interviews, and those from the literature review.

The entrepreneurial leaders in this study were aware of their abilities, values, strengths, and weaknesses. As regards their weaknesses, most of the entrepreneurial leaders made it a point of duty to work on correcting them. The findings from the

interviews are consistent with those from mainstream leadership literature. Good leaders are self-aware, a behaviour "...which is an understanding of one's own moods and emotions" (Yukl, 2010, p. 66). These include emotional self-awareness, accurate self-assessment, and conscientiousness (Boyatzis et al., 2000). They have an awareness of their cognitive processes (Marshall-Mies et al., 2000). The findings from this study also confirm the findings of Guo (2009) that entrepreneurial leaders have the ability to accurately perceive both their strengths and areas in need of improvement. The findings from this study support those of Swiercz and Lydon (2002) that entrepreneurial leaders understand their own strengths and weakness, and hire people to complement their weaknesses. The interview findings agree with those of previous studies in literature.

Finally, the interviewed entrepreneurial leaders said they had the ability to prioritise work effectively and manage their time well. The respondents emphasised the need for time management and time-consciousness, two abilities that do not feature prominently in the literature. Previous studies tend to place an emphasis on the efficient allocation and mobilisation of resources (Carpenter, 2012; Gupta et al., 2004; Hejazi et al., 2012). This difference in emphasis may be attributed to the rational approach taken by the entrepreneurial leaders in the retail pharmacy sector, who are more concerned about how they can make more effective use of their time due to the intense competition in the industry. Furthermore, the developing economy context and its challenges also make effective time management even more vital. In addition, several respondents identified the ability to multi-task as playing a critical role in their time management. Through this, these leaders were able to carry out multiple tasks at once while balancing them effectively. Surprisingly, there is little emphasis on this in entrepreneurial leadership literature; hence, these findings provide additional evidence to the canon of knowledge.

8.3.4.4 Entrepreneurial skills

This research has identified a skill set, which has been named entrepreneurial skills, as vital to effective entrepreneurial leadership. These skill set consists of three skills

namely opportunity identification, opportunity exploitation and risk management. These are discussed below:

Opportunity identification skills

The respondents (entrepreneurs and employees) recognised the ability to identify opportunities as an important skill required for success. It is arguably this skill that distinguishes entrepreneurial leadership from the other types of leadership highlighted in the broader leadership literature. This view is in line with numerous studies on entrepreneurial leadership (e.g. Carpenter, 2012; Currie et al., 2008; Gupta et al., 2004; Renko et al., 2012a; Renko et al., 2012b; etc.). The entrepreneurial leaders interviewed in this study were apt at recognising opportunities. This reflects the view of Renko et al., (2012a) that entrepreneurial leadership is based on the continuous recognition of new opportunities. The interviewed entrepreneurial leaders were able to recognise the trends in the industry that others could not see. This supports the findings of Kuratko (2007, p. 6) that entrepreneurial leaders are “aggressive catalysts” and recognise opportunities, whereas others see “chaos, contradictions or confusion”. Entrepreneurial leaders are good pattern recognisers, seeing roles others do not see (Carpenter, 2012). Where other people see problems, entrepreneurial leaders see opportunities (Hentschke, 2010). The respondents identified opportunities that spanned from good locations to scarcity of products. This view resonates with those of Renko et al. (2012a) that entrepreneurial leaders recognise new entrepreneurial opportunities and pursue their visions through creative, innovative, even risky tactics. Entrepreneurial leaders constantly seek opportunities for growth (Carpenter, 2012).

The respondents were able to spot opportunities because they were constantly educating themselves. They were updating their knowledge of the landscape. This relates to the studies of Currie et al. (2008) on entrepreneurial leadership in the public sector; Currie et al. remarked that entrepreneurial leaders should understand and know the political landscape so as to be able to identify and exploit opportunities.

Opportunity exploitation skills

The respondents believed that they were also able to exploit recognised opportunities. Such opportunities varied from expansion into emerging markets, to selling products with a short shelf-life to maximise profitability. For most of them, the main reason for their success was their ability to exploit opportunities. This resonates with the common perception found in the literature review that entrepreneurial leaders are able to exploit opportunities. According to Darling et al. (2007a), success for an entrepreneurial leader is not based on intellect; rather, it is attributed to their ability to recognise and exploit opportunities. The findings from this study also confirm the views of Hansson and Mønsted (2008) and Currie et al. (2008), in that research and public sector entrepreneurial leaders have the ability to exploit opportunities. In addition, the respondents believed that opportunities may not always be new, but their ability to quickly exploit them was more important. This relates to the finding of Surie and Ashley (2008) that entrepreneurial leaders respond quickly to environmental opportunities.

The respondents linked envisioning with opportunity exploitation. They were able to exploit opportunities because of their visionary capabilities. This finding supports the stance of Roomi and Harrison (2011), who claimed that entrepreneurial leaders are able to communicate a vision to engage people, and have an ability to develop and take advantage of opportunities to gain competitive advantage.

Risk management skills

All the respondents (17 entrepreneurs) shared the view that their businesses had an unavoidable element of risk; hence, they had to take them. This risk management element is not reflected within the Katz conceptual framework on leadership. This is not surprising, as risk taking behaviour is a concept that is more established in entrepreneurship rather than leadership theory. However, these findings resonate with research evidence from literature on risk taking as a characteristic of an entrepreneurial leader (Ahmed and Ramzan, 2013; Ballein, 1998; Carpenter, 2012; Chen, 2007; Currie et al., 2008; D'Intino et al., 2008; Gupta et al., 2004; Kansikas et al., 2012; Lippit, 1987; Okudan and Rzasa, 2006; Renko et al., 2012b; Tarabishy et

al., 2005). The respondents (entrepreneurs and employees) believed that they have the ability to manage risks they encountered in their business. This resonates with the findings of Guo (2009), who highlights risk management as a core competence of an entrepreneurial leader. However, Guo (2009) focuses on risk management entirely from a performance management perspective. Whereas, the findings of this study show that the respondents have the ability to manage risks by taking an analytical perspective. They identified, assessed, and evaluated risks. They always thought of ways to mitigate risks, and they estimated their impact on the financial position of their companies. Therefore, these findings provide a contribution to the canon of knowledge on risk management skills. In addition, there has been little emphasis on risk management as an entrepreneurial leadership skill. Since risk taking is inevitable, these entrepreneurial leaders have been able to manage risks so that they can be successful. Therefore, the findings from the interviews justify the inclusion of risk management as an essential skill that entrepreneurial leaders should possess.

8.4 Entrepreneurial leadership outcomes

Information on three outcomes was obtained from the findings of the study. These outcomes include business creation, business commercialisation, and business management. These are presented below:

8.4.1 Business creation

All the respondents (17 entrepreneurs) had started their own businesses, which had been in existence for no less than five years. However, they had not only created one business, but were able to expand and create more branches. This was a major outcome of their entrepreneurial leadership. For these respondents, entrepreneurial leadership has led to creation of more opportunities by starting their business. This findings support the work of Mapunda et al. (2007) that entrepreneurial leadership is

important for starting an indigenous business enterprise. It also resonates with the views of Kansikas et al. (2012) and Renko et al. (2012a) that entrepreneurial leadership is crucial for creating successful family businesses.

8.4.2 Business commercialisation

The interviewed entrepreneurs not only created businesses as a result of their entrepreneurial leadership; they were also able to commercialise them. Their businesses were successful and financially sound. By exploiting opportunities at their disposal, and with use of entrepreneurial leadership skills, they were able to expand into emerging markets and achieve commercial success. These confirm the finding from the literature review that entrepreneurial leaders constantly seek opportunities for growth (Carpenter, 2012). It resonates with the view of Agus and Hassan (2010) that entrepreneurial leadership has a positive impact on sales performance and customer satisfaction in a developing economy (Malaysia, in their case).

8.4.3 Business management

As well as creating and commercialising their businesses, the entrepreneurial leaders were able to manage their businesses effectively. This was another important outcome of their entrepreneurial leadership. The entrepreneurial leadership skills they possessed in the form of technical/business skills, conceptual skills, interpersonal, and entrepreneurial skills were instrumental for managing their businesses successfully. They were able to control, lead, organise, plan, and monitor their businesses. The interpersonal skills they possessed was instrumental for managing people including staff members, customers, suppliers, and other stakeholders directly or indirectly involved in the business. Their conceptual skills were important for understanding diverse complex business situations, and for analysing different options and making effective decisions. These findings confirm

those found in entrepreneurial leadership literature, in that entrepreneurial leadership is important for managing a business (Guo, 2009; Papalexandris and Galanaki, 2009).

Therefore, the combination of these three entrepreneurial outcomes is the pedestal upon which the interviewed entrepreneurs' successful businesses were created.

8.5 The concept of entrepreneurial leadership

The meaning of entrepreneurial leadership cannot only be attributed to opportunity recognition and exploitation, as perceived in prior studies (e.g. Kuratko, 2007; Renko et al., 2012a). In this sense, the results from this study point towards the role of entrepreneurial leadership skills in overcoming challenges, and recognising and exploiting opportunities in an entrepreneurial environment. Additionally, this leadership is seen to be influenced by other variables such as personality, family dynamics, culture, followers, limited resources, and experience.

According to Gupta et al. (2004, p. 242) entrepreneurial leadership is defined as "...leadership that creates visionary scenarios that are used to assemble and mobilize a 'supporting cast' of participants who become committed by the vision to the discovery and exploitation of strategic value creation". This widely accepted definition, which recognises the challenges of scenario enactment and cast enactment, does not acknowledge the importance of entrepreneurial leadership skills and context.

The participants in this study confirmed the importance of envisioning, creating, convincing, assembling resources, and exploitation; in addition, they identified more variables. Based on comments from all the respondents, an entrepreneurial leadership definition is therefore proposed that encompasses all the findings of this study on this new emerging paradigm. This definition is stated below:

Entrepreneurial leadership is a type of leadership capable of identifying and exploiting opportunities in an entrepreneurial environment.

Entrepreneurial leaders solve problems and improve performance by employing four broad fundamental skills: technical/business skills, conceptual skills, interpersonal skills, and entrepreneurial skills. In addition, these entrepreneurial leaders (and their performance) are also influenced by their personality, family, culture, the nature of their followers, availability of resources, and their experience.

Entrepreneurial leaders understand specific functional areas in their business. This understanding spans beyond their business to include situations of varying degrees of complexity. They generate ideas and question assumptions. These individuals understand their own behaviour as well as those of others, and hence are able to develop their abilities and those of their followers. They prioritise their work and manage risks, and are successful due to their ability to foster innovation.

8.6 Conclusion

In this chapter, the findings of the study have been discussed in the wider context of previous empirical literature. The findings from both the interviews and the literature review have answered the research questions. An empirical model of entrepreneurial leadership was proposed and discussed. The causal conditions for entrepreneurial leadership (which include challenges and opportunities) were discussed in the context of a developing economy. Specifically, the challenges were discussed with reference to literature on entrepreneurship.

Furthermore, the intervening conditions that facilitate and shape entrepreneurial leadership in a developing economy context have also been discussed. These conditions were highlighted by the respondents as important for entrepreneurial leadership, and they include attributes, culture, family, resources, management experience, and followers.

The entrepreneurial leadership skills, which form the core of the empirical model and which were identified by the respondents, were also discussed in line with literature. Entrepreneurial leadership skills include technical/business skills, conceptual skills, interpersonal skills, and entrepreneurial skills. It was discovered

during this study that although Katz identified three skills for leadership (which were considered in the data analysis), the participants identified four core entrepreneurial leadership skills. In fact, there has not been any universally established skill-based empirical model on entrepreneurial leadership within the context of a developing economy, and previous scholars have tended on adopting a trait-based approach (e.g. Gupta et al., 2004). Finally, based on the empirical findings of the study, a definition of entrepreneurial leadership was proposed and justified.

CHAPTER NINE - CONCLUSION

9.1. Introduction

This final chapter is an overview of the outcomes of the study in line with the research aim, objectives, and questions. The implications of the findings are considered, and the ways in which the research findings contribute to the canon of knowledge (both theoretically and methodologically) are discussed. The implication of the findings for practice and policy makers, and the limitations of the study are also highlighted. The chapter ends by outlining areas for future research and overall concluding remarks.

9.2. Overview

This thesis contains original research findings on the concept of entrepreneurial leadership, which are detailed in the sub-sections below:

9.2.1. Traditional narrative review

Through the narrative review of the literature on leadership, it was found that leadership in entrepreneurial settings had not been effectively defined in previous studies (refer back to Table 4). The setting is characterised by turbulence and dynamism and therefore requires a distinct type of leadership. From the review, it was found that leadership conception is under-developed, with most focus mainly on a limited set of elements, and ignoring the impact of the followers and of context. In addition, there exists limited research in mainstream leadership literature about entrepreneurial firms in developing economies. Notwithstanding these gaps and deficiencies, the review of literature in the entrepreneurship domain revealed that

entrepreneurship is a budding field that is the subject of much disagreement. As with leadership in general, no universal consensus has been reached in the domain.

9.2.2. Systematic literature review (SLR)

It was demonstrated through the SLR that entrepreneurial leadership is a comparatively new research area lagging behind in theoretical and conceptual development. The impact of entrepreneurial leadership in a developing economy has received limited attention. Evidence of this can be seen in the small number of cited sources about the impact of entrepreneurial leadership from the perspective of a developing economy (refer back to Table 10). A developing economy presents researchers with a challenging context. Entrepreneurs in countries with different levels of GDP per capita face different challenges, and policies and conditions favourable to entrepreneurship in one country (or region) may not be effective or favourable in another (Acs, 2006). In particular, it was shown through the SLR that there is a dearth of literature on entrepreneurial leadership skills in developing economies. The authors of most works cited in the SLR listed attributes (Gupta et al., 2004; Nicholson, 1998), while other scholars considered both attributes and skills as characteristics (Cogliser and Brigham, 2004).

9.2.3. Interviews

This study was an exploration of the perception of entrepreneurial leadership from the dual perspective of entrepreneurs and employees (to ensure triangulation of data). Rather than simply gathering information from entrepreneurs (as was the case in several previous research studies) (Jones and Crompton, 2009), the perspective of their employees concerning the entrepreneurial leadership of their employers was also considered in an effort to gain a better picture and a more stable view of reality. By adopting an approach which incorporates different viewpoints (Eriksson and

Kovalainen, 2011), a better understanding of entrepreneurial leadership was obtained.

An interpretivist-constructionist approach was adopted for this study. The research built theory on entrepreneurial leadership by the subjective experience of various retail pharmacy entrepreneurial leaders and their employees in a developing economy context. Since the study was related to understanding rather than measuring, it was judged necessary to adopt an approach that gave “voice” (Bluhm et al., 2011, p. 1871) to the individual entrepreneurs and enabled them to talk about their perceptions and the processes involved (Gartner et al., 1992; Smircich and Stubbart, 1985). This suggested a qualitative and idiographic methodology, an approach confirmed by the exploratory nature of the study (Paul and Whittam, 2010; Yin, 2003). The vehicle for data generation was in-depth interviews. Such an approach facilitates subsequent analysis in which patterns in the data can be examined (Taylor and Bogdan, 1998; Paul et al., 2007a) and from which rich contextual evidence and meanings in an area that has not been previously explored in depth can be obtained (Howorth et al., 2004; Paul et al., 2007b).

Therefore, face-to-face interviews with respondents (17 entrepreneurs and 34 employees) were performed. The research questions, aims, and objectives - along with the literature review - guided the development of the interview protocol. The respondents had a diverse range of backgrounds and experience, and so they provided key data for the study. The entrepreneurial leadership skills which the respondents believed enabled them to run their business effectively were highlighted. These entrepreneurial leadership skills include technical/business skills, conceptual skills, interpersonal skills, and entrepreneurial skills. The challenges that the entrepreneurial leaders faced in a developing economy was also identified. These include challenges within the industry, government and corruption, infrastructural deficit, and technology deficit. In addition, the perceptions of the entrepreneurial leadership skills of the entrepreneurs by their employees were examined, and the entrepreneurs’ skills were confirmed by the employees. Other themes also emerged from the interviews, which were useful in providing a better understanding of the concept of entrepreneurial leadership. They include attributes, culture, family, resource, management experience, and follower dynamics.

9.2.4. Analysis

Key findings were obtained from the analysis of the interviews. Four entrepreneurial leadership skill categories were identified (in slight contrast with the three categories put forward by Katz). Most of these skills are developed as a result of training, experience, culture, and family dynamics. Other emerging themes were identified as influencers of entrepreneurial leadership, in addition to the skill set. Therefore, a skill-based empirical model of entrepreneurial leadership was developed that identifies other variables and is appropriate in the context of a developing economy. As a result, the analysis provided a platform upon which the empirical model of entrepreneurial leadership in the context of a developing economy was built. Employing the reasoning of Strauss and Corbin (1998), the model was developed from the conceptual framework of Katz (1974), in line with the data originating from the interviews. The model consists of (i) causal conditions (which are factors) that lead to the occurrence of entrepreneurial leadership; these are identified as challenges and opportunities. The model also embraces (ii) contextual factors; (iii) intervening conditions that mitigate the opportunities and challenges relevant to entrepreneurial leadership (and include attributes, culture, family, resources, experience, and follower dynamics); (iv) strategies (which are entrepreneurial leadership skills), and (v) the outcomes of entrepreneurial leadership (the creation, commercialisation and management of a successful business).

9.2.5. Research aims, objectives and questions

The aim of this study was to examine the entrepreneurial leadership of entrepreneurs in a developing economy, namely; Nigeria. The purpose was to understand the challenges these people face, and the entrepreneurial leadership skills that are important for success in this context. On the basis of valid empirical evidence, a skill-based model of entrepreneurial leadership was developed.

The study has five research objectives (refer back to section 1.4). These research objectives were fully achieved by face-to-face interviews with the entrepreneurs and their employees. Four research questions were posed at the beginning of this study:

- What is entrepreneurial leadership?
- What are the challenges that entrepreneurs in a developing economy face in running their businesses?
- What are the entrepreneurial leadership skills that are valuable for running businesses successfully in this context?
- What are the employees' perceptions of the entrepreneurial leadership of the entrepreneurs?

Each question has been fully addressed by the findings from both the literature reviews and the interviews.

9.3. Implications of the research findings and contribution to knowledge

This research has contributed in various ways to the understanding of entrepreneurial leadership in a developing economy. The main contribution is the skill-based empirical model developed for entrepreneurial leaders in the context of a developing economy. This model accounts for key entrepreneurial leadership skills, namely technical/business skills, conceptual skills, interpersonal skills, and entrepreneurial skills. In addition, the model provides a representation of the interaction between the entrepreneurs and the environment in which they operate. Causal conditions such as challenges and opportunities and intervening conditions were therefore identified. It is acknowledged that such skills may, in part, be peculiar to the sector and the context of this study. However, the findings from the study provide a better theoretical, methodological, and practical insight into the phenomenon of entrepreneurial leadership.

9.3.1. Theoretical contribution

As emphasised in the previous sub-section, this research makes a contribution to theory with a skill-based model for entrepreneurial leadership in a developing economy. It is important to state that this is the first qualitative study in which such a skill-based model for entrepreneurial leadership in a developing economy such as Nigeria has been proposed. By relating the research findings to the Katz leadership skill framework and other notable studies (e.g. Mumford et al., 2000a to 2000d; Mumford et al., 2007) within the leadership domain, a contribution to knowledge has been made. The domain of entrepreneurial leadership is lacking in any definitive framework on entrepreneurial leadership skills. Most models identified are trait-based (Carpenter, 2012; Gupta et al., 2004). Therefore, the proposed model provides a rich description of entrepreneurial leadership based on a clearly delineated focus, namely skills.

There has been a paucity of scholarship that has examined the subject from the perspective of a developing country (Chen, 2007; Hejazi et al., 2012). By adopting a theoretical perspective, this study has contributed to this emerging paradigm. The findings of this study complement existing literature on entrepreneurial leadership. Through the SLR, it was shown that there has been little in-depth examination of entrepreneurial leadership from the perspective of a developing economy. Therefore, this deficit was addressed by investigating the phenomenon in Nigeria. The findings of this study are a contribution to the understanding of the entrepreneurial leadership skills required to succeed in a developing economy. The research findings are not limited to the realm of skills. In addition, the challenges that such entrepreneurial leaders face in a developing economy were also considered, and thus a contribution to literature on entrepreneurial leadership in developing economies has been achieved.

In addition, though the focus of the study was on entrepreneurial leadership skills, the research findings bridge a knowledge gap in the current body of literature by identifying intervening conditions such as attributes, family dynamics, culture, experience, followers, and availability of resources (which are relevant in a more holistic view of entrepreneurial leadership). Thus, the findings of this study answer

the call for researchers to develop more conceptual frameworks of entrepreneurial leadership (Renko et al., 2012b).

9.3.2. Methodological contribution

A systematic literature review (SLR) has been acknowledged by scholars (including Denyer and Tranfield, 2009; Tranfield et al., 2003) as a useful tool for producing reliable knowledge from an evidence-based perspective. This study included an SLR on entrepreneurial leadership. Such an approach has not been previously applied to the domain of entrepreneurial leadership. By using an SLR, relevant knowledge gaps were identified, and a research agenda was devised. The SLR was used to map the current state of research in the area as well as pinpoint where further empirical studies were required.

This thesis also makes a contribution to the methodology by embracing the data triangulation approach. According to Shenton (2004, p. 66), with triangulation, "...individual view points and experiences can be verified against others, and ultimately a rich picture of the attitudes, needs or behaviour of those under scrutiny may be constructed based on the contribution of a range of people". The leader/follower approach is well established in the leadership domain (e.g. Groves, 2005; Meindl, 1995), but is absent from the field of entrepreneurial leadership. By conducting face-to-face interviews with both entrepreneurs and their employees, a richer description of entrepreneurial leadership was obtained, which is also related to information in existing literature. The purpose of the study was to obtain a rich description of entrepreneurial leadership, and in order to confirm such data, multiple perspectives were used. A dual perspective of entrepreneurial leadership from both the retail pharmacy entrepreneurs and their employees was adopted in an effort to gain a better understanding of the behaviour and social world of the entrepreneurs, and the way they make sense of their actions.

9.3.3. Implications for practice and policy

The research offers a number of contributions to business practice and policy. The study was conducted in the retail pharmacy sector of a developing economy, namely Nigeria. The study of entrepreneurial leadership skills magnifies the role of training and development in the retail pharmacy sector within Nigeria. The skills identified in this study serve as a prerequisite for success. Prospective entrepreneurs should be trained to develop such skills, and existing entrepreneurial leaders should be trained to understand how to balance such competencies, as well as to reflect on their limitations. All such organisations can develop and expand the skills of their entrepreneurial leaders, thereby increasing the chances for success. The findings from this study not only include the skills employed by the retail pharmacy entrepreneurs, but also shed light on the intervening conditions that are important to their success. A better understanding of required attributes, and the influence of culture, family, experience, followers, and resources, altogether may increase the number of successful entrepreneurial leaders in this sector.

The concept of entrepreneurial leadership is of practical value and assistance to policy makers. This thesis will serve as a valuable document for policy-making decisions by stakeholders such as the Pharmaceutical Society of Nigeria (PSN), the Pharmacists Council of Nigeria (PCN), and the Association of Community Pharmacists of Nigeria (ACPN), and inform them on the reasons why entrepreneurial leadership skills are critical in influencing success in the sector. Given the challenges such entrepreneurs face in a developing economy, this study also makes a practical contribution, as the challenges such retail pharmacy entrepreneurs face in this context have been identified. In addition, this thesis provides policy makers such as the government of the Federal Republic of Nigeria with recommendations for overcoming the challenges faced by individuals in this sector. Government support in the form of consistent policies, good infrastructure, and anti-corruption measures will be beneficial to these entrepreneurs and their businesses in the Nigerian economy.

9.4. Limitations of the study

As with all research in the area of business and entrepreneurship, there are methodological limitations to this study that should be acknowledged. The limitations associated with this study concern the sample, mode of data collection, generalisability, and the empirical model used:

9.4.1. Sample

The criteria used for selecting the participants for the study were set out in sub-section 6.6.2.1. This limited the number of respondents, particularly the number of retail pharmacy entrepreneurs. However, a purposive sampling was more suited for the study rather than a random one, since it was essential to approach retail pharmacy entrepreneurs with a proven track record of success. The sample size is another limitation of this study. It was not possible to gain access to more than 17 retail pharmacy entrepreneurs. Future studies with a larger sampling base as well as a different sector may provide additional or different insights into the emerging theory of entrepreneurial leadership.

9.4.2. Data collection

The second limitation of this study is the effect of data collection on the research. The chosen method for data collection used for the study was a semi-structured interview approach. Although this approach is suitable due to its flexibility, it can introduce interviewee and interviewer bias. The interviewer could demonstrate bias in the way she/he interprets responses, and the interviewee may also introduce it by withholding relevant information on the topic of interest (Saunders et al., 2012). However, by gathering extensive knowledge through the literature reviews, conducting pilot interviews, identifying appropriate interview themes, and producing

a suitable guide, the overall bias was minimised, and interviewee bias was more recognisable.

The retail pharmacy entrepreneurs could also provide responses that were not a true reflection of their entrepreneurial leadership abilities. Previous research (Busenitz and Barney, 1997; Cooper et al., 1988) has indicated that entrepreneurs tend to have an over-exaggerated conception of their abilities; hence, in order to address this concern, interviews with employees were conducted in order to validate data from the interviews with entrepreneurs. It is also acknowledged that responses might have been different if the interview had been conducted at another point in time; however the benchmark for this study is to reflect the reality at a particular point in time, not to ensure repeatability.

Alternative approaches such as ethnography would have been suitable for the study since ethnography is characterised by the richness of its description of the world (Blumberg et al., 2011). Within the context of this research study, following such a methodology may have also provided valuable insights through a more in-depth understanding of the culture of the organisation. However, due to time constraints, such an approach would not have been practical. However, ethnography may be appropriate for future longitudinal studies.

9.4.3. Generalisability

The main limitation of qualitative research is its lack of generalisability. Nevertheless, this limitation does not affect the trustworthiness of the findings since the purpose of this study was not to generalise findings, but to obtain a rich description of entrepreneurial leadership. As stated back in Chapter 6, the purpose of this study was not to provide an objective evidence of reality but a socially created picture of it (Hammersley, 2002). The study was focused on the retail pharmacy context in order to capture the subjective perspective of the entrepreneurs and their employees. However, as previously stated, the concept of transferability or fittingness proposed by Lincoln and Guba (1985) needs to be considered; therefore, to make the research more transferable to other settings, rich and elaborate

information on the background of the respondents and the setting of the study were obtained.

9.4.4. Empirical model

Another limitation of this study was the use of the Katz model as the basis for examining the entrepreneurial leadership skills. The framework consists of three broad components which embrace a variety of associated elements. Therefore, there was a requirement to disaggregate many of the elements from the broader components. In addition, there was a considerable overlap of these skills in different categories; for example, communication skills is both a cognitive and an interpersonal skill in the Katz framework. Nevertheless, the findings of this study confirm the usefulness of the Katz framework on leadership skills, even in entrepreneurial settings. As stated earlier, the domain of entrepreneurial leadership currently lacks a definitive framework on entrepreneurial leadership skills, and most models identified are trait-driven (Carpenter, 2012; Gupta et al., 2004), hence the proposed empirical model developed based on robust findings offers a solution. However, further research is required to confirm the authenticity of the empirical model developed in this study.

9.5. Recommendations for future research

This study contains original empirical evidence in entrepreneurial leadership. However, there are a number of areas into which this study topic can be taken further. Six main areas have been identified:

9.5.1. Other sectors and countries

Although the research was carried out in a vibrant sector (the retail pharmacy sector in Nigeria), future research studies should examine other sectors, and thereby expand the scope of the study. By choosing a different sector and by increasing the number of participants in a developing economy, researchers could further confirm and enrich the evidence provided on entrepreneurial leadership. Moreover, the scope of the study can also be expanded to other developing countries. By testing the empirical model in other developing countries, the picture of an entrepreneurial leader proposed in this study can be confirmed.

9.5.2. The spiritual dimension

Spirituality was identified in the data analysis. Many of the respondents in the study were religious and attributed their success to their spiritual beliefs. Further research on the impact of spirituality in entrepreneurial leadership would be a useful avenue to explore. This could be attempted by conducting the research presented within this thesis in an agnostic context, by individuals who do not hold strong religious beliefs.

9.5.3. Entrepreneurial teams

The data was drawn from single owners of the retail pharmacies. Future research could examine entrepreneurial teams. This may provide additional insights into entrepreneurial leadership skills. Such a study could usefully examine employees' perceptions of the entrepreneurial leadership skills of each member of an entrepreneurial team.

9.5.4. National culture

It has been shown in this study that national culture is an intervening condition for entrepreneurial leadership. Such national culture is hard to change and influences the organisations present within that context. Therefore, future studies should consider the effect of national culture on the leadership skills of an entrepreneurial leader. Such a study may provide a deeper insight, not only by examining national culture, but also by examining the organisational culture and other sub-cultures.

9.5.5. Survey scale

The coding information on entrepreneurial leadership skills provided in Appendix 8 is valuable, and could be turned into a grid for readers to self-test their own entrepreneurial leadership style. Therefore, researchers of future studies could develop an appropriate survey scale, which could be used to ascertain the entrepreneurial leadership skill set for a larger sample size.

9.5.6. Alternative approaches

For future studies, researchers should adopt alternative approaches such as ethnography, which would provide a more in-depth understanding of the entrepreneurial leadership of these entrepreneurs. Such an approach may be appropriate for future longitudinal studies.

9.6. Conclusion

This study has examined the entrepreneurial leadership of entrepreneurs in a developing economy such as Nigeria. The challenges these entrepreneurs face in this

setting were explored, and the entrepreneurial leadership skills important for success in this environment were identified. The concept of entrepreneurial leadership was investigated by way of a qualitative approach comprising semi-structured interviews with 51 respondents. A dual perspective from the entrepreneurs and their employees was adopted for the study, which was useful in data triangulation. In addition, a systematic literature review was conducted, and this served as a valuable resource in identifying the knowledge gaps in the field, especially from the perspective of a developing economy.

In this study, a vivid picture of entrepreneurial leadership has been provided, and an empirical skill-based model of this phenomenon in a developing economy was proposed. The study has implications in both theory and practice. The results of the study provide an empirical skill-based framework on entrepreneurial leadership in a developing economy, a subject for which there exists a paucity of literature. In practice, this study serves as a useful reference for practitioners and policy makers in the retail pharmacy sector on the skills and other factors required of entrepreneurial leaders in this sector.

This thesis has therefore provided a valuable contribution to knowledge - theoretically, empirically, and methodologically. This investigation into the entrepreneurial leadership skills in a fast moving sector in a developing economy context has offered a new insight on this phenomenon.

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APPENDICES

Appendix 1: Interview guide

Appendix 1a: Interview Protocol for Employers

Section 1

Introduction and explanation of research- expand on previous email correspondence- provide additional background information

Underline the anonymity of interviewees will be maintained.

Section 2

Ask the Employers about their background, and how, when and why they established the business and the challenges faced.

Section 3

Ask the Employers about their skills

GENERAL QUESTIONS TO TEASE OUT THE SKILLS

What are your responsibilities and tasks in the organisation?

What skills do you think you possess that makes this pharmacy so successful?

What do you think makes you successful? (i.e. capable of running this business)

Is this the first place you have worked? What other organisations did you work for before establishing this one?

TECHNICAL SKILLS

When did you qualify as a pharmacist?

Do you think your educational qualification as a pharmacist has been useful in running this pharmacy?

What other qualifications do you think is valuable in a pharmacy business, apart from being a pharmacist? Do you have other qualifications?

CONCEPTUAL SKILLS

How do you effectively run your branches?

Who are your suppliers? How do you manage your relationship with them?

How do you make your decisions?

How do you manage competition?

How do you build a successful customer base?

INTERPERSONAL SKILLS

How well do you relate with your employees?

Employees are different, how do you respond to their varying personalities?

What do you look for in an employee?

Do you relate personally to your customers, suppliers and staff?

Have you ever had any issues / misunderstanding with any of your managers or staff?

How did you resolve it?

Section 4

Attempt to get the employer to talk about their personal qualities.

GENERAL QUESTIONS TO TEASE OUT THE TRAITS

Apart from the skills you mentioned initially, what will you say your personal qualities are? (i.e. What are your strengths in leading the organisation?)

What is the most important habit one needs to acquire to make a person more effective in everything one does?

What has been your most satisfying moment in business?

For example

HIGH ENERGY LEVEL AND STRESS TOLERANCE

How many hours do you work a day on average?

Do you think managing X branches is stressful?

SELF CONFIDENCE

Are you happy with the progress of X pharmacy to date?

How would others describe you?

INTERNAL LOCUS OF CONTROL

How long do you stick with an idea before giving up?

CREATIVITY / INNOVATIVENESS

Have you made any changes in the pharmacy since you started? What are the changes? Why did you make them?

RISK TAKING

Do you consider yourself as a risk taker?

What sacrifices have you had to make to be a successful entrepreneur?

VISION

Where do you see you and this pharmacy in the next 5 years?

If you had the chance to start your career over again, what would you do differently?

Section 5

Ask the employer about the challenges the business faces in the environmental context

For example

Has the business had challenges? What are the challenges?

What are the challenges your boss faces in running this business in Nigeria?

How was the business able to respond to them?

Section 6

Wrap-up. For example: Do you have more reflections on your leadership that you would like to share?

Ask interviewee if any significant information has been missed in relation to the skills of a successful entrepreneurial leader?

Thank interviewee and ask if you could, if necessary, contact them again to clarify any points.

Emphasise again the anonymity of the interviewees.

Appendix 1b: Interview Protocol for Employees

Section 1

Introduction and explanation of research- expand on previous email correspondence- provide additional background information

Underline the anonymity of interviewees will be maintained.

Section 2

Ask the Employees about their background, and when and why and how long they have worked for this company.

For example

Is this the first place you have worked? What other organisations have you worked for before this one?

What do you enjoy about working here?

What is the name of the owner of this pharmacy?

How close are you to her / him?

Section 3

Ask the employees about their Employer's skills

GENERAL QUESTIONS TO TEASE OUT THE SKILLS

How will you define your Boss?

What makes him or her good boss?

What are your Bosses' responsibilities or tasks in the company?

What skills do you think him/she possesses that makes him/ her successful?

What do you think makes he or she capable of running the business?

TECHNICAL SKILLS

Is your boss a pharmacist?

Do you think her/him being a pharmacist makes a difference to running the pharmacy?

What other qualifications do you think may be relevant in running the pharmacy?

CONCEPTUAL SKILLS

Who are your competitors?

How does your boss manage them?

You mentioned there were X branches, do you know how he or she effectively runs them all?

INTERPERSONAL SKILLS

How well does your boss relate with you and other employees?

Does he or she relate well with customers, suppliers and other stakeholders?

Have you ever had any issues / misunderstanding with your boss? How did you resolve it?

Would you say your boss is happy?

How often do you have meetings?

What is usually the agenda?

Do you receive bonuses, awards, recognitions, pay rise etc? How often? Do you think they are necessary for motivation?

Has there been a time where you thought of leaving the pharmacy? What was the situation? Why did you change your mind?

Section 4

Ask the employee about the employer's personal qualities

GENERAL QUESTIONS TO TEASE OUT TRAITS

Apart from the skills you mentioned earlier, what other personal qualities do you think your boss has that makes him/she better than your previous bosses?

What are his or her strengths in leading the organisation?

For example

HIGH ENERGY LEVEL AND STRESS TOLERANCE

Do you consider your boss as a hard worker?

SELF CONFIDENCE (Information available in general questions)

INTERNAL LOCUS OF CONTROL

How does your boss react to challenges / pressures?

CREATIVITY / INNOVATIVENESS

Can you tell me a time a change occurred in this business, as well as the result of the change?

RISK TAKING

What are the risks involved in running this kind of business?

VISION

Do you know what the plans are for the future of the business?

Section 5

Ask the employee about the challenges the business faces in the environmental context

For example

Has the business had challenges? What are the challenges?

What are the challenges your boss faces in running this business in Nigeria?

How was the business able to respond to them?

Section 6

Wrap-up. For example: Do you have more reflections on your employer's leadership that you would like to share?

Ask interviewee if any significant information has been missed in relation to the skills of a successful entrepreneurial leader?

Thank interviewee and ask if you could, if necessary, contact them again to clarify any points.

Emphasise again the anonymity of the interviewees.

Appendix 2: Sample invitation letter to participants

Christian Harrison
Business school,
University of the West of Scotland
Paisley, Scotland.

The CEO,

.....

Dear Sir/Madam,

Letter of introduction

I am a pharmacist by training and was born and bred in Nigeria. While practising as a pharmacist in Nigeria, I witnessed challenges and obstacles especially in the retail pharmacy environment. However, I realised that despite the turbulence and competition in this setting, some retail pharmacy entrepreneurs were more successful than others. Arguably, their success is attributed to their leadership skills. Therefore, this supposition serves as the backbone of my research.

I am currently pursuing a PhD at the University of the West of Scotland. My research involves examining Entrepreneurial leadership in the retail pharmacy sector of a developing economy namely; Nigeria. The aim of this study is to understand the challenges such entrepreneurs face in this setting and to determine if entrepreneurial leadership skills are important for success in this environment. Specifically, the research is concerned with understanding the impact of entrepreneurial leadership on the entrepreneurial process of the retail pharmacy sector. It is in this context that I write to ask you for your assistance in helping me contribute to knowledge in this domain.

From the information obtained from the Pharmacist council of Nigeria, it appears that you fit the ideal profile to provide the information I require to generate theory in this area. The information obtained show that you have been successful in this sector and have shown growth in terms of expansion in such a dynamic and turbulent environment.

I understand and appreciate that time is always the essence in business. Nevertheless, I would appreciate if you could spare me about an hour and thirty minutes of your time to talk about yourself and in particular what has made you successful. In addition, I will appreciate if I am given the opportunity to talk with two of your employees to serve as respondents in my study. If you might be concerned about the confidentiality of the information provided, I wish to assure you that all ethical guidelines will be observed and all information collected will be treated in confidence. In addition, the anonymity of your identity is guaranteed. I believe your generous participation will have a significant contribution to the study.

I hope you can assist me and I look forward to hearing from you.

Yours Sincerely,

Christian Harrison

Appendix 3: Systematic Literature Review

Databases	Search strings	Search Criteria	Results	Journals	Books	Case	Abstract Reviewed	Relevant Articles
Emerald	Entrep*	keyword	2,168	2,068	52	48		
	Lead*	all fields	1,816	1,723	51	42		
	Developing	all fields	1,389	1,319	42	28		
	"Entrepreneurial Leadership"	all fields	116	111	4	1	111	9
Wiley online	Entrep*	keyword	664	502	162	-		
	Lead*	all fields	573	455	118	-		
	Developing	all fields	532	431	101	-		
	"Entrepreneurial Leadership"	all fields	16	16	-	-	16	1
Sage Journals	Entrep*	keyword	641	641	-	-		
	Lead*	all fields	554	554	-	-		
	Developing	all fields	387	387	-	-		
	"Entrepreneurial Leadership"	all fields	27	27			27	1
Science Direct	Entrep*	keyword	1,475	1,431	47	24		
	Lead*	all fields	1,278	1,240	41	21		
	Developing	all fields	923	895	31	16		
	"Entrepreneurial Leadership"	all fields		46	2	1		

	Leadership"		48				48	6
Taylor & Francis	Entrep*	keyword	764	758		6		
	Lead*	all fields	694	690		4		
	Developing	all fields	665	663		2		
	"Entrepreneurial Leadership"	all fields	20	20			20	5
Web of knowledge	Entrep*	Topic	47,112					
	Lead*	Topic	2,861					
	Developing	Topic	748					
	"Entrepreneurial Leadership"	Topic	23				23	11
Springer link	Entrep*	all fields	63,729					
	Lead*	all fields	43,216					
	Developing	all fields	37,283					
	"Entrepreneurial Leadership"	all fields	224				224	3
Ingentaconnect	Entrep*	all fields	52,225					
	Lead*	all fields	27,956					
	Developing	all fields	26,321					
	"Entrepreneurial Leadership"	all fields	-					

FIRST SEARCH : TOTAL NUMBER OF RELEVANT ARTICLES 36

Databases	Search strings	Search Criteria	Results	Journals	Books	Case	Abstract Reviewed	Relevant Articles
Emerald	Lead*	keyword	4,920	4,866	37	17		
	Entrep*	all fields	891	869	11	11		
	Developing	all fields	639	622	10	7		
	"Entrepreneurial Leadership"	all fields	39	38	-	1	39	9
Wiley online	Lead*	keyword	8,209	5,634	2,564	-		
	Entrep*	all fields	314	157	157	-		
	Developing	all fields	292	153	139	-		
	"Entrepreneurial Leadership"	all fields	12	8	4	-	12	1
Sage Journals	Lead*	keyword	2,756	2,756	-	-		
	Entrep*	all fields	463	463	-	-		
	Developing	all fields	343	343	-	-		
	"Entrepreneurial Leadership"	all fields	10	10			10	1
Science Direct	Lead*	keyword	14,899			23		

				3,770				
	Entrep*	all fields	472	218				
	Developing	all fields	357	210				
	"Entrepreneurial Leadership"	all fields	19	10			10	5
Taylor & Francis	Lead*	keyword	3,793	3,770			23	
	Entrep*	all fields	218	218				
	Developing	all fields	210	210				
	"Entrepreneurial Leadership"	all fields	10	10			10	5
Web of knowledge	Lead*	Topic	5,485,535					
	Entrep*	Topic	2,861					
	Developing	Topic	748					
	"Entrepreneurial Leadership"	Topic	23				23	11
Springer link	Lead*	all fields	2,676,974					
	Entrep*	all fields	43,216					
	Developing	all fields	37,283					
	"Entrepreneurial Leadership"	all fields	224				224	3
Ingentaconnect	Lead*	all fields	702,472					

	Entrep*	all fields	27,956					
	Developing	all fields	26,321					
	"Entrepreneurial Leadership"	all fields	-					
SECOND SEARCH : TOTAL NUMBER OF RELEVANT ARTICLES 35								
Databases	Search strings	Search Criteria	Results	Journals	Books	Case	Abstract Reviewed	Relevant Articles
Emerald	"Entrepreneurial Leadership"	all fields	288	242	45	1		
	Pharm*	all fields	25	20	5		25	-
Wiley online	"Entrepreneurial Leadership"	all fields	370	348	22	-		
	Pharm*	all fields	40	34	6	-	40	-
Sage Journals	"Entrepreneurial Leadership"	all fields	174	174	-	-		
	Pharm*	all fields	12	12	-	-	12	-
Science Direct	"Entrepreneurial Leadership"	all fields	272	241	32	3		
	Pharm*	all fields	31	28	3		31	1
Taylor & Francis	"Entrepreneurial Leadership"	all fields	306	300	6			
	Pharm*	all fields	21	21				

							21	1
Web of knowledge	"Entrepreneurial Leadership"	all fields	68	68				
	Pharm*	all fields	1	1			1	1
Springer link	"Entrepreneurial Leadership"	all fields	261	121	136	4		
	Pharm*	all fields	27	9	16	2	27	1
Ingentaconnect	"Entrepreneurial Leadership"	all fields	240	240				
	Pharm*	all fields	-	-				

THIRD SEARCH : TOTAL NUMBER OF RELEVANT ARTICLES 4

Databases	Search strings	Search Criteria	Results	Journals	Books	Case	Abstract Reviewed	Relevant Articles
Emerald	"Entrepreneurial Leadership"	all fields	288	242	45	1		
	Developing	all fields	221	188	32	1		-
	Challenges OR Abilities OR Capabilities OR Attributes OR Competencies OR Skills	all fields	202	166	35	1	202	9
Wiley online	"Entrepreneurial Leadership"	all fields	370	348	22	-		
	Developing	all fields	353	334	19	-	-	-

	Challenges OR Abilities OR Capabilities OR Attributes OR Competencies OR Skills	all fields	339	320	19			339	7
Sage Journals	"Entrepreneurial Leadership"	all fields	174	174	-	-			
	Developing	all fields	127	127	-	-		-	-
	Challenges OR Abilities OR Capabilities OR Attributes OR Competencies OR Skills	all fields	-	-					
Science Direct	"Entrepreneurial Leadership"	all fields	272	241	32	3			
	Developing	all fields	193	167	27	2		-	-
	Challenges OR Abilities OR Capabilities OR Attributes OR Competencies OR Skills	all fields	185	160	26	2		185	8
Taylor & Francis	"Entrepreneurial Leadership"	all fields	306	300	6				
	Developing	all fields	289	285	4			-	-
	Challenges OR Abilities OR Capabilities OR Attributes OR Competencies OR Skills	all fields	268	264	4			268	10
Web of knowledge	"Entrepreneurial Leadership"	all fields	68	68					
	Developing	all fields	23	23				-	-

	Challenges OR Abilities OR Capabilities OR Attributes OR Competencies OR Skills	all fields	7	7			7	2
Springer link	"Entrepreneurial Leadership"	all fields	261	121	136	4		
	Developing	all fields	225	110	111	4		
	Challenges OR Abilities OR Capabilities OR Attributes OR Competencies OR Skills	all fields	216	105	107	4	216	4
Ingentaconnect	"Entrepreneurial Leadership"	all fields	240	240				
	Developing	all fields	-	-				
	Challenges OR Abilities OR Capabilities OR Attributes OR Competencies OR Skills	all fields	-	-				
FOURTH SEARCH : TOTAL NUMBER OF RELEVANT ARTICLES 40								
Grand Total of relevant articles 115								
Total number of duplicates 70								
Articles accepted 45								
FINAL SEARCH WITH GOOGLE SCHOLAR								
Databases	Search strings	Search Criteria	Results	Journals	Books	Case	Abstract Reviewed	Relevant Articles

Google Scholar	Entrepreneurial Leadership	In the title excluding citations and patents	263				263	56
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Duplicate articles after Google search 29

Articles accepted 27

Total number of articles 72

Articles accepted from citations and references of the 72 articles: 7

Total number of articles for the review: 79

Exclusion and Inclusion Criteria

Articles should be in English

Focus of the paper must be on entrepreneurial leadership as a style of leadership.

Appendix 4: Articles accepted for the Review

Author's name	Title and Year of Publication	Type of Publication	Name of journal	Number of citations	Relevant citations	Duplicate citations	Citations accepted	Number of References	Relevant references	Duplicate references	References accepted	Articles accepted
Kempster, S. & Cope, J. (2010)	Learning to lead in the entrepreneurial context. <i>International journal of entrepreneurial behaviour & research</i> , 16, 5-34.	Research Paper	<i>International journal of entrepreneurial behaviour & research</i>	36	9	7	2	116	4	4	0	2
Darling, J., Gabrielsson, M. & Seristö, H. (2007)	Enhancing contemporary entrepreneurs hip: a focus on management leadership. <i>European Business Review</i> , 19, 4-22.	Research Paper	<i>European Business Review</i>	27	2	2	0	46	0	0	0	0
Nicola Patterson, Sharon Mavin, Jane Turner, (2012)	"Envisioning female entrepreneur: leaders anew from a gender perspective", <i>Gender in Management: An International Journal</i> , Vol. 27 Iss: 6, pp.395 - 416	Conceptual Paper	<i>An International Journal</i>	1	0	0	0	93	6	6	0	0
Cogliser, C. C. & Brigham, K. H. (2004)	The intersection of leadership and entrepreneurship: Mutual lessons to be learned. <i>The Leadership Quarterly</i> , 15(6), 771-799.	Review Paper	<i>The Leadership Quarterly</i>	89	24	24	0	329	2	2	0	0
Vecchio. R. P. (2003)	Entrepreneurship and leadership: common trends and common threads. <i>Human Resource Management Review</i> 13(2), 303-327	Research Paper	<i>Human Resource Management Review</i>	177	22	22	0	107	0	0	0	0

Bagheri, A., and Pihie, Z. A. L. (2012)	Entrepreneurial Leadership Learning: The Critical Role of Involvement. Proceedings of the 7th European Conference on Innovation and Entrepreneurship, Vol 1 and 2 pp. 751-758	Research Paper	Proceedings of the 7th European Conference on Innovation and Entrepreneurship, Vol 1 and 2 pp. 751-758	0	0	0	0	45	8	8	0	0
Ballein, K. M. (1998)	Entrepreneurial leadership characteristics of SNEs emerge as their role develops. <i>Nursing administration quarterly</i> . Vol.22(2), pp.60-9.	Research Paper	<i>Nursing administration quarterly</i>	7	0	0	0	5	0	0	0	0
Hentschke, G. C. (2010)	Developing Entrepreneurial Leaders. <i>In Developing Successful Leadership</i> (pp. 115-132). Springer Netherlands.	Conceptual paper	<i>In Developing Successful Leadership</i> Springer Netherlands.	0	0	0	0	37	0	0	0	0
Greenberg, D., McKone-Sweet, K., and Wilson, H. J. (2013)	Entrepreneurial leaders: Creating opportunity in an unknowable world. <i>Leader to Leader</i> . Vol.2013(67), pp.56-62.	Conceptual paper	<i>Leader to Leader</i>	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Hmieleski, K. M., and Ensley, M. D. (2007)	A contextual examination of new venture performance: entrepreneur leadership behavior, top management team heterogeneity, and environmental dynamism. <i>Journal of Organizational Behavior</i> . Vol.28(7), pp.865-889.	Research Paper	<i>Journal of Organizational Behavior</i> .	68	2	2	0	104	4	3	1	1
Lang, J. A. (2013)	A Review of "The New Entrepreneurial Leader: Developing Leaders Who	Review paper	Journal of Education for Business.	0	0	0	0	2	0	0	0	0

	Shape Social & Economic Opportunity". Journal of Education for Business. Vol.88(3), pp.184-185.											
Leitch, C. M., McMullan, C. & Harrison, R. T. (2009)	Leadership development in SMEs: an action learning approach. <i>Action Learning: Research and Practice</i> , 6, 243-263.	Research paper	<i>Action Learning: Research and Practice</i> ,	11	1	1	0	78	3	3	0	0
Kansikas, J., Laakkonen, A., Sarpo, V. & Kontinen, T. (2012)	Entrepreneurial leadership and familiness as resources for strategic entrepreneurship. <i>International journal of entrepreneurial behaviour & research</i> , 18 (2), 141-158	Research Paper	<i>International journal of entrepreneurial behaviour & research</i>	5	0	0	0	39	9	8	1	1
Nicola Patterson, Sharon Mavin, Jane Turner, (2012)	"Unsettling the gender binary: experiences of gender in entrepreneurial leadership and implications for HRD", <i>European Journal of Training and Development</i> , Vol. 36 Iss: 7, pp.687 - 711	Research Paper	<i>European Journal of Training and Development</i>	2	0	0	0	106	4	4	0	0
Jones, H. & Crompton, H. (2009)	Enterprise logic and small firms: a model of authentic entrepreneurial leadership. <i>Journal of Strategy and Management</i> , 2(4), 329-351.	Research Paper	<i>Journal of Strategy and Management</i>	14	0	0	0	96	5	5	0	0
D'intino, R. S., Boyles, T., Neck, C. P. & Hall, J. R. (2008)	Visionary entrepreneurial leadership in the aircraft industry: The Boeing Company legacy. <i>Journal of Management</i>	Case Study	<i>Journal of Management History</i>	5	2	2	0	47	0	0	0	0

	<i>History</i> , 14, 39-54.											
Swiercz, P. M. & Lydon, S. R. (2002)	Entrepreneurial leadership in high-tech firms: a field study. <i>Leadership & Organization Development Journal</i> , 23, 380-389.	Research Paper	<i>Leadership & Organization Development Journal</i>	47	17	16	1	20	0	0	0	1
Van Assche, T. (2005)	The Impact of Entrepreneurial Leadership on EU High Politics: A Case Study of Jacques Delors and the Creation of EMU. <i>Leadership</i> . Vol.1(3), pp.279-298.	Case Study	<i>Leadership</i>	6	0	0	0	47	1	1	0	0
Strubler, D. C., and Redekop, B. W. (2010)	Entrepreneurial human resource leadership: A conversation with Dwight Carlson. <i>Human Resource Management</i> . Vol.49(4), pp.793-804.	Case Study	<i>Human Resource Management</i>	1	0	0	0	29	1	1	0	0
Ruvio, A., Rosenblatt, Z., and Hertz-Lazarowitz, R. (2010)	Entrepreneurial leadership vision in nonprofit vs. for-profit organizations. <i>The Leadership Quarterly</i> . Vol.21(1), pp.144-158	Research Paper	<i>The Leadership Quarterly</i>	17	4	4	0	95	3	3	0	0
Okudan, G. E. & Rzasa, S. E. (2006)	A project-based approach to entrepreneurial leadership education. <i>Technovation</i> , 26(2), 195-210.	Research Paper	<i>Technovation</i>	54	14	14	0	27	0	0	0	0
Gupta, V., MacMillan, I. C., & Surie, G., (2004)	Entrepreneurial leadership: developing and measuring a cross-cultural construct. <i>Journal of Business Venturing</i>	Research Paper	<i>Journal of Business Venturing</i>	188	29	29	0	89	2	2	0	0

	19(2), 241–260											
Bagheri, A., and Pihie, Z. A. L. (2010)	Entrepreneurial Leadership Learning: In Search of Missing Links. <i>Procedia - Social and Behavioral Sciences</i> . Vol.7(0), pp.470-479.	Research Paper	<i>Procedia - Social and Behavioral Sciences</i>	3	1	1	0	49	7	7	0	0
Bagheri, A., Akinaliah, Z., & Pihie, L., (2011)	Entrepreneurship leadership: towards a model for learning & development. <i>Human Resource Development international</i> 14(4), pp. 447-463	Research Paper	<i>Human Resource Development international</i>	2	0	0	0	68	11	11	0	0
Bagheri, A., Lope Pihie, Z. A., and Krauss, S. E. (2013)	Entrepreneurial leadership competencies among Malaysian university student entrepreneurial leaders. <i>Asia Pacific Journal of Education</i> . pp.1-16.	Research Paper	<i>Asia Pacific Journal of Education</i>	0	0	0	0	50	8	8	0	0
Bagheri, A., and Lope Pihie, Z. A. (2012)	Role of University Entrepreneurship Programs in Developing Students' Entrepreneurial Leadership Competencies : Perspectives From Malaysian Undergraduate Students. <i>Journal of Education for Business</i> . Vol.88(1), pp.51-61.	Research Paper	<i>Journal of Education for Business</i>	0	0	0	0	65	8	8	0	0
Wang, C. L., Tee, D. D., and Ahmed, P. K. (2012)	Entrepreneurial leadership and context in Chinese firms: a tale of two Chinese private enterprises. <i>Asia Pacific Business Review</i> .	Case Study	<i>Asia Pacific Business Review</i> .	0	0	0	0	78	3	3	0	0

	Vol.18(4), pp.505-530.											
Choi, E. K. (2009)	Entrepreneurial leadership in the Meiji cotton spinners' early conceptualisation of global competition. <i>Business History</i> . Vol.51(6), pp.927-958.	Research Paper	<i>Business History</i>	2	0	0	0	223	0	0	0	0
Leitch, C. M., McMullan, C. & Harrison, R. T. (2012)	The Development of Entrepreneurial Leadership: The Role of Human, Social and Institutional Capital. <i>British Journal of Management</i> , 24(3), 347-366	Research Paper	<i>British Journal of Management</i>	3	1	1	0	141	9	9	0	0
Surie, G. & Ashley, A. (2008)	Integrating Pragmatism and Ethics in Entrepreneurial Leadership for Sustainable Value Creation. <i>Journal of Business Ethics</i> , 81(1), 235-246.	Research Paper	<i>Journal of Business Ethics</i>	38	9	9	0	63	1	1	0	0
Oliver, T. R., and Paul-Shaheen, P. (1997)	Translating ideas into actions: entrepreneurial leadership in state health care reforms. <i>Journal of Health Politics, Policy & Law</i> . Vol.22(3), pp.721-788.	Research Paper	<i>Journal of Health Politics, Policy & Law</i> .	83	0	0	0	98	0	0	0	0
Renko, M., Tarabishy, A., Carsrud, A. L., & Brannback, M., (2012a)	Entrepreneurial leadership and family business. <i>International Studies in Entrepreneurship</i> . 15, 169-184	Case Study	<i>International Studies in Entrepreneurship</i>	0	0	0	0	35	3	3	0	0
Currie, G., Humphreys, M., Ucbasaran, D. & Mcmanus, S.	Entrepreneurial Leadership in the English Public Sector: Paradox or Possibility?	Research Paper	<i>Public Administration</i>	26	1	1	0	84	0	0	0	0

(2008)	<i>Public Administration</i> , 86(4), 987-1008.											
Chen, Ming-Hei (2007)	Entrepreneurial leadership & New ventures: Creativity in Entrepreneurial teams. <i>Creativity & Innovation Management</i> 16(3), pp. 239-249.	Research Paper	<i>Creativity & Innovation Management</i>	52	17	17	0	53	1	1	0	0
Lippitt, G. L. (1987)	Entrepreneurial Leadership: A Performing Art*. <i>The Journal of Creative Behavior</i> , 21(3), 264-270.	Conceptual Paper	<i>The Journal of Creative Behavior</i>	6	2	1	1					1
Nicholson, N., (1998)	Personality & Entrepreneurial leadership: A style of the heads of the UK's most successful companies. <i>European Management Journal</i> . 16(5), 529-539	Research paper	<i>European Management Journal</i> .	70	6	6	0	27	0	0	0	0
Pashiardis, P., and Savvides, V. (2011)	The Interplay Between Instructional and Entrepreneurial Leadership Styles in Cyprus Rural Primary Schools. <i>Leadership and Policy in Schools</i> . Vol.10(4), pp.412-427.	Case Study	<i>Leadership and Policy in Schools</i>	0	0	0	0	22	0	0	0	0
Darling, J. R., and Beebe, S. A. (2007)	Enhancing Entrepreneurial Leadership: A Focus on Key Communication Priorities. <i>Journal of Small Business & Entrepreneurship</i> . Vol.20(2), pp.151-167.	Conceptual paper	<i>Journal of Small Business & Entrepreneurship</i> .	5	0	0	0	53	0	0	0	0
Hansson, F. & Mønsted,	Research leadership as	Research paper	<i>Higher Education</i>	15	1	1	0	47	0	0	0	0

M. (2008)	entrepreneurial organizing for research. <i>Higher Education</i> , 55, 651-670.											
Tice, B. P. (2005)	Advancing pharmacy through entrepreneurial leadership. <i>Journal of the American Pharmacists Association</i> . Vol.45(5), pp.546-553.	Conceptual paper	<i>Journal of the American Pharmacists Association</i>	3	0	0	0	9	0	0	0	0
Kuratko, D. F., (2007)	Entrepreneurial leadership in the 21st century. <i>Journal of Leadership & Organizational Studies</i> . 13(4), 1-11.	Conceptual paper	<i>Journal of Leadership & Organizational Studies</i>	73	13	13	0	45	0	0	0	0
Fernald, L. W. Jr., Solomon, G. T. & Tarabishy, A. (2005)	A new paradigm: Entrepreneurial leadership. <i>Southern Business Review</i> , 30(2), 1-10.	Review paper	<i>Southern Business Review</i>	48	15	15	0	41	0	0	0	0
Van Zyl, H., and Mathur-Helm, B. (2007)	Exploring a conceptual model, based on the combined effects of entrepreneurial leadership, market orientation and relationship marketing orientation on South Africa's small tourism business performance. <i>S Afr J Bus Manag</i> . Vol.38(2), pp.17-24.	Research paper	<i>S Afr J Bus Manag</i>	23	1	1	0	63	2	2	0	0
Santora, J. C., Seaton, W., and Sarros, J. C. (1999)	Changing Times: Entrepreneurial Leadership In A Community-Based Nonprofit Organization. <i>Journal of Leadership & Organizational</i>	Research paper	<i>Journal of Leadership & Organizational Studies</i>	19	2	1	1	33	2	2	0	1

	<i>I Studies</i> . Vol.6(3-4), pp.101-109.											
Kuratko, D. F., & Hornsby, J. S. (1999)	Corporate entrepreneurial leadership for the 21st century. <i>Journal of Leadership & Organizational Studies</i> , 5(2), 27-39.	Research paper	<i>Journal of Leadership & Organizational Studies</i> ,	18	6	6	0	65	0	0	0	0
Okudan, G. E., and Rzasa, S. E. (2004)	"Teaching entrepreneurial leadership: A project-based approach" <i>Frontiers in Education</i> , 2004. <i>FIE 2004. 34th Annual. City: IEEE</i> , pp. T2E/18-T2E/23 Vol. 1.	Research paper	" <i>Frontiers in Education</i> , 2004. <i>FIE 2004. 34th Annual. City</i>	5	0	0	0	23	0	0	0	0
Devarajan, T., Ramachandran, K., and Ramnarayan, S. (2003)	"Entrepreneurial leadership and thriving innovation activity" <i>Proceedings of 7th International Conference on Global Business & Economic Development, Bangkok, forthcoming. City: Citeseer</i> , pp. 8-11.	Research paper	<i>Proceedings of 7th International Conference on Global Business & Economic Development, Bangkok, forthcoming. City</i>	7	0	0	0	50	0	0	0	0
Reimers-Hild, C., and King, J. W. (2009)	Six questions for entrepreneurial leadership and innovation in distance education. <i>Online journal of distance learning administration</i> . Vol.12(4).	Conceptual paper	<i>Online journal of distance learning administration</i> .	5	0	0	0	43	1	1	0	0
Bagheri, A., and Pihie, Z. A. L. (2009)	An exploratory study of entrepreneurial leadership development of university students. <i>European Journal of Social Sciences</i> . Vol.11(1), pp.177-190.	Research paper	<i>European Journal of Social Sciences</i> .	3	0	0	0	57	9	9	0	0
Mapunda, G.	Entrepreneurial leadership development of university students. <i>European Journal of Social Sciences</i> . Vol.11(1), pp.177-190.	Research paper	<i>Journal of Leadership & Organizational Studies</i> ,	3	0	0	0	19	0	0	0	0

(2007)	al Leadership and Indigenous Enterprise Development. <i>Journal of Asia Entrepreneurship and Sustainability</i> . Vol.3(3), pp.1-16.	paper	<i>Asia Entrepreneurship and Sustainability</i> .									
Bagheri, A., Akmaliah, Z., and Pihle, L. (2010)	Role of Family and Entrepreneurial Leadership Development of University Students. <i>World Applied Sciences Journal</i> . Vol.11(4), pp.434-442.	Research paper	<i>World Applied Sciences Journal</i>	2	0	0	0	43	9	9	0	0
Bremer, I. (2009)	Common factors between Swedish and Chinese entrepreneurial leadership styles. <i>Human Resource Management: Issues, Challenges and Opportunities</i> . p.135.	Research paper	<i>Business Intelligence Journal</i>	2	1	1	0	54	0	0	0	0
Roomi, M. A. & Harrison, C., (2011)	Entrepreneurial leadership: What is it & how should it be taught? <i>International Review of Entrepreneurship</i> 9(3), 1-44.	Review paper	<i>International Review of Entrepreneurship</i>	2	0	0	0	128	14	14	0	0
Flamholtz, E. G. (2011)	The leadership molecule hypothesis: implications for entrepreneurial organizations. <i>International Review of Entrepreneurship</i> . Vol.9 pp.1-23.	Research paper	<i>International Review of Entrepreneurship</i> .	1	0	0	0	32	1	1	0	0
Agus, A., and Hassan, Z. (2010)	The Structural Influence of Entrepreneurial Leadership, Communication Skills, Determination and Motivation on	Research paper	<i>INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF BUSINESS AND DEVELOPMENT STUDIES</i>	0	0	0	0	43	0	0	0	0

	Sales and Customer Satisfaction. <i>INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF BUSINESS AND DEVELOPMENT STUDIES.</i>											
Hejazi, A. M., Maleki, M. M., & Naeji, M. J., (2012)	Designing a scale for measuring entrepreneurial leadership in SME's. <i>International Conference on Economics Marketing & Management</i> 28, 1-7.	Research paper	<i>International Conference on Economics Marketing & Management</i>	1	1	1	0	15	7	7	0	0
Agbim, K. C., Oriarewo, G. O., and Owutuamor, Z. B. (2013)	An Exploratory Study of the Entrepreneurial Leadership Capabilities of Entrepreneurs in Anambra State, Nigeria. <i>Journal Of Business Management & Social Sciences Research.</i> Vol.2(9), pp.68-75.	Research paper	<i>Journal Of Business Management & Social Sciences Research</i>	0	0	0	0	32	11	11	0	0
Sundararajan, M., Sundararajan, B., and Henderson, S. (2012)	Role of Meditative Foundation Entrepreneurial Leadership and New Venture Success. <i>Spirituality, Leadership and Management.</i> Vol.6(1), pp.59-70.	Research paper	<i>Spirituality, Leadership and Management.</i>	0	0	0	0	97	5	5	0	0
Abbas, S., and Tatfi, M. (2010)	ENTREPRENEURIAL LEADERSHIP: CERTAINLY A TOOL NOT A MEANS TO ORGANIZATIONAL SUCCESS. <i>Leadership.</i> Vol.1(2), p.119.	Conceptual paper	<i>Leadership</i>	0	0	0	0	4	0	0	0	0
Renko, M., Tarabishy, A., Carsrud, A. L., & Brannback, M., (2012b)	Understanding & Measuring Entrepreneurial leadership. <i>Journal of Small Business Management</i>	Research paper	<i>Journal of Small Business Management</i>	1	0	0	0	101	10	10	0	0

	1-47											
Patterson, N., Mavin, S., and Turner, J. (2012)	Experiences Of Gender Within Entrepreneurial Leadership: Complexities And Tensions From Women Entrepreneurs ' Perspectives.	Research paper		0	0	0	0	97	4	4	0	0
Renko, M., El Tarabishy, A., & Carsrud, A. R. (2009)	ENTREPRENEURIAL LEADERSHIP- CONSTRUCT REFINEMENT AND SCALE DEVELOPMENT (INTERACTIVE PAPER). <i>Frontiers of Entrepreneurship Research</i> , 29(19), 11.	Research paper	<i>Frontiers of Entrepreneurship Research</i>	0	0	0	0					
Khayesi, J. N., and Antonakis, J. (2012)	THE CONTRIBUTION OF ENTREPRENEURIAL LEADERSHIP TO FIRM PERFORMANCE: A STUDY OF SMALL AND MEDIUM-SIZED ENTREPRENEURS IN KENYA (SUMMARY). <i>Frontiers of Entrepreneurship Research</i> . Vol.32(4), p.8	Research paper	<i>Frontiers of Entrepreneurship Research</i> .	0	0	0	0					
Ahmed, A., and Ramzan, M. A (2013)	Learning and Improvement Model in Entrepreneurial Leadership.	Research paper	<i>IOSR Journal of Business and Management</i>	0	0	0	0	69	11	11	0	0
Rahab, R. (2013)	"CONCEPTUAL MODELLING OF SMALL MEDIUM ENTERPRISES PERFORMANCE IMPROVEMENT BASED ON THE ENTREPRENEURIAL LEADERSHIP AND MARKETING STRATEGIC ORIENTATION : PROSPECTIVE ISSUE FOR FURTHER	Research paper	"TOWARDS EXCELLENT SMALL BUSINESS"	0	0	0	0	56	2	2	0	0

	EMPIRICAL RESEARCH"SEMINAR INTERNASIONAL "TOWARDS EXCELLENT SMALL BUSINESS". City.											
Carpenter, M. T. H. (2012)	Cheerleader, opportunity seeker, and master strategist: ARL directors as entrepreneurial leaders. <i>College & Research Libraries</i> , 73(1), 11-32.	Research Paper	<i>College & Research Libraries</i>	3	0	0	0	30	3	3	0	0
Nancy Papalexandris, Eleanna Galanaki, (2009)	"Leadership's impact on employee engagement: Differences among entrepreneurs and professional CEOs", <i>Leadership & Organization Development Journal</i> , Vol. 30 Iss: 4, pp.365 – 385	Research Paper	<i>Leadership & Organization Development Journal</i>	17	1	1	0	60	4	4	0	0
Sambrook, S., Henley, A., Jones, K., & Norbury, H. (2011)	A Biographical Approach to Researching Leadership and Entrepreneurship Development Processes in a Small Business Context. <i>Bangor Business School Research Paper</i> , (11/004).	Research Paper	Proceedings of the 7th European Conference on Management Leadership and Governance, pp. 199-205	0	0	0	0	37	2	2	0	0
Skjærseth, J. B., and Wettestad, J. (2010)	Making the EU Emissions Trading System: The European Commission as an entrepreneurial epistemic leader. <i>Global Environmental Change</i> . Vol.20(2), pp.314-321.	Research Paper	<i>Global Environmental Change</i>	25	0	0	0	48	0	0	0	0

Karanian, B. (2007)	AC 2007-2804: ENTREPRENEURIAL LEADERSHIP AND TRANSFORMATIONAL CHANGE.	Research paper	American Society for Engineering Education	0	0	0	0	68	4	4	0	0
Siddiqui, S. (2007)	An Empirical Study of Traits Determining Entrepreneurial Leadership-An Educational Perspective. Skyline Business Review, 4(1).	Research paper	Skyline Business Review	1	0	0	0	45	4	4	0	0
Darling, J. R., Keeffe, M. J., & Ross, J. K. (2007).	Entrepreneurial leadership strategies and values: Keys to operational excellence. Journal of Small Business & Entrepreneurship, 20(1), 41-54.	Conceptual paper	Journal of Small Business & Entrepreneurship	10	1	1	0	33	0	0	0	0

Appendix 5: Information about the 7 articles obtained

Author's name	Title and Year of Publication	Type of Publication	Name of journal	Number of citations	Relevant citations	Duplicate citations	Citations accepted	Number of References	Relevant references	Duplicate references	References accepted	Articles accepted
Bagheri, A., & Pihie, Z. A. (2011)	On Becoming an Entrepreneurial Leader: A Focus on the Impacts of University Entrepreneurship Programs. <i>American Journal of Applied Sciences</i> , 8(9), 884-892	Research paper	<i>American Journal of Applied Sciences</i>	0	0	0	0	59	7	7	0	0
Pihie, Z. A. L., & Bagheri, A. (2013)	The impact of principals' entrepreneurial leadership behaviour on school organizational innovativeness. <i>Life Science Journal</i> , 10(2), 1033-1041	Research paper	<i>Life Science Journal</i>	0	0	0	0	34	10	10	0	0
Covin, J. G., & Slevin, D. P. (2004)	The concept of entrepreneurial leadership. In M. A.Hitt, & R. D.Ireland (Eds.), <i>Entrepreneurship encyclopedia</i> . Malden, MA: Blackwell Publishing.	Chapter in an edited book	<i>Entrepreneurship encyclopedia</i>	3	1	1	0	26	3	3	0	0

Guo, K.L. (2009)	Core competencies of the entrepreneurial leader in health care organizations. <i>Health Care Manager</i> , 28, 19–29.	Research paper	<i>Health Care Manager</i> ,	10	1	1	0						
Nieuwenhuizen, C. (2009)	Entrepreneurial leadership and management for change and successful business growth.	Research paper		0	0	0	0	20	2	2	0	0	
Tarabishy, A., Fernald Jr, L. W., & Solomon, G. T. (2002)	Understanding entrepreneurial leadership in today's dynamic markets. School of Business and Public Management, Department of Management Science		School of Business and Public Management, Department of Management Science	1	0	0	0						
Tarabishy, A., Solomon, G., Fernald Jr, L. W., & Sashkin, M. (2005)	The entrepreneurial leader's impact on the organization's performance in dynamic markets. <i>The Journal of private equity</i> , 8(4), 20-29.		<i>The Journal of private equity</i>	51	3	3	0						

Appendix 6 Summary of past literature from the systematic literature review

CONCEPT	AUTHORS AND YEAR OF PUBLICATION
Convergence of entrepreneurship and leadership <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Vision • Influence • innovation and creativity • planning • achievement orientation • motivation • flexibility, • patience, • persistence • risk taking 	Cogliser and Brigham, (2004), Fernald et al. (2005)
Psychological and Behavioural profile <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Entrepreneurial leadership attributes • Communication skills • Personality profile • Entrepreneurial leadership scale • Entrepreneurial leadership functions • Entrepreneurial leadership strategies 	Gupta et al., (2004); Nicholson, (1998); Renko et al. (2012b); Renko et al., (2009); Karanian, (2007); Nieuwenhuizen, (2009); Darling and Beebe, (2007); Flamholtz, (2011); Strubler and Redekop, (2010); Darling et al., (2007a); Darling et al., (2007b); Siddiqui, (2007)

CONCEPT	AUTHORS AND YEAR OF PUBLICATION
Context of Entrepreneurial leadership <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • the innovative capabilities of SMES and the creativity of entrepreneurial teams. • Entrepreneurial leadership factors • Entrepreneurial leadership competencies • family business • Gender • research groups • public sector • non-profit organisations • directors of libraries • indigenous businesses • human, social and institutional capital • the air craft industry • Sweden and China • Japanese cotton industry • Politics • Nursing and state health reforms 	Chen, (2007); Swiercz and Lydon, (2002); Hejazi et al., (2012); Renko et al., (2012a); Kansikas et al., (2012); Leitch et al., (2009); Khayesi and Antonakis, (2012); Hansson and Monsted, (2008); Currie et al., (2008); Santora et al., (1999); Carpenter, (2012); Mapunda, (2007), Patterson et al., (2012a); Patterson et al., (2012b); Patterson et al., (2012c); Leitch et al., (2012); D'Intino et al., (2008); Choi, (2009); Wang et al., (2012); Bremer, (2009); Van Assche, (2005); Ballein, (1998); Oliver and Shaheen, (1997); Devarajan et al., (2003)
Theoretical Approach <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • entrepreneurship as a separate study • entrepreneurial leadership as a social • entrepreneurial leadership in corporations • Theories and principles 	Vecchio, (2003); Kempster and Cope, (2010); Kuratko and Hornsby, (1999); Kuratko, (2007); Daily et al., (2002); Greenberg et al., (2013); Covin and Slevin, (2004); Abbas and Tatfi, (2010); Reimers-Hild and King, (2013); Hentschke, (2010); Patterson et al., (2012c); Rahab, (2013); Van Zyl and Mathur-Helm, (2007); Ahmed and Ramzan, (2013); Lippit, (1987); Tice (2005)
Comparison with other forms of leadership <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Authentic leadership • Charismatic and transformational leadership 	Darling et al., (2007a); Jones and Crompton, (2009)
Ethics and values	Darling et al., (2007a); Darling et al., (2007b); Surie and Ashley, (2008)
Entrepreneurial leadership education	Pihie and Bagheri, (2013); Bagheri et al., (2013); Bagheri and Pihie, (2012); Pashiardis and Savvides, (2011); Okudan and Rzasa, (2004); (2006); Bagheri and Pihie, (2011); Bagheri and Pihie (2010); Roomi and Harrison, (2011)
Performance <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • entrepreneurial success • sales performance and customer satisfaction • employee's satisfaction, motivation, commitment and effectiveness • top management teams 	Agbim et al., (2013); Sundararajan et al., (2012), Agus and Hassan, (2010); Papalexandris and Galanaki, (2009); Hmieleski and Ensley, (2007); Tarabishy et al., (2005)

Appendix 7: Interview Sample Excerpts

Appendix 7.1a: Business skills: MBA

Example Comments

“I have my MBA which really helped expose me to lots of things as human resource and factors that help balance the business. Every day you have to put people and work mediations, manage finance, how much are the expenses? how much profits?, salary issues..” (O)

“So to run a community you need that broad base the MBA gives you and other management courses. It exposes you to accounting principles. It exposes you to better book keeping”. (A)

Appendix 7.1b: Business function skills: Administration skills

Example Comments

“We have a system which is at different places. I have a manager who goes around and does stock of the different places and gives daily reports and weekly reports of what happens at the different places. Then we have an accountant who goes around the different places and gives a general overview of what is happening. With that we just have a grasp of what is happening”. (E)

“For every branch, we have a manager. These managers are pharmacists. We have a store keeper who monitors the inventory and advises when we need to restock. We have internal software that detects shortages and surpluses. We also have a good manpower that assists in the day to day running as well”. (L)

“I have a pharmacy manager even though I shuttle between both pharmacies. I have a pharmacy manager at both ends and they communicate very well”. (M)

Appendix 7.1c: Business skills: Marketing skills

Example Comments

“Another skill is respect for your customers; making your customers and clients number one. Building your pharmacy around them, knowing that these are the people that will make you stay in business. Any time these clients are no longer there you will close shop and go. So you have to understand that these people are key and you give them the highest respect and treatment”. (Q)

“If you have something to offer like your relationship with your customers, how you talk them, what you offer them, the service outside the drugs you give to them and the information you pass to them makes you stand out. That has been our drive that is why our slogan says “providing the best community service”. Every point in time, I must personally make sure I talk to every customer. It might be in a lighter mood or a detailed mood but somebody must leave here with something positive”. (D)

“I could talk. I could interact and somehow I make them relaxed especially customers who come in and are uptight. I am able to maybe break down their feelings and they now feel relaxed and all that. So I have seen that work over time”. (E)

Appendix 7.1d: Conceptual skills: Strategic planning skills

Example Comments

“We try to do our thing our own way and sometimes we will not say we have turned our back on our competition because we have to be alert about what is happening. But we just try to create a niche for ourselves. We make sure that whatever our customers need from us we make it available. So that people don’t leave us and go to our competition because we don’t have what they want. So we just make ourselves relevant”. (E)

“So that’s how we worry about competitors, we know what they are doing and how much they are paying, making sure we are not underpaying our people. We are always one step ahead of competitors when it comes to the imports we do”. (A)

“But you just make sure that you give the best of service. Make sure that you are always well stocked that is very key, so that anybody that comes in will go out satisfied. So in that case I don’t think there is any better way than to make your pharmacy the best brand and household name, so that people refer their family members and their friends, if you are on top of your game”. (Q)

Appendix 7.1e: Conceptual skills: Decision making skills

Example Comments

“Literally, we discuss. We try to have weekly meetings and sometimes monthly. Among the staff we talk and they come up with suggestions. Sometimes we follow suit with what they say and sometimes we sit back and digest what has been discussed in the meetings and from there I can take decisions on what to do”. (E)

“We hold meetings. These meetings could be weekly or fortnightly. My husband stays in Delta state so he oversees that one. They do their weekly meetings and I go through their minutes and see their complaints, recommendations and everything, so based on that, we now at the top make decisions”. (I)

“We have a management team. I have a GM. She is not here. She is actually in charge of operations. She runs the nitty gritty of the business and we make decisions based on feedback from people at the front desk; that is pharmacists on the ground floor and support staff at the cash points. They get feedback from the customers, comments that are made, perceptions that people have and then we sit as a team; the GM, me, the pharmacists and the lady in charge of purchase”. (P)

Appendix 7.1f: Interpersonal skills: Team building skills

Example Comments

“Usually I will not want to say it is my skills that made it what it is today because I can’t do it alone. All along I have worked with other people. Whatever skill you have you have to be able to harness it to be able to work with people around you”. (E)

“You can’t do it only by yourself. You need people around you. That’s one of the things that actually contribute to success; the people around you... Nobody runs an enterprise and feels he is the only one that has all the intelligence. It doesn’t work like that. Oh Yes! We have some fantastic people. I don’t think the credit is to just 2 people; it is a team”. (J)

Appendix 7.1g: Interpersonal skills: Self-management skills

Example Comments

“I read management books and try to be contemporary. I read articles, the Economist, business magazines and responsible articles on leadership, business, management and all that”. (A)

“I have gone on short courses but they are not certificate courses... They know that I read. Even though I am busy, I am still ahead of them”. (C)

“I go for all these business trainings and seminars”. (F)

Appendix 7.2a: Government and corruption

Example Comments

“Corruption is also a factor because you need to bribe your way in, in some certain areas to bring in stuffs”. (J1)

“Most of these things corruption is one of the cardinal points because if you are straight in doing certain things you will not go so far. But if you are doing rubbish that is crooked things and you can spend your money you can go far distance”. (A1)

“Running pharmaceutical business in Nigeria has so many challenges because of our level of corruption. Nigeria is a highly corrupt country where they say something else in the book and they do something else”. (Q2)

Appendix 7.2b: Infrastructural deficit: Bad roads

Example Comments

“The roads are bad and because of this there is usually traffic and these sometimes affect our customers coming here. The fear of encountering traffic may prevent them from coming”. (B1)

“Some of our customers find it difficult to get here because of the bad roads here”. (D)

Appendix 7.3a: Conceptual skills: Idea generation skills

Example Comments

“She brings in new ideas. She makes the business grow at least she started the business and the business has grown from small one room apartment to will I call it a duplex apartment now”. (K1)

“When she travels there she gets new ideas back to Nigeria and you know here now our business is more different from others because of her ideas. She has good ideas about improving her business every year. Like I said next year now you will see a different idea and which people sometimes ask question how manage?” (K2)

Appendix 7.3b: Conceptual skills: Communication/listening skills

Example Comments

“So good listening skills and it does not only help with what we sell but also within the company. It helps numerous times to have a boss who likes to listen to what you have to say even if he has a difference in opinion, what you have to say still matters. You are given that respect so I will say a listening ear he has”. (A1)

“Even when you have complaints you can go to him directly and he will listen to you. He doesn't consider your position; no matter how small you are he will listen to you”. (B1)

“She is someone that will listen to you. She is very particular about her staff. She listens to everyone. Everyone has access unlike a lot of MDs in many companies; almost everybody has access to Mrs H’s phone number. So if there is an emergency or there is something that you really need to talk to her about, you have the opportunity to just call her. She is not the type that says no one should call me”. (H2)

Appendix 7.3c: People management and development skills: Role modelling

Example Comments

“She is a role model to young girls like me. She is just a wonderful lady. She is a very beautiful person both inside and outside”. (E2)

“Privately I watch everything she does. Why do I watch everything she does? Because I have found out that from watching her I have become a better person...She is like a private mentor. She might not even know that she is mentoring you. She mentors a whole lot of people. Apart from coming out and saying she is my mentor, just watching her life and following those same set of rules. It is not by magic but following those same set of rules and trying to do things right the way she does, that way you will just realise that you are one of the best out there. I have had the privilege of going to receive awards for her and you hear what they say and you know that it is true because you are seeing it every day. You are seeing it every day, it is not hearsay. You are seeing it every day”. (H2)

Appendix 8: Coding Frame

Entrepreneurial leadership skills

Sample Questions

1. Technical/Business skills

section 3a and 3b of the interview guide

1.1. Technical expertise

1.1.1. Pharmacy skills

1.2. Business function skills

1.2.1. Accounting and financial management

1.2.2. Administration

1.2.3. Marketing

1.2.3.1. Customer service

2. Conceptual skills

section 3a and 3c of the interview guide

2.1. Analytical skills

2.1.1. Critical thinking

2.1.2. Objective examination of facts

2.2. Idea generation skills

2.2.1. Challenge the status quo

2.2.2. Ideas obtained from others

2.2.3. Innovativeness

2.3. Problem solving skills

2.3.1. Solving customer problems

2.3.2. Solving employee problems

2.4. Envisioning skills

2.4.1. Foresight

2.4.2. Vision for the business

2.5. Strategic planning skills

2.5.1. Strategies

2.5.1.1. Niche products

2.5.1.2. Unique customer experience

2.5.1.3. Value for money

2.5.2. Anticipate change

2.5.3. Drafting plans

2.5.4. Focus

2.5.5. Forecasting

2.5.6. Goal setting

2.5.7. Positive mind-set

2.6. Decision making skills

2.6.1. Employees involved in decision making

2.6.2. Employees were not involved in decision making

2.6.3. Slow in making decisions

3. Interpersonal skills

section 3a and 3d of the interview guide

- 3.1. Empathy
 - 3.1.1. Empathy towards staff
 - 3.1.2. Empathy towards customers
 - 3.1.3. Empathy is useful
 - 3.1.3.1. Customer referrals
 - 3.1.3.2. Staff engagement
 - 3.1.4. Empathy a weakness
 - 3.1.4.1. Reduced profitability
- 3.2. Communication/listening skills
 - 3.2.1. Verbal communication
 - 3.2.2. Written communication
 - 3.2.3. Listening
- 3.3. Motivating skills
 - 3.3.1. Self-motivation
 - 3.3.2. Motivating others
- 3.4. People Management and development skills
 - 3.4.1. People management
 - 3.4.2. People development
 - 3.4.3. Role modelling
- 3.5. Team building skills
 - 3.5.1. Promoting team work
 - 3.5.1.1. Delegating tasks to employees
 - 3.5.1.2. Recruiting team oriented staff
- 3.6. Self-management skills
 - 3.6.1. Ability to prioritise
 - 3.6.2. Able to handle pressure
 - 3.6.3. Time management
 - 3.6.4. Self-development
 - 3.6.5. Awareness of strengths and weaknesses

4. Entrepreneurial skills

section of 3a of the interview guide

- 4.1. Opportunity identification skills
 - 4.1.1. Apt at recognising opportunities
 - 4.1.2. Location
 - 4.1.3. Providence
- 4.2. Opportunity exploitation skills
 - 4.2.1. Apt at exploiting existing opportunities
 - 4.2.2. Apt at exploiting new market opportunities
- 4.3. Risk management skills
 - 4.3.1. Calculative and analytical
 - 4.3.2. Risk sensitive
 - 4.3.3. Not risk averse

Challenges

- 1. Challenges of the industry**
 - 1.1. Drug distribution
 - 1.2. Fake and sub-standard drugs
- 2. Government and Corruption**
 - 2.1. Inconsistent government policies
 - 2.2. Inefficient legal system
 - 2.3. Failure of regulatory authorities
- 3. Inadequate finance**
 - 3.1. Inadequate capital
 - 3.2. High interest rates from banks
 - 3.3. Inability to get credit facilities from banks
- 4. Infrastructural deficit**
 - 4.1. Bad roads
 - 4.2. Erratic power supply
- 5. Technology deficit**
 - 5.1. Unavailability
 - 5.2. Lack of expertise

Attributes

1. Spirituality
 - 1.1. Religious
 - 1.2. Non-religious

Culture

1. National culture
2. Organisational culture

Family

1. Entrepreneurial leadership skill development
2. Support from family
3. Work-life balance

Followers

1. Dedication
2. Empowerment
3. Susceptibility to leadership

Management experience

1. Relevant work experience
2. Non-relevant work experience

Resources

1. Financial resources
2. Human resources

Success

1. Business creation
2. Business commercialisation
3. Business management

Appendix 9: Individual consent form

Title of Research	Entrepreneurial leadership in the retail pharmacy sector of a developing economy. A study in Nigeria
Name of Researcher	Christian Harrison
Name of Director of Studies	Dr Stuart Paul
Address for correspondence	Christian Harrison, Business school, University of the West of Scotland, Paisley, Scotland. PA1 2BE
Telephone	Office: +44 (01) 41 848 3474 Mobile: +44 7721913024
E-mail address	Christian.harrison@uws.ac.uk
Description of the broad nature of the research	To gather data via exploring the experiences of retail pharmacy entrepreneurs and their employees in Nigeria.
Description of the involvement expected of participants including the broad nature of questions to be answered and the expected time commitment	<p>The expected involvement of the research participants is an approximate 1.5 hour interview.</p> <p>The interviews will be semi-structured and based upon the entrepreneurs' experiences in leading the organisation as well as the employees' experience of being led by their employer.</p> <p>All interviews will be recorded with a digital voice recorder and transcribed verbatim.</p> <p>Anonymity will be assured by using codes rather than the names of the participants, organisation on the interview transcripts.</p> <p>Interview transcripts will be emailed or posted back to the respondents to verify the accuracy of the content. Participants are free to make any amendments, deletions or additions to the transcript.</p> <p>Confidentiality will be maintained in terms of storing data securely on a coded external storage and ensuring hard copies are stored in a locked cupboard.</p> <p>All data will be stored securely either electronically on coded external drive or in a hard copy version in a locked cupboard. As part of the data analysis process, hard copies of the anonymised transcripts may</p>

	<p>be given to the doctoral supervision team to review to ensure that the researcher's analysis is valid. Hard copies will be returned to the researcher and will not remain in the possession of the research participants.</p> <p>Data will be used and reproduced as case studies in a variety of research publications.</p>
Additional information about the research	The data collection timescale of this study is from March 2014 – August 2014

Information provided in this study will be anonymous (i.e. individuals and organisations will not be identified unless this is expressly excluded in the details given above).

Data obtained through this research may be reproduced and published in a variety of forms and for a variety of audiences related to the broad nature of the research detailed above. It will not be used for purposes other than those outlined above without your permission. Participation is entirely voluntary and participants may withdraw at any time.

By signing this consent form, you are indicating that you fully understand the above information and agree to participate in this study on the basis of the above information.

Name of Participant

Signature

Date

Name of Researcher

Signature

Date

Appendix 10: Extract from the field journal

Date: 5/7/2014

Duration of the interview: 1hour 5 minutes and 12 seconds

Activity: Interview with Respondent A

Person involved: Respondent A is the CEO of Pharmacy A

Aim: To understand the challenges entrepreneurs face in a developing economy and to determine the entrepreneurial leadership skills important for success in such setting

Personal thoughts and reflections

The interview took place in the entrepreneur's office but I had to wait for about 45 minutes because he was in a meeting. After the meeting, Respondent A invited me into his office and the interview started immediately. The interview was very engaging and tasking. It was interesting to see how Respondent A was so lively and happy to talk about his abilities and challenges. I had to make a conscious effort to ensure that he was guided by the interview protocol when I realised that he was providing so much information which was not exactly relevant to the research.

In addition, I was very prepared and took notes to guide my interpretation of today's activity. I found out that Respondent A is a very optimistic and a positive person. He struck me as a father figure. He even went on to advise me on my career options. I ended up getting a significant amount of information, which I intend to transcribe immediately. This was by far my most intense interview experience for now.